

**USMANU DANFODIYO UNIVERSITY, SOKOTO
(COLLEGE OF POSTGRADUATE STUDIES)**

**LOKACIN ABU A YI SHI: HAUSAWA DA DAMARMAKIN SANA'O'I A DUNIYAR
INTANET**

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BY

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SADUKARWA

Na sadukar da wannan kundi ga masu neman sanin gaskiya, da rayuwa bisa gaskiya da rikun amana, tare da wasiyya da rikun gaskiya.

CERTIFICATION

This Thesis by SANI, Abu-Ubaida (Adm No: 22310106005) has met the requirements for the award of the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Hausa Studies) of the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto and is approved for its contribution to knowledge.

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GODIYA

Da sunan Allah Mai rahama Mai jinkai. Tsira da mincinSa su tabbata ga shugaban halitta manzon tsira Annabi Muhammadu da iyalansa da sahabbansa. Na gode wa Allah Madaukakin Sarki da ya ba ni damar kammala wannan kundi cikin nasara.

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KALMOMIN FANNU

Kalmomin harshen Hausa da dama suna da yalwar ma'anoni. Akan samu kalma guda ta zo da ma'anoni mabambanta musamman yayin da aka yi amfani da ita a wadansu bagire na musamman. Wannan bangare na aikin yana d'auke da wadansu muhimman kalmomin fannu da suka shafi aikin. An kawo ma'anoninsu domin jagoranci ga mai karatu. A farfajiyar aikin, kai tsaye kalmomin suna d'aukar ma'anonin da aka alaƙanta su da su a matsayin bayanan kalmomin fannu, ko da kuwa suna da wadansu na daban a wani bagire koma-bayan binciken.¹

Duniyar Intanet: Duniyar intanet na nufin farfajiya ko bagiren intanet.

Intanet: Intanet fasaha ce ta zamani wadda ta kunshi had'akar tsauraran al'amura da suka hada da harsuna da na'urori da sabis waƙanda haɗuwarsu take samar da al'amari ko bagire da yake tattare da hadahada da fannoni tamkar waƙanda suke duniyar yau-da-kullum, ciki har da abubuwan da suka shafi sadarwa da makarantu da bankuna da kasuwanni da shaguna tare da sauran halittu kamar mutane da dabbobi da waninsu.

Kasuwanci: Kasuwanci fasaha ce ta saye da sayarwa ko musanyen abubuwa masu daraja domin samun riba, ta hanyar bin mataƙai da dabarun da suka hada da gano wurin d'auko kaya cikin sauƙin farashi da amfani da dabarun talla da jan hankali da tarairayar abokan hulɗa da fikrar daɗin baki a zantukan cinikayya.

¹ An yi cikakken bayani game da zaɓaɓɓun muhimman kalmomin fannu da batutuwan da suke cikin aikin a babi na biyu.

Sana'a: Sana'a na nufin hanyar amfani da fasaha da hikima da kayan aiki domin sarrafa wani abu, musamman dangin albarkatu saboda samar da wani abin amfani da za a iya sayarwa ko musanyawa da wani abu mai daraja, ko kuma gyara wani abin da ake mora da ya lalace ko tsaftace muhalli ko jiki, ko gudanar da ayyukan samar da warakar jiki da gamsuwar zuciya domin samun kuɗi ko wani abu mai dajara kwatankwacin na kuɗi.

Fassarori

Wannan binciken yana kunshe da waɗansu kalmomin fannu da ba su da fassarori na gama-gari. Ma'ana, ba a riga da an yi musu takamaiman fassarori da suka sanu a tsakanin dalibai da manazarta da masana Hausa ba. A bisa wannan dalili, binciken ya zayyano ire-iren waɗannan kalmomi ko batutuwa tare da bayyana fassarar da aka ba wa kowanne. An yi hakan domin mai karatu ko nazari ya fahimci abin da ake nufi da kowace kalma ko batu.

- a. Artificial Intelligence (AI): Kirkirariyar Basira
- b. Availability Check - Tambayar Damar Karɓar Aiki
- c. Digital Ethnography: Nazarin Al'adu a Duniyar Intanet
- d. Facebook: Fesbuk
- e. Followers - Mabiya (a kafar TikTok)
- f. Graph: Giraf
- g. Institutional Theory: Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma
- h. Natural: Al'adar Rayuwa
- i. Network: Netwok

- j. Service: Sabis
- k. Subscribers - Mabiya (a kafar YouTube)
- l. Translation Tools - Injunan Fassara
- m. Twitter: Tuwita

Fassarar Kalmomin Fannin Kudafe Da Kadarorin Intanet

Akwai kalmomin da suka kasance na fannu, waƙanda suka shafi ɓangaren kudafe da kadarorin kan intanet. An yi la'akari da siffa da bagire da yanayi wajen samar da fassarar da za ta iya dacewa da kowace kalma.

- a. Air Drop - Ruwan Kudɪ
- b. Arbitrage Trading - Kasuwancin Bin Kasuwanni
- c. Crypto – Kirifto
- d. Cryptocurrency – Kudɪn Intanet
- e. Day Trading - Kasuwancin Rana
- f. Farming - Noman Kudɪ
- g. Futures Trading – Kasuwancin Bashi Mai Takunkumi
- h. Margin Trading – Kasuwancin Bashi Mai 'Yanci
- i. Mining - Hako
- j. NFT Trading - Kasuwancin Dauwamammiyar Kadarar Intanet
- k. Position Trading – Kasuwancin Doguwar Ajiya
- l. Proof of Stake (PoS) - Shaidar Bayar Da Gudummawa
- m. Proof of Work (PoW) – Shaidar Aiki
- n. Scalping – Kasuwancin Fakafaka

- o. Security Deposit - Kafin Alkalami
- p. Spot Trading - Kasuwancin Kudi-Hanu
- q. Staking - Kulle Kudi
- r. Swing Trading - Kasuwancin Bin Hawa Da Saukar Farashi
- s. Trading – Kasuwanci

Takaitattun Kalmomi

Binciken yana kunshe da waƙansu takaitattun kalmomi. Sun haɗa da abajadan sunayen hukumomi (alphabetism) da kuma takaita sunayen hukumomi da batutuwa (abbreviation). An kawo ma’anonin ire-irensu a wannan ɓangare na aikin domin yin jagoranci ga mai karatu.

- a. **BBC:** British Braodcasting Corporation
- b. **DW:** Deutsche Welle
- c. **ND/nd:** No date (Ba shekara)
- d. **P.:** Page (Shafi)
- e. **para.:** Sakin layi (paragraph)
- f. **RFI:** Radio France Internationale
- g. **Sh.:** Shafi
- h. **SL.:** Sakin layi
- i. **VOA:** Voice of America

ABSTRACT

The direction of business and entrepreneurship in today's world is closely linked to the internet, and modern economic development largely depends on this digital system. This study, therefore, investigates the opportunities available to the Hausa people for engaging in online businesses. Guided by the Institutional Theory and employing Digital Ethnography as the research design, data were collected through an examination of thirty (30) Hausa websites and blogs, ninety (90) major international business platforms, and forty (40) Hausa social media spaces connected to online income generation, including WhatsApp (10), Facebook (10), YouTube (10), and TikTok (10). Supplementary interviews were conducted with selected Hausa professionals in relevant fields to deepen understanding of certain observations from the online analysis. The findings reveal numerous online business opportunities already being utilized by some Hausa individuals, such as freelancing, digital marketing, and crypto trading. The study also identifies key challenges, including poor electricity supply, unstable internet service, and government restrictions, as well as other problems like health and environmental risks associated with online activities. It concludes by recommending stronger collaboration among individuals, organizations, educational institutions, research centers, and government bodies to ensure effective and sustainable participation of the Hausa people in the expanding world of internet-based entrepreneurship.

TSAKURE

Alkiblar sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar yau tana da alaƙa sosai da intanet. Cigaban tattalin arziki ya dogara a kan wannan tsarin zamani. Hakan ne kuma ya samar da manufar wannan bincike, domin nazartar damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su na sana'o'i a intanet. Binciken ya ginu a kan Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma. Bisa tsarin Nazarin Al'adu a Duniyar Intanet, an tattara bayanai kai tsaye ta hanyar nazartar kafafen intanet na Hausa guda talatin (30) da manyan kafafen kasuwanci a duniya guda casa'in (90) da kafafen sada zumunta na Hausawa (masu alaƙa da neman kuɗi) guda arba'in (40) (WhatsApp (10) da Facebook (10) da YouTube (10) da TikTok (10)). An yi hira da wasu Hausawa kwararru a fannonin da binciken ya mayar da hankali kai, domin samun ƙarin haske game da abubuwan da aka lura da su yayin nazarin. Binciken ya gano damarmaki masu yawa na sana'o'i a duniyar intanet waɗanda tuni wasu Hausawa suka fara cin gajiyarsu, ciki har da ayyuka na ma'aikata masu zaman kansu da hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet. A ɗaya ɓangaren, an gano jerin ƙalubale (misali, matsalolin wutar lantarki da sabis ɗin intanet da takunkumai daga gwamnati) da illoli (misali, illa ga lafiyar jiki da muhalli) da suke dabiayye harkokin. An gabatar da matakan da za su taimaka wajen magance su. Sun haɗa da bukatar haɗin kai tsakanin ɗaiɗaikun mutane da ƙungiyoyi da makarantu da cibiyoyin bincike da kuma gwamnati domin tabbatar da bin ingantattun hanyoyin cin gajiyar sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.

BABI NA DAYA

GABATARWA

1.0 Shimfida

Tun farkon samar da halittu a doron duniya ake samun sauye-sauye a kusan dukkannin ɓangarorin rayuwa. Mahangar addini da ilimin kimiyya da fasaha da kuma hankalin tuwo duk sun tabbatar da hakan. Sauye-sauyen da ake samu sun hada da: (i) waɗanda suke aukuwa bisa tsarin halittar duniya (misali girma da duniya take ƙarawa² da raguwar girman jiki da tsawon rayuwar mutane) da (ii) waɗanda suke faruwa sakamakon ayyukan halittu (misali samuwar na'urori da sababbin gine-gine da makamantansu).³

Sana'o'i da kasuwanci suna da gurbi na musamman a rayuwar Hausawa. Yanayen yanayensu suna sauyawa da ƙara samun cigaba daga lokaci zuwa lokaci. Hausawa sun biyo waɗansu mata kai tun daga kan furfure/musanye na tsarin *ba ni gishiri in ba ka manda*, har zuwa matakin saye da sayarwa da fatauci. Samuwar hanyar rubutu da karatu ya buɗe musu wani sabon babin damar rubuta sunaye da farashin kayayyakin kasuwanci tare da samar da allunan talla. An sake samun cigaban zamani yayin da rediyo da talabijin suka samu. Su kansu sun kasance hanyoyin neman kuɗi a

² Kur'ani mai tsarki da ilimin kimiyya duk sun tabbatar da cewa duniya tana ƙara girma. A duba Kur'ani (51:47) da Gohd (2024).

³ Yana da kyau a lura da cewa, sauye-sauyen da suke faruwa a duniya suna kasancewa bisa wani sarkafaffen tsari mai alaƙa da juna. Misali a nan shi ne, yau da gobe da sauyin yanayi na tilasta wa mutane kirƙirar sababbin hanyoyin saukaƙa rayuwa. A ɓangare guda kuwa, sababbin hanyoyin saukaƙa rayuwa na yin tasiri tare da samar da sauyi ga yanayin duniya (kamar tiriri da hayaƙin ababen hawa da masana'antu da suke haifar da dumamar yanayi).

zamanance ta hanyar yin aiki tare da gidan rediyo ko talabijin.⁴ A bangare ɗaya kuwa, sun samar da sababbin hanyoyin tallata haja ga masu sana'o'i da kasuwanci daban-daban.

Samuwar intanet babban sauyi ne da duniya ta samu a karni na ashirin (K20). Hakan ya kara tabbata, yayin da a yau ake mayar da lamuran hulɗoɗin yau da kullum zuwa intanet. Harkar sana'o'i da kasuwanci suna daga cikin nau'o'in hulɗoɗin da suke kara samun gindin zama a duniyar intanet.

Sannu a hankali tallace-tallace suna ci gaba da komawa kan intanet. Daɗin daɗawa, intanet ɗin karan kansa ya zo da sababbin damarmakin kasuwanci ga Hausawa. Sun haɗa da gina kafafen intanet da kasuwancin kuɗin intanet da buɗe gidajen talabijin a kafafen intanet, da dai sauran damarmakin samun kuɗi waɗanda kai tsaye intanet ne ya zo da su.⁵

Wannan bincike ya yi imani da falsafar Hausawa ta “zamani riga”, wato idan kiɗa ya sauya, to dole rawa ma ta sauya. Sabanin haka zai haifar da yanayi bambarakwai! Yayin da Hausawa suka yi sakaci wurin sanya rigar zamani da taka rawar sabon kiɗan

⁴ Aiki a gidan rediyo ko talabijin bai takaita ga aikin jarida ba kawai. Ya haɗa da ɗaukar hotuna da bidiyoyi da gyara sauti ko bidiyo da tsara shirye-shirye da kula da na'urori da dai sauransu. Duk waɗannan hanyoyin samun kuɗi ne da suka zo wa Bahausha a zamanance.

⁵ Yana da kyau a lura da cewa, wannan aiki ya mayar da hankali ne a kan *sana'o'i da kasuwanci* a kan intanet. Kasancewar hanyar samun kuɗi tana da alaƙa da harshe ko adabi ko kimiyya da fasaha ko ilimin gama-gari, ba shi yake nuna cewa ya fita daga bagiren al'ada ba. Al'adar da take ciki ita ce kasancewar Hausawa suna kara rungumar waɗannan hanyoyin samun kuɗi tare da dogaro da su. Hakan bai fita daga farfajiyar sana'o'i da kasuwancinsu ba, wanda ya tabbatar da shi a matsayin wani ɓangare na al'adunsu da suka samu sakamakon tasirin zamani.

da ya zo da shi na kasuwanci a duniyar intanet, lallai ci gaba zai yi musu nisa, kafin su farga. Hakan zai haifar musu da koma-baya a bangaren tattalin arziki.⁶

Wannan bincike sharar fage ne da ya kuduri aniyar haska hanyar tudun-mun-tsira dangane da sabuwar alkiblar sana'o'i da kasuwanci da Hausawa suka dauka a karni na ashirin da faya. An karkasa aikin zuwa babuka shida domin ba shi tsarin bincike mai nagarta.

1.1 Dalilin Bincike

Samuwar intanet a shekarar 1983 (da bunkasarsa a cikin shekarun 1990 - 1995) ya zo da gagarumin sauyi a bangarorin rayuwa daban-daban a fadin duniya. Da wuya a samu wani al'amari da ya yi tasiri a kan rayuwar al'umma tamkar intanet. A yau, babu wani bangare na rayuwar dan'adam wanda intanet bai taɓa ba.⁷

Duk da an samar da intanet tun a karni na ashirin (K 20), karni na ashirin da faya (K 21) ya zo da sababbin abubuwa a fannin da suka girgiza duniya. Bunkasar kasuwancin duniyar intanet da samuwar kirƙirarriyar basira (Artificial Intelligence (AI)) sun sauya alkiblar rayuwa baki faya (Sadat, 2023). Tuni hankalin manyan 'yan kasuwar duniya ya karkata kan wannan fage. Wannan ne kuma ya samar da dalilin binciken na farko. Binciken ya ga muhimmancin nazartar wainar da ake toyawa a wannan sabuwar duniya ta intanet domin Hausawa su shiga da shiri.

⁶ Ko a yanzu, Hausawa suna bakin ƙoƙarinsu wajen shiga a dama da su a hadahadar kasuwancin duniyar intanet daban-daban. Ana iya Kallon hakan cikin ayyukan da suka haɗa da: Jibril (2023) da Sani et al. (2023).

⁷ Duk wani bangare na rayuwa da al'amuran zamantakewa da aka duba, sai an ci karo tasirin intanet ko dai kai tsaye, ko a kaikaice. Bayan taron watan Maris na shekarar 2010 da BBC ta shirya kan Tasirin Fasahar Intanet, ta wallafa a shafinta cewa: "Fasahar intanet fasaha ce da wasu masana suke cewa ta sauya fasalin yadda ake gudanar al'amuran rayuwa a duk fadin duniya." A duba BBC Hausa (2010 SL. 1).

A bangare guda kuwa, a yau rayuwar duniya baki daya tana kara karkata a kan intanet. Wannan ne ya ja hankalin Clement (2020 SL. 4) inda ya ce: *“By now, a world without the internet is unimaginable.”* Ma’ana: “A yanzu, ba za a iya kwatanta yadda duniya za ta kasance ba idan aka ce babu intanet.” Tawagar Pandora FMS (Pandora, 2023 SL. 1-18) na da fahimta makamanciyar wannan, inda har suke ganin cewa da wuya rayuwa ta gudana a yau idan babu intanet. Ire-iren waƙannan iƙirari ba romon baka ba ne kawai, domin kuwa a yau an wayi gari:

- a. Kasuwanci ba zai habaka ya yi gawurtar a-zo-a-gani ba, sai an haɗa da intanet.
- b. Makaranta ko cibiyar ilimi ba za ta kai kololuwa a fice ba, sai ta gwane wajen sarrafa intanet.⁸
- c. Kasa ba za ta samu bunkasa da karfin ikon faɗa-a-ji ba, har sai ta nuna wa duniya ita ba kanwar lasa ba ce a sha’anin intanet.
- d. Muryar malamin addini ba za ta karade duniya ba, har sai an haɗa da intanet.
- e. Al’adu da tadojin wata al’umma ba za su yaɗu a haƙikanin siffofi da sigoginsu ba, sai idan masu su sun auri intanet.

Wannan ne kuma ya samar da dalilin gudanar da binciken na biyu. Ya zama wajibi a gudanar da binciken da zai kara haska wa Hausawa hanyar shiga a dama da su a wannan fannin, cikin cikakken ilimin ba lalube cikin duhu ba. Za a cimma nasarar hakan ne ta hanyar samar da nazarin da zai fayyace ciki da wajen mu’amalolin kasuwancin duniyar intanet.

⁸ Yayin da makaranta ko cibiyar ilimi take son ta yi fice a duniya, dole ta kasance ta yi amfani da intanet yadda ya kamata. A ciki za ta baje hajarta. Hakan zai sa mutane daga ko’ina a faɗin duniya su ci karo da ayyukan da makarantar ko cibiyar take gudanarwa. Haka kuma, ayyukan malaman makarantar za su yi fice a duniya ne kawai idan sun kasance a kan kafafen intanet fitattu.

Wani dalilin gudanar da wannan bincike shi ne domin bunkasawa da yayata harshe da adabi da al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Yana da kyau a san da cewa, kafafen intanet na ɗaya daga cikin hanyoyin kasuwanci a zamanance. An samu karuwar kafafen intanet na Hausa musamman daga wajajen shekarun 2015 zuwa yau (2025). Babban kalubalen shi ne, wasu daga cikin waɗannan kafafen intanet ba Hausawa ne suke jagorantar su ba. Hausawan ma da suke jagorancin kafafen sun kasance ba masu ilimin harshe da al'adun Hausa ba.⁹

Wani babban dalilin gudanar da wannan bincike kuma shi ne, domin haska wa Hausawa sababbin hanyoyin sana'o'i da kasuwanci. Hakan zai yi matuƙar taimaka wa ɗaiɗaikun mutane wajen samun aikin yi da rage zaman banza. Zai kuma taimaka wajen bunkasa tattalin arziki da cigaban kasar Hausa da ma kasa baki ɗaya. Garba (2013 sh. 125) ya jaddada hakan inda yake cewa, bunkasar Hausa a intanet zai taimaka wajen bunkasar harshen da kuma cigaban yanki da kasa baki ɗaya.¹⁰

Daga karshe, wani dalilin gudanar da wannan bincike shi ne sha'awar mai nazarin a kan al'amuran da suka shafi kwamfuta da intanet. A takaice idan aka yi amfani da wannan sha'awa yadda ya kamata, sai sakamakon ya kasance wata dirka da za ta tallafi wani gefe na shigifar tattalin arziki da al'adun Hausawa. Wannan ɓangare kuwa ya shafi kare ilimantarwa da karfafa wa Hausawa guiwa domin rungumar nau'o'in kasuwancin duniyar intanet. A gefe guda kuwa, zai taimaka wajen tabbatar da

⁹ Yayin da aka yi rashin sa'a al'umma ba ta da wakilai a kan intanet, za a samu wasu mutane na daban waɗanda za su riƙa ɗora bayanai dangane da al'adunta. Ba dole ne su ɗora ingantattun bayanai ba kasancewar ba su da ilimi na haƙiƙa game da al'adun. I.S.S. Abdullahi, (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 1 ga watan Satumba 2017) ya yi tir da bayanai da ya ci karo da su a wata kafar intanet mai suna **Maguzawa**, kasancewarsa masani a wannan ɓangare.

¹⁰ "... may impact positively on the development of the language... Thus, it will lead to greater participation in the media by the majority and facilitate access in mass mobilization for national and regional development." (Garba, 2013 sh. 125)

ingancin wakilcin Hausawa a duniyar intanet tare da isar da al'adun nasu wuraren da ba su kai ba.

1.2 Manufar Bincike

Manufar wannan bincike ita ce nazartar sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet domin tantance inda aka kwana tare da fokarin samar da matakan inganta makoma (makomar sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a intanet).

1.3 Makasudin Bincike

Domin cimma manufar wannan bincike, akwai manyan makasudai guda huɗu (4) da aka zayyana. Su ne nazarta tare da fito da:

- i. nau'o'i da yanaye-yanayen sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet,
- ii. abubuwan da ake bukata domin cin gajiyar damarmakin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet,
- iii. kalubalen da suke dabaibaye da sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa na duniyar intanet, da kuma
- iv. matakan da za a iya bi domin shawo kan kalubalen da suke dabaibaye da sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

1.4 Tambayoyin Bincike

Akwai manyan tambayoyi guda huɗu (4) da wannan bincike ya dukufa wajen samar da amsoshinsu. Samuwar amsoshin nasu shi zai kai ga cin nasarar makasudan da aka

zayyana a sama (karkashin 1.3). Hakan kuwa shi yake tabbatar da cimma manufar wannan bincike. Tambayoyin su ne:

- i. Wadanne nau'o'in sana'o'i da kasuwancin kan intanet ne Hausawa suka runguma a yau?
- ii. Wadanne abubuwa ake bukata domin cin gajiya damarmakin sana'o'i da kasuwanci da ake da su a duniyar intanet?
- iii. Wadanne kalubale ne suka dabaibaye lamarin sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet?
- iv. Wadanne mata kai ne za a iya bi domin shawo kan kalubalen da suka dabaibaye sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet?

1.5 Muhimmancin Bincike

Akwai karfin guiwar cewa sakamakon wannan bincike zai taimaka ta bangarori da dama. Daga cikin muhimmancin binciken akwai:

1. Zai samar da muhimman bayanar da hukumomi za su iya amfani da su domin samar da tsare-tsaren koyar da sana'o'in zamani musamman ga mata da matasa. Hakan zai kasance babban cigaba a bangaren tattalin arziki da zamantakewa da samar da tsaro.¹¹
2. Zai zama sharar fage ga manazarta domin nazarin kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Wannan kuwa ya kasance wani bangaren da ba a mayar da hankali sosai a kansa ba. Kasuwanci kuwa daya ne daga cikin muhimman bangarorin al'adun al'umma. Nazarce-nazarcen da suka shafi al'ada da harshe da adabin

¹¹ Samar da aikin yi yana daya daga cikin matakan samar da zaman lafiya da tsaro mai dorewa a kasa. Hanya ce ta gina 'yan kasa hazikai masu muradin samar da cigaba.

Hausawa a kan intanet (kamar abin da ya shafi kasuwancinsu) za su ba da damar samar da ingantaccen wakilci a kowane bangare. Ana sa ran ya kasance wani abin nazari ga dalibai da malamai da manazarta domin neman bayanai da suka shafi al'adun Hausawa a intanet, musamman dangane da kasuwanci.

3. Kasancewar sana'o'in kan intanet sun hada da dora bayanai, aikin ya samar da nagartattun shawarwari kan ingantattun hanyoyin da za a bi domin yayata al'adun Hausawa a intanet a matsayin wani matakin neman kuɗi ko wata daraja. Hakan zai taimaka wajen samar da tabbatattun bayanai game da al'adun Hausawa tare da rage yaɗuwar gurɓatattu daga cikinsu .¹² Za a ci nasarar aiwatar da wannan ne yayin da aka samu masana harshe da al'adun Hausa sun rungumi harkokin sana'o'in duniyar intanet da suka shafi dora bayanai.
4. Zai taimaka wa dalibai da malamai a darrusan da suka shafi ilimin intanet da harshe (Language and ICT) da kuma ilimin harshe da zamananci (Language and Modernity). Nasarar hakan za ta tabbata kasancewar kudin zai kasance abin karatu a wannan fage da ake karancinsu.
5. Ana sa ran ya kasance wani mataki na samar da karin litattatafai da mujallu da makalu (da makamantansu) na Hausa a kan intanet. Bayan shi aikin kansa, zai buɗe fili ga wasu ayyukan bincike da za su tsiro daga cikinsa domin toshe giɓin

¹² Har yau ana kai-komo a kan tarihin Bahausha. "Maimakon a yi canjaras ga abu ɗaya, sai a ga kowane bakin wuta da irin nasa hayaki" (Bunza, 2014 sh. 1). Hakan ya biyo bayan kasancewar rubutattun bayanai farko kan tarihin ba Hausawa ne suka samar da su ba. Idan har aka yi sakacin barin duniyar intanet ba tare da wakilan fwarai ba, babu makawa tarihi na iya maimaita kansa. Kafin a farga, gurɓatattun bayanai kan Hausa da Hausawa na iya mamaye duniyar intanet yadda sauya su zai yi matuƙar wahala.

da a gaba za a iya fahimtar ya bari, ko kuma zurfafa bincike. Hakan zai taimaka wajen bunƙasawa da yayata al'adu har ma da harshe da adabin Hausa.

6. Zai taimaka a matsayin wani hobɓasa na sanya Hausa cikin jerin Harsunan duniya da suke gudun-ya-da-ƙanin-wani a duniyar intanet. Wannan kuwa ci gaba ne da zai iya ƙara wa harshen ɗaukaka tare da yawaitar makaranta da manazartansa a matakin duniya.
7. Zai taimaka wajen samar da ayyukan yi ga Hausawa waɗanda suka karanci Hausa, da ma waɗanda ba su karanta ba. Samar da ayyukan yin kuwa wani mataki ne na rage zaman banza da bunƙasar tattalin arziki a matakin ɗaiɗaikun mutane da matakin yanki da ma matakin kasa baki ɗaya.

1.6 Farfajiyar Bincike

Wannan bincike ya takaita ne a kan sana'o'i da kasuwanci na Hausawa. Kadadar binciken ba ta wuce duniyar intanet ba. Ko a duniyar intanet ɗin ba ko'ina aka duba ba. Kadadar ta ƙara takaita a harkallolin duniyar intanet na sana'o'i da kasuwanci waɗanda Hausawa suke da damarmakin shiga a dama da su. Duk da haka, an yi waiwayen inda aka fito game da sana'o'i da kasuwanci na Hausawa domin fahimtar bayanana daga tushe.

Ba a iyakance kafafen intanet da za a duba ba. Dalilin hakan kuwa shi ne, aikin ya mayar da hankali kan duk wata kafar intanet da ta shafi sana'o'i da kasuwancin da Hausawa suke iya shiga a dama da su. Duk da haka, akwai muhimman kafafen intanet da shafukan sada zumunta da aka keɓe domin yi musu nazarin ƙwafaf. An kawo su a ƙarƙashin "Hanyoyin Tattara Bayanai" a Babi na Uku.

Dangane da lokaci, aikin ya fi mayar da hankali kan karni na ashirin da faya (K 21). Wannan ba ya nufin an yi masa kadadar lokaci, domin kuwa ya leka karni na ashirin (K 20) saboda waiwaitar inda aka fito game da sana'o'i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet. Zai kuma nazarci alkaluman hasashen alkiblar duniya a shekaru masu zuwa.

Kasancewar kadadar binciken ta takaita kan sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet, zuciyar aikin ba za ta mayar da hankali a kan kasuwanci da sana'o'in Hausawa na gargajiya ba. Duk da haka, iyakancewar ba za ta hana a waiwaye su ba a matakin bita. Yin bitar su zai samar da haske musamman game da inda aka fito da matakin da ake a yau. Bugu da kari, zai kasance sharar fage, wato matakin takawa domin gina bayanana sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a zamanance, musamman a intanet. Ko ba komai, tuni aka fara mayar da waƙansu daga cikin nau'o'in kasuwancin Hausawa zuwa intanet.

An ba da kulawa ta musamman ga kafafen intanet na Hausa. An yi hakan ne domin nazartar kiyasin adadin Hausawa da suke cin gajiyar su. Za a cimma wannan manufan ne ta hanyar nazartar nau'o'in kafafen intanet din da funshiyarsu da kuma masu gudanar da su.

1.7 Nadewa

Hakika za a iya kallon intanet a matsayin duniya mai zaman kanta, duk da tana da alaƙa ta kai tsaye da duniyar zahiri. Da a ce intanet za ta bayyana a gan ta ciki da waje, tabbas da za a tarar tana furshe da duk wani abin da ake da shi a duniyar zahiri. Gudanar da bincike game da damarmakin da Hausawa suke da shi na sana'o'i a intanet zai kara fito da bayanana yadda abubuwan suke kasancewa cikin sauki. Da

haka ne za a haska wa Hausawa hanyar cin tagomashin wainar da ake toyawa a duniyar. Domin cimma manufar, an gina binciken kan makasudai guda huɗu (4). Sun shafi nazartar yanaye-yanayen sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet; da abubuwan da ake bukata domin cin gajiyyar su; da kokarin fahimtar kalubalen da harkallolin suka kunsu da matakan magance su. Kadadar binciken ba ta fita daga cikin da'irar al'adun Hausawa da duniyar intanet ba. Ko cikin al'adun, an mayar da hankali ne kan sana'o'i da kasuwanci.

BABI NA BIYU

BITAR AYYUKAN DA SUKA GABATA

2.0 Shimfida

An dade ana gudanar da bincike a kan intanet cikin harsuna daban-daban a fadin duniya. Zuwa yau, akwai ayyuka da dama da aka wallafa a wannan fagen ilimi. Kowanne daga cikinsu akwai abin da ya fi mayar da hankali zuwa gare shi. Wasu sun shafi tarihin samuwar intanet din; wasu dangantakarta da rayuwa; wasu matsaloli da ci gabanta, wasu kuwa kafafen da ake samu a kanta, da dai makamantansu. A karni na ashirin da faya (K21) kuwa, an karkata sosai kan kirƙirarriyar basira. Amfani da tasirin intanet da hasashen makomar duniya su suka ja hankalin dimbin manazarta zuwa wannan fannin. A fofarin wannan bincike na nazartar sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet, akwai buƙatar bitar wasu muhimman batutuwa. Sun shafi waiwaye kan tarihin intanet kansa da bibiyar nau'o'in tasirin da yake da shi ga al'adun al'umma. Daga nan ne za a iya fahimtar irin cigaba ko koma-baya da yake tattare da shi.

2.1 Bitar Muhimman Kalmomi

Manyan batutuwan da suka gina ruhin wannan bincike su ne "bida" da "tanadi" da kuma "intanet". Yana da kyau a bi taliyon muhimman batutuwan tare da daddagar ma'anoninsu. Daga nan ne za a iya bin diddigin dangantakar da take tsakaninsu da kuma tasirinsu a zamanin yau.

2.1.1 Sana'a Da Kasuwanci a Bahaushiyar Al'ada

Kalmomin *sana'a* da *kasuwanci* ba sababbi ba ne ga kunnuwan Hausawa. Suna daga cikin kalmomin da bakuna suke furtawa, sannan kunnuwa suke ji a-kai-a-kai. Haka kuma, sun mamaye duniyar nazari da rubuce-rubucen Hausa, musamman wafanda suka shafi al'ada.

Kalmar *sana'a* ararriya ce daga harshen Larabci (Jangebe a cikin Wushishi, 2011 sh. 23). Ibrahim, (2023 sh. 218) ya tabbatar da wannan inda ya bayyana cewa, asalin kalmar a Larabci tana da furucin *assana'atu*. A Larabci tana da ma'anar yin dabara "ta yin amfani da hikima da basira domin samar da wani abu, domin jama'a su amfana" (Ibrahim, 2023 sh. 218).

Masana da manazarta da dama sun bayyana ma'anar kalmar *sana'a*. Wushishi, (2011 sh. 23-26) ya yi kokarin bitar wafansu daga cikin ma'anonin. Wani abin lura daga cikin ma'anonin shi ne yadda ake samun shigen giragizai tsakanin *sana'a* da *kasuwanci* a cikinsu.

Dangane da ma'ana kuwa, *sana'a* hanya ce ta amfani da azanci da hikima na sarrafa albarkatu da ni'imomi da *ɗan'adam*¹³ ya mallaka don bukatun yau da kullum... *Sana'a* aba ce wadda ta danganci tono albarkatun kasa da sarafa¹⁴ hanyoyin kimiyya da fasaha da ni'imomin da suke tattare da *ɗan'adam*¹⁵ da sha'anonin kasuwanci na saye-da-sayarwa da ciniki da sauransu" (Tanko, 2000 sh. 35). Ko a cikin wannan ma'ana, za

¹³ haka

¹⁴ Haka

¹⁵ Haka

a ga cewa aikin na Tanko ya sanya kalmomin *kasuwanci* da *saye da sayarwa* da *ciniki* a cikin ma'anar sana'a.

A 2012 aikin Alti ya kawo ma'anar da ta yi fokarin ba wa sana'a gashin kanta. Ya bayyana cewa: "Sana'a wata hanyar rayuwa ce wadda kan ta'allafa da amfani da azanci da hikima a sarrafa albarkatu da ni'imomi da Allah ya yi wa dan'adam¹⁶ don samun abin biyan bukatun yau da kullum (Alti, 2012 sh. 29).

Binciken Rumbun Ilimi (n.d. SL. 1) ya nazarci ayyukan masana daban-daban sannan ya bayyana cewa "Sana'a kalma ce da aka aro ta daga Larabci, kuma take daukar ma'ana ta samar da wani abin amfani ta hanyar hikima a Hausance." Ya dauki kasuwanci abu mai cin gashin kansa a matsayin hanyar saye da sayarwa.

Idan aka so bayar da ma'anar sana'a a keɓance, ana iya cewa sana'a ita ce hanyar amfani da fasaha da hikima da kayan aiki domin sarrafa wani abu, musamman dangin albarkatu domin samar da wani abin amfani da za a iya sayarwa ko musanyawa da wani abu mai daraja, ko kuma gyara wani abin amfani da ya lalace ko tsaftace muhalli ko jiki, ko gudanar da ayyukan samar da warakar jiki da gamsuwar zuciya domin samun kuɗi ko wani abu mai dajara kwatankwacin na kuɗi.

A ɓangare guda kuwa, ma'anonin kasuwanci da dama da ayyuka suka zo da su suna da nason sana'o'i a cikinsu. Sukan kasance tamkar dai yadda aka ga nason *kasuwanci* a cikin ma'anar *sana'a* wacce (Tanko, 2000 sh. 35) ya bayar a sama (karkashin 2.1.3). Binciken Buhari (2021) ya bayyana ma'anar kasuwanci da cewa:

¹⁶ Haka

Kasuwanci dai yana nufin saye da sayarwa na wani abu ko kuma haja wanda abun nan yana iya kasancewa wanda ake gani ne kuma wanda ba a gani ne kamar mutum ya yi wani aiki a biya shi to duka suna daukar ma'anar kasuwanci. (Buhari, 2021 SL. 3)

Lura da waƙannan bayanai, ana iya cewa kasuwanci fasaha ne na saye da sayarwa ko musanyen abubuwa masu daraja domin samun riba, ta hanyar bin mata kai da dabarun da suka haɗa da gano wurin ɗauko kaya cikin saukin farashi da amfani da dabarun talla da jan hankali da tarairayar abokan hulɗa da fikirar daɗin baki a zantukan cinikayya.

2.1.1.1 Shigar Giragizai Tsakanin Kasuwanci Da Sana'a

Sana'a da *kasuwanci* kalmomi ne masu alaƙa da juna. Duk da cewa akwai rubuce-rubucen da suka yi fokarin bambance tsakaninsu (kamar yadda aka kawo sama), sau da dama akan kawo su cikin shigar giragizai. Akwai ma nazarce-nazarcen da suka kawo su a matsayin abu guda.

Gummi, (2014) bai rarrabe tsakanin sana'o'i da kasuwanci ba. Yayin bayani game da yankunan Sakkwato da Kebbi da Zamfara, ya bayyana cewa: "Daga cikin sana'o'in da ake gudanarwa a wannan yankin akwai noma da kiwo da su da kasuwanci da dai sauransu" (Gummi, 2014 sh. 77). A nan ya kawo *kasuwanci* a matsayin wani ɓangare na *sana'o'i*.

Aikin Alti, (2012) ma bai ware ba tsakanin sana'o'i da kasuwanci. Ya kawo su a haɗe a shafi na 32, ciki har da waƙanda suka shafi cinikayya da waƙanda suka shafi kere-kere da sarrafe-sarrafe. Yadda manazarta suke kallon kasuwanci da sana'a a matsayin

abu guda cikin rubuce-rubucensu abu ne mai jan hankali da yake bukar zurfafa nazarin kwaƙƙwafi.

A shekarar 2018 ma an samu nazarin da ya ginu a kan irin wannan ra'ayi. Abdullahi (2018 sh. 22) ya nazarci ma'anonin kamusu na *kasuwanci* da *kwadago* da *fatauci*. Daga karshe ya bayyana cewa, duk da bambancin da yake tsakaninsu ta fuskar ma'ana da yanayi da sigar aiwatarwa, Hausawa suna daukar su ne a matsayin abu guda. Ma'ana a nan ita ce, binciken Abdullahi (2018) na da fahimtar cewa, Hausawa sukan dauki *sana'o'i* ko nau'o'in *kasuwanci* a matsayin abu guda.

Aikin Abdullahi, (2021) ma ya kawo sana'a da kasuwanci a matsayin abu guda. Da yake ba da ma'anar sana'a, ya bayyana cewa tana nufin "... amfani da hikima da kaikawo da juriya da sarrafa albarkatun da suke kewaye da dan'adam¹⁷ wala'alla a binne suke a cikin kasa ko a sarari, domin biya wa kai bukatsu na yau da kullum" (Abdullahi, 2021 sh. 2). A nan ma za a iya lura da cewa, binciken Abdullahi ya haɗe sana'a da kasuwanci a wuri ɗaya. Dalili kuwa shi ne "sarrafa albarkatu" shi ne abin da ya fi kama da sana'a. Saye da sayar da shi kuma, shi ya fi kama da kasuwanci.

Nasir, (2021) ya nazarci ayyukan masana da manazarta daban-daban. Daga karshe ya kai ga yanke hukuncin cewa, idan aka yi la'akari da funshiyar ma'anonin da suka bayar game da sana'a, "za a fahimci suna da dangantaka da kasuwanci da saye da sayarwa" (Nasir, 2021 sh. 14). Ko ba komai, aikin Aliyu (2018) kacokan ya kira gwanjo da "sana'a", alhali abu ne da ya shafi saye da sayarwa.

¹⁷ Haka

La'akari da bayanan da wannan bincike ya tattara daga rubuce-rubucen da suka gabata, da kuma lura da dukkannin alkaluman da suke kunshe cikin ayyukan, an fahimci waɗansu 'yan bambance-bambance tsakanin *sana'a* da *kasuwanci*. An kawo su cikin jadawali na ɗaya (1) da yake kasa.

Jadawali Na 1: Bambance-Bambance Tsakanin Sana'a Da Kasuwanci

Fanni	Sana'a	Kasuwanci
Ma'ana	Sana'a ta fi shafar aikin da za a aiwatar da hannu ta amfani da kayan aiki. Ta shafi sarrafa ma'adanai domin samar da kayan amfani.	Kasuwanci ya fi shafar saye da sayar da kayayyaki domin samun riba.
Fasali	Ta fi shafar aikin da mutum guda yake aiwatarwa da hannaye da basirarsa domin sarrafa wani abu ya samar da wani abu.	Ya shafi sayen abu ko abubuwa daga hannun wani mutum ko waɗansu mutane da sayar da shi ga wani mutum ko waɗansu mutane.
Haɗarin Faɗuwa	Yawanci babu haɗarin faɗuwa. Ko da akwai, yakan kasance kaɗan. Abin da mai sana'a ya samar, shi zai sayar.	Yawanci lamari ne da ya shafi riba da faɗuwa. Dankasuwa kullum yana kan lissafin yadda zai kauce wa faɗuwa da yadda zai ci riba sosai.
Yanke Hukunci	Yanke hukunci kamar na abin da ya shafi farashi abu ne da mai sana'a zai iya yi nan take, musamman idan ba ta shafi sayen kayayyaki da za a sarrafa ba. ¹⁸ Misali, mai sana'ar yankan farce, ko nawa ya karɓa bai yi hasara ba sakamakon bai sanya waɗansu kudade masu yawa ba wajen tanadar kayan aikinsa.	Yanke hukunci game da farashi na buƙatar matuƙar taka-tsantsan don gudun hasara.
Kadada	Yawanci takan kasance takaitacciya da ta kunshi mutum guda ko mutane kaɗan.	Yana iya kasancewa mai girma da faɗi. Yana iya haɗawa da ma'aikata masu yawa.
Masu Gudanarwa	'Yan gado da koyo ta hanyar barantaka sun fi yawa.	Akan samu 'yan haye sosai.
Koyo	Yawanci akan ɗauki lokaci mai tsawo kafin hannu ya iya jiki ya saba.	Akan samu masu faɗawa dare ɗaya idan dai suna da jari.

Madogara: Daukar hannu daga ayyukan Sallau (2000) da Mika'il (2017) da Rambo (2018) da Buhari (2021)

¹⁸ Akwai sana'o'in da suke buƙatar a sayi kayayyakin gudanar da su. Misali, mai sana'ar rini a zamanance da ya sayi launuka, dole ne kuɗin da zai karɓa ya haura jimillar kuɗin launuka da ya saya. Saɓananin haka, to babu riba sai faɗuwa.

Yayin da aka nazarci bambance-bambancen da aka kawo a jadawali na ɗaya da yake sama, ana iya ƙoƙarin ware sana’o’i daga kasuwanci. An bayyana hakan a cikin jadawali na biyu (2) da yake ƙasa.

Jadawali Na 2: Wadansu Sana’o’i Da Kasuwancin Hausawa

	Sana’o’i		Kasuwanci
1.	Dakau	1.	Dillanci
2.	Dukanci	2.	Fatauci
3.	Jima	3.	Gwanjo
4.	Kira	4.	Sakai
5.	Kiwo		
6.	Noma		
7.	Rini		
8.	Saka		
9.	Sassaka		
10.	Su (kamun kifi)		
11.	Wanzanci		

Madogara: Sallau, (2009 sh. 37-45); Rambo, (2018 sh. 179-190)

A fahimtar wannan bincike, tattauna *kasuwanci* a kadadar al’adun Hausawa ba zai kammala ba har sai an haɗa shi da *sana’o’in Hausawa*. Hasali ma a bagire da dama suna iya wakiltar juna. Aikin Muhammad (2020 sh. 224) ya bayyana ma’anar sana’a a matsayin “hanyoyin da ake gudanar da saye da sayarwa.” Kai tsaye za a iya cewa wannan ma’ana tana bayani ne a kan *kasuwanci*. Ta yiwu cudeɗeniyar da take tsakanin *sana’a* da *kasuwanci* ne ya ja hankalin manazarcin wajen ba da wannan ma’ana.

Ko Rumbun Ilimi (n.d. SL. 1) da (Buhari (2021 SL. 3) da suka rarrabe tsakanin *kasuwanci* da *sana'a*, akwai wuraren da bayanansu suke nuna ba a iya rabe su. Misali, Buhari ya kawo “noma” da “kiwo” da “dinki” a cikin misalan kasuwanci. Ya yi hakan ne a fofarin nuna yadda Hausawa suke samun kuɗi da su. Idan aka fofa su a kan ma'anonin *kasuwanci* da *sana'a*, za a tarar da cewa sun fi dacewa da su zauna a farkashin rukunin sana'o'i.

Ko ba komai, za a tarar da cewa duk sana'ar da za a gudanar (misali kaɗi ko kira ko saka ko wanzanci da sauransu) to sai kasuwanci ya shiga ciki (ciniki, talla, da sauransu). Haka kuma duk kasuwancin da za a gudanar, to ana yi ne ta amfani da kayayyakin da aka samu sakamakon sana'o'i. Mai aiwatar da sana'a yana iya kasuwancin sayar da kayayyakin sana'arsa (misali masassaki ya sayar da turame da tabare da sauran kayan sassake-sassakensa). Haka kuma, fofan kasuwa mai zaman kansa yana iya gudanar da kasuwancin sayen kaya daga masu sana'o'i domin sayar da su (misali, sakai na iya sayen hatsi daga manoma don ya sayar ya samu riba).

Bugu da fofa kuma, a koyaushe al'ummar da take da harshe ita take ba wa kalmominta ma'anonin da ta ga dama. Zamani ko yanayi yana iya tasiri ta yadda har zai kai ga al'umma ta sauya wafansu kalmomin da take da su, ko ta faɗaɗa ma'anoninsu. A yau, Hausawa da dama sun mayar da kasuwanci zuwa wani matsayin reshe na sana'a, ko dai bisa niyya da fahimtar hakan, ko kuma ba tare da tunaninsu ya kai kan hakan ba. Za a iya kafa hujjar wannan ifirari da al'adar tambayar da ta kasance sababbiya ga harsunan Hausawa sannan 'yar gida ga kunnuwansu. Wannan tambaya tana zuwa cikin sigogi mabambanta kamar haka:

Wace sana'a yake yi?

Mece ce sana'arsa?

Yana da sana'a?

A takaice ke nan, Hausawa suna amfani da kalmar *sana'a* wajen wakiltar sana'a da kasuwanci. Amsar misalan tambayoyin da aka kawo a sama na iya kasancewa ɗaya daga cikin misalan kasuwanci da aka bayar a cikin jadawali na 2 da yake farkashin 2.1.3.1. Ko a dadadɗun rubuce-rubuce an samu inda aka kawo kasuwanci a matsayin wani nau'i na sana'a. Yayin lissafo jerin sana'o'in da ake gudanarwa a Talata Mafara, Cibiyar Binciken Tarihin Talata Mafara ta kawo kasuwanci a mataki na tara (9) cikin goma sha huɗu (14) da ta lissafo.¹⁹

2.1.2 Intanet

Intanet baƙon al'amari ne a duniya baki ɗaya. A bisa haka, "kalmar intanet baƙuwa ce a fannin nazarin Hausa" (Mukoshy, 2015 sh. 19). Asalin kalmar a Ingilishi ita ce "*internet.*" An samu bambancin fahimtar kalmar da ta fi dacewa a yi amfani da ita a Hausa. Akwai waɗanda suke ganin ya fi dacewa a yi amfani da *yanar gizo ko yanar gizo-gizo*. Daga cikin masu amfani da wannan fahimtar akwai 'Yartsakuwa (2017) da Gana (2020) da CMG Hausa (2022).

A ɓangare guda kuwa, akwai masana da manazarta da suke da fahimtar a Hausantar da ita zuwa "intanet." Amfani²⁰ yana da irin wannan fahimtar, a inda ya jaddada cewa

¹⁹ A duba (Cibiyar Binciken Tarihin Talata Mafara, 2007 sh. 73-121).

²⁰ A.H. Amfani (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, wajajen 7 zuwa 28 ga watan Mayu 2019)

“Furta *intanet* ai ba ta gagari Bahausha ba da har za a tsaya ana kame-kame.”²¹
Rubuce-rubucen da suka yi amfani da kalmar *intanet* sun hada da BBC Hausa (2010)
da Umar (2012) da Rambo (2014) da Mukoshy (2016) da Muryar Hausa²⁴ Online
Media (2020).

Muhimmanci da tasirin intanet ga rayuwar ɗan’adam ya sa a kullum ake samun
ƙaruwar rubuce-rubuce a wannan fanni cikin harsuna daban-daban. A shekarun
baya-bayan nan an samu ƙaruwar rubuce-rubuce cikin Harshen Hausa game da
intanet. Masana da manazarta da dama sun yi ƙoƙarin ba da ma’anar kalmar intanet.
Umar ya ce:

Intanet kafa ce wadda ta hada bayanai daban-daban, kuma an saukaƙa
hanyoyin amfani da waɗannan bayanai yadda kowa zai iya miƙa hannayensa a
kowane lokaci a ko’ina. (Umar, 2012 sh. 48)

Wannan ma’ana ta yi ƙoƙarin hasko yadda intanet yake ɗauke da tarin bayanai da
kuma yadda suke da sauƙin amfani. Wani ɗan raunin da yake cikin wannan ma’ana
shi ne, ba kowane lamarin intanet ba ne yake da sauƙi. Misali, su kansu bayanan da
suke kan intanet akwai waɗanda ba kai tsaye ake ɗauko su da zarar an miƙa hannu
ba. Wasu na sayarwa ne ko kuma waɗanda ake samu bayan an bi wasu ayyanannun
matakai. Haka kuma, a ɓangaren abin da ya shafi harsunan kwamfuta, akwai buƙatar
nazari da ƙwarewa kafin iya sarrafa bayanan. A ɓangare guda kuwa, ma’anar ta

²¹ Wannan bincike ya fi karkata a kan amfani da kalmar *intanet* a maimakon *yanar gizo*. An yi wannan
zaɓin ne kasancewar:

- a. Ta fi riƙe bakin Hausawa.
- b. Ta fi hasko hoton abin da ake nufi kai tsaye domin kamancen sauti da take da shi da furucin
kalmar *internet* a Ingilishi.
- c. Ta fi zagaya kafafen intanet da manhajojin fassara na ƙasa-da-ƙasa.

karkata ne kawai a kan bayanan da ake samu a duniyar intanet ba tare da mayar da hankali kan salailai da sigoginsu ko hanyoyin samar da su da sarrafa su ba.

Mukoshy (2015) ya nazarci wasu daga cikin ma'anonin intanet da masana da manazarta suka bayar.²² Daga karshe ya bayyana tasa ma'anar da cewa:

Intanet kafar sadarwa ce ta na'urorin zamani wadda ta game duk duniya. Tana ba da damar sadar da bayanai kowafanne iri, kuma zuwa ko'ina a duniya cikin dan kankananin lokaci. (Mukoshy, 2015 sh. 20).

Da alama Mukoshy ya yi aron hannu ga Umar, (2012) wajen fitar da wannan ma'ana ta intanet. Duka ma'anonin biyu (Mukoshy da Umar) suna nuna cewa, kowa na da damar yin amfani da intanet, sannan daga kowane wuri. Ma'anar da Mukoshy ya bayar ta zo da karin batun "na'urori" wadanda suka kasance gishiri cikin lamuran duniyar intanet.

Hafika wadannan ma'anoni sun ba da haske kan abin da ake nufi da intanet. Duk da haka, akwai muhimmin al'amari da ya kamata bayani kan kalmar ya kunsu. Wannan kuwa shi ne nuna bagire ko farfajiyar kafar sadarwar wadda ta kasance bisa hanyoyin iska wadanda ba a iya ganin su. Tun a shekarar 2010 Amfani ya kawo wannan cikin ma'anar da ya bayar inda yake cewa:

Intanet tsari ne da ya hada duniya, ta hadakar layin iska na kwamfutoci wadanda ke amfani da tsare-tsaren yanar gizo don biya wa biliyoyin masu amfani bukatu a fadin duniya. (Amfani (2010) a cikin Umar (2012 sh. 48)).

²² Sun hada da ma'anonin da suka fito daga Almajir (2008) da Muhammad (2011) da Umar (2012).

Yayin da aka nazarci wadannan ma'anoni da ma makamantansu, za a tarar da cewa akwai muhimman abubuwan da suka taru suka samar da kafar intanet. Za a iya kallon su a matsayin siffon intanet. Ko ma wace ma'ana ce ta fi kwanciya a ran manazarci, yana da kyau a fahimci cewa:

- a. Intanet al'amari ne da ya samu a zamanance.
- b. Intanet ya kasance al'amari mai faɗi da ban mamaki. Yana kunshe da dukkanin wasu fannoni da ake samu a duniyar rayuwar yau da kullum.
- c. Intanet ba ya gudanawa sai da taimakon na'urori masu kwaƙwalwa (nau'o'in kwamfuta daban-daban).²³
- d. Huldaiyyar intanet abu ce wadda ba a gani, amma ana kallon sakamakonta ta fuskokin kwamfutoci. Akwai kuma sakamakon da yake bayyana a gan shi a zahiri ko a ji sautinsa ko dumininsa, da sauransu.
- e. Intanet yana da harsuna daban-daban. Yayin da aka tura saƙo bisa intanet, sai ya fassaru cikin yaren da intanet yake ganewa. Daga nan kuma sai ya sake fassaruwa zuwa yare ko sigar da masu neman sakamakon yake iya fahimta.
- f. Babu wani al'amari na intanet da yake da damar yin kansa. Komai aka gani a duniyar, to yin sa aka yi. Duk da haka, ana iya ba wa wani al'amari a duniyar intanet damar maimaita kansa ko sarrafa kansa zuwa wasu sigogi mabambanta.

²³ Yana da kyau a tuna cewa, kwamfuta tana zuwa cikin sigogi da dama. Wayoyin hannu da agogwannin dijita da talabijin din dijita duk suna iya shiga cikin jerin nau'o'in kwamfutoci da ake da su.

- g. Intanet al'amari ne da ya jawo nesa kusa,²⁴ ya mayar da abu mai yawa ya zama kaɗan,²⁵ ya mayar da abu kaɗan ya zama mai yawa,²⁶ sannan ya tsuke faɗin duniya.
- h. Intanet haɗaka ce ta tsauration al'amura daban-daban. Sun haɗa da yarukan intanet da gine-ginensa da hanyoyin shigarsa da *sabis* ko *netwok* wanda shi yake ba da damar kaiwa gare shi.

Lura da waɗannan, ba da kammalalliyar ma'anar intanet da za ta bayyana dukkanin siffofinsa aiki ne ja. Duk da haka, ta bin sawun zaren tunanin magabata wajen ba da ma'anar intanet, za a iya cewa:

Intanet fasaha ce ta zamani wadda ta kunshi haɗakar tsauration al'amura da suka haɗa da harsuna da na'urori da sabis waɗanda haɗuwarsu yake samar da al'amari ko bagire da yake tattare da hadahada da fannoni tamkar waɗanda suke duniyar yau-da-kullum, ciki har da abubuwan da suka shafi sadarwa da makarantu da bankuna da kasuwanni da shaguna tare da sauran halittu kamar mutane da dabbobi da waninsu.

2.1.2.1 Waiwayen Tarihin Samuwa Da Bunkasar Intanet

Masana da manzarta sun gudanar da rubuce-rubuce masuyawa dangane da tarihin samuwar intanet da bunkasarsa cikin harsuna mabambanta.²⁷ Sake bibiyar tarihin tiryar-tiryar zai kasance tamkar maimaici ne ga ayyukan baya kawai ba tare da

²⁴ Misali, wanda yake zaune a kasar Hausa zai iya yin magana da wanda yake birnin Sin yayin da suke kallon juna. Zai kuma iya taya shi wani aiki da yake gudanarwa a kan intanet a wannan lokaci.

²⁵ Misali, kafar intanet guda za ta iya ɗaukar dubban miliyoyin manyan littattafai waɗanda idan ɗakin karatu za a gina domin adana su, abin sai wanda ya gani.

²⁶ Idan za a ba da wata sanarwa ta amfani da jarida ko wasifa, ana bukarar buga takardu masu matuƙar yawa domin rarrabawa ko lillikawa a wurare domin amfanin sakonnin su kai ga jama'a. Ta hanyar amfani da intanet, rubutu guda zai iya wadatarwa ba tare da an yi ta maimaitawa ba.

²⁷ Rubuce-rubucen da suka kawo tarihin intanet sun haɗa da Leiner et al. (1997) da Romualdo & Alessandro (2007) da Jonathan (2008) da Mukoshy (2015).

gabatar da wani sabon al'amari ko ilimi ba. Lura da haka, wannan bincike zai fi mayar da hankali wajen zakulo sauye-sauye da cigaba da aka samu a harkar intanet tun bayan kirkirarta.

Bincike da dama da suka gabata sun danganta tarihin intanet da yunkurin wata hukumar tsaro da take Amurka. Bincike Gerf (2004 sh. 1360) ya bayyana cewa, a shekarun 1970s ne aka samu hobbasa na kafar intanet na farko mai suna *ARPANET*. Wannan bayani ya yi daidai da wanda Mukoshy, (2015 sh. 21) ya rawaito daga Deitel da Deitel, (2009). Mukoshy ya yi karin bayani da cewa, kafar intanet ta ARFA ta samu ne bayan hukumar da aka fi sani da *The Advanced Research Project Agency (ARPA)* ta gudanar da taro a shekarar 1969. Wannan hukumar ta kasance farkashin *Department of Defense in United States*.²⁸

2.1.2.1.1 Bunkasar Sabis Din Intanet

A ɓangare guda kuwa, shi ma sabis ɗin intanet ba lokaci guda aka samar da shi cikin siga da tsarin da yake a yau ba. Bayan haka, bai kasance nau'i ɗaya kawai ba. Akwai nau'o'in sabis ɗin intanet daban-daban. Masana na samar da rabe-raben intanet ne ta la'akari da faɗin wurin da sabis ɗin intanet ɗin yake kaiwa.²⁹ Fitattu daga cikin nau'o'in sabis ɗin intanet su ne:

1. Kebantaccen Sabis Din Intanet - (*Personal Area Network (PAN)*)

Wannan shi ne nau'in sabis ɗin intanet da ya shafi wuri guda kawai. Yawanci ana samar da shi ne domin amfanin mutum ɗaya. Sau da dama sabis ɗin ba ya wuce faɗin

²⁸ A kasar Hausa kuwa, intanet ya fara shigowa a wajejen 1990 kamar yadda Mukoshy (2016 sh. 27) ya rawaito daga Almajir (2009). Duk da haka, bai bunkasa ba sai a wajejen 1998.

²⁹ Domin samun karin bayani game da ayyukan da aka gudanar kan sabis ɗin intanet, ana iya duba Bourgeois (2016) ko Dordal (2020).

mita goma (10). Misali, idan mutum ya tura bidiyo ko hoto daga kwamfuta zuwa wayarsa ko daga waya zuwa kwamfuta, to ya yi amfani ne da irin wannan nau'in sabis. Haka ma mutum na iya kunna sabis din wayarsa na hawa intanet domin ya ba wa kwamfutoci ko wayoyi sabis. Duk ire-iren wadannan ana kiran su da suna *PAN*.

2. Sabis Din Karamin Wuri - (*Local Area Network (LAN)*)

Wannan nau'in sabis ne da ya shafi ma'aikatu ko gidaje ko masana'antu. Za a iya samun ma'aikata mai kwamfutoci kamar guda goma (10) amma dukkanninsu suna amfani da sabis guda ne. Bayan haka, kwaƙwalen kwamfutocin na iya kasancewa a haɗe wuri guda. Wannan zai sa duk sauyin da aka yi a kwamfuta guda ya kasance ya shafi sauran kwamfutocin. Bayan haka, akan samu babban ofishi a ma'aikata da yake ɗauke da kwamfutoci da yawa a ciki. Ana iya tsara yadda dukkannin kwamfutocin za su rika tura takardun da za a gurza (printing) zuwa na'urar gurza takardu (printer) guda. Sabis din da ya haɗa kwamfutocin shi ake kira LAN. PAN daban-daban ne suke haɗuwa su ba da LAN.

3. Sabis Din Yanki - (*Metropolitan Area Network (MAN)*)

Wannan nau'in sabis ne da yake karɗe wani yanki. Nau'in sabis din da ake samu a manyan jami'o'i da suke da gine-gine da dama na iya kasancewa MAN. Bayan haka, ana iya samun wata ma'aikata da take da gine-gine ko ofisoshi a wurare daban-daban a cikin gari guda ko garuruwa da suke kusa da juna. Idan haka ta faru, ana iya amfani da sabis din MAN domin takaita adadin kuɗi da ma'aikatar za ta rika kashewa ga sabis. PAN daban-daban ne suke haɗuwa su ba da LAN. Su kuma LAN sai su haɗu su ba da MAN.

4. Sabis Na Dogon Zango - (Wide Area Network (WAN))

Wannan nau'in sabis ne da yake mamaye dogon zango. Yana kasancewa tsakanin gari da gari ko ma kasa da kasa. Babban misali a nan shi ne, akwai bankunan da suke da cibiyoyi a dukkan jahohin Nijeriya, inda kuma ake samun nau'o'in sabis-sabis da dukkannin cibiyoyin da suke jahohin suke amfani da su a tare. Manyan kamfanonin fassara suna da tsari makamancin wannan. Misalan wannan sun haɗa da kamfanonin fassara da suke da ma'aikata da dama, waɗanda kuma suke amfani da tsarin sabis guda. Ko a bangaren raba fayilolin fassara za a iya kallon wannan. Idan akwai fayiloli 20, za su kasance a kwamfutocin dukkannin ma'aikatan. Sannan kowannensu zai rika kallon fayil da aka riga aka yi aiki a kansa.³⁰ Yayin da PAN suka haɗu suka ba da LAN, su kuma LAN za su haɗu su ba da MAN. MAN kuwa su ne suke haɗuwa su ba da WAN.

A Nijeriya, akwai kamfanoni da dama da suke samar da sabis ɗin intanet. Akintaro, (2023 SL. 4) ya bayyana cewa, zuwa watan Nuwambar shekarar 2023, Hukumar Kula Da Harkokin Sadarwar a Nijeriya, wato *Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC)* ta ba da lasisi a kamfanonin da suke bayar da sabis ɗin intanet 253.

2.1.2.1.2 Samuwar Kafafen Intanet

Bullar kafafen intanet sun samar da wani sabon al'amari a duniya. Kafar intanet wani gida ne ko farfajiya ko rumbu da akan kirƙira. A cikinsa ne ake ajiye bayanai iri-iri. Za a rika bin wasu tsararrun hanyoyi wajen kaiwa ga wannan gida tare da ta'ammuli da kayayyakin da suke cikinsa. Binciken Armstrong (2019) ya tabbatar da

³⁰ Domin ƙarin bincike game da nau'o'in haɗakar sabis ɗin intanet, ana iya ziyartar <https://www.javatpoint.com/types-of-computer-network> ko <https://www.router-switch.com/faq/types-of-networks.html> ko <https://www.belden.com/blogs/network-types> ko kuma <https://afteracademy.com/blog/What-are-the-different-types-of-network>.

cewa, an kirkiro kafar intanet ta farko ne a shekarar 1991.³¹ Daga wannan lokaci aka ci gaba da samun bullowar kafafen intanet da bunƙasarsu. Ya zuwa shekarar 2016, kafafen intanet sun kai biliyan guda. Giraf da yake kasa yana d'auke da karin bayani.

Giraf Na 2.1: Adadin Kafafen Intanet a Duniya

Madogara: Armstrong (2019 SL. 1)

A giraf na 2.1 da yake sama, za a ga tarihin samuwar kafafen intanet a takaice. A shekarar 1991 kafar intanet guda d'aya aka samu. A 1992 adadinsu ya kai goma. A wajajen 2016, wannan adadi ya kai biliyan guda. Bayan haka, giraf din ya nuna shekarun da aka samar da wasu muhimman kafafen intanet kamar su:

³¹ Tim Berners-Lee da yake aiki a CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research) a Siwizalan (Switzerland) shi ya fara kirkiro kafar intanet a shekarar 1991. Kunshiyar kafar ta kasance game da intanet da yadda ake amfani da ita . Likau din da ya yi amfani da shi a wancan lokaci shi ne <http://info.cern.ch>. Domin karin bayani dangane da kafafen intanet, ana iya duba Armstrong (2019 SL. 1).

Jadawali Na 3: Samuwar Wasu Muhamman Kafafen Intanet

	Sunan Kafa	Shekarar Samarwa
1.	Yahoo (Yahu)	1994
2.	Google (Gogul)	1998
3.	Facebook (Fesbuk)	2004
4.	YouTube (Yutub)	2005
5.	Instagram (Insitagiram)	2010

A shekarar 2021, Armstrong ya fadada wannan bincike. Sabon binciken ya nuna cigaba da aka samu ta fuskar karuwar adadin kafafen intanet da ake da su a duniya. A duba sabon giraf din da ya samar a kasa:

Giraf Na 2.2: Adadin Kafafen Intanet a Shekarar 2021

Madogara: Armstrong (2021)

Yayin da aka nazarci giraf na 2.1 da 2.3 da aka kawo a sama, za a tabbatar da cewa duniya tana kara rungumar lamarin intanet. A shekarar 2019, akwai kiyasin kafafen intanet miliyan dubu ɗaya da ɗari bakwai da biyu (biliyan 1.72). Ya zuwa shekarar 2021 kuwa, sai ga adadin ya karu zuwa miliya dubu ɗaya da ɗari takwas da tamanin (biliyan 1.88). Wannan na nuna cewa, a cikin shekaru biyu kacal, an samu karuwar kimanin kafafen intanet miliyan ɗari da sittin (miliyan 160) a duniya.

2.1.2.2 Tasirin Intanet a Duniyar Yau

A yau, intanet ya zama wani ɓangare na rayuwar al'umma. A cikin giraf na 2.1 da 2.2 a babi na biyu, za a ga cewa a shekarar 1991 ne aka samar da kafar intanet ta farko. Ya zuwa shekarar 2017, adadin kafafen intanet sun kai biliyan ɗaya da miliyan ɗari bakwai da sitting (biliyan 1.76). Adadin ya sauka a shekarar 2018 da 2019. A 2019, adadin na kafafen intanet ya kasance kimanin biliyan ɗaya da miliyan ɗari bakwai da ashirin (biliyan 1.72). Adadin na kafafen intanet ya kara yawa a shekarar 2020 da kuma 2021. A shekarar 2021, adadin kafafen intanet sun kai biliyan ɗaya da miliyan ɗari takwas da tamanin (biliyan 1.88). Duk waɗannan alkaluma suna nuni ne ga yadda duniya ta rungumi al'amarin intanet.

A ɓangare guda kuwa, sama da rabin mutanen duniya ne suke amfani da intanet. An samu wannan rahoto daga kididdigar da *Statista* ta yi a farkon shekarar 2020. A yayin rubuta rahoton a kafar *Statista*, Clement (2020 SL. 2) ya bayyana cewa:

Almost 4.54 billion people were active internet users as of January 2020, encompassing 59 percent of the global population.

Fassarar Mai Bincike

Masu amfani da intanet ya zuwa watan Janairu na shekarar 2020 sun kai kimanin biliyan 4.54, wanda hakan ya kai kashi 59 na adadin mutanen duniya.

Giraf 2.3: Adadin Masu Amfani Da Intanet a Watan Janairu na Shekarar 2020

Madogara: Climent, (2020 SL. 1)

Ko bayan adadin mutanen da suke amfani da intanet, masu cudanya da duniyar intanet a kullum abin dubawa ne. Kowace kafa aka dauka za a tarar da akwai adadin mutane da suke ziyarta tare da gudanar da al'amura a kowace rana (wata ta fi wata yawan maziyyarta kwatankwacin ficenta da amfaninta). Wannan bincike ya yi yunkuri dauko hadahadar duniyar intanet da yake wakana a yanzu (shekarar 2024). Wannan

yunkuri ya ci tura sakamakon bayanan kai tsaye daga kafar da aka dogara a kanta wajen samun waɗannan alkaluma sun kafe a wannan lokaci, kamar yadda za a gani a cikin hoton da yake kasa:

Hoto Na 2.5: Bayanan *Kafar Internet Live Stats* a Kafe

Madogara: Internet Live Stats (2024 SL. 1-2)

A bisa dalilin kafewar bayanan wannan kafa, an yi amfani da waɗanda aka ɗauka ranar 20 ga watan Fabarairu na shekarar 2020. A wannan rana, an nazarci hadahadar da take gudana a duniyar intanet daidai karfe 11:30 na dare. A kasa an kawo bayanai game da alkaluman hadahadar duniyar intanet na wannan rana.

Hoto Na 2.6: Hadahadar Yau da Kullum ta Wasu Kafafen Intanet 1

Madogara: Internet Live Stats (2020 SL. 2)

A hoto na 2.6 da aka kawo a sama, za a iya lura cewa, sama da mutane biliyan biyar ne suka yi amfani da intanet ranar 20/02/2020. Adadin ya fi yawan rabin mutanen duniya. Wannan na nuni da tasirin intanet ga rayuwar al'umma. Har ila yau, adadin kafafen intanet masu aiki a wannan rana sun fi biliyan guda da miliyan dubu dari bakwai da hamsin da faya. Za a iya hasashen cewa, wannan adadi ya fi yawan adadin gidajen da suke duniya.³² A bangare guda kuwa, sakonnin imel da aka tura sun zarta biliyan dari biyu da hamsin da uku da miliyan dari da goma sha uku. Wannan ma na kara nuni ga yadda intanet ta zama wani bangaren rayuwar al'umma.

Hoto 2.7: Hadahadar Yau Da Kullum Ta Wasu Kafafen Intanet 2

Madogara: Internet Live Stats (2020 SL. 3)

A hoto na 2.7 da yake sama, za a iya lura cewa, an aiki tambayoyi sama da biliyan shida da miliyan dari takwas da hamsin da huɗu a Gogul a ranar 20/02/2020. Kada a manta da cewa, Gogul ba shi kafai ne injin nema a duniyar intanet ba.³³ A bangare guda kuwa, adadin sababbin labarai da aka dora a kan bulog-bulog a wannan rana

³² Kafar *The Conversation* ta wallafa rahoto a ranar 28 ga watan Fabrairun shekarar 2018 mai taken “*The world needs to build more than two billion new homes over the next 80 years*” wato “Akwai bukatar a gina sababbin gidaje sama da biliyan biyu a duniya a cikin shekaru 80 masu zuwa.” A cikin rahoton ta nuna cewa, gidajen da suke duniya sun kasance kimanin biliyan guda da fingo biyu (biliyan 1.2). A duba Smith (2018)

³³ Bayan Google akwai wafansu da dama da suka haɗa da AOL da Ask da Baidu da Bing da DuckDuckGo da sauransu.

sun haura miliyan shida da dubu ɗari biyar. Baya ga haka, an ɗora labarai sama da miliyan ɗari bakwai da hamsin da ɗaya a kafar Tuwita.³⁴

Hoto 2.8: Hadahadar Yau Da Kullum Ta Wasu Kafafen Intanet 3

Madogara: Internet Live Stats (2020 SL. 4)

A cikin hoto na 2. da aka kawo a sama, za a ga cewa, an kalli bidiyoyi sama da biliyan bakwai da miliyan ashirin da uku a Yutub a ranar 20/02/2020. Haka kuma, an ɗora hotuna sama da miliyan tamanin da biyu a kafar Insitagiram. La'akari da dukkanin waɗannan alkaluma, haƙiƙa intanet yana da matuƙar tasiri ga rayuwar al'umma.

Domin tantance cigaba da aka samu game da waɗannan alkaluma da suka daɗe,³⁵ an duba falkaluman da kafar *Worldometer*³⁶ ta bayar. An duba a ranar 1 ga watan Oktoba, shekarar 2025 daidai karfe 8:33 na dare.³⁷

³⁴ Yana da kyau a tuna cewa, adadin masu amfani da Fesbuk sun fi na waɗanda suke amfani da Tuwita nesa ba kusa ba. Wannan na nuna cewa, labaran da ake ɗorawa a Fesbuk ya wuce wannan adadi sosai.

³⁵ Bayanan sun tsufa kasancewar an ɗauke su tun a shekarar 2020. Ya zuwa shekarar 2025, sun kai tsawon shekaru biyar (5) ke nan.

³⁶ Worldometer (<https://www.worldometers.info/>) kafar intanet ce da ta shahara wajen samar da ƙididdigar alkaluman abubuwan da suke faruwa a lokacin da suke faruwa. Tana tattaro bayananta daga kafofi mabambanta ta amfani da fasahar intanet. American Library Association sun ayyana ta a matsayin kafa mai samar da bayanai masu nagarta.

³⁷ Kasancewar alkaluman suna cigaba da daɗuwa, kafin 12 daren wannan rana dole za su haura yadda suke a lokacin da aka ɗauko su.

Hoto Na 2.9: Hadahada a Wasu Kafafen Intanet

6,849,607,548	Internet users in the world today	[+]
279,367,318,988	Emails sent today	[+]
10,916,693	Blog posts written today	[+]
900,938,092	Tweets sent today	[+]
10,934,470,986	Google searches today	[+]

A hoto na 2.9 da yake sama, za a lura cewa an samu karuwar adadin mutanen da suke amfani da dukkannin waƙannan kafafen intanet idan aka kwatanta da yadda abin yake a shekarar 2020. Ga yadda bambance-bambancen ya kasance:

Jadawali Na 4: Karuwar Masu Amfani Da Kafafin Intanet (2020 da 2025)

Hadahada	2020	2025	Fifikon 2025 Kan 2020
Adadin masu amfani da intanet	4,481,081,889	6,849,607,548	2,368,525,659 (52.86%)
Adadin sakonnin imel da aka tura	253,113,097,224	279,367,318,988	26,254,221,764 (10.37%)
Adadin labarai da aka ɗora a kan bulog-bulog	6,550,597	10,916,693	4,366,096 (66.65%)
Adadin labarai da aka ɗora a kan Tuwita	751,526,101	900,938,092	149,411,991 (19.89%)
Adadin tambayoyin da aka aika a Gogul	6,854,869,102	10,934,407,986	4,079,538,884 (59.51%)

Madogara: Internet Live Stats da Worldometer

Chen et al. (2002 sh. 6) sun nazarci ayyuka daban-daban da aka gudanar game da tasirin intanet a kan al'ummomi. Ayyukan da suka nazarta sun haɗa da na Nie (2001) da Wellman (2001) da Nie et al. (2002). Bayan nazartar ayyukan, sun fitar da nau'o'in tasirin da intanet yake yi kan al'umma kamar haka:

- i. *The Internet decreases community* (Intanet yana samar da koma-baya ga al'umma)
- ii. *The Internet transforms community* (Intanet yana kawo sauye-sauye ga rayuwar al'umma)
- iii. *The Internet supplements community* (Intanet yana samar da wata al'umma ta daban)

Koma-baya da intanet yake haifarwa ga al'umma ya shafi fannonin rayuwarsu daban-daban. Daga cikinsu akwai yadda al'amuran nishaɗi da bata lokaci da intanet yake kunshe da su suke ɗauke wa mutane hankali da shagaltar da su. A haka ne al'umma take rungumar intanet a maimakon yin amfani da lokutansu wajen aikata ayyukan da za su taimake su a matsayin ɗaiɗaikun mutane, ko a matakin al'umma.

Sauye-sauyen da intanet ya zo da su kuwa nau'o'i biyu ne. Akwai masu amfani, akwai kuma waɗanda suke mazaunin ƙalubale.³⁸ A ɓangare guda kuwa, al'umma ta daban da intanet yake samarwa na nufin al'amura da hulɗayya da suke wanzuwa a duniyar intanet. Bayan nan, ya shafi yadda halaye da ɗabi'un mutane suke sauyawa sakamakon hulɗa da intanet.

³⁸ Saukafa sadarwa da kasuwanci da sauran nau'o'in hulɗoɗin al'umma cigaba ne da ya samu a sakamakon intanet. A ɓangare guda kuwa, akwai al'amuran da intanet ta zo da su waɗanda suka kasance koma-baya ko cikas ga al'adu da kuma zamantakewa. Sun haɗa da satar bayanan sirri da yaɗa alfasha da mugun aiki da cusa miyagun akidu da makamantansu.

Za a kara fahimtar tasirin intanet yayin da aka nazarci tasirin kafafen sada zumunta ga zamantakewar yau. A duniyar yau, kafafen sada zumunta sun zama wani ɓangare na rayuwar al'umma. Kusan za a iya cewa, duniyar mutane ba za ta iya rayuwa ba sai da su. Dalili kuwa shi ne, rayuwar mutane da dama ta dogara kacokan a kan ire-iren waɗannan kafafe. Nan ne cin su, nan ne shan su!³⁹

Binciken Ceci (2019 SL. 3) ya nuna cewa, masu amfani da kafar Whatsapp a watanni kafan bayan samar da kafar sun kai kimanin biliyan guda da miliyan ɗari biyar (1,005,000,000). Binciken da Jayasekara (2015), ya gudanar ya nuna cewa, ana samun karuwar masu amfani da kafafen sada zumunta matuƙa.

Masana da manazarta da dama sun yi bincike da rubuce-rubuce game da tasirin kafafen sadarwa a zamantakewa.⁴⁰ Siddiqui & Singh sun bayyana cewa:

Now a day's social media has been the important part of one's life from shopping to electronic mails, education and business tool. Social media plays a vital role in transforming people's life style. (Siddiqui & Singh, 2016 sh. 71)

Fassarar Mai Bincike

A yau, kafafen sada zumunta sun zama wani muhimmin ɓangare na rayuwar ɗan'adam tun daga kan sayayya da tura sakonni da ilimi har zuwa kasuwanci.

³⁹ A shekarar 2019, kafar intanet ɗin nan mai suna Sitatista da take adana bayanai dangane da kafafen intanet ta fitar da kididdigar ma'aikatan Fesbuk. Ta bayyana cewa, a shekarar 2018, ma'aikatan sun kai dubu ashirin da biyar da ɗari ɗaya da biyar (25,105). Ko bayan Fesbuk akwai manyan kafafen sada zumunta da suke da ɗimbin ma'aikata. Daga ciki har da Twitter da TikTok da makamantansu.

⁴⁰ Wasu daga cikin rubuce-rubucen sun haɗa da na Baruah (2012) da Korkmaz et al. (2014) da Owusu-Acheaw & Larson (2015) da Siddiqui & Singh (2016) da Dansabe (2019).

Kafafen sada zumunta suna taka muhimmiyar rawa dangane da salon rayuwar mutane.

Lallai wannan batu haka yake, domin kuwa ko a kasar Hausa akwai mutane da dama da suka raja'a matuƙa kan kafafen na sada zumunta. Akwai muhimman bangarorin rayuwa da waɗannan kafafe suka fi shafa. Sun haɗa da:

- i. Sana'o'i da kasuwanci
- ii. Ilimi da karantarwa
- iii. Nishadantarwa
- iv. Sada zumunta
- v. Tattaunawa a matakin daidaiƙu ko ƙungiyoyi

Tun farko dai waɗannan kafafe an samar da su ne domin sada zumunta. Misali, Fesbuk da aka samar a wajajen 2004, ya kasance hobɓasa ne na dalibin Jami'ar Harvard mai suna Mark Zuckerberg. Ya kirƙiri Fesbuk ne a matsayin kafar sada zumunta tsakanin daliban makarantar ta Harvard. Sannu a hankali daliban wasu makarantu na daban suka fara amfana da ita.⁴¹ A shekarar 2006 ne kuma aka fitar da ita a matsayin kafar sada zumunta da duniya gaba ɗaya za ta iya amfani da ita (Baruah, 2012 sh. 4; Ceci, 2019 SL. 2). A zuwa yau, Fesbuk ne yake kan gaba a duk cikin kafafen sada zumunta. Bayan shi, wasu daga cikin fitattun kafafen sada zumunta, su ne:

⁴¹ Makarantun da suka fara amfani da kafar sun haɗa da Columbia da Yale da Stanford (Ceci, 2019 SL. 2).

- a. Instagram
- b. Twitter
- c. WhatsApp

2.1.2.2.1 Tasirin Intanet Ga Hausawa

A yau, intanet ya yi matuƙar tasiri ga rayuwar Hausawa. Wannan tasiri ya shafi ɓangarori daban-daban, tun daga harshen kansa, har zuwa adabi da al'adun al'ummar. Al'ada da harshe da adabin Hausawa duk sun samu sauye-sauye a sakamakon tasirin zamani, musamman intanet. Dansabe (2019 sh. 138) yana da fahimtar cewa, kafafen sada zumunta suna taimakawa wajen haɓaka al'adun da suka haɗa da “abinci da sutura da sana'o'i da bukukuwa da tarbiyya da kuma zamantakewa.”

Tahir (2016) yana da fahimtar cewa, ta hanyar adana adabin baka a duniyar intanet ne kaɗai adabin harshe zai ci gaba da dauwama. Koma-bayan haka, sannu a hankali za a neme shi a rasa. Ya nuna cewa, matakin da za a iya ɗauka shi ne na adanawa da yaɗa adabin baka ta hanyar fasahar intanet. Ta haka ne za a samar da wani kamin kamin kundin adabin bakan (Tahir, 2016 sh. 133).⁴²

Wamba (2019 sh. 97) ya bayyana cewa: “Bayan sauyin zamani mai karfi na samuwar intanet, waƙoƙin baka sun samu haɓaka sosai.” Haɓakar waƙoƙin baka da aikin

Wamba (2019) yake magana a kansa zai iya shafar:

⁴² A Ingilishi ya rubuta cewa: *“The possible action that we take is to preserve and promote our oral traditions by the use of digital technology, creating a comprehensive and database of our oral traditions.”*

- a. Kafafen intanet da na sada zumunta da ake yada bidiyon waƙoƙi
- b. Yadda ake iya tura odiyo ko bidiyoyin waƙoƙin cikin sauki a wayoyi da sauran na'urori dangin kwamfuta ko memori na wayoyin hannu
- c. Yadda ake iya samar da manhajojin waƙoƙin sannan a dora su cikin rumbunan manhajoji kamar PlayStore da makamantansu
- d. Yadda ake daukar hannu daga salon waƙoƙi da kayan aikin hada waƙoƙi na waƙansu al'umma sakamakon kallo a kan intanet

Wani abin lura shi ne, binciken matakan adanawa da bunkasa harshe da al'ada da adabi na da matuƙar alaƙa da juna. Lura da tasirin da zamananci yake da shi a kan intanet, Yakasai (2010 sh. 126) yana da fahimtar cewa: "... a fili yake cewa matsalolin harshe a Nijeriya na buƙatar a yi wani abu na gaggawa domin adana harsunan gida, cikin kalubalen shirin zamanantar da duniya." Ya nuna cewa, ta wannan hanya ce kawai za a iya tabbatar da cigaban harshe da kuma al'adunsa. Ya jaddada cewa: "... duk kasar da ba ta ga fa'idar adana harsunanta ba, to kuwa ba za ta iya adana al'adunta ba, musamman ma da yake ta hanyar harshe kawai za a iya tabbatar da dorewar al'ada." Yakasai (2010 sh. 123).

A ɓangare guda kuwa, intanet yana da gurbi na musamman a harkar tsaro a yau. Hasali ma, koƙarin da ya fara samar da intanet an yi shi ne karkashin hukumar tsaro a Amurka kamar yadda binciken Bincike Gerf (2004 sh. 1360) da Mukoshy, (2015 sh. 21) suka tabbatar. Tasirinsa a yau a bayyane yake. Muhimmin bagire ne na yada farfagandar siyasa da yakin sunkuru.

Wani fannin da intanet ya yi tasiri a kan Hausawa shi ne a ɓangaren kasuwanci da san'o'insu. Ko a bayyane ana iya lura da hakan ta yadda sitatus-sitatus ɗin 'yammata da samari da dama suke cika da tallace-tallacen hajoji daban-daban. Ko da ma dai, sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet shi ne fashin bayan wannan bincike. Almajir (2013 sh. 9) da Rambo (2014 SL. 26) sun kawo yadda Hausawa suke kulla kasuwanci a kan intanet tare da amfani da katin banki wajen tura kuɗin sayayyar kaya. Aikin Mukoshy (2016) ma ya kawo yadda intanet yake taimakawa wajen samar da aikin yi da ba da damar gudanar da kasuwanci da biyan kuɗi ta kan intanet.

A kasa an taƙaita jerin amfanin intanet da aka zaƙulo daga cikin ayyukan binciken da aka ambata:

1. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen samun tallafi daga masu aikin jinkai a faɗin duniya, dangane da wata annoba ko wani aikin da ake son aiwatarwa.
2. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen yadfa bayanai cikin gaggawa.
3. Intanet yana ba da damar bayyana ra'ayoyi cikin sauki, waɗanda suka shafi siyasa da zamantakewa da makamantansu.
4. Intanet yana ba da damar kallon abubuwan da suke gudana kai tsaye a waɗansu wurare na kusa ko na nesa ta hanyar fasahar nuna abu kai tsaye (livestreaming).
5. Intanet yana ba da damar kauce wa hasarar kuɗi da dukiya ta hanyar adana kuɗi a bankunan zamani tare da amfani da tsarin taransifa.

6. Intanet yana ba da damar samar da makarantu da halartar su a saukake ba tare da wahalar da jiki ko neman wurin zama da bayyanannun kayan aikin koyarwa ba.
7. Intanet yana ba da damar samun bayanai masu muhimmanci game da fannonin rayuwa, kamar kiwon lafiya da tarihi da al'adu da al'ummomi da makamantansu.
8. Intanet yana ba da damar samun shawarwari daga abokai ko wafansu mutane da suke ba da haske da karfafa guiwa a kafafen intanet daban-daban.
9. Intanet yana samar da ayyukan yi ga mutane da dama.
10. Intanet yana samar da hanyoyin adana bayanai cikin sauki tare da kaiwa gare su a duk lokacin da ake bukata.
11. Intanet yana samar da hanyoyin gudanar da kasuwanci a saukake.
12. Intanet yana taimaka wa lafiyar kwakwalwa a matsayin wani abokin hira da debe kewa.
13. Intanet yana taimakawa a bangaren tafiye-tafiye, ta hanyar taswirorin wurare kamar *Google Map* da makamantansu.
14. Intanet yana taimakawa a bangaren tsaron kasa da na yankuna da na ma'aikatu.
15. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen adana muhimman bayanai da suka shafi al'adu da adabi da harshe da tarihi da sauran nau'o'in ilimummuka daban-daban.
16. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen aikin hadin guiwa cikin sauki tsakanin mutanen da suke da nisa da juna.

17. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen duba yanayi tare da tsara gudanar da lamura ta la'akari da yanayin da ake sa ran fuskanta, kamar ruwan sama ko iska da sauransu.
18. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen gwagwarmayar neman 'yanci, musamman ta hanyar shirya zanga-zangar lumana da tattauna ra'ayoyi da mafita game da waƙansu kalubalen danniya ko wariya ko rashin adalci da al'umma suke fuskanta.
19. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen kai saƙo ko samun saƙo daga wata uwa duniya, ko tura buƙatar wani abu kamar kiran direban mota da makamantansu.
20. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen rage cunkoson ababen hawa yayin da ya kasance mutane na ayyuka daga gida a maimakon zuwa ofisoshi.
21. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen sadarwa a saukake.
22. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen samar da dandali da gidajen nishadantarwa.
23. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen samun kawararrun ma'aikatan wucin-gadi (freelancers) domin gudanar da ayyuka masu buƙatar ƙwarewa da fasaha.
24. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen samun sababbin abokai.
25. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen sanya ido ga gida ko wurin aiki yayin da ake wani wuri na daban, ta hanyar kyamarorin zamani da suke tura hotuna da sautuka da bidiyoyi ta intanet.
26. Intanet yana taimakawa wajen fahimtar al'adun al'ummomi cikin sauki.

Duk waƙannan (da ma waƙansu da wataƙila tunani bai kai kan kansu ba) suna daga cikin nau'o'in alfanun da intanet ya zo da su, waƙanda kuma Hausawa suna daga cikin al'ummomin da suke cin gajiyarsu.

2.1.2.2.2 Tasirin Hausawa a Kan Intanet

Masu iya magana sun ce: "Idan an bugi jaki, sai a bugi taiki." A wannan gaba, yana da kyau a fahimci cewa tasirin da ake samu bai takaita ga wanda intanet yake yi a kan Hausa da Hausawa ba. Su ma Hausawa suna da tasiri a kan intanet. Ana iya fahimtar hakan tun daga yadda ake samar da gurabu da ba da kulawa ta musamman ga Hausa da Hausawa a intanet. Bugu da fari, a sau da dama akan ga hoton al'adunsu da addininsu a cikin hulfodinsu a kan intanet. Hakan ya yi daidai da bayanin Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma, inda akan samu al'adu da ra'ayoyi da addinin mutane sun yi tasiri a kan hulfodinsa na rayuwa baki daya.

A fannin kasuwancin kan intanet, an sanya Hausa a matsayin daya daga cikin harsunan da ake mu'amala da su a kan kafar hadahadar kuɗin intanet ta *Paxful* (<https://paxful.com>) a farkon shekarar 2021. Wannan yana nuni ga muhimmancin Hausawa a kan wannan kafa da tasirin da suke da shi na yin ciniki a cikinta . A duba hoton da yake kasa:

Hoto Na 2.10: Zabin Harshen Hausa a Kan Kafar Paxful

Madogara: Shafin shiga akawun din Paxful (<https://accounts.paxful.com/login/>)

Tasirin Hausa a duniyar intanet ya kai wani mataki inda har ta samu shiga cikin jerin harsunan da ake amfani da su a kafar Fesbuk. “Yanzu haka masu amfani da shafin da dama suna yi ne ta hanyar amfani da harshen Hausa a matsayin harshen umurni” (Morison a cikin ‘Yartsakuwa, 2017 sh. 26). Masu amfani da Fesbuk suna da damar mayar da saitin akawun dɪnsu cikin harshen Hausa.

Bayan haka, kamfanin Meta yana ba da dubban ɗaruruwan rubuce-rubuce da aka yi a kan Fesbuk domin a fassara su zuwa harshen Hausa. Duk wani rubutu da aka yi kan

Fesbuk cikin wasu harsuna daban, mutum yana da damar duba fassarorinsu cikin harshen Hausa. Idan ya kasance ba a fassara su zuwa Hausa ba a daidai lokacin da aka duba, injin ɗin Fesbuk zai yi kofarin fassara su ta hanyar amfani da ilimin makamantan fassarori da suka gabata. Hoton da yake kasa ya kawo misalin akawun ɗin Fesbuk cikin harshen Hausa:

Hoto 2.11: Tsarin Fesbuk Cikin Harshen Hausa

Madogara: Akawun Ɗin Abdulrahman Muhammad Manga na Fesbuk

A hoton da yake sama, za a iya lura da cewa akawun ɗin Fesbuk ɗin cikin harshen Hausa yake. Dukkanin ɓangarorin akawun ɗin an sanya sunayensu ne cikin harshen Hausa. Hakika wannan ci gaba ne sosai ga harshen. Hakan kuwa ya samo asali ne sakamakon tasirin da Hausawa suke da shi a wannan kafa ta Fesbuk, sakamakon yawansu da yanayin amfaninsu da kafar.

Yayin da aka bincika jerin harsunan da ake iya amfani da su a kan Fesbuk, za a tarar da cewa ba su kai ɗari da hamsin (150) ba (har ya zuwa ranar 17 ga watan Fabarairu na shekarar 2024). Kada a manta da cewa, harsunan duniya ba su gaza dubu bakwai (7,000) ba (Bunza, 2019 sh. 7). Ko Yoruba da Igbo da suke bi ma Hausa cikin harsunan Nijeriya ba su da gurbi a Fesbuk.

Bugu da ƙari, kamfanin Gogul ya daɗe da ba wa Hausa muhimmanci. Yakan fitar da dubban ɗaruruwan jumloli da kalmomi a-kai-a-kai domin fassara. Kamfanin yana da injin fassara wanda aka fi sani da *Google Online Translator* (Injin Din Fassarar Gogul Na Kan Intanet). Daga cikin harsunan da suke kan wannan tsari har da Hausa. Kasancewar harshen Hausa a kan wannan kafa na nuni da tasirinta a duniyar intanet. Manyan kamfanonin da suke ire-iren waɗannan muhimman ayyuka, ba sa yi har sai idan akwai wani alfanu da za su samu daga hakan.

Wani kalubale na wannannan injin ɗin fassara shi ne, yana iya kasancewa a ci karo da fassarar da ba ingantacciya ba. Hakan yana faruwa ne kasancewar yayin da jumlar da aka bincika ba ta da fassara a cikin injin ɗin, to injin zai kirkiri fassararta. Zai yi kirkiri fassarar ne ta hanyar amfani da ilimin fassarori makamantanta da suke kan injin ɗin. A kullum kamfanin yana ƙara inganta tsarin. A ƙasa an ba da misalin fassara mai inganci da marar inganci waɗanda aka ɗauko daga injin fassara na Gogul ranar 28 ga watan Fabrairun shekarar 2024:

Hoto 2.12: Fassara Mai Inganci Daga Injin Fassara na Gogul

Madogara: <https://www.google.com/search?q=english+to+hausa>

A hoton da aka kawo a sama, za a iya lura da cewa fassarar da injin na Gogul ya bayar tana da inganci. A kasa an kawo misalin fassara mai rauni (duba hoto na 2.13):

Hoto 2.13: Fassara Marar Inganci Daga Injin Fassara na Gogul

Madogara: <https://www.google.com/search?q=english+to+hausa>

A hoton da yake sama, za a iya lura da cewa, fassarar da injin na Gogul ya bayar tana da rauni. Ya fassara “liar” a matsayin “karya” a maimakon “makaryaciya”. Bayan haka,

bai yi amfani da bakin /k/ mai kugiya ba. Ko bayan haka, an yi amfani da Bagwariyar Hausa (suka ce) wanda hakan yake nuni da fassarar injin ce kai tsaye.

Ko bayan Gogul, akwai waƙansu injunan fassara a kafafen intanet waƙanda Hausa take ɗaya daga cikin harsunan da suke kansu (supported languages). Wasu kuwa kamusoshin fassara ne daga cikin harshen Hausa zuwa wasu harsuna daban, ko kuma daga wasu harsuna zuwa harshen Hausa. A kasa an kawo misalan wasu daga ciki:

1. Bargery Online Dictionary (Kamusun Bargery na Kan Intanet). Adiresinsa shi ne: <http://maguzawa.dyndns.ws/>.
2. Hausa Dictionary (Kamusun Hausa). Adiresinsa shi ne: http://hausadictionary.com/Main_Page.
3. Stars 21 (Taurari 21). Adiresinsa shi ne: https://www.stars21.com/translator/english_to_hausa.html.
4. Translation 2 (Fassara 2). Adiresinsa shi ne: <https://translation2.paralink.com/English-Hausa-Translator/>.
5. Translator (Mai fassara). Adiresinsa shi ne: <https://imtranslator.net/translation/hausa/to-english/translation/>.

Bugu da kari, akwai manhajojin fassara daban-daban da ake iya amfani da su a kan wayoyin salula. Ana iya sauke ire-irensu daga rumbunan manhajoji kamar PlayStore ko F-Droid da sauransu. A kasa an kawo misalai cikin hoto:

Hoto Na 2.14: Misalan Manhajojin Fassara Zuwa Harshen Hausa

Madogara: Rumbun Manhajoji na PlayStore.

A ɓangare guda kuwa, kafar Wikifidiya (Wikipedia) fitacciya ce a duniyar intanet.⁴³ Da wuya a binciki wata kalma a injin nema na Gogul ba tare da an ci karo da zaɓin Wikifidiya ya fito a shafin farko ba. Rubuce-rubucen wannan kafa ya shafi dukkanin ɓangarorin rayuwa tun daga kan siyasa da zamantakewa da addini da tarihi har zuwa kiwon lafiya da harsuna da al’adu da dai sauransu. A yanzu haka, wannan kafa ta fara samar da bayanai cikin harshen Hausa.⁴⁴ Babu makawa wannan kafa za ta taimaka wa harshen matuƙa wajen yaɗuwa da yayatuwa a duniya.⁴⁵ A fasa an kawo misalin shafin farko na wannan kafa cikin hoto.

⁴³ Domin ƙarin bayani a kan wannan kafa ana iya duba <https://wikipedia.org>.

⁴⁴ Shafin farko wanda ake kira “gida” (home page) na Hausa da yake kan kafar Wikifidiya yana da adireshi kamar haka: https://ha.wikipedia.org/wiki/Babban_shafi.

⁴⁵ Ya rage ga masana da manazarta Hausa da su shiga a dama da su cikin harkar bunƙasawa da inganta wannan kafa. Koma bayan haka, kafin a farga, ɓarnar da za a yi wa Hausa a ilimance ba za ta misaltu ba!

Hoto 2.15: Kafar Wikifidiya ta Hausa

Madogara: Shafin farko na Wikifidiyan Hausa ([https://ha.wikipedia.org/wiki/Babban shafi](https://ha.wikipedia.org/wiki/Babban_shafi))

A hoto na 2.15 da aka kawo a sama, za a iya lura da cewa wannan shafi na Wikifidiya cikin harshen Hausa yake. A zuwa lokacin da aka dauki hoton (ranar 28 ga watan Fabrairu, shekarar 2024), an dora rubuce-rubuce guda dubu talatin da takwas da dari biyar da sittin da bakwai (38,567) a kansa. Wannan ya nuna yadda shafin yake ci gaba sosai. Dalili kuwa shi ne, a ranar 25 ga watan Maris na shekarar 2020, makalun da suke kan shafin sun kasance dubu huɗu da dari bakwai da tara (4,709) kawai.

Za a iya fahimtar wani tasirin Hausawa a kan intanet daga al'amarin da ya faru na dakatar da ayyukan Tuwita (Twitter) a Nijeriya (5 ga watan Yunin shekarar 2021 zuwa 13 ga watan Janairun shekarar 2022). Duk da cewa wannan ya shafi Nijeriya ne baki daya, ba Hausawa kawai ba, Hausawan suna daga cikin waɗanda ake yawan kallon rubuce-rubucensu a kan wannan kafa. Katse harkallolin Tuwita a Nijeriya ya yanyo wa kamfanin hasarar kuɗaɗe masu tarin yawa.⁴⁶

⁴⁶ Domin samun karin bayani, ana iya duba BBC Hausa (2022).

Adadin Hausawan da suke kan manhajar TikTok ma yana nuni da tasirinsu a kan intanet. Dubban Hausawa maza da mata ne suke amfani da wannan kafa. Suna gudanar da harkalloli daban-daban tun daga kan abin da ya shafi barkwanci da nishadantarwa da wa'azantarwa har zuwa kan koyar da nau'o'in ilimomi daban-daban.⁴⁷

2.1.2.2.3 Illolin Intanet Ga Hausawa

Intanet hanjin jimina ne, akwai na ci akwai na zubarwa. Duk da dumbin alfanun da yake tattare da intanet, ya zo da tarin matsaloli da kalubale. Waƙannan kalubale sukan samu ne sakamakon ayyukan 'yan'adam. Daga cikinsu akwai waƙanda suka kasance gama-gari. Akwai kuma waƙanda suka shafi al'ummar Hausawa kai tsaye (da sauran al'ummu da suke al'adu da falsafa irin na Hausawa).

Rambo (2014 SL. 42-56) ya kawo waƙansu illolin intanet ga Hausawa. Sun haɗa da taɓarɓarewar tarbiyya da yada karya da haddasa gaba da tonon silili da makamantansu. Haka kuma, yana da fahimtar cewa intanet yana daga cikin dalilan da Hausawa suka rungumi rayuwar karya a yau, musamman domin burgewa a kafafen sada zumunta. Wannan fahimta ta yi daidai da ta Umar (2012 sh. 119-127) inda har ya jaddada cewa, wayoyin zamani suna daga cikin dalilan mace-macen auren Hausawa a yau.

Masana da manazarta daban-daban sun bayyana yadda intanet yake da tasiri a kan Hausa da Hausawa. Aikin Dansabe (2019) ya fi mayar da hankali a kan yadda intanet yake tasiri a kan al'ada da adabi. Dansabe (2019 sh. 143) ya zayyano illolin intanet

⁴⁷ Za a kawo cikakken bayanin harkokin Hausawa a kan TikTok a babi na huɗu.

musamman kafafen sada zumunta kamar haka: (a) gurbata tarbiyya da (b) koyar da shigar fitsara da (c) koyar da fasikanci da (d) durkusar da adabin Hausa.

Gobir & Sani (2021 sh. 117-120) sun nuna yadda intanet da kafafen sada zumunta suke haifar da dusashewar wasannin gargajiya na Hausawa, musamman wasannin kwaikwayo. Hakan yana faruwa ne yayin da hankula suke karkata a kan wasannin zamani da suke kan na'urori. Dusashewar wasannin kuwa yana haifar da gushewar dankon zamantakewa da cudanya tsakanin yara. A bangare guda kuwa, yana haifar da dusashewar wadannan al'adu masu matufar taimakon yara a fannin motsa jiki da fasaha da ilimantarwa da koyar da lissafi da sauran dabarun zaman duniya.

Kamar yadda Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma ya zayyana, tasirin al'adu da addini da ra'ayoyin al'umma yakan bayyana a hulfofinsu. A bisa wannan, dole ne Hausawa su rika cin karo da wasu bakin al'adu da fahimta da dabi'u na wasu al'ummu yayin da suke mu'amala da intanet.

Wadannan bayanai suna nuni da cewa, illolin da suke samuwa a sakamakon intanet (masu alaƙa da Hausawa, waɗanda kansu ne binciken ya mayar da hankali) sun haɗa da:

1. Akan yi amfani da intanet domin cin mutunci ko bata suna ga wani mutum ko wadansu mutane.
2. Ana iya dogaro sama da kima a kan intanet wanda hakan nakasu ne ga bunkasar basirar mutum. Wannan ya haɗa da neman kowane nau'in bayani ko mafita a kan intanet kai tsaye ba tare da amfani da basira wajen fokarin samun mafita ba.

3. Aurar intanet yana iya haifar da nakasu ga koyon muhimman lamuran zamantakewa, kamar jawabi ga mutane ko zurfafa tunani da yanke hukuncin da ya dace game da abubuwan da suke bukar nazarin.
4. Intanet kalubale ne ga sirrin duk wani mai amfani da ita .
5. Intanet yana haifar da salwantar waƙƙansu adabin baka.
6. Intanet yana haifar da tabarbarewar zamantakewa.
7. Intanet yana iya haifar da matsalolin da suka shafi rashin bacci yayin da yake ɗauke wa mutum hankali daga bin tsarin hutun da ya dace a bisa yanayin halittar ɗan'adam.
8. Intanet yana iya kasancewa hanyar damfara da zamba.
9. Intanet yana janyo bata lokaci da koma-baya ga gudanar da ayyuka yadda suka kamata.
10. Intanet yana kame zuciyar ta yadda har akan kwallafa rai da rungumar ta ba-ji-ba-gani.
11. Kwallafa rai a kan intanet yana iya haifar da kauracewa wa al'umma da zaman kafaici sama da kima wanda hakan ka iya shafar lafiyar mutum.
12. Labaran karya suna da saurin yaƙuwa sakamakon intanet.
13. Mutane suna hasarar kuɗaɗe a kan intanet yayin da suka bata datarsu ba ta hanyar wani abin da yake mai amfani a gare su ba.
14. Tarbiyya tana iya gurbacewa ta dalilin intanet.
15. Tasirin intanet yana haifar da mutuwar al'adu.

16. Yawan amfani da intanet yana iya illata lafiya, misali yin kiba sama da kima yayin da aka auri intanet, ko kuma ciwon ido na ɗan lokaci yayin da aka tsananta kallon fuskar na'ura.

2.1.3 Sana'o'i Da Kasuwanci a Faifan Zamani

Zamani ya yi tasiri matuƙa a kan ɓangarorin rayuwar Hausawa, ciki har da abin da ya shafi sana'o'i da kasuwancinsu. Akwai sana'o'in da aka samu sakamakon cudanya tsakanin Hausawa da wasu bakin al'ummu, kama sana'ar kanikanci da kafinta da ɗinkin keke da mesin da dai sauransu.

Cudanyar Hausawa da bakin al'ummu musamman Larabawa da Turawa da kuma sauyawan zamani sun samar da sauye-sauye da dama a fannin sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa.⁴⁸ Haka kuma, a har kullum Hausawa suna kara samun wayewa ta fuskar kasuwanci tare da faɗaɗawa da bunkasa sana'o'insu da kuma hanyoyin tanadinsu. Bunkasar kasuwancin Hausawa yana kasancewa cikin manyan sigogi guda biyu kamar haka:

1. **Bunkasar Kasuwanci:** Bunkasar kasuwanci yana faruwa ne yayin da ribar da ɗan kasuwa yake samu a cikin wani ayyanannen lokaci (misali wata guda) ta ƙaru. Wannan yana iya kasancewa sakamakon ɗaya daga cikin abubuwan da aka zayyano a ƙasa:
 - a. Faɗaɗar kasuwanci

⁴⁸ Wannan bincike yana da ra'ayin cewa, ko da Hausawa ba su yi cudanya da kowace al'umma ba, za su samu sauye-sauye da cigaban zamani a harkokin rayuwarsu. A har kullum halin rayuwa yana tilasta wa ɗan'adam amfani da fikira wajen sama wa kansa sauƙi da mafita daga kalubalen da yake dabaibaiye da matakan rayuwarsa. Sakamakon haka, yadda kullum yanayin duniya yake sauyawa tare da bullo da sababbin kalubale da ɗan'adam bai taɓa cin karo da su ba, haka yake ƙara ƙirƙiro hanyoyin fuskantar matsalolin. Waɗannan su ne suke haɗuwa su samar da cigaban zamani. Domin samun ƙarin bayani game da wannan mahangar falsafa, ana iya duba Cropley (2019).

- b. Daukakuwar darajar kasuwanci
- c. Raguwar kudaden da ake kashewa a kan sana'a⁴⁹

2. **Fadafar Kasuwanci:** Kasuwanci yana samun fadafa ne yayin da kayayyakin da yake samarwa suke isa hannun adadin mutane sama da yadda abin yake a baya. Wannan ma yana iya kasancewa ta fuskokin da suka hada da:

- a. Fadafar kasuwanci na cikin gida⁵⁰
- b. Fadafar kasuwanci na waje⁵¹

Yana da kyau a lura da cewa, dukannin matakan biyu (bunkasa da fadafar kasuwanci) suna samuwa sakamakon tasirin zamani. Dalilan samuwarsu sun hada da (i) saukakar hanyoyin sufuri da (ii) bunkasar hanyoyin sadarwa da (iii) sababbin matakan sarrafawa da makamantansu.

Ana iya kallon tasirin zamani kan kasuwancin Hausawa ta fuskoki daban-daban kamar haka:

- i. Kare-Kare
- ii. Kirkire-Kirkire
- iii. Hulfayya

Kamar yadda masu iya magana suke cewa, "ruwa ba ya tsami banza," akwai dalilai daban-daban da suke samar da waƙannan sauye-sauye a sha'anin kasuwancin

⁴⁹ Ana iya samun raguwar kudaden da ake kashewa wurin gudanar da sana'a ta hanyoyin da suka hada samun kayayyakin gudanar da ita mafiya sauki ko samun saukakan hanyoyin jigilar kayayyakinta zuwa wurin sarrafa su, da dai makamantansu.

⁵⁰ Wannan yana faruwa yayin da aka samu karin mutane a muhalli ko mafwabta ko cikin al'ummar mai sana da suka fara amfani da kayayyakin da mai sana'ar yake samarwa.

⁵¹ Wannan na faruwa yayin da waƙansu al'ummu na nesa suka fara amfani da kayayyakin da mai sana'a yake samarwa.

Hausawa. Idan aka ce “tasirin zamani,” dunksulallen zance ne da yake tattare da abubuwa mabambanta. Yayin da aka bankafa cikinsa, za a tarar da daidaiƙun dalilan da suka hada da:

- a. **Daukar Hannu:** Wannan ya shafi kwaikwayo daga fasahohin wafansu al’ummu na daban. Misali, a yau maƙeran Hausawa suna samar da kayayyaki daban-daban ta hanyar daukar hannu daga kere-kereƙen kasashen ketare. Haka ma kafintoci Hausawa suke kera sababbin nau’o’in abubuwan amfani ta hanyar daukar hannu. Babban misali shi ne bodin babbar mota (roka) da ake amfani da kataƙai da karafa wajen keraƙa.
- b. **Yanayi/Tilasci:** Sauyin yanayi da ya shafi rayuwa ko muhalli na kai ga an samar da sababbin kasuwanci tare da sauye-sauye a wafanda ake da su. Kasuwancin sayar da datar intanet da ta POS da Hausawa suka runguma a yau, duk misalai ne na sababbin nau’o’in kasuwanci da suka samu a sakamakon tasirin yanayi. Haka kuma awara/wara/kwai-da-kwai da take kara mamaye kasar Hausa tana da alaƙa da yanayin yunwa da talauci da Hausawa suke ciki (R.B. Adamu, keƙantacciyar tattaunawa, 8 ga watan Disamba 2023). A lokacin annobar korona kuwa (2019-2022), Hausawa da dama sun tara kuƙi ta hanyar kasuwancin takunkumin fuska (face mask).⁵²
- c. **Yayi:** Akan samu lokutan da yayi na wani nau’in kaya yake sauyawa. Sannu a hankali sai a sake shi a koma kan wani abu sabo. Irin wannan sauyi yana kasancewa cikin yanayin da abu ne mai wuya a iya bayanin mene ne haƙifanin

⁵² A matakin duniya, bincike ya nuna cewa, annobar korona ta sa an yi cinikin takunkumin fuska da ya kai na dala biliyan saba’in da huƙu da miliyan dari tara (\$74.90bn) a watanni huƙun farko na shekarar 2021 kawai. A duba Olaoluwa (2021) domin samun farin bayani.

dalilin da ya sa aka saki tsohuwar al'adar. Sau da dama sai dai a ce an samu sauyi ne sakamakon "wayewar zamani."⁵³

A ɗaya ɓangaren kuwa, an samu sauye-sauye game da hanyoyin tanadin Hausawa. Kamar yadda aka tattauna matakan tanadin Hausawa, a yau an samu sauye-sauye da kare-kare masu tarin yawa. Daya daga cikin misalan waɗannan sauye-sauye shi ne salon adashen zamani ('Yar kati).⁵⁴

A ɓangaren turkan dabbobi ma an samu sauye-sauye da suka haɗa da amfani da allurai da magunguna da sauran dabarun zamani da suke sa dabbobi girma da wuri tare da kare su daga waɗansu cututtuka. Asusu kuwa a yau ya koma kan bankuna daban-daban da kuma adana kuɗi ko kadara cikin nau'o'in kuɗaɗen intanet mabambanta.

Waɗannan bayanai duk sun shafi lamuran sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa ne a zamanance. La'akari da waɗannan sauye-sauye, akwai bukatar a yi bitar rabe-raben kasuwancin Hausawa. Hakan zai ba da damar ganin ko an samu karin nau'o'in kasuwanci?

⁵³ Babban misalin wannan shi ne yadda matasan Hausawa suka riki babban wando (fantalo) a matsayin kwalliya (tsukakken wando kuma ya kasance fauyanci), har zuwa wajajen shekarar 2008. Daga baya kuma sai yayi ya sauya, inda aka ɗauki fantalo a matsayin fauyanci, shi kuwa tsukakken wando ya koma wayewa. Duk lokacin da irin haka ya faru, masu kasuwancin wandunan dole su sauya domin samar da abubuwan da mutane za su saya ba waɗanda za su yi kwantai ba.

⁵⁴ Adashe 'yar kati wani nau'in adashe ne ko ajiyar kuɗi mai kama da tsarin banki. Babu wani takamaiman lokacin zubawa da lokacin ɗiba. Bayan haka, kowane mai zubawa yana cin gashin kansa ne, koma bayan na gargajiya da ake tarawa a ba wa mutum guda (mai ɗiba). Ana amfani da kati wajen adana bayanan zubawa da ɗiba da kuɗin mai ajiya. R. Muhammad, (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 6 ga watan Maris 2024).

2.1.3.1 Matakan Samar Da Rabe-Raben Sana'o'i a Zamanance

Akwai ayyuka da dama da suka gabaci wannan waƙanda suka yi ƙoƙarin kawo rabe-raben sana'o'i. Mafi yawansu sun raba sana'o'i ne zuwa rukunoni biyu, (i) na gargajiya da (ii) na zamani. Daga cikin waƙanda suka bi saƙun wannan rabo akwai Abdullahi (2018 sh. 23) da Nasir (2021 sh. 14-15).

Wannan binciken yana da fahimtar cewa, ba za a iya samun rabe-raben sana'o'i a kammale ba, har sai an ɗora shi bisa alƙaluma daban-daban. Sanyinnawal (2015 p 23-35) yana da irin wannan fahimta. Ya bi mataƙai daban-daban wajen samar da rabe-raben sana'o'i. A ciki har da jinsi da darajar sana'o'in a idon jama'a. Abdullahi (2021 sh. 70-73) ma ya yi ƙoƙarin bin mataƙan samar da rabe-raben sana'o'i. Ya kawo mataƙai da suka haɗa da *lokaci* da *jinsi* da kuma *ta la'akari da abubuwan da sana'o'in kan samar*.

A ɓangare guda kuwa Nasir (2021 sh. 14-15) ya rawaito inda Umar ya raba kasuwanci zuwa gida biyu: (i) Kasuwanci ta hannun dillali, da (ii) Kasuwanci kai tsaye. Daga ƙarshe kuwa, Nasir ya raba kasuwanci zuwa manyan kaso guda biyu ta la'akari da tasirin da zamani ya yi kan rayuwar Hausawa. Ya bayyana su a matsayin (i) Kasuwancin gargajiya, da (ii) Kasuwancin zamni.

Bayan nazartar ayyukan da suka gabata, wannan bincike ya yi amfani da alƙaluma daban-daban wajen samar da rabe-raben sana'o'i kamar haka:

2.1.3.1.1 Rabe-Raben Sana'o'i Ta La'akari da Jinsi

Yayin da aka yi la'akari da jinsi, za a iya raba nau'o'in kasuwancin Hausawa zuwa manyan rukunoni guda uku wato:

- a. Sana'o'in maza
- b. Sana'o'in mata
- c. Sana'o'in tarayya

2.1.3.1.1.1 Sana'o'in Maza

Wadannan su ne sana'o'in da al'ada ta shaidi maza zalla da gudanar da su. Sun haɗa da:

- | | | |
|------------|-----------------------|------------------|
| a. Dori | b. Dukanci | c. Farauta |
| d. Fatauci | e. Gini | f. Jima |
| g. Kira | h. Malantar gargajiya | i. Noma |
| j. Rini | k. Sassaka | l. Su/Kamun kifi |
- m. Wanzanci, da sauransu

2.1.3.1.1.2 Sana'o'in Mata

Wadannan su ne nau'o'in sana'o'in da al'adar Hausawa ta shaidi mata kaɗai da aiwatar da su. Sun haɗa da:

- | | | |
|-------------------|------------|--------------------------|
| a. 'Yar mai ganye | b. Aikatau | c. Kaɗi |
| d. Kitso | e. Kuku | f. Lalle/kunshi |
| g. Shika | h. Sussuka | i. Ungozoma, da sauransu |

2.1.3.1.1.3 Sana'o'in Tarayya

Wannan nau'o'in sana'o'i ne waɗanda a bisa al'adar Hausawa ta sanya maza da mata a matsayin masu gudanar da su. Sun haɗa da:

- | | | |
|------------------|-------------|----------------------|
| a. Arkomi | b. Dillanci | c. Fawa |
| d. Ginin tukwane | e. Jagale | f. Kiɗa |
| g. Kiwo | h. Kwarami | i. Noma |
| j. Roƙo | k. Saƙa | l. Waƙa, da sauransu |

2.1.3.1.2 Rabe-Raben Sana'o'i Ta La'akari Da Zamani

Ana iya samar da rabe-raben sana'o'in Hausawa ta la'akari da zamanin da sana'o'in suka samu. A farkashin wannan, za a ci karo da sana'o'in da suke da daɗaɗɗen tarihi a tsakanin Hausawa, waɗanda ake gudanar da su tun shekaru masu yawa da suka gabata. Ta fuska guda kuwa, akwai sana'o'in da Hausawa suka same su a zamanance. A takaice, ana iya raba sana'o'in Hausawa zuwa gida biyu a farkashin wannan rukuni, wato:

- a. Sana'o'in gargajiya
- b. Sana'o'in zamani.

2.1.3.1.2.1 Sana'o'in Gargajiya

Waɗannan su ne nau'o'in sana'o'in da suke da daɗaɗɗen tarihi a tsakanin Hausawa. Hausawa sun naƙalce su, sannan sun ci gaba da gudanar da su tun zamani mai tsawo da ya shuɗe. Misalansu sun haɗa da:

- a. Dukanci
- b. Farauta
- c. Sassafa
- d. Jima
- e. Kira
- f. Noma

- g. Saka
- h. Sassaka, da sauransu

2.1.3.1.2.2 Sana'o'in Zamani

Wadannan su ne nau'o'in sana'o'in da Hausawa suka koya a zamanance. Cudanyarsu da bakin al'ummu da kuma wayewa da sauye-sauyen zamani sun taka rawa wajen samuwa da bunkasar wadannan nau'o'in sana'o'i.

- a. Dinki
- b. Faci
- c. Kabukabu/acaba
- d. Kafintanci
- e. Kanikanci
- f. Tuki (mota)
- g. Walda, da sauransu

2.1.3.1.3 Rabe-Raben Sana'o'i Ta La'akari Da Tasirinsu Ga Rayuwa

Kowace sana'a ta shafi sarrafa wani abu domin samar da wani abu. Abin da ake sarrafawa da wanda ake samarwa yana iya kasancewa bayyananne, na duniyar zahiri (misali saka kaba domin samar da tabarma). Yana kuma iya kasancewa wanda ba a gani, na duniyar badini wato boyayyiyar gaskiya (misali sanya matakan tsaro a wani gida da yake kan intanet). Kowace sana'a tana da nau'in tasiri ko amfani da take da shi a rayuwa. Ana iya la'akari da tasirin wajen samar da rabe-raben sana'o'in Hausawa a yau. Misali:

- a. Samar da abinci
- b. Samar da kayan aiki
- c. Samar da sutura

- d. Kwalliya da gyaran jiki
- e. Samar da magunguna, da sauransu

2.1.3.1.3.1 Samar Da Abinci

Wadannan su ne nau'o'in sana'o'in da ta hanyarsu ne Hausawa suke samar da abinci tare da riskar da shi zuwa ga mutane daban-daban. Sana'o'in da suke farkashin wannan rukuni sun haɗa da:

- a. Awo
- b. Farauta
- c. Fawa
- d. Kiwo
- e. Noma
- f. Sakai
- g. Su/kamun kifi
- h. Awo, da sauransu

2.1.3.1.3.2 Samar Da Kayan Aiki

Wannan rukuni ne na nau'o'in sana'o'in Hausawa waɗanda ta hanyar su ne ake samun kayan aiki. Kayan aiki a nan na iya kasancewa na amfani a cikin gida ko a daji ko kuma waɗanda ake amfani da su wajen aiwatar da waɗansu sana'o'in na daban. Misalan sana'o'in da suke samar da kayan aiki sun haɗa da:

- a. Dukanci
- b. Gyartanci
- c. Jima
- d. Kaɗi
- e. Kira
- f. Sassaƙa, da sauransu

2.1.3.1.3.3 Samar Da Sutura

Hausawa suna da waɗansu fitattun sana’o’in da suka shahara wajen samar musu da sutura, tun daga kan kayan sakawa da na ɗaurawa har zuwa na sanyawa a kafa.

Wadannan sana’o’i sun haɗa da:

- a. Dukanci
- b. Dinki
- c. Jima
- d. Rini
- e. Saka

2.1.3.1.3.4 Sana’o’in Kwalliya Da Gyaran Jiki

Akwai sana’o’in Hausawa da suke taimakawa kai tsaye wajen ado da gyaran jiki. Sun haɗa da:

- a. Kitso
- b. Koli
- c. Kunshi/lalle
- d. Wanzanci

2.1.3.1.3.5 Sana’o’in Samar Da Magunguna

Wadannan su ne sana’o’in da babban amfaninsu shi ne samar da da magunguna. Magungunan nan suna iya kasancewa na wata cuta ko na biyan wasu bukatun zuciya.

Daga cikin sana’o’in akwai:

- a. Bokanci
- b. Bori
- c. Dori
- d. Magori

- e. 'Yar mai ganye

2.1.3.1.4 Rabe-Raben Sana'o'i Ta La'akari Da Matsayinsu a Cikin Sana'o'i

Daga cikin sana'o'in Hausawa, akwai waƙanda suke tamkar bishiyoyi, inda ake samun waƙansu sana'o'in na daban sun tsira daga cikinsu. Ma'ana a nan ita ce, sukan haifar da waƙansu sana'o'in a farkashinsu. Da a ce babu su, to lallai sana'o'in da suka dogara da su za su samu koma-baya, ko ma su daina wanzuwa kwata-kwata. A farkashin wannan rukuni ana iya samun manyan nau'o'in sana'o'i guda biyu kamar haka:

- i. Manyan sana'o'i
- ii. Kananan Sana'o'i

2.1.3.1.4.1 Manyan Sana'o'i

Manyan sana'o'i sun kasance masu taimakawa kai tsaye ga waƙansu sana'o'in na daban. Akan samu sana'o'i da suka dogara da su kai tsaye, ko dai don su samar musu da kayan aiki ko kuma domin su samar musu da kayayyakin gudanar da kasuwanci.

Ire-irensu sun haɗa da:

- a. Kiwo⁵⁵
- b. Kira⁵⁶
- c. Noma⁵⁷

⁵⁵ Sana'o'in da suke amfana da sana'ar kiwon dabbobi sun haɗa da fawa da jima da dukanci da kiɗa da kuma kira.

⁵⁶ Sana'ar tana taimakawa wajen samarwa da gyara waƙansu kayayyakin noma (kamar fartanya da garma/galma) da kitso (kamar kibiya) da aski (kamar aska) da fawa (kamar wuƙa) da makamantansu.

⁵⁷ Sana'o'i da dama sun samu ne a farkashinsa, kamar su sakai da sussuka da dakau da makamantansu.

2.1.3.1.4.2 Kananan Sana'o'i

Koma-bayan manya, kananan sana'o'i ba su da waƙansu sana'o'in da suka dogaro kai tsaye a kansu. Ma'ana, ba sa taka muhimmiyar rawa wajen samar da kayan aikin gudanar da waƙansu sana'o'i. A maimakon haka, yawanci al'umma suna amfani ne kai tsaye da kayayyakin da ire-iren sana'o'in suke samarwa. Misalansu sun haɗa da:

- a. Dakau
- b. Gyartai
- c. Kitso

2.1.3.1.5 Rabe-Raben Sana'o'i Ta La'akari Da Kimarsu

Kimarsana'o'i a nan na nufin darajarsu da ta masu aiwatar da su a idon al'umma. Wannan suna da alaƙa da gudummawar da suke bayarwa ga al'umma da kuma yanayin kuɗin da sana'o'in suke samarwa ga masu gudanar da su. A wannan ɓangare ma ana iya raba sana'o'i zuwa manyan rukunoni guda biyu:

- i. Masu kima
- ii. Marasa kima

2.1.3.1.5.1 Masu Kima

Waƙannan su ne nau'o'in sana'o'in da al'umma suka fi ganin darajarsu da darajar masu aiwatar da su. Sun haɗa da:

- a. Kira
- b. Masu jima a da
- c. Noma
- d. Wanzanci

2.1.3.1.5.2 Marasa Kima

Wannan rukuni ne na sana'o'in da al'umma ba ta fiye kallon su da daraja ba bisa al'adar rayuwa. Sun haɗa da:

- a. Dakau
- b. Gyartai
- c. Kitso
- d. Kwadago

Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, kima ko rashin kimar sana'a ya danganta ne da yadda al'umma suka ɗauke ta. Dangane da wannan, Sanyinnawal (2015 sh. 35) ya bayyana cewa:

Galibi sana'o'in yi wa jama'a hidima musamman waɗanda ake yi don gyaran jiki ana danganta su da sana'o'in da ba su da kima. Ba kuma don ba su da amfani ba, sai dai saboda ladar aikin da ake ba masu irin wannan sana'ar ba ta da wani yawa. Ire-iren waɗannan sana'o'i sun haɗa da: Wanzanci da igidi da sussuka (koda) da dakau da kitso da kwadago da fawa da garuwa (taula) da gyartai da faskare da ginar rijiya ko masai. Wani dalili da ke sa ake yi wa waɗannan sana'o'i kallon rashi kima shi ne wasu daga cikinsu talauci ko rashi ke haifar da su. Wasu kuma ɗabi'ar masu aiwatar da su ke jawo wa sana'o'in matsalar rashin ganin su da kima.

A nan za a iya lura da inda ya jaddada cewa, abubuwan da suke sa a ɗauki sana'a a matsayin marar kima sun haɗa da ɗabi'un masu aiwatar da sana'ar da kuma kasancewar talauci ne yake sa masu yin ta ci gaba da yi.

2.1.3.1.6 Rabe-Raben Sana'o'i Ta La'akari Da Duniyarsu

Wannan bincike yana da ra'ayin cewa akwai manyan duniyoyi biyu da Hausawa suke gudanar da sana'o'i a cikinsu a yau. Duniyoyi biyu da Hausawa suke gudanar da kasuwancinsu a cikinsu su ne:

- i. Duniyar zahiri
- ii. Duniyar intanet

2.1.3.1.6.1 Sana'o'in Duniyar Zahiri

Dukkannin sana'o'in Hausawa na gargajiya sun kasance na duniyar zahiri. Su ne waƙanda ake ganin su ko a taƙa su ko a shaidi sakamakon su a zahirance. Haka kuma, masu aiwatar da sana'o'in da waƙanda suke amfana da su, duk a duniyar zahiri suke tattaunawa. Nau'o'in su sana'o'in da zamani ya kawo wa Hausa, da dama daga cikinsu na duniyar zahiri ne. Misalansu sun haɗa da:

- a. Fawa
- b. Kaɗi
- c. Kisto
- d. Kira
- e. Noma
- f. Rini

2.1.3.1.6.2 Sana'o'in Duniyar Intanet

Sana'o'in duniyar intanet su ne waƙanda yayin gudanar da su, harƙallar mai saye da sayarwa takan kasance a cikinta. Takardar Sadat (2023 sh. 708) ta tabbatar da cewa, a yau akan yi sayayya cikin sauƙi a kan intanet. Lamari ne da yake ba wa mutum damar sayen kaya ko ya sayar da kaya ko ya nemi wanda zai yi masa wani aiki ko shi

ya yi wa wani aiki alhali masu wannan mu'amalar ba dole ne ya kasance sun taba ko da jin labarin ɓangarorin duniyar da kowannensu yake rayuwa ba.

Dahiru et al. (2014) sun bayyana yadda masu sana'o'i da kasuwanci daban-daban a Kano suke rungumar hanyoyin biyan kuɗi na zamani. Duk da a karshe sun nuna cewa, akwai karancin karɓar wannan sauyi na zamani (Dahiru et al., 2014 sh. 9). Binciken Enejo & Ojabo (2024) ya nuna cewa ana samun cigaba a wannan fannin. Duk da haka, binciken nasu ya gano cewa kimanin kashi ashirin (20%) na kanana da matsakaitan kasuwanci a yankin Arewacin Nijeriya ba su taba amfani da wani nau'in kasuwancin kan intanet ba (sh. 92). A takaice ke nan, har yanzu akwai buƙatar fara bincike domin fito da damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su na neman kuɗi a kan intanet.

Dogaro da kai ta hanyar kasuwanci yana fara zama abu mai sauƙi a yau. Hakan yana faruwa ne da taimakon intanet da yake bayar da damar riskar kwastomomi cikin sauƙi, da kuma sauyin tsarin kasuwancin kansa a duniyar yau. A yau, mutane suna da damar fara kasuwanci da kuɗi ɗan kalilan kawai. Hanyoyin samun kuɗi masu sauƙi da suke ƙoƙarin mamaye dukkannin ɓangarorin duniya sun haɗa da ƙirƙirar bidiyoyi da rubuce-rubuce domin ɗorawa a intanet.⁵⁸ Duk da haka, abubuwa daban-daban ne suke ba da ƙarfin guiwa ko kashe ƙarfin guiwa ga masu ƙoƙarin neman kuɗi a kan intanet. Kamar yadda Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma ya nuna, sun shafi dokoki da ƙa'idojin gwamnati da kuma tanade-tanaden addini da al'ada da fahimta da makamantansu.

⁵⁸ Waɗanda suka ɗora abubuwa a intanet suna da damar yin kasuwanci ko dai ta hanyar sayar da su abubuwan kansu, ko kuma ta hanyar ɗora tallace-tallace a kafafe da shafukansu.

Dangane da ayyuka a kan intanet kuwa, tsarin ya samu bunkasa musamman bayan bullowar annobar Korona. Masana'antu da hukumomi da dama sun ga damarmakin da suke tattare da aiki daga gida (ta kan intanet) (Ringle et al., 2020 sh. 88). Daga wannan lokaci an samu faruwar rungumar tsarin ayyuka ta kan intanet. A yau ya kasance wata alkibla wadda kasuwancin duniya ya saka a gaba.

A yanzu 'yan kasuwa ba sa cikin takunkumin takaita kasuwancinsu a muhalli daya, ko da kuwa karamin jari suke da shi. Wannan yana faruwa ne sakamakon shirin game-duniya da kuma wadatuwar hanyoyin cinikayya ta kan intanet (Mishrif & Khan, 2023 sh. 7-8). Ko 'yan kasuwan da ba su da damar buɗe kafafen intanet ɗin kasuwancinsu, suna da damar haɗa guiwa da manyan kafafe daban-daban domin gudanar da kasuwancin a kan intanet. Kasuwannin kan intanet irin su *Amazon* da *Alibaba* da *Shopify* sun yi fice a wannan fannin.

A nan akwai manyan batutuwa biyu waɗanda suka kamata hankali ya kai gare su. Na farko shi ne, sana'a tana iya kasancewa ta duniyar intanet kasancewar a nan ne ake kulla harkallar gudanar da ita. Tana iya kasancewa akwai makamanciyarta da ake gudanarwa a duniyar zahiri. Bambancinsu a nan kawai shi ne farfajiyar gudanarwa.

Misali:

- a. Dan Nijeriya yana iya yin aikin fassara da wani kamfani da yake Amurka, ba tare da ya taɓa jin murya ko kallon hoton waɗanda suke magana da shi daga kamfanin ba. Komai za a gudanar da shi ne a duniyar intanet.

- b. Bauhaushe yana iya buɗe shagon sayar da datar waya a kan intanet. Masu yi masa ciniki za su sayi kayayykinsa ne kawai kai tsaye daga intanet ba tare da sanin a duniyar da yake ba a wannan lokaci.

A ɓangare guda kuwa, sana'a tana iya kasancewa ta duniyar intanet zamowar abubuwan da ake sarrafawa ko samarwa a cikinta suke. Misali:

- a. Mai gina kafar intanet tamkar mai ginin gida yake a duniyar zahiri. Zai sayi fili da sunan gida sannan ya zana filin ya fitar da ɗakuna da zauruka da sauransu. Duk waɗannan a duniyar intanet za su kasance.
- b. Wanda ya sanya matakan tsaro a wata na'ura ko wani zaure a kan intanet, to ya yi hakan ne a cikin wata boyayyiyar duniya (duniyar intanet).

2.1.3.1.6.3 Bambance-Bambance Tsakanin Sana'o'in Duniyar Zahiri Da Na

Intanet

Akwai bambance-bambance tsakanin sana'o'in duniyar zahiri da waɗanda ake gudanarwa a duniyar intanet. Bangarorin da ake samun waɗannan bambance-bambance sun haɗa da:

- a. Abataya (Overtime) da alawus
- b. Damar yi wa kaya kallon ƙwaƙwaf
- c. Faɗaɗa
- d. Hanyoyin biyan kuɗi
- e. Hulɗa
- f. Lokacin aiwatar da kasuwanci
- g. Tallata kasuwanci
- h. Tsaro
- i. Wuraren ajiye kayan aiki da kayayyakin sayarwa da wurin zaman ma'aikata

j. Wurin aiwatar da aiki

An yi karin bayani game da su a cikin jadawali na 5 da yake kasa.

Jadawali Na 5: Bambance-Bambancen Sana'o'in Duniyar Zahiri Da Na Intanet

	Sana'o'in Duniyar Zahiri	Sana'o'in Duniyar Intanet
Abataya da alawus	Mai sana'ar duniyar zahiri na iya bukatar abataya ko wadansu alawus-alawus na tafiye-tafiye da wurin kwana da makamantansu.	Mai sana'ar duniyar intanet ba ya bukatar wurin kwana da kudaden tafiye-tafiye. ⁵⁹
Damar yi wa kaya kallon kwakwab	A sana'ar duniyar zahiri, kwastoma yana da damar yi wa kaya kallon kwakwaf, har ma ya taɓa ko ya jinjina, da makamantan hakan.	A sana'ar duniyar intanet, wanda zai sayi kaya yana da damar kallon hoto ko bidiyon kayan ne kawai. Ba zai iya kallon sa za a zahirance ba har sai idan an kawo masa shi (idan wanda ake kawowa ne).
Fadafa	Sana'ar duniyar zahiri tana bukatar mata kai masu yawa kafin fadafa zuwa wadansu yankuna na nesa. Sun hada da karin ma'aikata da ababan jigila kamar mota ko jirgi.	Fadafa sana'a zuwa bangarori daban-daban abu ne mai sauki ga mai sana'ar duniyar intanet. Zai yi hakan ne kawai ta hanyar dora bayanansa da na kasuwancinsa a kafafen intanet da masu neman ma'aikaci irinsa za su iya shiga.
Hanyoyin biyan kudi	A sana'o'in duniyar zahiri, ana iya biyan kudi hannu (takardu ko tsaba) ko a yi taransifa ko amfani da POS ko cek da makamantansu.	A sana'o'in duniyar intanet ba su da zabin biyan kudi hannu-da-hannu. Bayan haka, akan samu zaɓuɓɓukan hanyoyin biyan kudi masu tarin yawa. Misali, kafar Paxful tana ba da damar a biya kudi ta hanyoyi sama da dari huɗu da hamsin (450). ⁶⁰

⁵⁹ A maimakon abataya (overtime), ana iya samun *kudin gaggawa* ko *kudin uzzurawa* (rush fee).

⁶⁰ Domin samun karin bayani, ana iya duba su kai tsaye a kafar: <https://paxful.com/university/new-payment-methods>.

	Sana'o'in Duniyar Zahiri	Sana'o'in Duniyar Intanet
Hulfa	Mai sana'ar duniyar zahiri yana hulfa da kwastomominsa a zahiri. Suna iya kama hannayen juna domin gaisawa ko taba juna da makamantansu.	Mai sana'ar duniyar intanet ba ya hulfa ta gaba-da-gaba da kwastomominsa.
Lokacin aiwatar da kasuwanci	Yawanci mai gudanar da sana'a yana da takamaiman lokacin aiki a kowace rana ko mako. Misali, mai shagon aski na zamani yana iya budewa daga karfe 9:00 na safe zuwa karfe 9:00 na dare.	Girkakku ko saitattun sana'o'in kan intanet suna iya aiki a kowane lokaci. Misali, wanda ya saita shagonsa na sanyar da katin wutar lantarki, to masu ciniki na iya sayayya dare da rana ba tare da an ci karo da wani lokaci da shagon yake rufe ba.
	Mai sana'ar duniyar zahiri yana bukatar ya yi aiki a cikin wani kayyadadden lokaci. Misali, maginin zamani (mesin) yana da damar yin gini ne daga safe zuwa yamma kawai. ⁶¹	Mai aiwatar da sana'a yana da damar yin aiki a kowane lokaci tare da hutawa a kowane lokaci. Misali, wanda yake fassara dogon aiki a kan Trados, yana da damar dakatawa ya huta ko ya yi wata hidima a kowane lokaci sannan ya ci gaba da aiki a duk lokacin da ya ga dama.
Tallata kasuwanci	Hanyoyin tallata sana'ar duniyar zahiri sun hada da tattaunawar gaba-da-gaba da rama takardun talla da sanyawa a gidajen rediyo da talabijin da makamantansu. ⁶²	Tallata sana'a tana kasancewa a kan intanet kai tsaye.
Tsaro	Barazanar tsaro a wannan fannin ya shafi fasa shago ko	Barazanar tsaro a sana'o'in duniyar intanet ya fi shafar kutse

⁶¹ Akan samu lokutan da ake gudanar da ire-iren ayyukan nan har cikin dare. Hakan ba zai yiwu ba sai an yi waɗansu tanade-tanade na musamman, kamar samar da wadataccen haske da sauransu.

⁶² Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, a yau ana amfani da kafafen intanet domin tallata sana'o'in duniyar zahiri. Duk da haka, abin ba kamar na sana'o'in duniyar intanet yake ba. Dalili shi ne, sana'o'in duniyar zahiri ba su cika shafar al'ummomi da suke nesa da mai sana'a ba. Misali, kafintan fasa da yake Kano a Nijeriya, ba zai yi tunanin tallata hajarsa ga 'yan Amurka da Burtaniya da Kanada ba (sai dai idan ya bunkasa sosai da sosai).

	Sana'o'in Duniyar Zahiri	Sana'o'in Duniyar Intanet
	wurin aiki da satar kaya da makamantansu.	da tatsar bayanai ta bayan gida.
Wuraren ajiye kayan aiki da kayayyakin sayarwa da wurin zaman ma'aikata	Wanda yake da sana'ar da ta bunkasa, misali kafintan kasa, to yana bukatar wuraren ajiye kayan aikinsa da wuraren ajiye kayayyakin sayarwa (gadaje da kujeru da sauransu, waƙanda aka haɗa domin a sayar)	Wanda yake sana'a a duniyar intanet ba ya bukatar wurare a zahirance na ajiye kayayyakin sayarwa. A maimakon haka, yakan ajiye su ne a duniyar intanet cikin tsarin da ake kira <i>hosting</i> ko <i>storage</i> .
Wurin aiwatar da aiki	Yana iya kasancewa yana da wuri na musamman da ake gudanar da shi (kamar maƙera domin kira ko masaka domin saka)	Mai sana'a ko masu sana'a suna iya kasancewa a ko'ina. Farfajiyar aiwatar da sana'ar ita ce intanet (misali kafar Proz da ake ɗaukar hayar ma'aikata)
	Yana iya kasancewa ma'aikaci sai ya je wurin da ake bukatar aiwatar da aikin domin kera wani abu ko gyara wani abu (misali kafintan sama sai ya je gidan da aka gina kafin ya yi rufin kwano).	Mai sana'a ba ya bukatar ya je wurin da ake bukatar aiwatar da aiki (misali mai gina zaure a kan wata kafar intanet zai yi hakan a duk inda yake, alhali waƙanda zai yi wa aikin za su ga ya kammala a kan intanet).

Madogara: Lura ta kai tsaye da nazarin kwaƙƙwafi

2.2 Bitar Ra'i

An ɗora wannan bincike (a matsayinsa na binciken ilimi) a kan ra'i. Ra'in yana matsayin ka'idar da za ta zama fitila ko jagora ga binciken. Zai taimaka wajen fahimtar muhimman batutuwa da bayyana yadda abubuwa suke gudana da kuma gina sakamakon binciken bisa tsari da ka'idar binciken ilimi. Ka'idojin ra'in suna mazaunin wasu ginshikai da za a ɗora bayanai da fahimta a kai, domin a tabbatar da cewa binciken ba kawai tarin bayanai ba ne, face mai tsari da kuma tushe na ilimi.

Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma (Institutional Theory) shi ne ya yi wa aikin jagoranci. Wannan ra'i ya mayar da hankali kan bayanin yadda dokoki (regulative systems) da al'adu da dabi'u (normative systems), da kuma ra'ayoyi da akidu da suka zama ruwan dare ko wafanda aka saba da su (cognitive systems) suke tsara yadda mutane da fungiyoyi suke gudanar da harkokinsu. Daya daga cikin muhimman harkoki a rayuwar al'umma kuwa shi ne gudanar da sana'o'i da kasuwanci. Ka'idar ra'in tana jaddada cewa, mutane da fungiyoyi ba kara zube suke gudanar da harkokin yau da kullum ba (Woodhouse, 2024 sh. 213). Duk abubuwan da suke gudanarwa suna bisa ginshikai da suke tallafe da zamantakewar al'umma.

Masanan da suka assasa Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma sun haɗa da John W. Meyer da Brian Rowan (a shekarar 1977) da kuma Paul DiMaggio da Walter Powell (a shekarar 1983). Muhimman ayyukansu da suka tattauna wannan ra'i su ne (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Meyer & Rowan, 1977). Daga baya W. Richard Scott (a shekarun 1995, 2001, 2008) ya fayyace shi sosai a cikin jerin littattafai da ya rubuta (a duba Richard Scott, 1995, 2001, 2008).

Idan aka dora wannan bincike (wanda ya shafi Hausawa da damarmakin sana'o'i a intanet) a bisa alkaluman ra'in, za a samu fassarar cewa, ba samuwar fasahar intanet ba ce kaɗai take buɗe sababbin kofofin kasuwanci. Abubuwa daban-daban ne suke haɗuwa domin bayar da damar rungumar wannan sauyin zamani. A bayanan Mohamed (2017 sh. 151-154), sun haɗa da tsarin addini (religion) da al'ada (culture) da dokokin gwamnati (government regulations). Duk waɗannan suna da tasiri wajen zaburar da mutane domin karɓar wannan sauyi ko kuma kashe musu kwarin guiwa.

Babban misali a nan shi ne, ka'idodin addinin Musulunci (Islamic principles) game da halal da haram suna taka rawa wajen irin hajojin da ake tallatawa. A nan ne Hausawa masu dora tallace-tallace (advertisements) a kan kafafensu na intanet za su iya kauce wa waƙanda suka shafi giya da caca da sauran abubuwa ki a fuskar Musulunci. Su kuwa dokokin gwamnati da suka shafi kasuwanci da tsarin kuɗi na dijital (digital finance) (kamar POS da mobile money da taransifa ta banki da hulɗa da kuɗaɗen kasashen ketare) suke kara ko rage damar shiga a dama da mutane a harkokin kasuwancin kan intanet.

A bisa wannan, amfani da Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma a wannan bincike zai ba da dama a fahimci yadda waƙannan ginshikai na doka (regulative), al'ada (normative), da akida (cognitive) suke daidaitawa da karfafawa ko kuma kalubalantar Hausawa wajen cin moriyar damar kasuwanci ta hanyar intanet. Wannan yana nuni da cewa ra'in ya dace ya yi jagorancin binciken nan, domin yana haɗa zamantakewa (social context) da cigaban fasahar intanet (digital opportunity) a wuri guda. Kamar yadda Alvesson & Spicer (2019 sh. 214-216) suka bayyana, ra'in tamkar madubi ne wanda ta cikinsa za a iya fahimtar tsarin kasuwanci.

2.2.1 Muhimman Batutuwa a Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma

Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma (Institutional Theory) ya tafi kan cewa, abubuwan da ke tsara harkokin mutane da fungiyoyi ba kawai sun ta'allafa ne ga burinsu na samun riba ba. A maimakon haka, suna karkashin tasirin dokoki da al'adu da dabi'u da kuma ra'ayoyi da akidu da aka gina a cikin al'umma. Wannan rarrabewa

ya fito fili ne a cikin ayyukan Richard Scott (1995, 2001, 2008), wanda ya bayyana waƙannan muhimman batutuwa uku a matsayin “pillars” (ginshikai) na ra’in.

A - Ginshikin Doka (Regulative Pillar)

Wannan yana nufin tasirin dokoki (laws), ka’idoji (rules), da hukunce-hukunc (sanctions) da gwamnati ko hukumomi suka kafa wajen tsara yadda ake gudanar da aiki. Misali, a Najeriya, dokokin gwamnati kan kasuwanci da tsarin kuɗi na dijital (digital finance systems), da dokokin da suka shafi hanyoyin biyan kuɗi ta intanet (online payment systems) suna da matuƙar tasiri wajen yadda Hausawa suke gudanar da harkokin kasuwanci a yanar gizo. Idan doka ta ba da dama, kasuwanci zai bunkasa; idan ta kaƙaba takunkumai, to damarmakin shiga za su ragu. Game da wannan ne (Yuga & Anas, 2020) suka bayyana cewa:

The regulatory pillar is an institutional capacity that can establish rules, monitor compliance with its environment, and create sanctions in influencing environmental behavior, or it can be seen mechanically as a coercive mechanism. (Yuga & Anas, 2020 sh. 4)

Fassarar Mai Bincike

Kinshikin doka yana kasancewa ne a matakin hukuma wadda za ta iya samar da dokoki tare da sanya ido kan bin dokokin a cikin al’ummarta sannan ta samar da ka’idoji waƙanda suke da tasiri a kan yadda ake mu’amala a cikin al’ummartar, ko kuma ana iya kallon ta a matsayin wadda take da ƙarfin tirsasawa.

A kan haka ne Woodhouse (2024 sh. 215) ya nuna cewa, masana masu bin Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma ginu kan fahimtar: "Dokoki da ka'idojin hukuma su ne suke bayar da damar duk wani motsi a fannin tattalin arzki." Saboda haka, Ginshikin Doka (Regulative Pillar) yana nuna cewa, damar kasuwanci a kan intanet da Hausawa suke da ita ba wai kawai ta dogara ga fasaha ba ne, face ta hada har da yadda gwamnati take tsara dokoki.

B - Ginshikin Al'adu da Dabi'u (Normative Pillar)

Wannan ya shafi kimomi da tsare-tsare (values) da ka'idojin zamantakewa (social norms) da al'umma ta dauka a matsayin abin da ya dace ko wanda bai dace ba. Woodhouse (2024 sh. 214) ya bayyana cewa, hakan yana da tasiri a kan yanayin kasuwanci. A al'adar Hausawa, akwai dogaro sosai ga aminci (trust) da dawainiya da juna (reciprocity) da kuma bin dokokin addini (religious principles) musamman na Musulunci, kamar yadda ya zo a Aminu (2024 sh. 105-106). Wannan yana bayyana a kasuwancin intanet inda Hausawa masu yawa suke amfani da harshen Hausa da kalmomin addini kamar "amana" ko "halal" ko rantsuwa (kamar 'wallahi' ko 'na rantse da Allah') domin gina amincewa a tsakanin mai saye da mai sayarwa. Wannan ginshiki yana da matuƙar muhimmanci wajen fahimtar yadda al'adu da addini suke tsara damar kasuwanci ta kan intanet.

A bisa irin wannan fahimtar ce Khaby Lame wanda ya fi kowa mabiya a kafar TikTok ya gwammaci ya yi asarar miliyoyin kudafe a kan ya saba wa dokokin addininsa. Ya yi wannan asarar yayin da ya fi karɓar tallar 'giya' saboda hakan ya saba wa dokokin

addini (Kingdom Media, 2025). Wannan kuwa babban misali ne na yadda ginshikin nan yake da tasiri a fannin kasuwancin kan intanet.

Hausawa sukan buɗe zauruka a kafafen sada zumunta waɗanda suke ba da damar tattaunawa da kulla zumunci. Hakan yana nuna cewa, waɗannan harkokin neman kuɗi a intanet suna ci gaba da ɗaukar birbishin tsarin al’adun Hausawa. Ita kuwa al’adar sannu a hankali tana sauya zani zuwa turbar zamani. Bugu da ƙari, suna da dogon tarihi a harkar kasuwanci, kuma al’adunsu suna matuƙar tasiri a mu’amalolinsu na kasuwanci. Misali:

- a. **Aminci (trust):** Mai sayarwa da mai saye suna ganin gaskiya da rikon amana a matsayin ginshiki.
- b. **Addini (religion):** Musulunci yana ƙayyade irin hajojin da za a tallata (halal ko haram).
- c. **Zumunci da haɗin kai (social ties):** Amfani da kafafen sada zumunta kamar su WhatsApp da Facebook domin tallata kaya ga dangi da abokai.

Wannan ginshiki yana nuna cewa, kasuwancin intanet a tsakanin Hausawa yana tasirantuwa daga al’adunsu, duk da kuwa yana amfani da sabon siga da farfajiyar gudanarwa (digital platforms).

C - Ginshikin Akida da Ra’ayi da Fahimta (Cognitive Pillar)

Wannan ginshiki yana magana ne kan ra’ayoyi da akidu da fahimta (beliefs and assumptions) da mutane suka ginu a kansu, waɗanda aka ɗauka a matsayin gaskiya ta zahiri ko abin da ya kamata Jepperson & Meyer (2021 sh. 209). Misali, a cikin al’ummar Hausawa, akwai akidar cewa kasuwanci sana’ar mutunci ce, kuma an daɗe

ana kallon Hausawa a matsayin 'yan kasuwa. Wannan fahimta ta ci gaba da rayuwa har cikin duniyar intanet, inda za a iya ganin hakan a matsayin ci gaba na dabi'ar gargajiya ta kasuwanci.

Dagane da waƙannan ginshikai guda uku, Yuga & Anas (2020 sh. 4) sun jaddada cewa:

These three institutional pillar concepts can be applied in analyzing the innovation transformation process in various forms of business and social environments.

Fassarar Mai Bincike

Ana iya amfani da waƙannan ginshikai guda uku domin kalailaice matakan sauye-sauye da ake samu na cigaba a na'ukan kasuwanci daban-daban da kuma muhallan zamantakewa.

A bisa irin wannan fahimtar ce kuma aka dora binciken a kan wannan ra'in.

2.3 Bitar Ayyuka Masu Dangantaka Ta Kai Tsaye Da Aikin

An gina wannan bincike ne a matsayin ci gaba da binciken da aka gudanar kafinsa (kundi digiri na biyu), wato Sani (2022). A aikin da ya gabata, an nazarci yanayen-yanayen al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet da kuma ci gaba da koma-baya da kalubale da suke fuskanta. A takaice, aikin ya kasance sharar fage da za a gina batu a kansa game da sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

Wannan bincike ya ci karo da ayyuka da dama da suke da dangantaka da shi. Mafi yawansu an yi su ne cikin wasu harsuna ba Hausa ba. Wannan bangare na binciken zai bibiyi ayyukan da suka gabata waƙanda suke da matuƙar kama da binciken.

Hakan zai tabbatar da an kauce wa maimaita aikin da aka riga aka gudanar. Bugu da kari, nazartar ayyukan zai ba da haske tare da jagoranci ga wannan bincike. An kawo bitar daki-daki inda aka fara da kundayen digiri. Daga nan an gangaro kan litattattafai da mujallu da mukalu.⁶³

2.3.1 Kundayen Digiri

Wannan ɓangare na aikin yana ɗauke da bitar kundayen digiri a matakan ilimi daban-daban. An raba su zuwa manyan rukunoni guda uku, wato digiri na uku da na biyu da kuma na farko.

2.3.1.1 Kundayen Digiri Na Uku

Wannan bincike bai ci karo da wani kundin digiri na uku da yake da makusanciyar alaƙa da shi ba. Duk da haka, an ci karo da kundayen da suka taɓo batutuwa masu alaƙa da binciken da ake gudanarwa. Sun haɗa da aikin Nadama (1977). A cikin aikin an kawo batun zuwan Turawa kasar Hausa wanda shi ne ya yi sanadiyyar rugujewar daulolinta da dama. Dangantakar kundin nasa da wannan bincike kawai shi ne kasancewar dukkanninsu biyu sun taɓo batu kan sauye-sauyen da suke aukuwa sakamakon sauyin zamani. Hasali ma, a lokacin duniya ba ta fara gudanar da sana'o'i a kan intanet ba.

Kundin Akodu (1985) ya yi magana a kan sauye-sauyen da aka samu ga rayuwar Maguzawa a zamanance. 'Yar alaƙar da kundin yake da shi da wannan bincike ba ta

⁶³ Wannan ba shi ne kadai tsarin da ake bi wajen nazartar ayyukan da suka gabata ba. Akwai masana da suke da ra'ayin cewa ba za a raba ayyukan da aka nazarta zuwa rukunnai ba. A maimakon haka, za a bi tsarin shekaru ne (daga mafi dadewa zuwa mafi sabunta). Daga cikin masana masu wannan ra'ayi akwai Fraenkel & Wallen (2003) da McCombes (2023).

wuce batun zamananci ba. Bai tabo maganar intanet ba ballantana kasuwanci a cikinsa.

Binciken Bako, (1990) ya kalli tarihin zamantakewa da tattalin arzikin Sabon-Garin Kano daga 1913-1989. Aikin nasa yana da alaƙa da wannan bincike kasancewar ya dubi sauye-sauyen da kasuwanci ya samu cikin tsawon shekaru. Duk da haka, za a iya lura da cewa, a kadadar shekarun da ya ware, ba a ko fara gudanar da kasuwancin intanet na sosai ba.

Asiru, (2009) ya dubi sana'ar dinki da cigabanta a kasar Kano. A ciki ya nuna Hausawa sun samu sababbin dinkuna daga bakin al'ummu, ciki har da Girkawa. Hakan kuwa yana nuni ga tasirin zamani kan wannan sana'a. Binciken nasa yana da alaƙa da wannan aikin ta fuskar magana game da sana'a da sauye-sauyen zamani. Duk da haka sun bambanta kasancewar binciken nasa bai tabo sana'o'in Hausawa na duniyar intanet ba.

Binciken Sallau (2009) ma yana da 'yar alaƙa da wannan aiki kasancewar ya tabo batun sauye-sauyen da zamani ya samar ga sana'ar wanzanci. Duk da haka, bai yi maganar kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

Aikin Aminu (2015) kuwa ya mayar da hankali wajen nazartar nason al'adun Turawa a kan al'adun Hausawa musamman a lardin Sakkwato. Tarihin zuwan Turawa kuwa ba ya cika ba tare da an taɓo batun sauye-sauyen zamani ba. Hakan ne kuma abin da ya alaƙanta shi da binciken da ake gudanarwa. A ɓangare guda kuwa, kai tsaye sun bambanta kasancewar kundin nasa bai tabo kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

Kundin Rambo (2018) ya nazarci sana'ar sassaka da yadda take ga Hausawa. Duk da kundin ya taɓo batun tasirin zamani ga sana'ar da kuma yadda shirin game-duniya yake tasiri a kanta, kai tsaye sun bambanta da wannan bincike. Kundin nasa bai shafi nau'o'in sana'o'i da kasuwancin da Hausawa suka runguma a duniyar intanet ba.

Ibrahim, (2023) ya nazarci jima da dukanci a kasar Hausa jiya da yau. Ya yi amfani da kafafen sadarwa cikin hanyoyin gudanar da bincken. A shafi na 303-305 ya kawo tasirin shirin game duniya kan waɗannan sana'o'i. A ciki ya nuna yadda yanzu aka rungumi kafafen intanet wajen gudanar da cinakayya. Duk da haka, bai nazarci yadda sana'o'in duniyar intanet suke ba.

2.3.1.2 Kundayen Digiri Na Biyu

Aikin Nasir (2009) ya kasance yunkuri irinsa na farko a fagen karatun Hausa inda aka samu gabatar da tatsuniya a zamanance cikin sigar katun (hoto mai motsi). Kundin nasa yana da danganta da wannan aiki kasancewar dukansu biyu sun mayar da hankali kan Hausa a duniyar zamaninta. Hada hoto mai motsi yana daga cikin nau'o'in sana'o'in kan intanet. Duk da haka, ayyukan sun bambanta kasancewar na Nasir bai taɓo sana'o'i da kasuwanci na Hausawa a kan intanet kai tsaye ba.

Almajir (2009) ya yi rubutu kan yadda abubuwan zamani suka yi tasiri a kan rayuwar matasa Hausawa. Manya daga cikinsu sun shafi kafafen intanet. Daga ciki kuwa har da Fesbuk da Was'af a matsayin kafafen sadarwa. Akwai kuma kafafen da ake gurbata tarbiyya. Kundin Almajir yana da dangantaka da wannan bincike kasancewar dukansu sun shafi intanet da al'adun Hausawa. Duk da haka, Almajir bai mayar da hankali kan sana'o'i da kasuwancin da ake gudanarwa a duniyar intanet ba.

Binciken Sanda (2011) ya kalli gudummawar da Turawa suka ba wa sana'o'in mata, ciki har da abin da ya shafi ungozama da kitso. Kasancewar binciken ya shafi sana'o'i da tasirin zamani a kansu, hakan ne ya alaƙanta shi da wanda ake gudanarwa. Duk da haka, sun bambanta kai tsaye ta fuskar manufa da kunshiya.

Mukoshy (2015) ya ya yi kokarin tattara wasu muhimman kalmomin kwamfuta musamman waƙanda suka shafi intanet tare da samar da fassarorinsu. Kalmomin da ya fassara sun haɗa da na intanet da na kwamfuta da na burauzozi da makamantansu. Kundi nasa yana da dangantaka da wannan bincike kasancewar duka sun taɓo duniyar intanet. Bugu da ƙari, duka suna kira da faɗakar da Hausawa kan inganta matsayinsu a wannan duniya ta intanet. Duk da haka, ayyukan biyu mabambanta ne. Kundi Mukoshy ya mayar da hankali ne kan fassarawa da adana kalmomin fannu da suka shafi intanet da kwamfuta. Wannan aiki kuwa ya karkata ne kan nazartar sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

Faruk (2017) ya nazarci yadda biɗau ya ratsa ƙagaggun labaran zube na Hausa. Kundi nasa na da alaƙa da wannan aikin; kasancewar duk suna magana ne game da biɗa. Duk da haka, sun bambanta, domin kundi nasa ya mayar da hankali ne kan biɗau a matsayin wani tubalin gina labaran zube. Wannan bincike kuwa yana da manufar nazartar sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

Aikin Suleiman (2017) ya nazarci salon karɓa-karɓa a tattaunawar zaurukan kan intanet na Hausa. Alaƙar aikin nasa da wannan bincike shi ne batun duniyar intanet. Duk da haka, aikin nasa bai nazarci sana'o'in da Hausawan suke gudanarwa a duniyar intanet ba.

Wani aikin da yake da dangantaka da wannan bincike shi ne na Magaji (2018). Kundin ya bayyana cewa, hanyoyin sadarwar zamani sun yi tasiri a kan zumuncin Hausawa. Hanyoyin kuwa sun shafi kafafen intanet na sadarwa irin su Was'af da Fesbuk. Sanannen abu ne cewa zumunci yana daga cikin boyayyun al'adun Hausawa.⁶⁴ Kundin Magaji da wannan bincike sun yi tarayya kan batun tasirin intanet a kan al'adun Hausawa. Duk da haka, kundin na Magaji ya tafaita ne kawai a kan zumunci. Wannan bincike kuwa ya shafi sana'o'i da kasuwanci ne a duniyar intanet.

Kundin Shu'aibu (2018) ya nazarci take da kirarin kamfanonin sadarwa a Nijeriya na MTN da GLO da Etisalat (9mobile). Yana da kyau a tuna cewa, yawancin take da kirarin suna zuwa ne yayin tallace-tallacensu. Ko ba komai, kamfanonin baki daya suna da babban gurbi a fagen sana'o'in Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Duk da haka, aikin nasa bai nazarci sana'o'in Hausawa na intanet kai tsaye ba.

Binciken Abdullahi, (2021) ya nazarci yadda sana'o'i suke fitowa a cikin finafinai. Sana'o'in da ya duba sun hada da, farauta da kiwo da fawa da wanzanci da kitso. Finafinai na daga cikin abubuwan da suka samu a zamanance. Harkar fim kanta sana'a ce ta zamani. Wadannan kuwa su ne dangantar da take tsakin binciken nasa da wannan da ake gudanarwa. Duk da haka sun bambanta kasancewar bai kawo sana'o'in Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

Nasir, (2021) ya yi bincike a kan tasirin kungiyanci kan kasuwancin Hausawa a birnin Kano. A shafi na 15, ya kawo rabe-raben kasuwanci ta la'akari da tasirin zamani ga rayuwar Hausawa. Rabo na biyu da ya kawo shi ne "kasuwancin zamani," inda ya

⁶⁴ Rubuce-rubuce da dama sun tabbatar da "zumunci" a matsayin daya daga cikin boyayyun al'adun Hausawa. Daga cikinsu akwai Yahaya (2018 sh. 102) da Maikwari (2020 sh. 106).

bayyana cewa nau'in kasuwanci ne da ake gudanarwa a kan intanet. Kundin nasa bai kawo ire-iren sana'o'i da kasuwanci na Hausawa a kan intanet ba ballantana ya tattauna su. Wannan kuwa shi ne abin da binciken nan ya sa gaba.

Kundin Jibril (2023) ya yi kokarin nazartar d'aya daga cikin nau'o'in hanyoyin samun kuɗin da Hausawa suke cin gajiyarsa a duniyar intanet. Kundin ya takaita ne kawai a kan tallata haja a kafafen sada zumunta. Kadadarsa ta takaita kwarai ta fuskoki da dama da suka hada da jinsi (an zaɓi mata) da wuri (an takaita a Kano) da kafafen sada zumuntar (an takaita kan WhatsApp da Instagram). Duk da aikin yunkuri ne mai kyau na zaburar da Hausawa su shiga a dama da su cikin hanyoyin samun kuɗi na intanet, ya bar wagegen gibi da yake buƙatar cikewa. Hasali ma, ya kasance tamkar ganyen bishiya da yake makale a wani reshen babbar bishiya. Bishiyar kuwa ita ce, sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.

Ayyukan da suka yi magana game da kasuwanci da sana'o'in Hausawa sun hada da na: Musa, (1983) ya waiwaiyi tarihin wanzanci a kasar Hausa da yanaye-yanayensa da kuma tasirinsa ga rayuwar Hausawa. Aikin Sharifai (1990) take da kirarin wadansu sana'o'in Hausawa ya kawo tare da tsokaci kan muhimmanci da tasirinsu, misali wajen karfafa guiwa. Halliru, (1993) ya takaita ne a kan sana'o'i da hanyoyin bunkasa tattalin arzikin Hausawa na gargajiya kawai. Sallau, (2000) ya dubi wanzanci ne a matsayinsa na al'ada da sana'a. Shi kuwa Tanko, (2000), ya mayar da hankali ne a kan yadda al'adu da sana'o'in Hausawa suka yi tasiri kan na Gwarawa. Aikin Kabakawa, (2007) ya karkata ne a kan sana'o'in hannu na matan Hausawa kawai.

A bangare guda kuwa, duk da cewa aikin Ammani (2008) ya duba tasirin bakin al'ummu ne kan sana'o'in Hausawa, bai tattauna kasuwancin kan intanet ba. Aikin Umar, (2008) kuwa ya yi duba ne kan Hausar mata ma'aikata a Kano, musamman salon tafinsu. Aikin Bagudo (2010) ya mayar da hankali kan gudummawar da mata suke bayarwa ga sana'o'i a Sakkwato. Wushishi, (2011) ya yi duba ne kan dangantakar magunguna da wadansu sana'o'in gargajiya. Aikin Alti (2012) ya yi magana game da wasu dabarun gargajiya na kawar da talauci a birnin Katsina. Dalijam (2012) ya duba gudummawar da noma yake bayarwa ga tattalin arzikin Hausawa. Abubakar, (2016) sana'o'in rini da dinki ya kalla a Kudancin Katsina.

Mika'il (2017) ya yi kokarin zayyano bayanin kayayyakin noma da kira da fawa. Ibrahim (2017) ya nazarci Hausar 'yan gwanjo ne a garin Kano. Ya mayar da hankali kan 'yan gwanjon da suke kasuwar Wambai. Aliyu (2018) ya dubi yadda ake gudanar da sana'ar gwanjo ne a garin Sakkwato. Duk da ya duba tasirin zamani kan sana'ar, bai kawo ta a matsayin kasuwancin duniyar intanet ba. Ibrahim (2018) ya duba ire-iren tasirin da 'yan haye suke yi wa lamuran sana'o'in gargajiya. Ginsau (2018) ya yi zawarcin kayayyakin sana'o'in Hausawa a cikin karin maganganun Hausa. Kundin Mukhtar (2019) ya nazarci ire-iren sana'o'in da ake yi a cikin unguwannin birnin Zariya jiya da yau. Sauyin da zamani ya kawo a kan sana'o'in shi ne alafarsa da wannan bincike. Aikin Abubakar (2021) ya karkata ne kan duba rayuwa da tattalin arzikin mata a garin Kaduna. Tattalin arzikin bai shafi sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet ba. Kundin Shehu (2022) ya nazarci sana'ar fawa jiya da yau. Duk da akwai batun sauye-sauyen zamani a ciki, bai tafo sana'o'i a duniyar intanet ba.

Sauran ayyukan kundin digiri na biyu da suke da dangantaka ta nesa da wanan aiki sun haɗa da Inuwa (2000) da Akibu (2001) da N. M. Muhammad (2002) da Guibi (2006) da Adamu (2011) da Mu'azu (2021).

2.3.1.3 Kundayen Digiri Na Daya

Akan alaƙanta rauni ga kundayen digiri na farko. Hakan na faruwa ne kasancewar marubutansu sun kasance a matakin koyon rubutun kundin digiri karon farko. Duk da haka, wannan bincike ya karanci kundayen digiri na farko da suke da alaƙa da shi. An yi hakan ne musamman domin binciko ayyukan masana da manazarta da ire-iren waɗannan kundaye suka kafa hujja da su.

Aikin Sule (1986) ya yi magana a kan biɗa, amma a matsayin salo a cikin kaƙaggun labarai. Kundin Makuwana (2011) ya nazarci yadda Hausa ta yaɗu a duniyar intanet. Yaɗuwar ta haɗa da kafafen intanet daban-daban da kuma kafafen sada zumunta. Abin da ya bambanta kundin da wannan bincike shi ne, Makuwana ya mayar da hankali ne a kan nazartar bunkasar Hausa a duniyar intanet. Wannan bincike kuwa yana da manufar nazartar sana'o'i da kasuwanci na Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

Ashiru (2012) ya rubuta kundin digiri na farko wanda yake da dangantaka da wannan bincike. A ciki an nazarci hanyoyi daban-daban da adabin Hausawa yake bunkasa a dalilin intanet. Sun haɗa da rubuce-rubucen adabi da suke kan kafafen intanet. Bugu da kari, akan dora waƙoƙin Hausa har ma da littattafai da aka karanta a matsayin odiyo. A takaice, kundin ya mayar da hankali kan yaɗuwar adabin Hausawa a intanet. Bambancinsu shi ne, wannan nazari ya mayar da hankali ne kan sana'o'i da kasuwanci na Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

Aikin 'Yartsakuwa (2017) ya mayar da hankali wajen nazartar sadarwa a kafar intanet ta Whatsapp. Daga shafi na 15 zuwa na 17, an kawo tarihin intanet. A shafi na 37, an kawo illolin intanet a kan al'adun Hausawa. Illolin sun fi shafar gurbata tarbiyya da bata lokaci. Kundin yana da alaƙa da wannan bincike musamman la'akari da cewa dukkansu sun mayar da hankali a kan al'adun Hausawa da duniyar intanet. Duk da haka, kundin 'Yartsakuwa ya fi karkata a kan sadarwa a intanet. Bai bibiyi lamarin sana'o'i da kasuwancinsu a duniyar intanet ba.

Sauran kundayen digiri na farko da aka duba masu 'yar alaƙa da bida ko tanadi ko duniyar intanet sun haɗa da na: Sambo (2009) da Nura (2019) Ahmad (2023) da Junaidu (2023) da Hoang (2023) da Umar (2023).

2.3.2 Bugaggun Makalu

Almajir (2008) ya rubuta maƙala wadda ta mayar da hankali a kan nazartar matsayin Hausawa a duniyar intanet da yadda ake amfani da ita wajen sadarwa. Duk da maƙalar tasa ta shafi Hausa a duniyar intanet, bai taɓo sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa ba.

Maƙalar Yakasai (2010) ta nazarci tasirin shirin zamanantar da duniya a kan nazarin harshe a Nijeriya. A ciki ya nuna dole ne a yi foƙarin shiga zamani don tabbatar da ba a bar harsunan Nijeriya a baya ba, ciki kuwa har da Hausa. Duk da haka, maƙalar tasa ba ta taɓo sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

Garba (2013) ya nazarci Hausa a kafafen sadarwa na intanet. Duk da ya yi magana game da Hausa a duniyar intanet, maƙalar tasa ta fi karkata a kan harshen Hausa. Bai kawo batun sana'o'i da kasuwanci ba.

Sarbi (2013) ya nuna yadda fassara take taimaka wa cigaban tattalin arzikin kasa. Fassara kuwa tana daya daga cikin hanyoyin bidar da wadansu Hausawa suke cin gajiyarta a yau a duniyar intanet. Duk da haka, makalar tasa ba ta kalli wannan bangare na sana'o'in duniyar intanet ba. Makalar tasa tana kama da ta Shehu (2013) inda ya nazarci yadda ake gurbata ma'ana a Hausar gidan rediyon Iran.

Makalar Dahiru et al., (2014) ta nazarci yadda 'yan kasuwa da masu sana'o'i a Kano suke rungumar hanyoyin biyan kudi masu alaƙa da intanet. A ciki har da amfani da *e-wallet* da *POS* da intanet da sauransu (sh. 8). Makalar tasu tana da alaƙa da wannan bincike musamman da yake Kano kasar Hausa ce. Duk da haka, ba su faɗaɗa bincike ba zuwa damarmakin neman kudi a kan intanet da Hausawa suke da shi.

Faruk (2016) ya nazarci yadda akan yi amfani da *bidau* wajen gina tatsuniyoyi. Ya fi mayar da hankali kan tatsuniyoyin da suka fito a cikin littafin Bukar Usman mai suna *Taskar Tatsuniyoyi*. Bidau din da ya yi aiki a kai ya shafi adabi ne. Hakan kuwa ya bambanta aikin nasa kai tsaye da wannan bincike.

Tahir (2016) ya yi rubutu game da taskace adabin baka na Hausa a intanet. Duk da aikin nasa ya shafi Hausa da duniyar intanet, bai tabo sana'o'in Hausawa ba.

Aikin Sallau (2017) ya kawo yadda zamani ya yi tasiri kan sana'ar wanzanci. Makalar tasa ta yi tarayya da wannan bincike ta fuskar nazarin da ya shafi zamananci da sana'a. Duk da haka, aikin nasa ya takaita ne a kan sana'ar wanzanci, sannan bai dubi duniyar intanet ba.

Binciken Nasiru (2018) ya nazarci yadda bida take zaman wata al'ada mai matuƙar tasiri wurin haifar da kaura. A cikin takardar, ya bayyana yadda aka samu kaura

tsakanin Agades da sauran sassan kasar Hausa. Duk da ya kawo bidar arziki a matsayin daya daga cikin nau'o'in bida da yake fitar da Hausawa daga gidajensu, bai taɓo lamarin bidar a duniyar intanet ba.

Makarar Shehu & Aliyu (2019) ta mayar da hankali wajen nazartar illolin wayar salula a ga al'adun Hausawa. Daga shafin 708 zuwa 710, makalar ta bibiyi yadda shafukan intanet suke gurbata tarbiyya. Ta fi mayar da hankali a kan shafukan Fesbuk da Was'ap. Duk da makalar ta taɓo waɗansu al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet, ba ta tattauna sana'o'in Hausawan ba.

Shehu & Rambo (2019) sun rubuta makala wadda ta yi kokarin fito da yadda kafar intanet ta Was'af take lalata tarbiyyar Hausawa. A shafi na 359, makalar ta kawo ire-iren sakonni da ake iya turawa ta kafar Was'af. Sun haɗa da rubutu da sautin magana da kuma bidiyo. Daga nan sai suka mayar da hankali wajen bayyana hanyoyin da wannan kafar intanet take gurbata tarbiyya. Duk da makalar ta taɓo al'adun Hausawa da na'urar zamani da intanet, sun bambanta da wannan bincike kasancewar ba ta kawo batun sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa ba.

Slyanbola & Patrick (2020) sun nazarci yadda wasu 'yan Nijeriya suke tallakata kayan fatu a kan intanet (nau'in takalma da jakakkuna). Duk da aikin nasu ya haɗa har da kasar Hausa da kuma kasuwancin kan intanet, ya bar gibi kasancewar bai mayar da hankali kan damarmakin neman kuɗi a kan intanet ba.

Makarar Sadat (2023) ta yi bayani game da tasirin da kirƙirarriyar basira (AI) take da shi a kan sana'o'i da kasuwanci a yau. Abin da ya bambanta su da wannan bincike shi

ne farfajiyar gudanarwa da kuma makasudai. Wannan ya takaita ne a kan damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su na sana'o'i a kan intanet.

Enejo & Ojabo (2024) sun yi bincike kan yadda kanana da matsakaitan 'yan kasuwa a Arewacin Nijeriya suka karɓar tsarin kasuwancin kan intanet. Sun fahimci cewa, ana samun cigaba sosai a fannin. Amma duk da haka, akwai kalubale mai yawa da ake fuskanta. Ciki har da matsalar intanet da rashin karɓar sauyi da karancin ilimi a fannin, da sauransu (sh. 91). Duk da haka, makalar tasu ta bar gibi game da damarmakin da Hausawa suke da shi ne neman kuɗi a ta hanyar intanet.

Sauran bugaggun makalu da aka nazarta masu 'yar alaƙa da wannan bincike sun haɗa da: Azare & Abdullahi, (2016) da Faruk (2018) da Dansabe (2019) da Musa & Yusuf (2019).

2.3.3 Makalu

Makalar Amfani (2010) ta mayar da hankali kan kalomomin intanet na Hausa. Ta kawo kalmomi da dama da ake amfani da su a harshen Hausa waɗanda suka shafi intanet. Hakika makalar ta Amfani tana da dangantaka da wannan bincike kasancewar duk sun tabo intanet da kuma Hausawa. Duk da haka suna da bambanci domin binciken nasa ya takaita ne a kadadar harshen Hausa. Wannan bincike kuwa ya fi mayar da hankali kan al'ada, wato sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

A shekarar 2013 an fitar da gagarumin aiki da ya shafi al'ada da zamananci. Hukumar Raya Tarihi da Al'adu ta Jahar Katsina (*Katsina State History and Culture Bureau*) ita ce ta gudanar da gagarumin taron kara wa juna sani tare da haɗin guiwar Jami'ar

Umaru Musa 'Yar'aduwa, Katsina. An tattara mukalun da aka gabatar yayin wannan taro inda aka wallafa su a matsayin babban kundi a watan Yuni na shekarar 2013. Littafin ya kunshi mukalu da suke da alaƙa da wanna aiki. Daga cikinsu akwai J. S. Adamu (2013)⁶⁵ da A. A. Ahmad (2013)⁶⁶ da S. A. Garba (2013a)⁶⁷ da Getso (2013)⁶⁸ da Guibi & Bakori (2013)⁶⁹ da Isah (2013)⁷⁰ da Kiyawa (2013)⁷¹ da Mai'aduwa (2013)⁷² da Mwami (2013)⁷³ da I. Shehu (2013)⁷⁴ da Sulaiman (2013)⁷⁵ da B. U. Umar (2013).⁷⁶

Mafakar Mukoshy & Umar (2013) ta mayar da hankali wajen nazartar yadda za a iya bunkasa karatun Hausa ta hanyar amfani da intanet. Ta bayyana yadda intanet yake taimakawa a harkar ilimi, musamman abin da ya shafi d'akunan karatu bisa intanet da mujallun da suke kan intanet da makamantansu. Mafakar tasu tana da dangantaka da wannan bincike musamman idan aka duba kiran da ta yi cewa: "Mafakar tana kira ga

⁶⁵ Ya fito da gudummuwar shirye-shiryen gidan radiyon Muryar Jama'a, Kano wajen kare taɓarbarewar al'adun Hausawa. Ya fi mayar da hankali kan shirin 'Aiki Da Hankali' da 'Tamburan Kano.' Bai taɓo sana'o'in Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

⁶⁶ Ya nazarci ire-iren tasirin da wayar salula ta samar a kan al'adun Hausawa. Za a iya lura da cewa, bai mayar da hankali wajen nazartar hanyoyin biɗa ko tanadi na Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

⁶⁷ Ya duba yanayin auren zoben Bahaushe a karni na 21. Ya d'ora gidan Rediyon Rahama 97.3 FM a faifan al'ada. Shi ma wannan bai taɓo sana'o'in Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet ba.

⁶⁸ Ya nazarci irin rawar da kafafen yaɗa labarai suke takawa wajen bunkasawa ko ruguza al'adun Hausawa. Shi ma wannan bai taɓo sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet ba.

⁶⁹ Mafakar ta nazarci rawar da kafafen yaɗa labarai suke takawa kan al'adun Hausawa. Suna iya bunkasa su ko su janyo taɓarɓarwarsu. Ita ma ba ta bai taɓo sana'o'in Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet ba.

⁷⁰ Ya taƙaita nazarinsa kan rawar da gidan rediyon Companion FM 104.5 Mhz Katsina yake takawa wajen bunkasa al'adun Hausawa.

⁷¹ Aikin ya taƙaita kan nazartar tasirin finafinai a kan tarbiyyar Bahaushe.

⁷² Shi ma wannan nazari ya taƙaita kan nazartar tasirin finafinai a kan tarbiyyar Bahaushe.

⁷³ Ya nazarci yadda finafinai suke haifar da taɓarɓarwar tarbiyyar Hausawa. Ya nuna cewa wannan ya kara ruruta wutar samuwar daba.

⁷⁴ Wannan nazari ya kebanta kan duba tasirin wasannin kwaikwayon gidajen rediyo wajen bunkasa al'adun Hausawa. Ya fi mayar da hankali kan shirin 'Duniya Budurwar Wawa' da 'Jami'ar Jatau Na Albarkawa.'

⁷⁵ Takardar ta nazarci tasirin finafinai wajen gurbata tarbiya, musamman abin da ya danganci fyaɗe.

⁷⁶ Mafakar ta nazarci wata addu'ar da 'yammata suke yi wadda ta yaɗu a cikin wayar salula. Ta nuna cewa, zamananci ya yi tasiri a kan al'amarin zaɓen mijin aure a yau.

ɗalibai da manazarta Hausa da su kara kokari wajen amfani da intanet wajen taskace sahihan bayanai domin bunkasa bincike da nazarin harshen Hausa” (Mukoshy & Umar, 2013 sh. 10). Duk da haka, ba ta tattauna sana’o’i da kasuwanci na Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

Idris (2015) ya yi bincike dangane da yadda masu aikin fassara da sauran rubuce-rubuce a kan intanet da na’urori suke shan wahala wajen rubuta bakafake masu kugiya (K, k, D, d, B, b). Tarayyar takardar tasa da wannan bincike ita ce kasancewar dukkanninsu sun tabo kalubalen sana’o’i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Duk da haka, takardar tasa ta takaita ne a kan rubutun bakafen Hausa masu kugiya. Yana da kyau a lura cewa, a yanzu an wuce babin wannan matsalar tun bayan da kamfanin Microsoft (Microsoft Corporation) ya samar da hanyar rubuta su.

Makarar Mukoshy (2016) ta yi kokarin bayyana wasu hanyoyin kasuwanci da hadahada a duniyar intanet wadanda za su iya taimaka wa tattalin arzikin Hausawa. Sun hada da kasuwanci a intanet, da biyan kuɗi ta intanet. Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, makalar ta fi ba da karfi a bangaren harshe. Bayan haka, ta dubi hadahadar duniyar intanet ɗin ne kawai, musamman kalmomin da suka shafi biyan kuɗi. Ba ta tattauna nau’o’in sana’o’i da kasuwancin da Hausawa suke gudanarwa a intanet ba.

Makarar Yakasai & Idris (2016) ta nazarci tasirin intanet a kan zamantakewar yau a tsakanin al’ummar Nijeriya. Ita ma wannan makalar ba ta tabo sana’o’i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

Sauran makalar da take da ‘yar alaka da wannan aikin ita ce ta A. U. Adamu (2004).

2.3.4 Bugaggun Littattafai

Madabo, (1979) ya rubuta littafi dangane da sana'o'in kasar Hausawa. A cikin aikin babu duniyar sana'o'in duniyar intanet. Littafin Rimmer et al. (1985) ya kawo bayani mai fadi game da sana'o'in Hausawa. Yana da kyau a lura cewa, lokacin da aka yi shi ba a fara sana'o'i a duniyar intanet ba.

Littafin Garba, (1991) ya kawo waƙansu sana'o'in Hausawa na gargajiya. Shi ma babu batun intanet a cikin littafin. Littafin Cibiyar Binciken Tarihin Talata Mafara (2007) ya kawo nau'o'in sana'o'in da ake gudanarwa a Talata Mafara. A ciki babu sana'o'in duniyar intanet. Littafin M. S. Muhammad (2020) ya kawo bayanai game da waƙansu sana'o'in Hausawa. Duk da haka, bai yi magana game da waƙanda suka shafi duniyar intanet ba.

Yakasai (2024) ya wallafa binciken da ya yi dangane da rawar da intanet da na'urori suke takawa wajen adana harshe da al'adu a yau. A ciki ya kawo yadda tasirin na'urori da intanet suke barazanar gurbata al'adun Hausawa, wanda hakan ya samar da alaƙa tsakanin littafin nasa da wannan bincike. Duk da haka, littafin bai kawo bayanai game da sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

Sauran litattattafan da hannu ya kai kansu masu 'yar alaƙa da wannan aikin sun haɗa da: Rimmer & Ingawa (1948) da Durumin Iya (2006) da Asiru (2017).

2.3.5 Jaridu Da Kafafen Intanet

Abdullahi, (2000) ya taɓo yadda harshe da al'adun Hausawa suke bunkasa a kan intanet. Duk da haka, bai yi magana game da sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa ba.

A. U. Adamu (2000) ya yi rubutu cikin harshen Ingilishi a kan harshe da al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet. A ciki ya bibiyi yaƙuwar rubuce-rubuce da al'adun Hausawa da yadda suke a intanet. Rubutun nasa ya bambanta da wannan bincike kasancewar bai kawo bayanai game da sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

A. S. Abubakar (2007) ya yi kofarin fito da tasirin intanet a kan ɓangarorin rayuwar al'umma. Wannan ya haɗa da kasuwanci da ilimi da sauran ɓangarorin rayuwa. Duk da haka, bai daddagi hanyoyin da Hausawa suke gudanar da sana'o'i a duniyar intanet ba.

Buhari (2021b) ya yi rubutu game da kuɗin intanet da yadda ake hadahadarsa. Ya yi rubutun ne a matuƙar tafaice yadda bayanin bai wadatar ba. Bugu da ƙari, bai kawo wani bayani game da sauran nau'o'in kasuwancin kan intanet ba.

Bayan waɗannan ayyuka da suke da alaƙa ta kusa da binciken, an nazarci wasu ayyukan waɗanda za su iya taimakawa wajen kammaluwarsa cikin nasara. Sun kasance masu dangantaka ta nesa da wannan bincike. Kai tsaye sun fi shafar fannonin kwamfuta da intanet da sauran fasahohin zamani masu dangantaka da waɗannan. Daga cikinsu akwai: Gana (2020) da Muryar Hausa24 Online Media (2020) da CMG Hausa (2022) da Saleeman & Adamu (2022).

2.4 Hujjar Ci Gaba Da Bincike

A binciken Mukoshy (2015) an nazarci ayyukan masana da manazarta, sannan aka fitar da sakamakon da yake cewa: "Hausa tana da kyakkyawar safiya. Duk da haka, matuƙar ana son wannan harshe ya ci gaba da haskakawa, dole masana su taskace

sababbin kalmomi na sha'anin kwamfuta da intanet da kuma sauran bangarorin da ci gaban zamani ya kawo. Saboda haka Hausawa su shiga a dama da su a kowane bangare na amfani da kwamfuta da intanet" (Mukoshy, 2015: X). Wannan gagarumar yekuwa ce da take da bukatar gudummuwar manazarta a wannan fannin. Nazartar damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su na samun kuɗi a duniyar intanet, mataki ne na buɗe hanya da jagoranci ga mutane da dama a wannan fannin.

Yana da kyau a lura da cewa, babu wani aiki da ya gabata wanda ya yi canjaras da wannan bincike ta fuskar manufa da farfajiya. Hatta ayyukan da suke da makusanciyar dangantaka da wannan bincike (wadanda aka yi bita a baya), za a tarar da cewa sun bambanta ta fuskar manufa da kadada. Misali, kundin Jibril (2023) ya takaita kwarai a kadadarsa. Haka kuma, sauran rubuce-rubuce da aka yi a kan intanet wadanda kai tsaye suke bayani game da hanyoyin samun kuɗin duniyar intanet, sun kasance takaitattu matuƙa. Lura da duka wadannan, musamman muhimmancin binciken da rashin samun aikin da ya cike wannan gibi a baya, gudanar da shi zai kasance babbar gudummawa ga cigaba da bunkasar Hausawa da harshen Hausa.

2.5 Nadewa

An daɗe ana gudanar da bincike a kan intanet da dangantakarta da al'adu da harsunan al'umma. Wannan ya haɗa har da binciken da aka gudanar a kan tattalin arziki da sana'o'i a duniyar intanet. Hakan ya biyo bayan dambin tasirin da intanet ɗin yake da shi ga rayuwar al'umma a yau. Binciken masana da manazarta da suka gabata da dama sun yi kira da a nazarci al'amarin intanet sosai domin shiga cikin jerin al'ummun da suke cin gajiyarta. Da alama manazarta da daliban ilimi sun amsa

wannan kira ganin yadda aka ci karo da ayyuka da dama a wannan fanni. Duk da haka, akwai gurbin da ba a cike ba wanda ya shafi nazartar lamarin sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Wannan aikin ya sha damarar cike wannan gibi.

BABI NA UKU

HANYOYIN GUDANAR DA BINCIKE

3.0 Shimfida

Duk da 'yan rubuce-rubuce da aka yi game da sana'o'in Hausawa na kan intanet, ana iya cewa wannan fage sabo ne. Dalili kuwa shi ne, ayyuka sun yi kamfa matuƙa a fannin. Sun takaita fwarai yadda babu bayanai game da mafi yawan ire-iren damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su na samun arziki a duniyar intanet. A bisa haka, dabarun gudanar da wannan bincike za su fi shafar tattara bayanai daga majiya ta farko kai tsaye. Za a bi falsafar *Nazarin Al'adu a Duniyar Intanet (Digital Ethnography)* sau da kafa don tabbatar da an bi dukkannin ingantattun hanyoyin bincike mafiya sabunta yayin gudanar da binciken. Ana sa ran hanyoyin gudanar da binciken su kasance zakaran gwajin dafi wajen rungumar sauye-sauyen zamani domin saukakawa da samun ingantaccen sakamakon bincike.

3.1 Tsarin Bincike

An gina wannan bincike ne bisa tsarin *Nazarin Al'adu a Duniyar Intanet (Digital Ethnography)*. Wannan tsari yana ba wa mai bincike damar shiga cikin kafafen intanet da zaurukan sada zumunta kamar *WhatsApp* da *Facebook* domin nazartar yadda Hausawa suke gudanar da harkokin kasuwanci. Wannan ya shafi hulɗar cinikayya da yadda suke hulɗa da juna da yadda al'adu da akidunsu suke bayyana a wannan duniyar (kamar dai yadda *Ginshikin Al'adu da Dabi'u (Normative)* na ra'in binciken ya ayyana).

Babban abin da ya sanya a gaba shi ne fahimtar damarmaki da kalubale da Hausawa suke samu wajen shiga sana'o'in kan intanet. Wannan ya haɗa da sanya ido kan mu'amaloli da dabarun kasuwanci da hanyoyin da ake amfani da su wajen jawo kwastomomi. Har ma da gano yadda dokoki da al'adu da ra'ayoyi (regulative, normative, da cognitive systems) na Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma (Institutional Theory) suke tasiri a kan hulɗayyar kasuwancin.

Nasarar binciken ta rataya kan samar da gamsassun bayanai da za su nuna yadda Hausawa suke amfani da intanet a matsayin sabuwar duniyar kasuwanci, da kuma yadda suke daidaita al'adunsu da sauye-sauyen zamani. Haka kuma, binciken ya haska yadda fungiyoyi da al'ummomi a intanet suke tsara tsarin hulɗa da mu'amaloli ta hanyar sanya ka'idoji da dokoki da wasu tsare-tsare na musamman.

A bisa wannan tsarin bincike, mai nazarin yana da rawar takawa a matsayin mai lura (*observer*) da kuma wani lokaci mai shiga cikin hulɗa (*participant observer*) domin gano ma'anoni da ake kirƙira a cikin mu'amalar dijital. Wannan ya dace da manufar binciken na fahimtar yadda Hausawa suke amfani da intanet wajen bunkasa sana'o'i da kasuwanci.

3.2 Kayan Aikin Tattara Bayanai

Masu ba da bayanai a wannan bincike su ne Hausawa da suke gudanar da harkokin sana'a a cikin duniyar intanet. Bisa tsarin binciken Nazarin Al'adu a Duniyar Intanet (*Digital Ethnography*), an tattara bayanai ne daga kafafen intanet da kafafen sada zumunta daban-daban waɗanda Hausawa suke amfani da su domin kasuwanci da hulɗoɗin cinikayya.

An yi amfani da kafafen intanet da bulog-bulog na Hausa da zaurukan WhatsApp da zauruka da shafukan Facebook da shafukan YouTube da kuma shafukan mutane a kan TikTok waɗanda ake amfani da su wajen tallace-tallace da kasuwanci. Waɗannan wuraren sun ba da damar lura da yadda al'adu da ɗabi'u da tsarabe-tsarabe suke bayyana a duniyar kasuwancin kan intanet na Hausawa. Bugu da ƙari, sun bayar da damar fahimtar damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su na kasuwanci a kan intanet.

Jadawali Na 6: Manyan Tushen Bayanai (Online Sources of Data)

Tushen Bayanai	Adadi	Dalilin Zaba
Kafafen intanet na Hausa	30	Domin nazartar yadda Hausawa suke amfani kafafen intanet ta hanyoyi daban-daban domin neman kuɗi, tare da nazartar kalubalen da suke fuskanta
Zaurukan WhatsApp	10	Domin bin diddigin hulɗar kai tsaye, saye da sayarwa, da dabarun kasuwanci
Zauruka da shafukan Facebook	10	Domin ganin yadda tallace-tallace da sadarwa suke gudana a zauruka da shafukan Facebook
Tashoshin YouTube	10	Don nazartar dabarun talla da koyarwa ta hanyar bidiyo
Akawun-akawun na TikTok	10	Domin nazartar yadda sabuwar kafar take ba da damar kasuwanci
Jimilla	70	

Bugu da ƙari, an yi wasu tattaunawa (*interviews*) da zaɓaɓɓun mutane domin ƙara fahimtar wasu abubuwan da aka lura da su a cikin waɗannan kafafe na intanet. Amma, tattaunawar ba ita ce tushen ainihin bayanin binciken ba. An yi ta ne kawai domin samun ƙarin haske kan abubuwan da aka gani a kafafen intanet ɗin da aka ziryarta.

Jadawali Na 7: Mutanen Da Aka Yi Tattaunawa da su (Interview Participants)

Rukuni	Adadin Mutane	Dalilin Zaba
Masu girke-girke	10	Don fahimtar yadda ake amfani da intanet wajen koyar da girke-girke da jawo mabiya da samun kuɗi
Masu hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet	10	Domin fahimtar yadda masu hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet/kirifto suke gudanar da harkokinsu
Masu kafafen intanet	10	Domin fahimtar rawar da rubuce-rubuce suke takawa a matsayin hanyar neman kuɗi ga Hausawa
Masu tallata haja a kafafen sada zumunta	20	Domin nazartar yadda ake amfani da Facebook, WhatsApp, da sauran kafafe wajen tallata haja da kulla cinikayya da samun sababbin kwastomomi
Sauran mutane	10	Domin samun ra'ayoyin mutane game da harkokin neman kuɗi a kan intanet.
Jimilla	60	

Domin sake fahimtar damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su na neman kuɗi a kan intanet, an nazarci wasu kafafen intanet kai tsaye da suka shafi nau'ukan sana'o'i daban-daban. Sun kasance kamar haka:

Jadawali Na 8: Kafafen Intanet Da Aka Nazarta Masu Alaƙa Da Sana'o'i Da Kasuwanci

Rukuni	Adadin Kafafe	Dalilin Zaba
Kasuwancin kan intanet (sayar da kayayyaki)	10	Domin fahimtar yadda manyan kamfanoni suke sayar da kayayyakinsu a kan intanet. Hausawa za su iya buɗe ire-iren waɗannan kafafe ta hanyar ɗaukar hannu daga manyan kafafen da suka riga suka samu ɗaukaka.
Kafafen Intanet da Suka Shafi Gudanar da Ayyuka	10	Domin nazarta da fahimtar tsari da yanayin tafiyar da manyan kafafen intanet da suka shafi gudanar da ayyuka. Hausawa suna iya buɗe kafafen da suka shafi tallata ayyuka, inda za su

Rukuni	Adadin Kafafe	Dalilin Zaba
		rika samun kuɗi/kamasho yayin da mambobin kafafen suka gudanar da ayyuka.
Kafafen da Suke Samun Kuɗi ta Hanyar Rajista da Mambobi Suke yi	10	Domin fahimtar yadda manyan kafafe a duniya suke samun kuɗi ta hanyar rajistar da mambobi/mabiyansu suke yi. Hausawa suna iya ɗaukar salo makamancin nasu domin samun kuɗi yayin da aka yi rajista a kafafensu.
Kafafen Intanet da Ake Samun Kuɗi ta Hanyar Dogaro da Abubuwan da Ake Dorawa a Kansu (Content)	10	Domin fahimtar dabarun jan hankali da kuma salo da tsari wanda ire-iren kafafen suke amfani da su. Hausawa za su iya bunkasa nasu kafafen tare da kirƙirar wasu sababbi.
Kafafen Koyar da Karatu da Bayar da Horaswa	10	Domin ganin tsarin makarantun kan intanet. Hakan zai ba wa Hausawa damar ɗaukar hannu yayin gina nasu makarantun na dijital.
Kafafen Sayar da Na'urantattun Kirƙire-Kirƙire (Digital Products)	10	Domin ganin yadda ake tsara kasuwannin sayar da na'urantattun kirƙire-kirƙire a kan intanet (nau'ukan hotuna da zane-zane har ma da waƙoƙi da makamantansu). Hausawa za su iya bunkasa harkokinsu da suka shafi na'urantattun kirƙire-kirƙire.
Kafafen Hadahadar Kuɗi da Saka Hannayen Jari	10	Domin fahimtar salo da tsarin kafafen hadahadar kuɗaɗe da saka hannayen jari a duniya. Hausawa suna iya shiga a dama da su a wannan fannin.
Kafafen da Suka Shafi Kiwon Lafiya	10	Domin fahimtar yadda jami'an kiwon lafiya suke samun sababbin hanyoyin samun kuɗi ta intanet. Hausawa masana kiwon lafiya suna iya bunkasa harkokinsu ta hanyar kaiwa ga ɓangarorin duniya daban-daban.
Kafafen da Suka Shafi Tafiye-Tafiye da Masaukai	10	Domin fahimtar yadda kamfanoni suke tsara wa baki tafiye-tafiyensu da masaukai a kan intanet tare da yi musu jagoranci zuwa wurare daban-

Rukuni	Adadin Kafafe	Dalilin Zaba
		daban yayin da suka bukaci hakan. Hausawa suna da damarmaki a wannan fannin.
Jimilla	90	

Domin tafiya da zamani bisa falsafar *zamani riga*, an girke manhajar tsarin manazarta ta kamfanin Google wato Zotero. An girke samfurinta mafi sabunta wato 6.0.35 (Zotero version 6.0.35). Gurbin wannan manhajar zamani cikin binciken shi ne tabbatar da an taskace tare da gabatar da dukkannin ayyukan da aka ambata bisa tsarin manazartar APA mafi sabunta, wato fitowa ta bakwai (APA 7th Edition).

3.3 Hanyoyin Tattara Bayanai

Domin samun ingantattun bayanai tare da cimma manufar binciken, an bi wasu tsararrun hanyoyin gudanar da bincike ta amfani da kayan aikin tattara bayanai. An bibiya tare da nazartar duniyar intanet ta fuskoki daban-daban. Wannan ya hada da nazarin sigar duniyar da hadahada da kai-komo da sauran al'amura da suke gudana cikinta. A ɓangare guda kuwa ya shafi bincike kan fididdigaggun alkaluman sha'anoninta na yau da kullum. Wannan mataki ne na samun haske a yunkurin da ake yi na nazartar sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Kai tsaye an mayar da hankali wajen:

Yin amfani da injunan nema domin zakulo bayanai da suka shafi al'adun Hausawa a duniyar ta intanet musamman dangane da sana'o'i da kasuwanci. Ta hanyar su ne aka samo jerin manyan kafafen kasuwanci na duniya. Bugu da fari ta nan ne aka samo

jerin kafafen intanet da na sada zumunta na Hausawa, waɗanda suka shafi sana'o'i da kasuwanci. Waɗannan injuna sun haɗa da:

- a. AOL Search (<https://search.aol.com>)
- b. Ask.com (<https://www.ask.com>)
- c. Baidu (<https://www.baidu.com>)
- d. Bing (<https://www.bing.com>)
- e. DuckDuckGo (<https://duckduckgo.com>)
- f. Google (<https://www.google.com>)
- g. Yahoo (<https://www.yahoo.com>)
- h. Yandex (<https://www.yandex.com>)

A cikinsu an fi mayar da hankali kan Gogul kasancewar ya fi tattara bayanai sama da sauran injunan. Binciken Pandey et al. (2015 sh. 138-143) ya tabbatar da cewa Gogul ne yake fara zuwa koyaushe kafin sauran injunan. A takaice, ninkaya cikin intanet da karance-karance da hirarraki su ne dabarun da suka taimaki binciken domin haƙa ta cimma ruwa.

Bugu da kari, an bi hanyar 'halarta da sa ido' (participant observation) domin yin kallon kwakwaf da kara fahimtar lamuran da suka shafi hadahadar sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a kan intanet. Wannan ya haɗa da shiga zaurukan kafafen sada zumunta na 'yan kasuwa da ma'aikata masu zaman kansu a kan intanet. Kafafen intanet na Hausa da aka nazarta su ne:

Jadawali Na 9: Kafafen Intanet Na Hausa Da Aka Nazarta

	Sunan Kafa	Likau	Rukuni
1.	Abincin Hausawa	https://abinci.com/	Al'adun Hausa
2.	Al'ummar Hausa	https://www.alummarhaus.com.ng	Al'adun Hausa da Tarihi
3.	Al'ummar Hausa	https://www.alummarhaus.com.ng	Hausawa da Al'adun Hausa
4.	Amsoshi	https://www.amsoshi.com	Karatun Hausa
5.	Arewa Fresh	https://www.arewafresh.com.ng	Cimakar Hausawa
6.	Arewa Nishadi	https://www.arewanishadi.com	Adabin Hausa
7.	Arewarmu	https://www.arewarmu.com.ng	Tarihi
8.	Azare Online	http://azareonline.com	Al'adun Hausa da Tarihi
9.	Baban Sadik	https://www.babansadik.com	Kimiyya da Fasaha
10.	Bakandamiya	https://www.bakandamiya.com	Karatun Hausa
11.	Dandali	http://www.dandali.com	Karatun Hausa
12.	Duniyarso	http://duniyarso.blogspot.com	Adabin Hausa
13.	Freedom Radio Kano	https://freedomradionig.com	Labarai
14.	Gidan Karatu	https://www.gidankaratu.com	Karatun Hausa
15.	Gidan Novels	https://gidannovels.guidetricks.com	Littattafan Hausa
16.	Gobir Mob	https://gobirmob.com/ha	Karatun Hausa
17.	Hausa Dictionary	http://hausadictionary.com	Kamusun Hausa
18.	Hausa Online	https://hausasonline.wordpress.com	Karatun Hausa
19.	Hausa Top	http://www.hausatop.com	Adabin Hausa da Nishadantarwa

20.	Hausa Weddings	https://hausaweddings.com	Al'adun Hausa
21.	Hikaya Bakandamiya	https://hikaya.bakandamiya.com	Adabin Hausa
22.	Isyaku	https://www.isyaku.com	Labarai
23.	Jakadan Fasaha	https://www.jakadanfasaha.com	Kimiyya da Fasaha
24.	Kano Online	http://kanoonline.com	Karatun Hausa da Sada Zumunta
25.	Katsina Post Hausa	http://katsinaposthaus.com	Nishadantarwa
26.	Makarantar Hausa	https://makarantarhaus.com	Karatun Hausa
27.	Managarciya	https://managarciya.com	Karatun Hausa
28.	Rumbun Ilimi	https://www.rumbunilimi.com.ng	Karatun Hausa
29.	Tsangayar Adabi	http://tsangayaradabi.blogspot.com	Karatun Hausa
30.	WikiHausa	https://www.wikihaus.com.ng	Karatun Hausa

Zauruka da shafukan da aka shiga domin halarta da sa ido su ne:

Jadawali Na 10: Zauruka Da Shafukan Da Aka Shiga Domin 'Halarta Da Sa Ido'

	Suna	Rukuni	Yawan Mabiya ⁷⁷	Likau
Zaurukan WhatsApp				
1.	Bakandamiya Reading Clum - BRC	Tattaunawa, ilimantarwa da tallata litattattafai	341	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
2.	BBC News Hausa	Yada labarai (Channel)	1,161,309	https://whatsapp.com/channel/0029VahbuTkEwEjqW42kXB2K

⁷⁷ Wannan ya takaita ne ya zuwa 6 ga watan Oktoba, shekarar 2025.

	Suna	Rukuni	Yawan Mabiya⁷⁷	Lifkau
3.	GIADE Trends Collections	Tallan kayayyaki nau'ukan tufafi	457	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
4.	KASUWAR KALAMBAINA	Tallata haja	99	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
5.	Littattafan Hausa Zalla Daga marubuta daban daban	Tura rubuce-rubuce da odiyo da tallata littattafai	249	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
6.	MARUBUTA:	Tallata littattafan Adabin Kasuwar Kano	606	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
7.	Pi Updates	Kuɗin intanet	83	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
8.	RFI Hausa	Yafa labarai (Channel)		https://whatsapp.com/channel/0029VafIzTDJkK7AzyjH5R2O
9.	TAMBAYA DA AMSA	Tambayoyi da amsoshi game da mas'aloli da suka shafi Musulunci (Channel)	10,123	https://whatsapp.com/channel/0029VaA8YpB42DcZdoRuCj3G
10.	WEB 3.0 MINING	Kuɗin intanet	164	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
Zauruka da Shafukan Facebook				
11.	Hadiza Aliyu	Dandalin hira da jaruman Kannywood	1,800,000+	https://web.facebook.com/AdizatouGabon
12.	Arewa Radio 93.1	Gidan rediyo	1,100,000+	https://web.facebook.com/arewaradio931
13.	Freedom Radio Nigeria	Gidan rediyo	1,900,000+	https://web.facebook.com/FreedomRadioNigeria

	Suna	Rukuni	Yawan Mabiya⁷⁷	Lifkau
14.	Maibiredi Tv	Gidan talabijin	494,000+	https://web.facebook.com/maibiredity
15.	Amsoshi 360	Labarai da barkwanci	19,100+	https://web.facebook.com/amsoshi360
16.	MATAN JOS AJIN FARKO KASUWANCI ZALLAH	Tallata haja	48,700+	https://web.facebook.com/groups/1473822286777322/
17.	Kasuwancin kayan hannu tare da dillanci	Kasuwanci da dillanci (musamman na kayan hannu)	286,500+	https://web.facebook.com/groups/860393198758763
18.	HADDIN MAGANIN MATA ZALLAH	Magunguna	75,600+	https://web.facebook.com/groups/3529442237382569/
19.	Crypto Hausa Nigeria - Africa	Hadahadar kudaden intanet	244,500+	https://web.facebook.com/groups/125428506013657
20.	KASUWAR GIDAJE DA FILAYE	Tallata haja	225,700+	https://web.facebook.com/groups/639950390394829
Tashoshin YouTube				
21.	Abdulkabo Tech	Koyar da hanyoyin samun kuɗi a kan intanet	16,800+	https://www.youtube.com/@Abdulkabo_tech
22.	ABIS_FULANI	Labarai da barkwanci	100,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@abis_fulani
23.	Ali Artwork	Barkwanci	173,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@AliArtwork1
24.	Aminu Tech	Kimiyya da fasaha	36,400+	https://www.youtube.com/@aminutech
25.	Amsoshi TV	Karatun Hausa	7,100+	https://www.youtube.com/@

	Suna	Rukuni	Yawan Mabiya ⁷⁷	Lifau
				AmsoshiTV
26.	Bushkiddo	Barkwanci	102,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@Bushkiddo
27.	Dan Bello	Ilimi, barkwanci, kasuwanci	91,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@bellogaladanchi
28.	Nazifi Asnanic	Waka	290,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@nazifiasnanic
29.	SCTv Africa	Hadahadar kudafen intanet	53,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@SunusiCryptoTV
30.	Umar Top TV YouTube	Kimiyya da fasaha	3,840+	https://www.youtube.com/@umartoptv
Akawun-Akawun na TikTok				
31.	Ali Jita	Waka	1,500,000	https://www.tiktok.com/@realalijita
32.	Arewa multiclassic foods	Magungunan gargajiya da girke-girke	59,300+	https://www.tiktok.com/@arewa_multiclassic_food
33.	Dauda Kahutu Rarara	Waka	2,000,000+	https://www.tiktok.com/@kahuturarara
34.	Fulanys_kitchen_kano	Girke-girke	491,100+	https://www.tiktok.com/@fulanys_kitchen_kano
35.	HydarFx	Hadahadar kudafen intanet	33,800+	https://www.tiktok.com/@hydarfx
36.	Kasuwar Bello	Sayar da kayayyaki	170,600+	https://www.tiktok.com/@kasuwarbello
37.	KING KABEER	Barkwanci	2,500,000+	https://www.tiktok.com/@kingkabeer66
38.	Maibiredi Charity	Gidauniya	21,500+	https://www.tiktok.com/@maibiredicharityfoundati

	Suna	Rukuni	Yawan Mabiya⁷⁷	Likau
	Foundation			
39.	Maryaaamah	Girke-girke	984,100+	https://www.tiktok.com/@maryamaskitchen
40.	Yahaya_Crypto	Hadahadar kudafen intanet	81,800+	https://www.tiktok.com/@yahaya_crypto

Bayan wannan, an tattara wasu bayanan imel wadanda suka shafi binciken. Wasu sun shafi yadda ake turo ayyuka a kan intanet. Wasu kuwa sun shafi sakonni masu alaƙa da ayyukan ‘yan damfaran kan intanet. Saboda tsaro da sirrantawa, ba a bayyana sunayen masu imel dɪn ba. A maimakon haka, an yi amfani da hotunan sakonnin imel dɪn (screenshots) a matsayin misalai, tare da bayanai domin sauƙin ganewa.

A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, an yi karance-karancen kundayen digiri da kamusoshi da littattafai da mujallu da maƙalu da jaridu. Bai tsaya a nan ba, ya shafi nazartar duk wani ma’adanin ilimi a rubuce ko cikin bidiyo ko sauti (odiyo). An cimma hakan ta hanyar ziyartar ɗakunan karatu da cibiyoyin nazari (musamman na nazarin Hausa). Wannan duka sun taimaka wajen samun ƙarin haske kan batun da ake magana a kansa. Bugu da ƙari kuma, sun taimaka wajen haskaka wasu kalmomi da batutuwa da suka shafi binciken.

Duk da ‘hira’ ba ita ba ce babbar hanyar tattara bayanan, an yi hira da wasu keɓantattun mutane na musamman. An zaɓe su ta la’akari da ƙwarewarsu da iliminsu a fannonin da binciken yake nazarta. Ga su kamar haka:

Jadawali Na 11: Fitattun Waƙanda Aka Yi Hira Da Su

Rukuni	Adadi	Dalilin Zaɓe
Masu gudanar da sana'o'i da kasuwanci a kan intanet	9	An zaɓe su saboda gogewarsu a fannin hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet. Bayanansu sun taimaka wajen fahimtar abubuwan da aka nazarta daga kasuwannin hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet.
Masu koyar da girke-girke a kan intanet	4	An zaɓe su domin ƙara fahimtar yadda suke gudanar da sana'o'insu a kan intanet. An kuma samu bayanai game da nau'ukan ƙalubale da suke fuskanta.
Masu gudanar da kafafen intanet na Hausa	9	An zaɓe su domin ƙara fahimtar yadda suke gudanar da kafafen intanet na Hausa tare da fahimtar nau'ukan ƙalubale da suke fuskanta.
Malamai (Masana Hausa)	11	An tatattauna da su domin samun ra'ayoyinsu da fahimtarsu game da sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.
Sauran mutane	5	Domin tantance wasu bayanai da suka shafi sana'o'i da kasuwanci.
Jimilla	38	

Babbar gudummawa da suka ba wa binciken shi ne ƙara haska wasu bayanai da aka nazarta a kan intanet, tare da bayar da misalai na gani-da-ido.

3.4 Hanyoyin Kwankwance Bayanai

Kasancewar wannan bincike ya ginu ne a kan tsarin Nazarin Al'adu a Duniyar Intanet (Digital Ethnography), hanyar kwankwance bayanai da aka tattara ta kasance mai salo na kwankwance bayanai (qualitative analysis), ba ta ƙididdigar alƙaluma ba. An mayar da hankali kan fahimtar ma'anoni da tsarin sadarwa da yadda al'adun Hausawa suke bayyana a mu'amalarsu da harkokin kasuwanci a intanet da kuma damarmakin da Hausawan suke da shi na sana'o'i da kasuwanci a kan intanet.

An tattara bayanai daga kafe da shafukan sada zumunta na intanet da aka ambata kamar WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube, TikTok, da bulog-bulog. Bugu da kari, an tsara tare da kawo bayanai a farkashin manya da kananan take yadda zai yi sauƙin fahimta. An tattauna kowane al'amari a farkashin karamin take guda. A kowane farkashin take, an yi koƙarin kawo misalai kai tsaye daga kafafen intanet da aka ziyarta.

An yi amfani da dabarar kwatance da hada bayanai daga tushe daban-daban (data triangulation). A bisa wannan tsarin, an kwatanta bayanai da aka samo daga WhatsApp da Facebook da YouTube tare da tattaunawa da mutane domin tabbatar da sahihancin sakamakon.

3.5 Nadewa

Bincike dangane da sana'o'i da kasuwanci abu ne mai buƙatar takatsantsan. Shigowar gurɓatattun bayanai marasa inganci suna iya samar da mummunan sakamako ga waƙanda za su yi amfani da shawarwarin binciken. Tun da sana'o'i da kasuwanci sun shafi haƙallan dukiya da kadara, bayanai marasa inganci suna iya kaiwa ga hasara da salwantar dukiya. Wannan ne ya sa aka bi amintattun matakan zaɓen kayan aikin tattara bayanai da za su yi kyakkyawan jagoranci ga binciken wajen tattarawa da kwankwance ingantattun bayanai.

BABI NA HUDU

GWAGWARMAYAR SANA'O'I DA KASUWANCIN HAUSAWA A DUNIYAR INTANET

4.0 Shimfida

Kamar yadda aka kawo a babi na biyu, Hausawa sun biyo mata kai daban-daban dangane da sana'o'i da kasuwancinsu. A kowace gaba, al'adunsu sukan yi tasiri a kan hulfofin kasuwancinsu, kamar dai yadda Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma ya zayyana. Sauyin zamani ya rika samar da sauye-sauye a harkokin da suka shafin tattalin arzikinsu. Sannu a hankali har abin ya kai duniyar intanet a yau. Farfajiyar duniyar intanet kuwa tana da matuƙar faɗi. Nau'o'in kasuwanci da sana'o'in da ake gudanarwa a cikinta suna da yawa. A intanet za a iya samun makamantan duk waɗansu hadahadar kasuwanci da ake gudanarwa a duniyar zahiri. Wannan babin ya mayar da hankali kan fito da nau'o'i da yanaye-yanayen sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa waɗanda suka shafi duniyar intanet. Bugu da ƙari, ya mayar da hankali wajen yin ƙarin haske game da damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su a ɓangarori masu yawa na kasuwancin duniyar intanet.

4.1 Hausawa Da Sana'o'i Da Kasuwanci a Duniyar Intanet

Intanet yana da matuƙar tasiri a kan rayuwar al'umma kamar yadda aka kawo a cikin babi na biyu. Tasirin ya shafi ɓangarorin rayuwar Hausawa daban-daban. A yau har ya kai ga ya fara mamaye harkokin kasuwanci da sana'o'insu. Intanet ya kasance hanyar samun kuɗi ga mutane da dama. Wannan yana faruwa ne ta manyan hanyoyi guda biyu kamar haka:

- a. Gudanar da wata sana'a ko kasuwanci a kan intanet domin samun kuɗi

- b. Amfani da intanet domin inganta ko bunkasa kasuwanci ko kuma sana'ar da aka saba gudanarwa

A wannan bangare na binciken, an nazarci hanyoyi daban-daban na samun kuɗi ga Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Binciken ya nazarci kafafen intanet domin sake fahimtar damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su na neman kuɗi ta hanyar digital. Haka kuma, ya tattauna da wasu Hausawa waɗanda suka rungumi ayyukan kan intanet a matsayin hanyar dogaro da kai tare da fita daga taskun talauci.⁷⁸

4.1.1 Aikin Masu Zaman Kansu a Kan Intanet (Online Freelancing)

A cikin wannan bincike, an fassara '*Freelancer*' da *Ma'aikaci Mai Zaman Kansa*. Shigowar intanet ya samar da sauye-sauye a ayyukan masu zaman kansu da sauran nau'ukan ayyuka. A yau abin yana kasancewa ta manyan fuskoki guda uku, kamar haka:

- i. Ayyukan da ake nemo ma'aikaci mai zaman kansa a kan intanet, a ba shi aiki a kan intanet, ya kammala shi a kan intanet, sannan a amfana da sakamakon aikin yayin da yake kan intanet. A irin wannan nau'in aikin na ma'aikata masu zaman kansu, babu bukatar mai bayar da aiki ya ga ma'aikaci mai zaman kansa ko ya ji muryarsa. Bugu da kari, aikin da za a gudanar kacokan a kan intanet ake aiwatar da shi. Haka kuma, sakamakon aikin abu ne da zai kasance a kan intanet, ba wanda za a sauke shi kasa zuwa duniyar zahiri kafin a amfana da shi ba. Misalan nau'o'in ayyuka na ma'aikata masu zaman kansu a kan intanet da suke farkashin wannan rukuni sun haɗa da: (a) bayar da tsaro a kafafen

⁷⁸ "Talauci shi ne rashin samar wa rayuwa ingantattun abubuwa da take bukata waɗanda suka haɗa da abinci da kiwon lafiya da kyakkyawan muhalli da ilimi da kuma sutura." (Sarkin Gulbi, 2007 sh. 47)

intanet da (b) gwada kutse a kafafen intanet da (c) gina kafafen intanet, da sauran makamantansu.

- ii. Aikin da ake nemo ma'aikaci mai zaman kansa a kan intanet, a ba shi aiki a kan intanet, amma kammalallen aikin da kuma sakamakonsa za su kasance ana amfani da su ta hanyar tu'ammuli da su kai tsaye a duniyar zahiri. Fassararriyar takardar amincewa da halartar gwajin wani magani babban misali ne na wannan nau'in aikin.⁷⁹
- iii. Ayyukan da ake nemo ma'aikaci mai zaman kansa ta kan intanet, amma aikin da zai gudanar yake kasancewa a duniyar zahiri. Misalan wannan sun haɗa da (a) tafinta da kamfani zai nemo a kan intanet domin ya yi tafintanci a zahiri a wani wurin da aka ayyana; (b) mai koyar da harshen da za a nema a kan intanet domin ya je wani wurin da zai koyar a zahiri na tsawon wani lokaci.

A yau, Hausawa da dama sun rungumi harkar aiki na ma'aikata masu zaman kansu a duniyar intanet. Nau'o'in ayyukan da suke yi sun shafi fannonin kwarewa da dama.

Daga cikinsu akwai bangarorin:

- a. Kimiyyar harshe
- b. Intanet da na'urori
- c. Hotuna da bidiyoyi
- d. Bincike

⁷⁹ A irin wannan yanayi, kamfanin fassara za su nemo mai fassara a kan intanet. Za su ba shi fassarar, yayin da shi kuma zai kammala ya tura musu ta kan intanet. Takardun da aka fassara kuwa, za a gurza su sannan a gabatar da su hannu da hannu ga waɗanda za su rattaba hannu cikin harjejeniyar amincewar.

Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, duk ire-iren waƙannan ayyukan a yau suna da gurbi na musamman a al'ada. A matsayinsu na nau'o'in sana'o'in wasu Hausawa suka kama a matsayin hanyar dogaro da kai, ba su da waƙansu sunaye da suka wuce kasuwanci da sana'o'i. Kasancewar sun samu ne a zamanance sannan sun shafi fasahohin zamani, hakan bai sauya musu suna ba. Ko da ma dai, a kowace gaba a tarihin ƙan'adam, akan samu sababbin abubuwa da suke bijiro wa rayuwarsa. Da zarar ya karbe su a matsayin hanyar gudanar da rayuwa kuwa, shikenan sun nashe sun koma cikin al'adarsa.⁸⁰

4.1.1.1 Ayyuka a Fannin Harshe Da Kimiyyar Harshe (Language and Linguistic Services)

Ilimin harshe⁸¹ a nan yana ƙaukar ma'ana mai faɗi da ta haɗa da al'ada da adabi da kuma nahawun harshe. Sanin waƙannan fannonin ilimi shi ne yake ba wa mai aiki a wannan fannin damar gudanar da ayyuka ba tare da tasgaro ba. Bunza (2017 SL. 1) ya jaddada muhimmancin naƙaltar al'adar harshe ga masu aikin fassara. Haka lamarin yake ga nau'o'in ayyuka da dama waƙanda suka shafi harshe da kimiyyar harshe.

Kimiyyar harshe ma wani fage ne wanda masanansa suke cin abinci ta hanyar amfani da iliminsu wajen samun ayyuka a intanet. Dangane da ma'anar ilimin kimiyyar harshe kuwa, "... wani muhimmin fage ne a wajen nazarin harsuna, wanda ke nazarin

⁸⁰ Haƙiƙa Hausawan da za su taso bayan ƙarnuka biyar, ba za su koyi tunanin jayayya game da kasuwanci da sana'o'in kan intanet a matsayin wani ɓangare na al'adun Hausawa ba.

⁸¹ Harshe yana nufin baiwa da hikimar da ƙan'adam yake da ita ta magana. Ta haɗa da amfani da gaɓoɓin furuci wajen fitar da sautuka na musamman da suka bayar da ma'anoni na musamman ga masu sauraro da fahimtar su. Shi ne kuma yake bayar da damar yin tunani da mafarki da kwatancen zuci. Muhammad (2024 sh. 293) ya fassara ma'anar harshe da Anyanwu ya bayar da cewa: "Harshe yana daga cikin halaye na ƙan'adam wanda yake da tsari na musamman. Haka kuma, wata muhimmiyar hanyar ce wadda ƙan'adam yake amfani da ita wajen hulɗayya cikin al'umma."

harshe a kimiyyance tun daga matakin furuci da tsarin sauti da kirar kalma da ginin jumla da kuma ma'ana" (Abbas & Umar, 2015 SL. 2).⁸² A takaice ke nan, ilimin kimiyyar harshe ya shafi nazarin harshe baki dayansa, tun daga kan yadda ake samar da kwayoyin sauti har zuwa yadda ake nazarin ma'anar jumloni, har ma da alakar harshe da wasu harsuna na daban.

Akwai nau'o'in ayyuka daban-daban da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe waɗanda Hausawa suke shiga a dama da su. Yawanci akan yi musu kuɗin goro da sunan *ayyukan fassara*. Wannan ne ma ya sa kamfanonin da suka gudanar da ire-iren ayyukan aka fi sanin su da suna *kamfanonin fassara*. A haƙifanin gaskiya kuwa, ayyukansu ba su tsaya kan fassara kaɗai ba. Sun shafi jerin ayyuka mabambanta da ake gudanarwa bisa mabambantan manufofi.

Kasuwan fassara tana matuƙar ci a duniya. A ciki har da ayyukan fassarar da suka shafi harshen Hausa. Binciken da Mordor Intelligence suka gabatar a shekarar 2024 ta nuna yadda kasuwar take matuƙar haɓaka. A yanzu haka kasuwar tana da darajar da ta kai ta dalar Amurka biliyan saba'in da shida da miliyan saba'in da takwas (\$76.78). Ya zuwa shekarar 2029, zai iya karuwa da kashi shida da digo talatin da biyu (6.32%) inda zai kai dalar Amurka biliyan ɗari da huɗu da miliyan talatin da ɗaya (\$104.31) (Mordor Intelligence Research & Advisory, 2024 SL. 2-3). Waɗannan alƙaluma suna nuni da cewa, kasuwar fassara ta kasance mai kawo kuɗi wadda ya kamata kada a bar Hausawa a baya wajen cin gajiyarta.

⁸² Sa'idu (2019) ya ba da ma'ana makamanciyar wannan inda yake cewa: "Kimiyyar harshe nazari ne na harshe ta fannin sautinsa, kalmominsa, jumloninsa da kuma gina kalmomi da sautan abubuwan da suka shafi maana har ma da walwalar harshe" (Sa'idu & Umar, 2019 SL. 2).

A kullum ana kara samun sababbin kamfanonin fassara a cikin gida Nijeriya da nahiyar Afirka da kuma uwa-uba a faɗin duniya baki ɗaya. Daga cikinsu akwai waɗanda suka sanya Hausa a cikin jerin harsunan da suke gudanar da ayyuka a kansu.⁸³ Misalan kamfanonin fassara waɗanda suke gudanar da ayyuka a kan harshen Hausa sun haɗa da:

- a. Andovar (<https://www.andovar.com/>)
- b. Bayan-Tech (<https://bayan-tech.com/>)
- c. Cal Interpreting & Translations (CIT) (<https://calinterpreting.com/>)
- d. Crowdin (<https://crowdin.com/>)
- e. Datamundi (<https://www.datamundi.be/cms/>)
- f. db Group (<http://www.dbgroupintl.com/>)
- g. EA Language Solutions (<http://www.ealanguagesolutions.com/>)
- h. Mars Translation (<https://www.marstranslation.com>)
- i. Nile Bridge (<http://nilebridge.com/docs/index.php>)
- j. One Hour Translation (www.onehourtranslation.com)
- k. Packy Caruso – Language & Communication Services
(<https://packycaruso.weebly.com/>)
- l. Sawa Tech (<https://sawa-tech.com/>)
- m. Translated (<https://www.translated.net>)

⁸³ Yana da kyau a lura da cewa, kowane kamfanin fassara yana da jerin harsuna da yake aiki a kansu. Ba kowane kamfani ba ne yake karɓa da bayar da ayyukan Hausa.

A kasa an kawo jerin nau'o'in ayyukan kan intanet waɗanda Hausawa suke cin gajiyarsu, waɗanda kuma suke farkashin rukunin ayyukan fassara.⁸⁴

4.1.1.1.1 Bin Kwakkwafin Ma'ana (Linguistic Evaluation)

Wannan nau'in aiki ne wanda ya danganci kimiyyar harshe. Ya shafi fokarin gano matsayin kalmomi a cikin harsuna daban-daban. Akan turo aikin bin kwakkwafin ma'ana cikin harshen Hausa domin gano matsayin wasu kalmomi a cikin harshen. Matsayin kalmomi a nan yana nufin zubin harufansu da yanayin furucinsu a harshen da ake aiki a cikinsa da kuma makamanciyar ma'ana ko ma'anoni da za a iya samu tsakanin sautin furucin kalmomin da wasu kalmomi a cikin harshen da ake bincike a cikinsa (misali yadda za a furta wata kalma a harshen Ingilishi ya yi kamata da furucin wata kalma a Hausa). Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, wannan yana da bambanci da kalmomi masu kinin sauti da bambancin abajadi (homophones).⁸⁵

Yayin da wata ma'aikata ko wani kamfani ko gwamnati suke shirin fito da sababbin shirye-shirye ko muhimman sunayen abubuwan da suka shafe su, sukan bukaci wannan aikin. Yadda ake yi kuwa shi ne, za a tura kalmomin zuwa ga masana harsuna daban-daban. Kowane masanin harshe, zai nazarci kalmomin ta fuskoki da dama. Hausa tana daga cikin harsunan da ake irin wannan bincike a cikinsu. A kasa an kawo misalin kwakkwafin ɗaya daga cikin kalmomin sunan kamfani:

⁸⁴ Abu ne mai wahala a gane mafi muhimmanci a cikinsu, domin kuwa muhimmancinsu ya danganta da lokaci da bukatun al'umma da kuma manufofin kamfanoni. A sakamakon haka, an jero su bisa tsarin abajadin sunayensu.

⁸⁵ Merriam Webster sun kawo ma'anar *homophones* a matsayin: "one of two or more words pronounced alike but different in meaning or derivation or spelling (such as the words to, too, and two)." (Merriam Webster, 2024a). Ma'ana: "... ɗaya daga cikin kalmomi biyu ko sama da haka waɗanda suke da makamancin furuci amma ma'anarsu ko tushensu ko abajadinsu daban.

Jadawali Na 12: Misalin Bin Kwakkwafin Ma'anr Kalmar Uber

Kalma: Uber ⁸⁶		
	Tambaya	Amsa
1	Shin a cikin kalmar akwai harafin da zai yi wa Hausawa wahalar furtawa?	A'a
2	Shin kalmar tana da sauƙin furtawa ga Hausawa?	E, saboda ta yi kama da furucin kalmar 'uba.' Duk da haka, Bahaushen da bai sani ba zai iya furta ta a matsayin /'u.bər/.
3	Idan aka furta kalmar, shin akwai wata kalma da za ta bijiro a tunanin Hausawa?	E
4	Idan amsar tambaya ta 3 ta kasance 'E', shin ma'anar kalmar da za ta bijiro a Hausa tana da wata ma'ana mai sosa rai ko wadda ta saba wa al'ada?	A'a. Uba yana nufin "father." Kalmar ba ta sosa rai ko saba wa al'ada sai idan an yi amfani da ita da manufar cin mutunci.

Bin kwakkwafin ma'anonin kalmomi wani mataki ne mai muhimmanci ga manyan kamfanoni da ma'aikatu a fadin duniya. Ta haka ne za su tabbatar da cewa kalmomin da suka yi amfani da su wajen sanya sunayen kayayyakin su ba su kasance masu wahalar fada ko bayar da fassara mai aibu a wadansu harsuna na daban ba. Hausawan da suka yi rajista da wadansu daga cikin kamfanonin fassara da aka zayyano a farkashin 4.1.1.1 suna da damar samun ire-iren wadannan ayyuka.

Yanayin samun kudi a irin wannan aikin ya danganta da kamfani da kuma kwarewar ma'aikaci a fannin. Biyan da ake yi yana kamawa tun daga kan dala goma (\$10) har zuwa dala ashirin (\$20) ko sama da haka a kowane awa ɗaya (1). Ma'ana a kowane aikin awa ɗaya da Bahaushe ma'aikacin kan intanet ya yi a wannan fannin, zai samu

⁸⁶ Daya daga cikin kalmomin sunan kamfanin *Uber Technologies Inc.*

kwatankwacin wannan kuɗi. Wannan daidai yake da kimanin nera dubu goma sha shida zuwa dubu talatin da biyu (N16,000 - N32,000) a kuɗin Nijeriya.⁸⁷

4.1.1.1.2 Fassara (Translation)

Fassara babban fage ne a fannin kimiyyar harsuna. Kasuwarsa ta daɗe tana ci, sannan kullum kara bunkasa take yi. Duk da yawan rubuce-rubuce da aka yi dangane da fassara, ma'anarta ba ta kasance mai ruɗani ko janyo muhawara ba. Abbuwan da ake da bambancin ra'ayi game da su sun haɗa da matakan gudanar da fassarar da yiwuwar samun ingantacciyar fassara da makamantansu. Sulaiman (2013 sh. 201) ya nazarci ayyukan Malumfashi (2012) da Yakasai (2012) da Sarbi (2012) sannan ya fitar da ma'anar fassara da cewa: "... na nufin mayar da ma'anar wani bayani ko kalma daga harshen bayarwa zuwa harshen karɓa."

A saukake ana iya cewa, fassara tana nufin aikin da ya shafi fasahar bin tsararrun matakan samar da ma'anar kalma ko kalmomi ko jumloji ko bayanai da aka yi a cikin wani harshe (wanda ake kira harshen bayarwa) zuwa wani harshe (wanda ake kira harshen karɓa)⁸⁸ ba tare da salwantar da ainihin ma'anar kamar yadda take a harshen bayarwa ba, bisa la'akari da muhimman abubuwan da suka haɗa da bambance-bambancen al'adu da tsarin ginin jumla da suke tsakanin harsunan biyu. Musa da Sani (2010) sun jaddada cewa: "Mai fassara masani ne na harasa fiye da ɗaya, amma kwararre a harshen uwa. Don haka, kowane mai fassara da irin basirarsa ta fahimtar harshe daidai gwargwado. (Musa & Sani, 2010 sh. 104).

⁸⁷ An yi wannan lissafin a watan Yulin shekarar 2024. A lokacin kowace dala ɗaya tana matsayin nera dubu ɗaya da ɗari shida (\$1 = N1,600).

⁸⁸ Ko bayan wannan suna (harshen bayarwa da harshen karɓa), akwai waɗansu sunayen da ake musu. Sun haɗa da (a) harshe na ɗaya da harshe na biyu, ko (b) harshen aiki da harshen mai aiki.

Ayyukan fassara suna taimakawa ta fuskoki daban-daban. Ko bayan samar da aikin yi ga masana harshe, sukan taimaka ta fuskar bunƙasa fannonin da suka shafi addini da adabi da harshe da kimiyya da fasaha.⁸⁹ Sarbi (2010 sh. 84-85) ya nazarci yadda ayyukan fassara suka taimaka matuka wajen samar da cigaba a duniya. Bisa wannan ne yake ganin ya kamata a samar da makarantun fassara na musamman domin bincike da fassara ayyukan kimiyya da fasaha kamar yadda aka yi a cibiyar da ake kira *House of Wisdom*⁹⁰ a Bagadada.

A cikin dukkannin nau'oin ayyukan da suke karkashin kimiyyar harshe, za a iya cewa aikin fassara ya fi yawa. Wannan yana daga cikin dalilan da suka sa aka fi kiran kamfanonin da suke gudanar da ayyukan da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe da suna 'kamfanonin fassara' (kamar yadda aka yi bayani a karkashin 4.1.1.1 da yake sama).

A aikin fassarar kan intanet, an fi yin lissafin kuɗin aiki cikin dala. Bugu da kari, ana biya ne kalma-kalma ba kuɗin goro ko shafi-shafi ba. Farashin kowace kalma ya danganta kan alkaluma da suka haɗa da:

- a. Harsunan fassara (na bayarwa da na karɓa)
- b. Yanayin kamfanin
- c. Yanayin kunshiyar abin da za a fassara (wahalarsa ko saukinsa ko darajarsa)
- d. Kwarewar mai aikin fassarar
- e. Yawa ko karancin abin da za a fassara

⁸⁹ Domin karin bayani, a duba Sarbi (2013 sh. 145).

⁹⁰ Domin samun bayanin *House of Wisdom*, a duba Sarbi (Sarbi, 2010 sh. 79-83).

A aikin fassara daga waƙansu harsuna zuwa harshen Hausa, yawanci kuɗin yana kamawa daga dala 0.03 zuwa 0.8 ga kowace kalma. Wannan ya kama wajajen naira arbain da takwas zuwa ɗari da ashirin da takwas (N48 – N128) ga kowace kalma.

Akwai manyan nau’o’in fassara guda biyu; (a) fassara zuwa harshen karɓa da (b) mayar da fassara zuwa harshen bayarwa. An kawo bayaninsu a kasa, kamar haka:

- a. **Fassarar Gaba (Front Translation):** Wannan shi ne nau’in fassarar da aka fi sani da sabawa da shi. Ya shafi yin fassara kai tsaye daga harshen bayarwa zuwa harshen karɓa. Misali shi ne fassara daga Ingilishi zuwa Hausa, ko daga Larabci zuwa Hausa.
- b. **Fassarar Baya (Back Translation):** Wannan nau’in fassara ne a inda ake sake mayar da fassara zuwa harshen bayarwa. Ma’ana ke nan, bayan an yi fassara daga harshe na ɗaya zuwa harshe na biyu, sai kuma a sake mayar da shi daga harshe na biyun zuwa harshe na ɗaya. Idan aka yi la’akari da misalan da aka bayar a sama a karkashin “a” da yake kasan “4.1.1.1.2”, to wannan nau’in fassarar zai kasance sake mayar da abin da aka fassara zuwa harsunan farko (wato daga Hausa zuwa Ingilishi da Larabci).⁹¹

4.1.1.1.3 Daidaita Fassarori (Harmonization)

Wannan ma ɗaya ne daga cikin nau’o’in ayyukan fassara waɗanda suka shafi harshen Hausa. Kamar yadda sunan ya nuna, daidaita fassarori yana nufin nazartar fassarorin

⁹¹ Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, idan kai tsaye aka bayar da aikin fassara daga Hausa zuwa Ingilishi ko Larabci, to wannan ba fassarar baya ba ce. Za ta kasance fassarar baya idan aka sake buƙatar fassara abin da yake cikin harshen Ingilishi da Larabcin zuwa Hausa. Ana yin fassarar baya ne domin tabbatar da cewa ma’anar sakon da aka fassara bai salwanta ko ya gurɓace ba yayin da aka yi fassarar gaba. Yayin da aka lura da gurɓacewar ma’ana, to akwai buƙatar wani sabon aiki mai suna *Daidaita Fassara* (Harmonization). An tattauna wannan a kasa a karkashin 4.1.1.1.3.

da masu fassara biyu ko sama da haka suka yi domin samar da ingantacciyar fassara daga cikinsu. A kowane yankin fassara, za a dauki wadda ta fi dacewa, ko kuma a dauko bangarori (misali farkon fassara ta farko da karshen fassara ta biyu) domin samar da fassara mafi nagarta. Aikin daidaita fassara yana tasowa sakamakon manyan dalilai guda biyu kamar haka:

- a. **Bayar da fassara kai tsaye ga masu fassara daban-daban:** Ana iya ba wa mutane daban-daban fassara tun a karon farko domin muhimmancin abin da ake son fassarawa, ko don wani dalili na daban. Daga karshe kuma, sai a samu wani kwararre na daban domin daidaita fassarorin da suka samar.⁹²
- b. **Fassarar baya:** A duk lokacin da aka bayar da fassarar baya (misali mayar da Hausa zuwa Ingilishi), to za a duba domin tabbatar da cewa ba a samu gurbatar ma'ana ba a fassarar gaba da aka yi. Idan an samu gurbacear ma'ana, to za a tafi matakin daidaita fassara. A wannan gaɓar, za a samu kwararren da zai nazarci fassarorin biyu (ta gaba da ta baya) da kuma asalin harshen karɓa (source language) domin daidaita wuraren da suke da matsala.

4.1.1.1.4 Fassara Da Kirkira (Transcreation)

Aikin *fassara da kirkira* yana matuƙar kama da aikin fassara, musamman mai 'yanci. Babban bambancinsu shi ne, a aikin fassara da kirkira, an fi mayar da hankali kan kirkiro maganganu da suka dace da al'ada da adabin al'ummar da ake son isar wa saƙo. Wannan yana nuna cewa, za a fi mayar da hankali kan daidaiton kalamansu cikin rubutun da al'adun Hausawa da salon furta kalamansu. Wannan ma yana kara

⁹² Sau da dama Hausawa da suka goge a aikin fassara sukan yi korafin yadda suke cin karo da gurbatattun fassarori waɗanda a bayyane suke cewa ba Hausawa na haƙiƙa ba ne suka yi su.

jaddada bukatar Hausawa su shiga a dama da su a ire-iren ayyukan nan don kauce wa gurbacewar al'adun Hausa a hannun baubayi.

Mai aikin fassara da kirƙira yana da damar rafi da ƙari mai yawa daidai da manufar sakon. Wannan ne yake ba da dama sako ya fito ɗauke da salon magana da falsafar zance irin na masu magana da harshen a matsayin harshen uwa. Wannan yana nuna cewa, ana sa ran Bahaushe ya maye gurbin karin maganganun da ya ci karo da su da na Hausawa masu makamanciyar ma'ana da na harshen da yake aiki a kai. Aikin Mirela (2024) ya kawo cikakkiyar ma'anar 'fassara da kirƙira' da cewa:

Transcreation is a process in the field of language services where content is not just translated from one language to another but also creatively adapted to suit the cultural and emotional context of the target audience. (Mirela, 2024 SL. 6).

Fassarar Mai Bincike:

Fassara da kirƙira wani mataki ne a farfajiyar ayyukan da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe a inda ba wai kawai ana fassara ƙunshiya ba ne daga wani harshe zuwa wani, face ana yi masa kwaskwarima cikin ƙwarewa domin ya dace da al'ada da tunanin masu harshen da ake fassara zuwa cikinsa.⁹³

A duniyar ayyukan kimiyyar harshe a yau, dole ne a bambance tsakanin 'fassara' da kuma 'fassara da kirƙira.' Ayyukan fassara da dama suna da tsari da ƙa'idojin da suka shafi takaitawa da bin harshen karɓa sawu da ƙafa. Wannan yana faruwa musamman

⁹³ Domin samun ƙarin bayani game da 'fassara da kirƙira' ana iya duba Katan (2016) da Carreira (2023).

idan ana fassarar ne domin koyar da wata manhajar 'kirkirariyar basira' (AI). Yawanci kamfanonin fassara sun fi zaɓan kwararru yayin bayar da wannan aikin. Dole ne mai aikin ya kasance yana da kwarewa a harshe da adabi da al'ada. A taikaice ke nan, wanda yake da gogewa a fannin harshe da adabi da al'adun Hausawa, shi ne zai iya gudanar da wannan aiki yadda ya kamata. A duba hoton da yake kasa:

Hoto Na 4.1: Kamfanin fassara suna neman mai aikin fassara da kirkira cikin harshen Hausa

Madogara: Sakon imel

4.1.1.1.5 Fassarar Kan Sikirin (Subtitling)

Fassarar kan sikirin fassara ce da ake yi na maganganu da sautukan da halittun cikin bidiyo suke furtawa, tare da sanya su yadda za su riƙa bayyana a kan sikirin ɗin na'urar da ake kallon bidiyon a daidai inda ake samar da wannan sautin ko ake furta maganar.⁹⁴ A yau da duniya ta rungumi kallo da sauraro sama da karatu, bidiyoyi suna kara yawaita a duniya. Yayin da shirin game-duniya yake kara kankama, a kullum duniya tana kara bukatar fassarar kan sikirin. Kamfanoni da ma'aikatu da

⁹⁴ Domin ƙarin bayani game da 'Fassarar Kan Sikirin' (Subtitling), ana iya duba Ishika (2023).

gwamnatoci sukan sanya fassarar kan sikirin a bidiyoyin da suke tallata haja ko manufofinsu domin sakonnin su kai ga al'ummu daban-daban a fadin duniya. A duba misali a hoton da yake kasa:

Hoto Na 4.2: Bidiyon Hausa da fassarar kan sikirin cikin Ingilishi

Madogara: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0dQn93P8ZiM>

Wannan waka ce ta Nazifi Asnanic (Nazifi Abdulsalam Yusuf) da Ali Jita (Ali Isah) da kuma Naziru Sarkin Waka (Naziru M Ahmad). Tana da taken “Nonon Uwa Na Farko”. Za a lura da cewa, an yi mata fassarar kan sikirin cikin harshen Ingilishi.

Ko bayan wadannan, ana samun bidiyoyi masu tarin yawa cikin harshen Ingilishi dauke da fassarar kan sikirin cikin harshen Hausa. Haka kuma, akwai dubbannin bidiyoyin Hausa wafanda suke dauke da fassarar kan sikirin cikin Ingilishi.⁹⁵ Wannan

⁹⁵ Bidiyoyi masu tarin yawa a kan TikTok da YouTube (da sauran kafafen makamantansu) suna dauke da fassarar kan sikirin.

ya samar da wata kasuwa ga ma'aikata a kan intanet waƙanda suka kware a fannin samar da fassarar kan sikirin.

4.1.1.1.6 Gyaran Rubutu (Editing)

Gyaran rubutu wani babban reshe ne na ayyukan kan intanet da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe. A wannan mataki, ana son tabbatar da cewa an gyara duk waƙansu kurakurai da suka shafi kunshiyar rubutun. A Hausa, ya haɗa da daidaita jumloli domin dacewa da yadda Bahaushen kwarai zai faɗe su, da kuma tabbatar da rubutun bai kauce wa al'adar maganar Hausawa ta yau da kullum ba.

Aikin gyaran rubutu yana iya cin gashin kansa. Haka na faruwa ne idan rubutun da za a gyara a cikin harshe ɗaya yake (misali Hausa). A nan, mai gyaran zai bi rubutun ne domin daidaita zaman jumloli da yadda aka kulla zaren tunani a cikinsa.

A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, aikin gyara na iya biyo bayan wani aikin kimiyyar harshe da aka kammala. Misalan wannan sun haɗa da gyaran rubutu bayan kammala aikin fasara ko aikin fassarar kan sikirin, da dai sauran makamantansu. A irin wannan yanayi, akwai buƙatar mai gyara ya nazarci rubutu cikin harsuna biyu.⁹⁶ A duba misali a hoton da yake kasa:

⁹⁶ Domin karin bayani game da aikin gyaran rubutu, ana iya duba Saldanha & O'Brien (2014) da Cadwell et al. (2018).

Hoto Na 4.3: Kamfanin fassara na Game Lang suna neman wanda zai yi aikin gyaran rubutu

Madogara: Sakon imel daga kamfanin fassara na Game Lang

'TEP' a aikin fassara yana nufin "*Translation, Editing, and Proofreading*", wato fassara da gyaran rubutu da kuma karatun bita. A cikin wannan hoto da aka kawo a sama, za a ga cewa kamfanin suna neman wanda zai iya waɗannan ayyuka game da harshen Hausa. A irin haka ne waɗanda ba Hausawa ba suke amsa gayyatar yayin da aka rasa Hausawa kwararru a kusa.

4.1.1.1.7 Gyara Fassarar Na'urori (Machine Translation Post-Editing (MTPE))

Gyaran fassarar na'urori (MTPE) yana nufin gyara fassarorin da na'urorin fassara suka samar. Daya daga cikin manyan sauye-sauye da aka samu a fannin kimiyyar harsuna shi ne na'urorin fassara. Kamfanoni da dama sun samar da manhajojin fassara. Yanzu da ilimin kirƙirarriyar basira (AI) yake kara bunkasa, dabarun samar da manhajojin fassara suna kara yawa a duniya. Hausa tana ɗaya daga cikin harsunan da suke samun wannan tagomashi. Tana cikin jerin harsunan da suke kan manhajojin fassara da dama. Daga cikinsu akwai:

1. Bing Translator (<https://www.bing.com/translator>)
2. Google Translate (<https://translate.google.com>)
3. Lanfrica (HausaMT) (<https://lanfrica.com>)
4. Masakhane (NLP Project) (<https://www.masakhane.io>)
5. MyMemory Translation (<https://mymemory.translated.net>)
6. Translated.net (<https://www.translated.net>)

Kasuwar ayyukan MTPE tana kara bunkasa. Akwai manyan dalilai biyu da suke haifar da hakan. Na farko shi ne kasancewar ana kara samun kamfanonin da suke bayar da horaswa ga manhajojinsu na fassara. Yayin aiwatar da hakan, dole ne su fitar da samfuri fassarorin da injunan suka yi domin a yi musu gyare-gyare. Da wadannan gyare-gyaren ne ake kara inganta basirar na'urorin.

A bangare daya kuwa, ana ci gaba da samun karuwar injunan fassara na Hausa masu nagarta. Wannan ya sa wadansu masu bukatar fassara suke amfani da su. Da yake har yanzu injunan ba su kai kason nagarta da ake bukata ba (ana kan inganta su), dole ne a bayar da aikin MTPE domin yin gyararraki ga ire-iren fassarorin da aka yi ta hanyar amfani da injunan. Hakan ya haifar da karuwar ayyukan MTPE na Hausa.⁹⁷

Binciken Mykhalevych (2024) ya nuna yadda harsunan da ake yawan amfani da su a kan intanet suke kara samun ingantuwar fassara a kan injin din fassara na Google (Google Translate). A shekarar 2022, cibiyar bincike ta Preply ta nazarci mizanin ingancin fassarar GT. Sakamakon da ta samu ya kasance kamar haka:

⁹⁷ Ya zuwa shekaru masu zuwa, haka na iya cimma ruwa inda injunan fassara na Hausa za su iya kai wajajen mizanin samar da daidaitacciyar fassara da ta kai kashi casa'in cikin dari (90%). Idan haka ta faru, lallai ayyukan fassara za su yi matuƙar raguwa. A maimakon haka, ayyukan MTPE ne kawai za su yawaita.

Fassarar Ingilishi zuwa Sifaniyanci ya kai matakin 96.58% na daidaituwa. Ingilishi zuwa Jamusanci kuwa ya kai 94.56%. Shi kuwa Ingilishi zuwa Italiyanci ya kai 94.12%. Yayin da aka fassara rubutun harunan nan zuwa Ingilishi kuwa, makin daidaiton ya kai 97.18%. (Mykhalevych, 2024 SL. 13).

Binciken Schäferhoff (2023 SL. 46) ya nuna cewa, harsunan da aka fi amfani da su a kan intanet ne suka fi samun daidaitacciyar fassara a kan injunan fassara.⁹⁸ Binciken Taira et al. (2021) ya tabbatar da cewa har asibitoci sukan dogara da fassarorin da injunan fassara suke samarwa a yau (p. 3361). Duk da haka, fassarar GT ba ta kai a dogogara da ita ba tukunna (p. 3364). A duba misalin aikin gyaran fassarar na'urori cikin harshen Hausa da aka turo a cikin hoton da yake fasa:

Hoto Na 4.4: Aikin gyaran fassarar na'urori cikin harshen Hausa

Madogara: Sakon imel daga kamfanin fassara na Transparent

⁹⁸ Taira et al. (2021 sh. 3364) ma sun jaddada yadda ingancin fassara ya danganta daga harshe zuwa harshe. Wannan ya sa ya zama babban kalubale ga Hausawa musamman manazarta da su dukufa wajen ganin Hausa ta ci gaba da shiga cikin duniyar intanet.

4.1.1.1.8 Jarabawa (Evaluation)

A fannin aikin kan intanet da ya shafi kimiyyar harshe, jarabawa nau'in aiki ne wanda ya shafi aunawa da sanya maki ga ayyukan da waɗansu suka yi. Akan samu lokutan da kai tsaye akan ba da aikin fassara domin jarabawa, misali idan za a ɗauki sababbin ma'aikata Hausawa.⁹⁹ Yayin da mai fassara ya kammala fassara kalmomin jarabawa da aka ba shi, to za a ba wa kwararre wanda zai duba sannan ya sanya maki.

A waɗansu lokuta kuwa, ana iya ɗauko ɓangaren wani aiki mai yawa da aka gudanar a tura shi domin dubawa da sanya maki. Wani abin lura shi ne, jarabawa a wannan fannin ya bambanta da fannonin ilimi da matakan karatu da ake da su. Dalili kuwa shi ne, a mafi yawan lokuta, dole ne mutum ya samu kashi casa'in da bakwai a cikin ɗari (97%) kafin ya ci jarabawar. Da zarar ya yi kasa da haka, to za a ɗauke shi a matsayin mai rauni.¹⁰⁰ Ka'idojin sun ci karo da faɗin Hausawa cewa: "Dan'adam ajizi ne" ko "Dan'adam tara yake bai cika goma ba." Wani abin da ya kara bambanta su shi ne jerin ka'idojin abubuwan da ake dubawa yayin jarabawar. Gudanar da aikin jarabawa yana iya kasancewa a kan wata manhajar intanet, ko kuma a kan fayil ɗin Excel. A duba misali a cikin hoton da yake kasa:

⁹⁹ Yawanci kamfanonin ayyuka a kan intanet da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe sukan yi jarabawa kafin fara aiki da ma'aikaci mai cin gashin kansa.

¹⁰⁰ Daya daga cikin kalubalen ayyukan kan intanet da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe shi ne, ana iya cewa tsarin bai yarda da batun "ɗan'adam ajizi ne" ba.

Hoto Na 4.5: Aikin jarabawa da aka turo cikin harshen Hausa

English to Hausa Review Project- 30 Minutes

Projects - EALSTP|ByLanguages <[redacted]@ealanguagesolutions.com>
to me

Tue, Aug

Hello [redacted],

We have a new Hausa review task for your consideration - 30 minutes.

INSTRUCTIONS

Please revise the attached test translation.

A new candidate did this test, and we would like to assess their translation skills.

Madogara: Sakon imel daga kamfanin fassara na ByLanguages

A cikin wannan sakon imel da aka turo, za a tarar da cewa kamfanin sun yi jarabawa ne a sabon mai aikin fassara zuwa harshen Hausa. An turo fassarar Hausar da ya yi a matsayin aiki domin a duba a saka mata maki.

4.1.1.1.9 Karatun Bitu (Proofreading)

Aikin karatun bitu yana matuƙar kama da na ‘gyaran rubutu.’ Bambancinsu shi ne, karatun bitu mataki ne da yake gaba da na gyaran rubutu. Ana yin sa ne bayan an kammala gyara rubutu. A wannan gaɓar, abin da ake buƙata kawai shi ne dubawa da tabbatar da babu tuntuben alkalami ko ɗan jirkicewar tsarin rubutu. Akan daidaita wuraren da kwamfuta take jirkita rubutun Hausa, misali “book” a matsayin “boko.”

Kamfanin *Terra Translations* sun bayyana cewa, tsarin fassara yana iya kunsar mataki biyu kawai wato ‘fassara’ da ‘gyaran rubutu.’ Yana kuma iya kunsar matakai uku (3), wato ‘fassara’ da ‘gyaran rubutu’ da kuma ‘karatun bitu.’ (Marco, 2022 SL. 1).

Karatun bita ya kasance ɗaya daga cikin ayyukan kan intanet na ɓangaren kimiyyar harshe da suke da kalubale mai yawa. Dalili kuwa shi ne, akwai masu karɓar ayyukan Hausa da dama a kan intanet waɗanda ba kwararru ba ne. Da yawa daga cikinsu ba ko Hausawa ba ne. A sakamakon haka, mai karatun bita zai iya cin karo da ayyukan da suke tattare da ɗimbin matsaloli. Matsalolin suna iya haɗawa da ka'idojin rubutu da ma nahawun harshen kansa.¹⁰¹

4.1.1.1.10 Kirƙirar Rubutu (Content Creation)

Rubutu ba ya yin kansa. Duk wani rubutu da aka gani a kan intanet (kafafen intanet) ko a fuskar na'ura ko allunan tallace-tallace (da sauransu), to rubuta su aka yi. Fagen kirƙirar rubutu yana da matuƙar faɗi. Kasuwarsa ta dade tana ci a duniya. A matakin duniya, duk wani babban kamfani da zai iya zuwa kwaƙwalwar mutum, to lallai wannan kamfani yana aiki da masu kirƙirar rubutu. Haƙƙinsu ne su samar da:

- a. Bayanin kamfani cikin salo mai jan hankali,
- b. Tallace-tallacen hajojin kamfanoni,
- c. Bayanan yadda ake sarrafawa ko amfani da kayayyakin kamfani,
- d. Samar da rubuce-rubucen da za su ɗaga darajarsu da karfinsu a duniyar intanet (online ranking), da makamantan waɗannan.

Ba sosai ake samun aikin kirƙirar rubutun Hausa ba a kan intanet. Dalili kuwa shi ne, yawancin kamfanoni da ma'aikatu da hukumomi suna bayar da ire-iren ayyukan nan ne cikin harshen Ingilishi, ko wani babban harshen kasar da suke. Yayin da ake son

¹⁰¹ Wannan babban kalubale ne ga Hausawa, musamman manazarta harshen Hausa. Idan ba su tashi domin amfani da damarmakin da ake da su na ayyukan da suka shafi Hausa a kan intanet ba, wasu na daban za su ci gaba da cin gajiyar damarmakin. Abu mafi muni shi ne samar da gurɓatattun bayanai dangane da harshen.

samar da na Hausa, to sukan bayar da aikin fassara ne, ko kuma fassara da kirƙira.¹⁰² Kamfanin *Speak Your Language (SYL)* sun bayyana ‘takaita kashe kuɗi’ a matsayin ɗaya daga cikin amfanin fassara rubutu a maimakon kirƙirar sabo (*Speak Your Language (SYL)*, 2023 para 8-10).

4.1.1.1.11 Maye Gurbin Sauti (Voice Over)

Maye gurbin sauti fasaha ce ta share sautin da aka yi amfani da shi a cikin wani bidiyo (misali Larabci) tare da ɗora wani sauti na daban (yawanci a cikin wani harshe na daban, misali Hausa) cikin salo da tsarin da zai yi daidai da wanda aka cire ɗin (misali, motsawar baki ko wucewar hotuna, da sauransu). Kamfanin *Bunny Studio* ya bayyana ma'anar 'maye sauti' da cewa: "Voice over translation is an audio-visual conversion of dialogue from one language to another" (Weiss, 2021 SL. 7). Ma'anar ita ce, fassarar maye sauti fasaha ce ta sauya magana a cikin bidiyo daga wani harshe zuwa wani.

A yau, maye gurbin sauti ba sabon abu ba ne ga Hausawan da suke kallon finafinai ko labarai a talabijin ko kafafen intanet. A cikin labaran Hausa na talabijin, za a iya hasko bidiyon wani yana magana da wani harshe na daban wanda ba Hausa ba. A ɓangare guda kuwa, za a samu wanda zai fassara maganganun da yake faɗa sannan a ɗora sautin maganar cikin harshen Hausa domin maye gurbin ainihin sautin da ake magana da shi.¹⁰³

Akwai nau'o'in bidiyoyi daban-daban da ake neman masu aikin maye gurbin sauti domin yin aiki a kansu. Sun haɗa da:

¹⁰² An tattauna waɗannan a farkashin 4.1.1.1.2 da 4.1.1.1.4 a sama.

¹⁰³ Domin samun karin bayani game da a 'maye gurbin sauti', ana iya duba Matamala (2018) da Flis & Szarkowska (2024).

- a. Tallace-tallace
- b. Sanarwa
- c. Wasannin bidiyo (video games)
- d. Finafinai

Misalan finafinan da aka fassara daga wani harshe zuwa harshen Hausa sun hada da:

1. Lord of the Rings – Zoben Sihiri (an fassara shi daga Ingilishi zuwa Hausa)
2. Bang Bang! – Jihadi (an fassara shi daga Indiyanci zuwa Hausa)

4.1.1.1.12 Sassautawa (Localization)

Sassautawa a farfajiyar ayyukan kan intanet da ya shafi kimiyyar harshe yana nufin sassauto da rubutu ko maganar da aka yi cikin tsattsauran harshen kwarewa tare da saukafa shi ta yadda wafansu da harshen bai kasance na uwa a gare su ba za su iya fahimta. Yadda Hausawa suke da fasaha da kwarewar sarrafa harshe, ya bambanta da yadda sauran wafanda suka koyi harshen suke magana da shi. Wannan bambancin yana shafar zaɓen kalmomi da amfani da su a cikin jumloji. Misali, yadda Turawan Amurka suke rubutu da magana da harshen Ingilishi, ya bambanta da yadda Hausawa a Nijeriya suke rubutu da kuma magana da wannan harshen.¹⁰⁴

Yayin da Bature kwararre a fannin ‘kirkirar rubutu’ (kamar yadda aka tattauna a karkashin 4.1.1.1.9) ya rubuta talla cikin Ingilishi, to ba kowane Bahaushen da yake jin Ingilishi ba ne zai iya fahimta. A irin wannan yanayi, akwai bukatar turo tallar a wani Bahaushe wanda ya iya aikin *sassautawa*. Bukata ita ce ya sassauta rubutun

¹⁰⁴ An yi rubuce-rubuce daban-daban game da Ingilishin Nijeriya (Nigerian English) da nau’o’insa. Domin karin bayani ana iya duba Igboanusi (2002) da Nwachukwu (2022).

cikin saukafakafen harshe da salon da Bahaushe zai iya fahimta. A duba misali a cikin hoton da yake kasa:

Hoto Na 4.6: Aikin sassautawa daga Ingilishin Amurka zuwa Ingilishin Nijeriya domin Hausawa

English(US) to English Nigeria Localization Project- 1000 Words. 📧

Projects - EALSTP|ByLanguages <[redacted]@ealanguagesolutions.com>

Tue, Nov 5, 2024, 7:38 P

to me ▾

Hello [redacted],

We have a new task for your consideration- 1000 words.

Madogara: Sakon imel daga kamfanin fassara na ByLanguages

A wadansu lokuta kuwa, akan bukaci mai aikin sassautawa ya sauya wani rubutu daga wani karin harshe zuwa wani daban. Misali, ana iya bayar da rubutun da yake cikin Hausar Kamaru, sannan a bukaci a mayar da ita daidaitacciyar Hausa ko daya daga cikin kare-karen harsunan Nijeriya.

4.1.1.1.13 Tabbatar Da Ingancin Fassara (Linguistic Quality Assurance (LQA))

Yayin da aka kammala fassara, akwai bukatar dubawa da tabbatar da ingancinta. Mafi yawan manhajojin fassara (CAT Tools da Workbenches) suna da tsarin tabbatar da ingancin fassara a cikinsu. Wadansu daga cikin manhajojin fassara da suke da wannan tsari wadanda kuma ake ayyukan Hausa a kansu sun hada da:

- i. Crowdin (<https://crowdin.com/>)
- ii. memoQ (<https://www.memoq.com/>)
- iii. Phrase (<https://phrase.com/>)
- iv. TMS (<http://gt.gotransparent.com/>)

- v. Wordfast (<https://www.wordfast.net/>)

Yayin da mai fassara yake aiki a kan ire-iren waƙannan manhajoji, kai tsaye zai iya duba matsalolin da suke tattare da fassarar domin gyarawa. Akwai kuma manhajojin da suka shahara a bangaren fitar da rahoton ingancin fassara. “Hausawa masu aikin fassara sukan yi amfani da irinsu” A.M. Umar (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 17 ga watan Satumba 2024). Yayin da aka gudanar da fassara, za a shiga sashen da zai duba matsalolin da suke tattare da fassarar. Daga nan za a sauke rahoton a matsayin fayil mai cin gashin kansa. Waƙannan manhajoji sun haɗa da:

- i. Transform
- ii. Xbench

Yayin da aka ciro bayanansu matsalolin da suke tattare da fayil, akan nemi kwararre da ya iya aikin domin a ba shi. Nau’o’in matsalolin da ake iya samu a tattare da aiki sun haɗa da:

- a. Ba wa wani bangaren rubutu (iri ɗaya da ya fito a wurare biyu ko sama da haka) fassarori daban-daban¹⁰⁵
- b. Ba wa bangarrorin fassara biyu mabambanta fassara iri ɗaya¹⁰⁶
- c. Fassara wuraren da ba a fassarawa (DNTs)¹⁰⁷
- d. Saba wa gurbin kunshiyar rubutu (placeholder)¹⁰⁸

¹⁰⁵ Wannan nau’in matsalar ana kiran ta ‘Rashin Daidaito a Sashen Tushe’ (Inconsistency in Source).

¹⁰⁶ Wannan nau’in matsalar ana kiran ta ‘Rashin Daidaito a Sashen Manufa’ (Inconsistency in Target).

¹⁰⁷ Ana kiran su da suna ‘Kada a Fassara’ (Do Not Translate (DNTs)).

¹⁰⁸ Gurbin kunshiyar rubutu (placeholder) alamomi ne da ake sakawa a cikin fassara waƙanda bami idan ya gan su, ba zai iya gane abin da suke nufi ba. A kashin kansu ba su da wata ma’ana. Duk da haka, kwararre zai iya karanta rubutun da yake wurin daidai ta hanyar ba su wata ma’ana ta musamman. Misali, yayin da aka rubuta “%^% da wasu mutane %#\$ sun duba rubutun da ka ɗora ranar

- e. Saba wa ka'idojin rubutu¹⁰⁹
- f. Sanya adadin harufan da suka haura waƙanda aka kayyade a fassara¹¹⁰
- g. Tsallake kalmomi ba tare da an fassara ba

Ko bayan waƙannan da aka zayyano, akwai nau'o'in matsalolin da na'ura za ta iya zayyanowa a matakin *Tabbatar Da Ingancin Fassara*. Wani abin lura a nan shi ne, ma'aikacin kan intanet da yake wannan aikin zai iya cin karo da matsaloli nau'o'i biyu:

- i. Matsalolin gaskiya (Actual/Real Issues)
- ii. Matsalolin da ba na gaskiya ba (False Positive)

Yana da kyau a tuna cewa, na'urori ne suke fito da jerin wuraren da aka samu matsala ba mutane ba. Akwai wuraren da na'ura za ta ɗauki wani al'amari a matsayin matsala, alhali a zahirin gaskiya ba matsala ba ce. Ire-iren wuraren su ake kira '*False Positive*' (FP). Misali mai sauƙi a nan shi ne, a duk lokacin da aka rubuta kalma mai ɗauke da hamza a *sashen manufa* (target string), to na'ura za ta bayyana sashen a matsayin mai matsala saboda ba ta ga hamza a *sashen tushe* (source string) ba. Misali, yayin da aka fassara freedom da yanci, to na'ura za ta nuna */* a matsayin *rashin daidaiton alamomin rubutu* (inconsistency in punctuation). A irin wannan yanayi, ma'aikacin da yake aikin zai nuna cewa matsalar ba ta gaskiya ba ce (FP).

%#@", hakifanin yadda yake yana iya kasancewa **"Musa da wasu mutane 85 sun duba rubutun da ka ɗora a ranar 23/07/2024."**

¹⁰⁹ Ana kiran wannan da suna 'Rashin Daidaiton Alamomin Rubutu' (Inconsistency in Punctuations)

¹¹⁰ Akwai fayilolin fassarar da ake kayyade adadin harufan da ake buƙata ga fassarar kowane sashe. Yayin da aka haura adadin ko da da harafi ɗaya ne, to akwai buƙatar sai an duba an bi wata hanyar da za a rage adadin harufan.

4.1.1.1.14 Tafintanci (Interpretation)

Tafintanci nau'in fassara ne wanda ake gudanarwa kai tsare da baki a maimakon a rubuce. Wani karin bambancinsu da fassara shi ne, tafintanci ana gudanar da shi ne tsakanin bangarori guda biyu wafanda ba su fahimtar maganar juna. Mai irin wannan aikin ana kiran sa da suna *tafinta*. Yakan saurari magana daga bangaren farko (misali, Hausa) sannan ya fassara wa bangare na biyu (misali, Ingilishi). Haka kuma, zai saurari jawabin bangare na biyu (Ingilishi) sannan ya fassara wa bangare na farko (Hausa). A takaice, tafintanci wani aiki ne da ya shafi kimiyyar harshe inda bangarori biyu na mutanen da ba su fahimtar harsunan juna suke iya tattaunawa a tsakaninsu nan take da taimakon tafinta, inda shi tafinta yake fassara wa kowane bangare abin da fada bangaren ya fada.

Tafintocin kan intanet sukan samu ayyuka ta hanyoyi guda biyu:

- a. Ana iya duba bayanann tafinta a kan intanet sannan a bukaci ya je wani wurin da za a gabatar da aiki gaba da gaba. Za ta iya yiwuwa a kotu ne ko a wurin wani taro, da makamantansu.
- b. Ana iya neman tafinta daga kan intanet, sannan ya gudanar da tafintancin a kan intanet. Wannan yana yiwuwa ta hanyar waya ko wata manhajar da take ba da damar tattaunawa kai tsaye cikin bidiyo.

Gile (2009 sh. 17-35) da Pöchhacker (2016 sh. 10-40) sun tattauna nau'o'in tafintanci.

Ta fannin yanayin gudanarwa, akwai manyan nau'o'in tafintanci guda biyu. Su ne:

1. **Ba-Jira (Simultaneous):** Wannan nau'in tafintanci ne inda mai magana ba ya jira ko sararawa domin tafinta ya fassara abin da yake fada. A maimakon haka,

tafinta zai ci gaba da yin fassara yayin da mai maganar yake yi. Dole tafinta ya kasance yana da basirar iya sauraro da fahimtar magana tare da fassara ta ga masu sauraro, duk a lokaci ɗaya. A duba misali a kasa:

Hoto Na 4.7: Aikin tafintanci cikin harshe Hausa

Madogara: Sakon imel daga kamfanin fassara na Translate 4 Africa

- 2. Daki-Daki (Consecutive):** Wannan nau'in tafintanci ne a inda mai magana yake ɗan jinkirtawa domin tafinta ya samu damar fassa abin da ya faɗa kafin ya ci gaba.

4.1.1.1.15 Tsara Rubutu a Kwamfuta (Typesetting)

Tsara rubutu a kwamfuta yana nufin amfani da kwarewa da bin mata kai na musamman domin daidaitawa da shirya rubutu cikin wani kayyadadden salo da aka buƙata. Ya haɗa da zaɓen salo da girman rubutu da tazara tare da daidaita duk sauran abubuwan da suke cikinsa dangin hotuna da giraf da jadawali da sauransu.

Rubutun Hausawa a kwamfuta yana da alamar sauki a ido. Kowane madanni yana ɗauke da alamar rubutun da zai fito yayin da aka danna shi. A zahirin gaskiya kuwa, samar da rubutu mai tsari ya wuce yadda mai hange daga nesa yake tunani. Abu ne wanda yake bukatar kwarewa da mayar da hankali.

Ma'aikatun da ake yi wa aikin tsara rubutu suna da yawa. Bugu da kari, ɗaiɗaikun mutane sukan nemi kwararru wajen tsara rubutu a kwamfuta domin tsara musu wani aikinsu, kamar littafi ko takarda. Jami'ar Franklin ta wallafa jerin wuraren aiki da suke bukatar masu fasahar tsara rubutu a shafinta na wayar da kai game da ayyuka da sana'o'i.

Hoto Na 4.8: Kiyasin Adadin Masu Tsara Rubutu a Ma'aikatu

Madogara: Franklin University (n.d. SL. 8)

A hoto na 4.8 da yake sama, za a iya lura cewa kashi ashirin da bakwai da ɗigo takwas (28.7%) na masu wannan nau'in aiki sukan samu ayyuka ne a gidajen jaridu da mujallu da kamfanonin wallafa littattafai da makamantansu. Kashi takwas da ɗigo biyar (8.5%) kuwa suna aiki ne a kamfanoni da ma'aikatu da suke fannin ɗaukar ma'aikata. Kaso shida da ɗigo bakwai (6.7) sun kasance a fannonin tallace-tallace da na hulɗa da jama'a da makamantansu. Fannin tallafa wa kasuwanci suna da kaso biyar (5%), yayin da hukumomi da kungiyoyin addinai suke da kaso huɗu da ɗigo takwas (4.5%). Bangarorin da suka shafi zamantakewa da fasaha da ayyukan

kwararru suna da kaso hudu da diko biyar (4.5). A jimillar sauran bangarori ne kuma ake samun ragowar kaso arba'in da ɗaya da diko takwas (41.8%).

Wannan yana nuni ga ɗimbin gurabun da masu kwarewa a bangaren tsara rubutu suke da shi na samun ayyuka. Da taimakon intanet, ma'aikacin kan intanet yana iya samun ire-iren waɗannan ayyukan daga wasu kasashe na daban, ba lallai sai kasarsa ba. Mujallun Hausa irin su Tasambo JLLC (www.tasambo.com) da Dundaye Journal of Hausa Studies (www.dundaye.com) duk suna bin tsarin rubutu irin na mujallun kasa da kasa. Za su iya tura takardu ta kan intanet ga wani Bahaushe da ya iya irin wannan aikin domin ya yi musu.

4.1.1.2 Ayyuka Da Suka Shafi Intanet Da Na'urori

Akwai nau'o'in ayyuka daban-daban da suka shafi intanet da na'urori waɗanda Hausawa suka runguma a yau. Mukoshy (2015) ya yi kokarin tattara wasu muhimman kalmomin kwamfuta musamman waɗanda suka shafi intanet tare da samar da fassarorinsu. Kalmomin da ya fassara sun haɗa da na intanet da na kwamfuta da na burauzozi da makamantansu. A shafi na 108, ya yi kira da cewa: “Ya kamata Hausawa su shiga cikin sha'anin nazarin fannin kwamfuta, su yi ruwa, su yi tsaki a dukkan bangarorinta.” Ya nuna bunkasa da matuƙar alfanu da tagomashin da harkar intanet da kwamfuta take da shi a shafuka na 107-108. Wannan ɓangare na aikin yana ɗauke da bayanai game da ire-iren damarmaki da ake da su a wannan fannin.

4.1.1.2.1 Gina Kafafen Intanet (Website Design)

Idan aka ce kafar intanet, ana nufin *website* ko *blog* a Ingilishi. Gini ne da ake yi a kan intanet bisa tsari na musamman wanda yake d'auke da shafi (ga kafa mai shafi d'aya) ko shafuka (ga kafa mai shafuka da yawa). A kullum kafafen intanet kara yawa suke yi a duniya, ciki kuwa har da na Hausa. A duniyar intanet, kafafe sun kasance tamkar gine-gine da ake da su a duniyar zahiri. Nau'o'in gine-ginen sun danganta ga dalilin da aka yi su dominsa. Wadansu kasuwanni ne, wadansu shaguna, wadansu kuwa wuraren shakatawa ne, da dai sauransu. Binciken Reboot Online (2024 SL. 4) ya bayyana cewa, a shekarar 2024, akwai kimanin kafafen intanet da suka kai biliyan d'aya da miliyan d'ari da talatin (biliyan 1.13).

Hausawa da dama a yau sun riki gina kafafen intanet a matsayin hanyar cin abinci. Wani abin lura shi ne, ba sai wadanda suka karanci ilimin kwamfuta da intanet a jami'o'i ko kwalejojin ilimi ba ne suke iya cin abinci a wannan fanni. "Ko rukunin da suka zo na d'aya a gasar da Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo Sakkwato ta saka wanda ya shafi intanet, ba 'yan sashen ilimin kwamfuta ba ne, duk da cewa 'yan sashen ilimin kwamfuta sun shiga gasar.¹¹¹ Bugu da fari, dukkanninsu Hausawa ne" A. Sani (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 17 ga watan Satumba 2024).

Maginan kafafen intanet sun kasu zuwa manyan rukunoni guda uku, kamar haka:

1. **Maginan Fili (*Front End Developers*):** Maginin fili su ne wadanda suke gina bangarorin kafafen intanet da masu ziyarar kafafen suke iya gani. Ya hada da shafin farko da duk sauran shafukan da za a iya shiga. Ya shafi hotuna da

¹¹¹ Wadanda suka yi na d'aya sun fito ne daga Tsangayar Nazarin Fasahar Magunguna da Sashen Kiyon Lafiya (*Faculty of Pharmaceutical Science* da *College of Health Sciences*).

rubuce-rubuce da bidiyoyi da duk sauran abubuwan da mai ziyarar kafa zai iya gani. Aiki ne da yake buƙatar nazari da kwarewa. Mai yin wannan aiki dole ya samu kwarewa a kan ire-iren launukan rubutu da na hotuna da zai yi amfani da su, da yanayin girman rubutu da gurabun da ya kamata dukkannin abubuwan kan kafar su kasance.

2. **Maginan Boye (*Back End Developers*):** A kafafen intanet, ba kowane nau'in bayanai ba ne mai ziyarar kafa yake iya gani. Misali, yayin da ɗalibi zai yi rajista da kafar MIS ta Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo da take Sakkwato, to zai sanya keɓantattun bayanansa, ciki har da sunan mai akawun (*username*) da kuma kalmar sirri (*password*). Waɗannan bayanai za su tafi rumbun bayanai ne domin a adana su. Mai ziyarar kafar, ba zai iya ganin bayanan ba. Mutanen da suke gina wuraren da ake adana bayanan da samar da tsarin sarrafuwar bayanan, su ne ake kira *maginan boye*.
3. **Maginan Komai-Da-Ruwanka (*Full-Stack Developers*):** Akwai waɗanda suke samun kwarewa a dukkannin fannonin guda biyu, wato ginin bayyane da na boye. Waɗannan su ne ake kira *maginan komai-da-ruwanka*.¹¹²

Akwai nau'o'in harsuna (programming languages) da ake yin amfani da su yayin gina kafafen intanet. Sun kasance tamkar bulo-bulo da sauran kayan gini a duniyar zahiri. Yadda nau'in gine-ginen da za a yi a zahirance suke buƙatar kayan aiki na musamman, haka abin yake a lamarin ginin kafafen intanet. Dole ne Bahaushe ya nakalci waɗannan harsuna kafin gogewa a fannin. Ginin da za a yi, shi yake nuni ga nau'in

¹¹² Domin ƙarin bayani game da ayyukan gina kafafen intanet, ana iya duba Myers (2024) da Zeldman & Marcotte (2024).

harsunan da za a yi amfani da su. Duckett (2011 sh. 172-193) da Niederst Robbins (2018 sh. 93-200) sun yi bayanin harsunan intanet da yadda ake amfani da su.

Misalansu sun haɗa da:

- a. HTML (HyperText Markup Language)¹¹³
- b. CSS (Cascading Style Sheets)¹¹⁴
- c. JavaScript¹¹⁵
- d. PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor)¹¹⁶
- e. Python¹¹⁷
- f. TypeScript¹¹⁸

Akwai Hausawan da suka rungumi sana'ar gina kafafen intanet wa kwastomomi na kusa (*local programming*). A bangare ɗaya kuwa, akwai waɗanda suka dukufa wurin neman aiki a kan kafafen intanet (*online sourcing*).¹¹⁹ Kafafen intanet da suka kasance kasuwannin baje haja ga maginan kafafen intanet sun haɗa da:

- a. Fiverr (<https://www.fiverr.com>)
- b. Freelancer (<https://www.freelancer.com>)
- c. Guru (<https://www.guru.com>)

¹¹³ An fi amfani da shi wajen tsara kunshiyar kafafen intanet.

¹¹⁴ Ana amfani da shi wajen ba wa shafuka tsari da launi da girman rubutu.

¹¹⁵ Da shi ake samar da tsarin hulɗayya tsakanin masu ziyara da kafafen intanet (misali shi yake ba wa kafar intanet damar gane sunan maziyarci) da kuma sauyawar abubuwa da kansu (kamar motsawar rubutu ko hotuna).

¹¹⁶ Ana amfani da shi wajen gina fannonin da suka shafi 'ginin boye.'

¹¹⁷ Shi ma ana amfani da shi wajen gina fannonin da suka shafi 'ginin boye.'

¹¹⁸ Harshe ne mai aiki irin na JavaScript, sai dai ya fi JavaScript bunkasa. An fi aiki da shi a manyan kafafe da manhajoji masu sarkakiya.

¹¹⁹ M. Bello (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 20 ga watan Janairu 2024). Ya kasance Bahaushe wanda ya dogara da gina kafafen intanet a matsayin sana'a. <https://misaumodel.com.ng> ɗaya ce daga cikin kafafen intanet da ya gina (Kafa ce ta Misau Model Academy). Ya bayya cewa: "Ana cin wannan kasuwa da Hausawa masu yawa."

- d. PeoplePerHour (<https://www.peopleperhour.com>)
- e. Upwork (<https://www.upwork.com>)¹²⁰

Wani abin burgewa ga sana'ar gina kafafen intanet shi ne, duk kafar da maginin ya gina, to za ta ci gaba da kawo masa kudi na tsawon lokaci. Hakan yana faruwa ne sakamakon akwai gyare-gyare da sabunta bayanai da masu kafar za su bukaci maginin ya yi. Yayin gudanar da sauye-sauyen kuwa, to za a biya shi wasu kudafe na musamman. Ko bayan wannan, lokaci zuwa lokaci akan samu sabuntawa na gama-gari da za a yi. Shi ma sai an biya maginin kafin ya aiwatar. Akan yi aiki a kan kafar intanet a bisa dalilai da dama. Wasu daga ciki su ne:

- a. Bukatar sauya wasu bayanai (rubutu ko hotuna ko bidiyoyi) a kan intanet
- b. Sabunta biyan kuɗin rumbun ajiye bayanai (hosting)
- c. Sabunta biyan kuɗin sunan kafar intanet (domain name)
- d. Bunkasa/girman kunshiyar intanet da zai kai ga bukatar farin girman rumbun ajiye bayanai
- e. Gyara wata matsala da za ta iya bullowa
- f. Muradin sauya fasalin shafukan kafar intanet
- g. Samuwar sababbin fasahohi sakamakon cigaban zamani

Lura da duka waɗannan, sana'ar gina kafafen intanet ta kasance mai maiko wadda take ci gaba da kawo wa mutum kudi ko bayan kammalawa. Ana iya kwatantan shi da ginin gidan duniyar zahiri a kasar Hausa. Yayin da aka gina gida, hakan ba ya nufin an

¹²⁰ A cikin waɗannan kafafe, akwai Hausawa masu yawa. Wannan yana nuni ga yadda Hausawa suke da damar shiga a dama da su a wannan fannin.

kammala aikin dindindin. Lokaci zuwa lokaci za a kira mai fenti ko kafinta ko fulamba domin gyara wani abin da ya baci. Haka abin yake ga kafafen intanet.

4.1.1.2.1.1 Masu Zana Gini (UI UX Designers)

Kamar yadda injiniyoyi suke zana gidaje kafin a fara gininsu a duniyar zahiri, a duniyar intanet ma akwai masu sana'ar zana gine-ginen intanet. Ba dole ne ya kasance suna da ilimin yin ginin ba. A maimakon haka, bukata kawai ita ce su kware a fannin kirkiro yadda tsarin ya dace ya kasance. Hakan yana nuna cewa, Hausawa suna da damar shiga a dama da su a wannan fage ko da ba su kware a gina kafafen intanet ba.

“UI”¹²¹ yana nufin duk waƙansu abubuwa da ake iya gani kuma a yi mu'amala da su a kan kafar intanet. Sun haɗa da hotuna da zane-zane da alamomi da shafuka da sauran rubuce-rubuce. A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, “UX”¹²² yana nufin tsarin yadda masu ziyarar kafafen intanet za su yi hulɗa da kafafen. Ana iya kwatanta tsarin da abin da yake faruwa a duniyar zahiri. Misali, idan mutum ya je babban kanti, zai zaɓo kayan da yake son saye, sannan ya zo wurin da zai biya kuɗin kayan. Kwatankwacin haka abin yake a kan intanet idan kafar ta kasuwanci ce. *UX* ya shafi tsara matakan yadda za a je a zaɓo kaya da yadda za a biya kuɗinsu (da sauransu).

Kafin maginin kafar intanet ya fara wani aiki, dole ne sai ya san abin da yake da niyyar ginawa. Matakin farko shi ne samun bayanin dalilin samar da kafar da yadda ake son tsarin ya kasance da mutanen da za su yi amfani da kafar. Yayin da kwararre a zana ginin kafar intanet ya saurari bayanan abin da mai bayar da aiki yake bukata, to zai

¹²¹ *User Interface*

¹²² *User Experience*

iya samar da zanen tsari mai kyau. Kai tsaye maginan kan intanet za su yi amfani da wannan zane domin aiwatar da ginin. Masu kafafen *Hausa* irin su *Amsoshi* da WikiHausa da *Bakandamiya* (da sauransu), sukan tattauna a tsakaninsu domin kara wa juna sani game da tsarin gine-ginen kafafensu.

4.1.1.2 Bayar Da Tsaro Ga Kafafen Intanet Da Na'urori (Cyber Security)

Kamar yadda ake bayar da tsaro a gidaje da kasuwanni da ma'aikatu a duniyar zahiri, akwai makamancin wannan a duniyar intanet. Kowanne daga cikin kafafen intanet kimanin biliyan biyu¹²³ da ake da su a yau suna ci gaba da wanzuwa ne sakamakon ana ba su kariya. Tsaro da ake ba wa kafafen intanet ya shafi kare su daga masu kutse waƙanda za su iya dakatar da ayyukan kafafen tare da sace muhimman bayanai da suke kansu. Ko bayan wannan illar, masu kutse suna iya amfani da kafafen intanet domin satar bayanan maziƙarta kafafen tare da koƙarin damfarar su.

Akwai Hausawa da suka kware a wannan fanni. Wani abin burgewa shi ne, "fage ne da yake matuƙar kawo kuɗi ga waƙanda suka nakalce shi" J. Abdullahi (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 7 ga watan Fabarairu 2023). Hakan yana da nasaba da karacin gwanaye a fannin sakamakon tsauri da wuyar sha'ani da yake da shi.¹²⁴

Waƙanda suka yi na ɗaya da na biyu a Gasar Gwanin Kutse a Nijeriya (HackBoss Nigeria) a shekarar 2017 duka Hausawa ne. Abdulmalik Ibrahim shi ne ya zo na farko,

¹²³ Binciken Wise (2023) ya bayyana biliyan biyu a matsayin kiyasin adadin kafafen intanet a duniya ya zuwa shekarar 2023 (duk da cewa binciken Reboot Online (2024) ya bayar da adadin da bai kai haka ba).

¹²⁴ Waƙanda suka zo na farko da na biyu a gasar kutsen kan intanet ta *CS2 HackBoss* ta 2017 duka Hausawa ne. Wannan yana kara nuni da yadda Hausawa suke daɗa rungumar wannan fanni na kutsen kan intanet. A duba ITREALMS, (2017).

yayin da Shehu Awwal ya zo na biyu (ITREALMS, 2017). Wannan yana nuni ga yadda Hausawa suka yi nisa a harkar.

4.1.1.2.3 Gina Manhajoji (Software Programming)

Manhaja aba ce da take da siffar kafar intanet, wanda ake iya saukewa a kan na'ura kamar waya ko kwamfuta domin amfani da ita. Wannan yana nuna cewa, ta bambanta da kafar intanet kasancewar ita kafar intanet, dole ne a hau ta kan burawuza kafin a iya buɗe ta. Ita kuwa manhaja tana cin gashin kanta a inda za a iya buɗe ta kai tsaye yayin da aka sauke ta a kan na'ura.

Duk da haka, yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, a lokuta da dama manhajoji sun kasance tamkar hoto ne ko inuwar kafafen intanet. Ma'ana a nan ita ce, akan samu kafafen intanet da aka yi wa manhajoji. A irin wannan yanayin, manhajojin za su kasance suna tsotso bayanai ne daga kafafen. Idan kuwa manhaja ce da take ba da dama ga ɗaiɗaikun mutane su sanya bayanai a ciki, to bayanan da suka sanya za su tafi ne zuwa rumbun ajiyar kafar.

A yau, bukatar samar da manhajoji tana kara yawaita a duniya. Ba sai an tafi shekaru da yawa baya ba, a wajajen 2006 kadai “da wuya a kirga Hausawa biyar (5) a birane ko kauyuka ba a sami ɗayansu da rediyo ba” (Bunza, 2006 sh. 21). Ya zuwa 2024, tuni lamarin ya sauya zane. Hausawa da dama sun koma amfani da wayoyin hanu wurin sauraron labarai. Lura da hakan ya sa gidajen rediyo da na talabijin suka samar da manhajojin da za su ba da damar kallo ko sauraron shirye-shiryensu ko da an riga da an kammala gabatarwa. A nan sai a lura da cewa, duk gidan rediyo ko talabijin da

suka yi saken kasa sanya rigar zamani, lallai sai dai su ga ana yi. Waƙansu daga cikin manhajojin sauraron labarai a yau sun haɗa da:

Sunan Manhaja	Tambari
1. Hausa Radio	
2. Freedom Radio	
3. Dala FM	
4. Arewa Radio	
5. Izala Radio	

Madogara: Rumbun Manhajoji Na Google (Google PlayStore)

A yau akwai Hausawa da suka shahara a wannan fage na samar da manhajoji. Daga shekarar 2020 lokacin da Hasawa suka rungumi kasuwancin sayar da datar waya a intanet, an ci gaba da samun karuwar manhajoji mallakin Hausawa. Haka kuma, an ci gaba da samun Hausawa da suke rungumar wannan fanni na gina manhajoji (K. Sani, kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 12 ga watan Ogusta 2024).

Sana'ar gina manhajoji tana matufkar kama da ta gina kafafen intanet. Kamar yadda aka yi bayani a karkashin 4.1.1.2.1 da yake sama, kammala ginin ba ya nufin aiki ya fare. Lokaci zuwa lokaci za a buƙaci gyararraki. Wannan yana nuna cewa, yayin da

mutum ya gina manhajoji masu yawa a kamfanoni da daidai mutane, to yana da tabbacin ci gaba da samun kuɗin shiga.¹²⁵

4.1.1.2.4 Gwada Inganci Manhajoji Da Kafafen Intanet (Beta Testing)

Yayin da aka gina manhajoji da kafafen intanet, akwai bukatar a gwada su domin tabbatar da suna aiki yadda ya kamata. Hakan ba ya nufin kowane gama-garin mutum zai iya shiga ya duba. Aiki ne da yake bukatar kwarewa da sanin bangarorin da za a bincika tare da gano shafukan da suka aiki daidai da waɗanda suke da matsala.

Wani abin burgewa a wannan aikin shi ne, har Hausawa waɗanda ba su iya gina kafafen intanet ba suna iya ‘gwada ingancin manhajoji da kafafen inganet.’ Babban ilimin da ake bukata shi ne na sanin yadda kafa ko manhajoji suke aiki da kuma yadda ake gane matsalolinsu.

4.1.1.2.5 Gwada Kutse (Penetration Testing)

Gwada Kutse sana’ar kan intanet ce mai zaman kanta. Duk da haka, tana da matuƙar alaƙa da sana’ar ba da tsaro a kafafen intanet (wadda aka tattauna a farkashin 4.1.1.2.2). Dalili kuwa shi ne, duk ayyukan biyu masu ilimin kutse a na’urori ne suke iya gudanar da su.

Yayin gudanar da aikin gwada kutse, akan biya ma’aikaci domin ya yi bakin fofarinsa wajen kutsawa cikin wata na’ura ko manhaja ko kafar intanet (hacking). Yayin da ya samu nasara yin hakan, sakamakon zai nuna wa masu gina kafar cewa akwai tasgaro

¹²⁵ Ya zuwa watan Agustan shekarar 2024, manhajojin da suke cikin Google PlayStore kafai sun kai miliyan biyu da dubu dari uku (miliyan 2.3) (Ceci, 2024).

a aikinsu. Daga nan za su yi saurin toshe hanyoyin da suke ba da damar yin wannan kutse.

Lokaci zuwa lokaci manyan kamfanoni sukan sanya mafukan kudafe tare da barin kafa a buƙe ga duk wanda zai ba da rahoton gano wata damar yin kutse a kafa ko na'urorinsu. Hakan yana taimaka musu wajen tabbatar da miyagun masu kutse (black hat hackers) ba su yi musu ba zata ba.

Trend Micro (2024) sun kawo Bahausha a cikin jerin sunayen wafanda suka taɓa taimaka musu wajen gano wata matsalar da za ta iya bayar da dama a yi kutse. Wannan yana nuni da yadda Hausawa suka fara yin nisa a wannan fannin.

4.1.1.2.6 Tsara Manhajin Wasanni (Games Developing)

Tarihin ɗan'adam ciki yake da wasanni daban-daban. Sun haɗa tun daga kan wasannin da ake aiwatarwa ta hanyar furuci domin raha da barkwanci, har zuwa wafanda ake gudanarwa da gabobin jiki. Wani abin burgewa shi ne, yawancin wasannin suna da dokoki da ka'idoji na musamman. Bugu da kari, an gina su ne kan manufofi na musamman wafanda suka haɗa da ilimantarwa ko fadakarwa ko koyar da jarumta ko wayo da dabara, da dai sauran makamantan wafannan kamar yadda Sani & Gobir (2021 sh. 8-16) suka nuna.

Sauye-sauyen zamani, musamman samuwar intanet ya haifar da muhimmin canji da tasiri ga lamarin wasanni a duniya. Wannan tasirin ya shafi wasannin Hausawa.¹²⁶ Hakan ya faru ne sakamakon wasannin kan na'urori da na kafafen intanet da aka

¹²⁶ Domin samun karin bayani game da tasirin zamani a kan wasannin Hausawa, ana iya duba Sani & Gobir (2021).

samar. A takaice an samu wasanni a duniyar zahiri da kuma kwatankwacinsu a duniyar baƙini.

Kasuwar wasannin zamani kullum fara faɗaɗa take yi. Akwai waɗanda suke tunanin gina manhajojin wasanni aiki ne na Turawa kawai. A zahiri ba haka abin yake ba. Akan samu wasannin da ma'aikata masu yawa ne suke haɗuwa su gina manhajojinsu. Kowane ma'aikaci za a ba shi ɓangaren da zai gina, tamkar yadda mesin-mesin masu yawa suke haɗuwa su gina babban gida.¹²⁷ Hausawa suna da damar yin ayyuka a waɗannan kamfanonin haɗa wasanni.

Wani abu mai kayatarwa game da lamarin manhajojin wasanni shi ne, rukunonin ma'aikata da yawa ne suke cin abinci daga gare shi. Daga ciki akwai:

1. Masu zana gini (an kawo bayaninsu a farkashin 4.1.1.2.1.4): Su ne za su tsara yadda wasan zai kasance. Akwai wasanni da suka kunshi gidaje da garuruwa da kasashe da ababan hawa. Aikin masu zanen ne fitar da tsarin yadda abin zai kasance a matsayin matakin farko kafin fara ginin gadan-dagan.
2. Masu gina manhajoji (an kawo bayaninsu a farkashin 4.1.1.2.3): Su suke gina ɓangarorin manhajar sannan a haɗe ta wuri ɗaya domin bayar da kammalalliyar manhajar wasan kan intanet ko cikin na'ura.
3. Masu kirƙirar rubutu (an yi bayaninsu a farkashin 4.1.1.1.9): Su ne suke rubuta duk waɗansu bayanan wasa. Bayanan sun haɗa da na shafukan wasannin da kuma tattaunawa da ake yi tsakanin 'yan wasa a cikin manhajar.

¹²⁷ Magina dubu takwas da ɗari shida da casa'in da biyu (8,692) ne suka yi aikin gina wasan *Diablo IV* wanda kamfanin *Blizzard Entertainment* ya samar. Idan aka haɗa da sauran ma'aikata (misali masu aikin maye sauti da aka tattauna a farkashin 4.1.1.1.10 da masu aikin gwada ingancin manhajoji da kafafen intanet da aka tattauna a farkashin 4.1.1.2.4), jimillar waɗanda suka yi aikin sun kai dubu biyu da ɗari huɗu da sittin da huɗu (2,464). A duba Samoylenko (2023).

4. Masu aikin maye sauti (an kawo bayaninsu a farkashin 4.1.1.1.10): Su ne suke furta duk maganganun da ake cin karo da su a cikin wasannin kan intanet. Wannan ya fi shafar wasannin da suke da tsarin da yake ba wa 'yan cikin wasannin damar tattaunawa a tsakaninsu, da kuma wadanda ake bayar da umarni ko furta wadansu maganganu yayin da ake wasa.
5. Masu fassara (an kawo bayaninsu a farkashin 4.1.1.1.2): Su ne ake ba wa fassarar bayanan da suke cikin manhajojin wasanni domin fassarawa. Yayin da aka yi fassara kuwa, to ana iya bukatar bita ko gyaran fassara kafin aikin ya kammala.
6. Masu gwada inganci da amincin manhajoji da kafafen intanet (an yi bayaninsu a farkashin 4.1.1.2.4): Suna da gurbi na musamman a wannan fage. Dole ne a gwada manhajar wasa sosai kafin sake ta ga al'umma. Manhajojin wasanni sun kasance masu matukar sarkakiya.

Lura da waƙannan, fagen wasannin zamani na manhajojin na'urori da kafafen intanet babbar kasuwa ce da Hausawa suke da damar shiga a dama da su. Ana iya mayar da wasannin Hausa daban-daban zuwa cikin na'urori.

4.1.1.3 Ayyuka Da Suka Shafi Gyaran Hotuna Da Bidiyoyi

Samar da suran mutane da halittu al'ada ce da ta dade a rayuwar 'yan'adam. Hausawa ma ba a bar su da baya ba a wannan fannin. Tarihin shekaru aru-aru yana kunshe da sassake-sassake da zane-zanen surori daban-daban. Akan yi su domin cimma mabambantan manufofi da suka hada da:

- a. Ado ko kwalliya

- b. Adana tarihi
- c. Bauta

Ci gaban zamani ya buɗe sabon babi a wannan fage yayin da ɗan’adam ya samu fasahar ɗaukar hotuna da bidiyoyi. Hausawa da dama sun rungumi wannan sana’a a matsayin hanyar cin abinci. Akan je shagunansu domin a ɗauki hoto, a wanke sannan a ba wa mai shi. Haka kuma, akan gayyace su wararen taruka ko gidaje ko makarantu da sauransu, domin su ɗauki hotuna da bidiyoyi.

Samuwar intanet ya sake kawo sabon ci gaba a wannan fannin. A yau an samu hanyoyin samun kuɗi da dama waɗanda suka shafi sarrafa hotuna da bidiyoyi. Al’adar wanke hotunan kati ta fara dusashewa. Hotuna sun koma cikin wayoyi da kwamfutoci da kafafen intanet da kuma manhajoji.

A farkashin wannan, akwai manyan nau’o’in aikin guda uku (3), wato:

- a. Sarrafa Hotuna Da Bidiyoyi (Photo and Video Editing)
- b. Tsara Hotuna Da Zane-Zane (Graphic Design and Illustration)
- c. Katun (Animation)

4.1.1.3.1 Sarrafa Hotuna Da Bidiyoyi (Photo and Video Editing)

Daukar hotuna da bidiyoyi tare da sarrafa su, sana’a ce wadda kasuwarta take kara faɗaɗa. A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, kamfanonin wayoyi suna kara inganta kamerorin wayoyinsu. Wannan ya sa sau da dama ba a buƙatar mai ɗaukar hoto na musamman kafin samar da hotuna masu kyau. Duk da haka, bukukuwa da dama a kasar Hausa a

yau ba sa kammaluwa ba tare da gayyato masu daukar hotuna da bidiyoyi ba. Haka ma abin yake ga taruka na musamman.

Abubuwa da dama na gyaran hotuna da bidiyoyi sun koma kan intanet. Ana amfani da manhajoji daban-daban ko kafafen intanet na musamman domin yin hakan. Wannan ya shafi cire bangarorin da ba a so ko musanya su ko fara haskensu ko ko ragewe, da dai sauran nau'o'in gyararraki masu yawa.

Wadansu daga cikin manhajojin da ake amfani da su domin gyaran hoto su ne:

1. Adobe Photoshop (<https://www.adobe.com/products/photoshop.html>)
2. GIMP (GNU Image Manipulation Program) (<https://www.gimp.org/>)
3. Canva (<https://www.canva.com/>)
4. Snapseed (<https://snapseed.online/>)
5. Pixlr (<https://pixlr.com/>)
6. VSCO (<https://vSCO.co/>)
7. Fotor (<https://www.fotor.com/>)
8. Affinity Photo (<https://affinity.serif.com/photo/>)
9. PhotoScape X (<http://x.photoscape.org/>)

Wadansu daga cikin manhajojin da ake amfani da su domin gyaran bidiyoyi su ne:

1. Adobe Premiere Pro (<https://www.adobe.com/products/premiere.html>)
2. Final Cut Pro (<https://www.apple.com/final-cut-pro>)
3. iMovie (<https://www.apple.com/imovie/>)
4. Filmora (<https://filmora.wondershare.com/>)
5. KineMaster (<https://www.kinemaster.com/>)

6. InShot (<https://inshot.com/>)
7. CapCut (<https://www.capcut.com/>)
8. Lightworks (<https://lwks.com/>)
9. Shotcut (<https://shotcut.org/>)

A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, Hausawa masu irin wannan sana'a suna da damar buɗe akawun-akawun a kafafen intanet da na sana zumunta. Hakan yakan kasance riba biyu a gare su. Na farko shi ne ƙara samun sanuwa wanda hakan zai kai ga sun ƙara samun kwastomomi. Na biyu kuwa shi ne kasancewar sannu a hankali kafafen nasu suna iya bunkasar da za su kai gacin fara ɗora tallace-tallace domin samun ƙarin kuɗin shiga. Yawanci sukan ɗora samfuran hotuna da bidiyoyi da suka ɗauka a wurare daban-daban a matsayin tallatawa.

Misalan ire-iren waɗannan akawun-akawun na kafafen sada zumunta sun haɗa da:

1. Ahmed Bube (Bube Photography - Sokoto)¹²⁸
2. Faisal H. Adam (Faisal Photography - Kano)¹²⁹
3. Fa'iza Ibrahim Birnin Magaji (Famnoor Photography - Zamfara)¹³⁰
4. Haruna Alengo (Alengo Photography - Bauchi)¹³¹

Wani ƙarin dama da ake da ita dangane da ɗaukar hotuna da bidiyo ita ce sayar da su a manyan kafafen dillancin hotuna. Hausawan da suka ɗauki hotuna masu kyau suna

¹²⁸ Akawun ɗinsa na Facebook shi ne: <https://www.facebook.com/p/Bube-Photography-100066431712579/?rdr>

¹²⁹ Akawun ɗinsa na Instagram shi ne: https://www.instagram.com/faisal_photography/

¹³⁰ Akawun ɗinta na Instragram shi ne: https://www.instagram.com/famnoor_photography/

¹³¹ Akawun ɗinsa na Instragram shi ne: https://www.instagram.com/alengo_photography/?hl=en

da damar buɗe akawun da tallata hotunan a kan intanet. Misalan kafafen intanet waɗanda ake sayar da hotuna sun haɗa da:

1. Adobe Stock (<https://stock.adobe.com>)
2. Shutterstock (<https://www.shutterstock.com>)
3. Getty Images (<https://www.gettyimages.com>)
4. Alamy (<https://www.alamy.com>)
5. Foap (<https://www.foap.com>)
6. Dreamstime (<https://www.dreamstime.com>)
7. Etsy (<https://www.etsy.com>)
8. Zenfolio (<https://www.zenfolio.com>)
9. SmugMug (<https://www.smugmug.com>)
10. Wirestock (<https://www.wirestock.io>)

4.1.1.3.2 Tsara Hotuna Da Zane-Zane (Graphic Design and Illustration)

A gargajiyance akwai Hausawan da suke da kwarewa a fannin zane-zane. Sukan yi amfani da kayan aiki daban-daban, dangogin tawada da alkalami. Zamani da shigowar na'urori da intanet ya sa an buɗe sabon babin zane-zane. A garuruwan kasar Hausa, Hausawa da dama suna gudanar da aikin tsara hotuna da zane-zane a shagunan aikin kwamfuta. Su ne suke tsara katunan gayyata zuwa taron aure da sauran taruka, har ma da katunan godiya da fastocin 'yan takarar siyasa.

Ana buƙatar aikin tsara hotuna da zane-zane domin dalilai masu yawa. Wasu daga ciki su ne:

- a. Samar da katunan gayyata na aure

- b. Samar da takardun sanar da gayyata zuwa tarukan ilimi ko na siyasa
- c. Tsara tallace-tallacen hajoji
- d. Tsara bangwayen littattafai da na finafinai
- e. Tsara tambarin fungiyoyi da ma'aikatu da makarantu
- f. Tsara tambura da hotuna a jikin kayayyakin sakawa da na amfani

Hausawa kwararru a fannin tsara hotuna da zane-zane suna da damar da za su iya ayyuka a kan intanet. Suna iya karɓar ayyuka daga kwastomomi na kusa da na nesa. Babban misali a nan shi ne, wanda ya tsara bangon mujallar Tasambo (Tasambo Journal of Language, Literature, and Culture) na farko a kan intanet aka same shi. Shi ne kuma ya samar da kayataccen hoton da aka dora a shafin farko na kafar intanet din mujallar (www.tasambo.com).

4.1.1.3.3 Katun (Animation)

Katun tsarin bidiyo ne a inda ake amfani da fasaha ta musamman domin samar da hotuna da zane-zane masu motsi. Yawanci akan tsara motsinsu bisa wani labari wanda hakan yake mayar da su tamkar finafinai. Akan yi amfani da fasahar 2D ko ta 3D yayin samar da katun.

Yayin da aka yi maganar *katun*, abin da zai fara zuwa tunanin mutane da dama shi ne *Tom & Jerri*. A tsakanin Hausawa kuwa, mutane da dama za su iya tuna *Kiriku*. Kiriku katun ne wanda aka fassara zuwa harshen Hausa. Ya yi tashe sosai a lokacinsa. Ya karafe garuruwan Hausawa da dama inda har aka samu sababbin kalmomi daga shirin. Daga cikinsu akwai:

Jadawali Na 13: Misalan Katun Din Hausa

Kalma	Asali	Ma'ana
Kiriku	Sunan babban tauraron cikin katun dɪn Kiriku	Karamin mutum mai fitina ko wayo
Karaba	Sunan bokanya a cikin katun dɪn Kiriku	Fitinanniyar mace

Tushen Bayani: Kebantacciyar Tattaunawa¹³²

Ko bayan wannan, wakofi da wafansu lafuzzan da aka samo daga cikin katun dɪn sun zamo sara. Daga cikinsu akwai:

- a. "Kiriku dɪn yaro, amma shi sadauki ne!"
- b. "Ruwa ya zo, ruwa ya zo!"

Duka da wafannan suna nuni da yadda katun dɪn ya samu karbuwa.

Tun a shekarar 2009 akwai babban yunkuri da manazarci a matakin digiri na biyu ya yi a Jami'ar Bayero da take Kano. Ya yi nazarin ne a kan yadda za a iya mayar da tatsuniyoyin Hausa cikin katun. Yunkuri irin wannan zai sa a tafi da zamani, tare da rage dogaro kan bidiyoyi da suke fitowa daga al'ummun da ba Hausawa ba, wafanda kuma ba su dace da tunani da al'adun Hausawa ba. Ko katun dɪn Kiriku, daya daga cikin dalilan samun karbuwarsa shi ne kasancewar ya dace da al'adun Hausawa. Ko da ma dai, labarin ya samo asali ne daga al'adu da salon tatsuniyoyin Afirka. Fitattun masu katun dɪn Hausa a yau sun hada da:

- a. Akili and Me - Hausa¹³³

¹³² (A.M. Manga, kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 4 ga watan Fabarairu 2023) da (A. Umar, kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 7 ga watan Fabarairu 2023)

¹³³ Ana iya duba bidiyoyinsu a <https://www.youtube.com/@AkiliHausa>.

- b. Baban Yellow TV¹³⁴
- c. Hausa Fairy Tales¹³⁵
- d. Muib Toons¹³⁶
- e. Official MMBSTUDIOS¹³⁷

Katun hanya ce ta samun kuɗi cikin sauƙi. Yayin samar da bidiyoyin katun, ba a buƙatar ‘yan wasa a zahiri ko kuma kamera da haske da sauran kayan ɗaukan bidiyo. A maimakon haka, komai a cikin kwamfuta ake haɗa shi. A ciki ake samar da ‘yan wasa tare da tsara yadda bidiyon zai gudana. Wannan dama ce ga Hausawa.

4.1.1.4 Ayyuka Da Suka Shafi Bincike

Kalmar bincike ba baƙuwa ba ce ga baƙuna da kunnuwan Hausawa. Ta karade rayuwar ɗan’adam ta yau da kullum. Kusan a kowane bagire ana amfani da ita ko kalmomin da suke zaman masu kinin ma’ana a gare ta.¹³⁸ A bisa haka, kalmar tana iya ɗaukar ma’anoni da dama mabambanta ta fuskar manufa da matakan aiwatarwa. (Bunza, 2017a sh. 22-23) ya kawo ma’anar binciken ilimi bayan nazartar jerin ma’anonin da manazarta daban-daban suka bayar. Ya ce:

Bibiyar diddigin wani abu ta hanyar taliyon mafarinsa da sabgoginsa da yanaye-yanayensa. Bincike shi ne fito da wani abu sabo daga cikin abubuwan da aka sani ko ake gani ko ake ji ko ake amfani da su...

¹³⁴ Ana iya duba bidiyoyinsu a <https://www.youtube.com/@BabanYellow>.

¹³⁵ Ana iya duba bidiyoyinsu a <https://www.youtube.com/@HausaFairyTales>.

¹³⁶ Ana iya duba bidiyoyinsu a <https://www.youtube.com/@Muibtoon>.

¹³⁷ Ana iya duba bidiyoyinsu a [https://www.youtube.com/@MMBStudios ng](https://www.youtube.com/@MMBStudiosng).

¹³⁸ A har kullum mutane suna kan neman bayanai da suka shafi na zahiri da na baɗini. A kowace rana ba a rasa jin Hausawa sun ambaci kalmomi da suke da alaƙa da bincike (a bagiren yau-da-kullum) irin su “dubawa” ko “nema” ko “bin diddigi” ko “cigiya” da makamantansu. Bunza (2017a sh. 2) yana ganin cewa ire-iren waɗannan kalmomi ne da suka kasance takwarorin kalmar “bincike.”

(Mannir, 2018 SL. 4) ya ba da ma'ana makamanciyar wannan inda yake cewa: "A ilimance, bincike na nufin aiwatar da nazari kan wani al'amari ko abu domin fito da wani sabon abu ko inganta wani abu, ko kuma warware wata matsala domin cimma wani buri ko biyan wata bukata."

Za a iya lura da cewa akwai muhimman kalmomi da suke haduwa su gina ma'anar bincike. Fahimtar su a matsayin daidaiƙun kalmomi tare da fahimtar alaƙar aikin da suke yi kafaɗa da kafaɗa shi zai ba da hoton zuci na haƙifanin ma'anar binciken ilimi.

Kalmomin kuwa su ne:

- i. Matsala
- ii. Manufa/makasudi
- iii. Matakai
- iv. Dabaru
- v. Bayanai
- vi. Kwankwancewa/kalailaicewa
- vii. Sakamako/Mafita

Lura da wannan, ana iya cewa binciken ilimi yana nufin tunkarar wata matsala a ilimance cikin bin tsararrun matakai da dabaru bisa manufar tattara bayanai da bin ingantattun matakan tace su da kalailaice su don samun sakamako ko mafitar matsalar da ta haifar da makasudin gudanar da aikin.

Ko bayan binciken ilimi, akwai nau'o'in binciken da suka shafi kasuwanci ko tsaro da dai makamantansu. A yau, Hausawan da suke da fwarewa a fannonin bincike suna da damar yin ayyukan da suka shafi bincike a kwastomomi na kusa da na nesa. Akwai fitattun hanyoyi guda uku da ake iya gudanar da aikin da ya shafi bincike. Su ne:

1. Neman Bayanai (Data Sourcing)

Neman bayanai da tattara su wani babban mataki ne a lamarin gudanar da bincike. Binciken yana iya kasancewa na ilimi ne ko na wani nau'in kasuwanci. Dangane da misalin binciken kasuwanci, neman bayanai sun haɗa da tattaro ra'ayoyi da muradu da ɗabi'un al'umma game da wani nau'in kayan kasuwanci. Akan tattara bayanai game da ra'ayoyin al'umma (misali, Hausawa) ta hanyar kira ta waya, ko yin tambayoyi gaba-da-gaba, ko kuma ta kafafen intanet.

Dangane da binciken ilimi kuwa, ya shafi tattara bayanai game da nau'o'in abubuwa daban-daban. Sun haɗa da wurare da abubuwa da tarihi da kayan karatu da sauransu. Duk waɗannan akan nemi kwararrun da za su gudanar da su ta kafafen intanet. Hausawan da suke irin wannan aikin, sukan tura ta intanet, sannan a biya su ta intanet, ba tare da bukatar sai an haɗu gaba da gaba ba.

2. Kalailaice Bayanai (Data Analysis)

Kalailaicewa ko kwankwance bayanai yana nufin nazarta tare da kwankwance bayanan da aka tattara domin fitar da sakamako. Wannan fasaha ce mai zaman kanta wadda take bukatar kwarewa. Waɗanda suka nemi ilimi a wannan ɓangaren suna da damar samun ayyuka daga wurare daban-daban. Hanyoyin da ake bi domin kalailaice bayanai suna da yawa, sannan sun shafi nau'in bayanan da kuma nau'in binciken da ake gudanarwa. Hausawa suna da damar shiga a dama da su a wannan fage. Ana iya amfani da manhajoji daban-daban yayin gudanar da aikin. Sun haɗa da:

- a. Atlas.ti – <https://atlasti.com>
- b. Google Forms – <https://forms.google.com>

- c. NVivo – <https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo>
- d. R – <https://www.r-project.org>
- e. SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) - <https://www.ibm.com/spss>
- f. Stata - <https://www.stata.com>
- g. SurveyMonkey – <https://www.surveymonkey.com>

3. Mataimakin Mai Bincike (Research Assistant)

A nau’o’in bincike da dama akan yi amfani da mataimakin mai bincike. Yawanci shi yake taimakawa wajen tattara bayanai da tsara su ta yadda za su yi sauƙin kalailaicewa da kwankwancewa. Idan binciken ya shafi ziyarar gani da ido, yawanci mataimakin mai binciken yakan kasance wani da yake da ido a yankin da za a kai ziyarar. Zai zama wanda ya san al’adunsu da harshensu. Turawa da sauran ‘yan kasashen waje da suke zuwa kasar Hausa domin bincike, sukan nemi mataimaka domin gudanar da ayyukansu cikin sauƙi. Haka kuma, manazarta da cibiyoyin binciken da suka shafi Afirka ko harshen Hausa sukan nemi mataimaka Hausawa daga lokaci zuwa lokaci.

4.1.2 Baje Haja/Koli

A nan, baje haja ko baje koli yana nufin bayyanawa ko gabatarwa ko baza kayan da dankasuwa yake sayarwa domin kwastomomi su gani su saya. A kullum Hausawa suna kara rungumar intanet a matsayin kasuwar baje hajojin da suke sayarwa. Wannan yana ɗaya daga cikin misalan harkallolin da ake gudanarwa a duniyoyi guda biyu (na zahiri da na baɗini). Tun a shekarar 2021, (Oyekanmi, 2021 SL. 3) ya bayyana cewa rahoton *National Bureau of Statistics* (Hukumar Kididdiga ta Kasa) ta

nuna cewa kashi 22% na masu kananan kasuwanci ne suke amfani da intanet wajen gudanar da kasuwancinsu.

Hausawa masu kanana da manyan kasuwanci da dama suna amfani da kafafen intanet daban-daban domin tallata kasuwancinsu. Wadansu suna amfani da kafafen sada zumunta (WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, da sauransu).¹³⁹ Wadansu kuwa sukan buɗe kafafensu na kansu ko su haɗa guiwa da wasu masu kafafen intanet domin a sama musu gurabun baje hajojinsu. A farkashin nau’o’in kasuwancin kan intanet da suka shafi baje haja, akwai manyan rukunoni guda uku, wato:

1. Baje Haja/Koli a Kafar Intanet Mallakin Mai Kaya
2. Baje Haja/Koli a Kafafen Intanet Na Haya
3. Baje Haja/Koli a Kafafen Sada Zumunta

4.1.2.1 Baje Haja/Koli a Kafar Intanet Mallakin Mai Kaya

A yau, masu manyan kasuwanci sukan buɗe kafafen intanet domin baje hajojinsu. Yakan kasance wani abu mai kama da manya da kananan kantuna da kuma kasuwannin duniyar zahiri. Yayin da aka dauki matakin duniya, fitattun kafafen sayayya sun haɗa da *Amazon* (<https://www.amazon.com>) da *Alibaba* (<https://www.alibaba.com>). A Afirka kuwa, *Jiji* (<https://jiji.ng>) da *Jumia* (<https://www.jumia.com>) sun kasance zakarun gwajin dafi. Hausawa ma ba a bar su a baya ba wajen amfani da wannan cigaban zamani. Masu nau’in kasuwanci daban-daban sukan buɗe kafafen intanet domin baje hajojinsu. Amfanin kafafen sukan haɗa da:

¹³⁹ Da wuya mutum ya karɗe sitatus dinsa na WhatsApp ba tare da cin karo da hajojin da Hausa suke tallatawa ba, irin su tufafi, turare, na’urori, da sauransu.

- a. Tallata haja domin samun kwastomomi na kusa da na nesa
- b. Bayar da damar cinikayya ta kan intanet
- c. Adana muhimman bayanai game da kasuwanci

Misalan kafafen intanet na baje haja mallakin Hausawa sun hada da:

- a. A.Y.M. Shafa Holdings Limited (<https://aymshafaholdings.com/>)¹⁴⁰
- b. Dangote Sugar (<https://dangote.com/our-business/sugar-refining/>)¹⁴¹
- c. Hikaya Bakandamiya (<https://hikaya.bakandamiya.com/>)¹⁴²
- d. Misau Model Academy (<https://misaumodel.com.ng/>)¹⁴³
- e. Rano Rice Mill (<https://aarano.org.ng/services/rano-rice-mill/>)¹⁴⁴

4.1.2.2 Baje Haja/Koli a Kafafen Intanet Na Haya

Bude kafar intanet da kuma daukar dawainiyar kula da ita ba karamin aiki ba ne. Abu ne da yake buƙatar kuɗi da lokaci. A bisa wannan dalili, ba kowane karamin kasuwanci ba ne zai iya daukar nauyin kafar intanet. A wadansu lokutan kuma, hajar da za a tallata ba ta da yawa yadda har za a ware mata kafar intanet mai zaman kanta. A maimakon haka, Hausawa suna iya tallata ire-iren wadannan hajoji a wadansu kafafen intanet mallakin wadansu mutane na daban. Yayin da aka sayar da kaya, masu kafar sukan dauki wani kamasho bisa yarjejeniyar kasuwancin da aka fulla.

Yin haka yakan zo da wadansu alfanu da kuma nakasu. Daga cikin alfanun akwai:

- i. Karancin kashe kuɗi, sakamakon babu buƙatar gudanar da kafa mai zaman kanta

¹⁴⁰ Yana kasuwancin abubuwa daban-daban. Daya daga ciki shi ne man fetur.

¹⁴¹ Kamfanin da yake samarwa da sayar da sikari. Reshe ne na kamfanin *Dangote Industries Limited*.

¹⁴² Hajar da suke bajewa ta shafi littattafai da suke saya daga wurin marubuta daban-daban. Masu karantu sukan biya kuɗi domin a ba su damar karanta littattafan.

¹⁴³ Wannan kafar intanet ce ta makarantar kuɗi.

¹⁴⁴ Shinkafa ake tallatawa. Wani reshe ne na kamfanin *AA RANO Nigeria Limited*.

- ii. Gushewar fargabar samun kutse (daga masu kutsen kan intanet)
- iii. Samun damar bayyana a injunan nema cikin sauki da sauri¹⁴⁵

Nakasu ko kalubalen da suke tattare da tsarin kuwa sun haɗa da:

- i. Mai kasuwanci ba shi da cikakkiyar damar sarrafa kafar zuwa sigar da yake so.
- ii. A kaikaice yana kara tallafa wa wata kafa ne domin ta kara karfi da sanuwa a maimakon bunkasa kansa.

Amazon yana bayar da damar buɗe akawun da ɗora littattafan sayarwa. Duk littafin da aka sayar, mai littafin zai samu kimanin kashi 70 na kuɗin yayin da *Amazon* za su ɗauki sauran a matsayin ladan amfani da kafarsu.¹⁴⁶ Ko a kafafen intanet na Hausa, *WikiHausa* suna da irin wannan tsarin. Ga misalin wasu littattafan da ake sayarwa a kan kafar:

Hoto Na 4.9: Wasu Litattafan Da Ake Sayarwa a Kan Kafar *WikiHausa*

Madogara: <https://wikihausa.com.ng/littattafai/>

¹⁴⁵ Hajojin da aka ɗora a manyan kafafen intanet su ne suke kan gaba wajen samun damar bayyana a injunan nema cikin sauki. Sababbin kafafen intanet suna buƙatar a yi musu ayyuka na musamman kafin su iya gogayya da waɗanda suka riga suka yi musu nisa.

¹⁴⁶ A cikin shekarun 2023 da 2024, Hausawa sun mayar da hankali sosai kan wannan. Har an samu waɗanda suka gudanar da laccoci game da yadda ake samun kuɗi a *Amazon*.

4.1.2.3 Baje Haja/Koli a Kafafen Sada Zumunta

A kullum tasirin kafafen sada zumunta karuwa yake yi a tsakanin al'ummun duniya. Wannan tasiri ya shafi Hausawa da kasar Hausa. Adadin Hausawa da suke amfani da kafafen sada zumunta yana karuwa sosai. An fahimci hakan ta la'akari da sababbin mabiya da ake samu a kafafen intanet na Hausa da kuma zauruka da shafukan Hausa a kafafen sada zumunta. Su ma adadin kafafen sada zumunta karuwa suke yi kasancewar ana kan kirkiro sababbi. Tuni suka kasance wata kasuwa ta musamman da ake baje haja a cikinta. Hausawa ma ba a bar su a baya ba wajen cin gajiyyar wannan garabasa.

Akwai manyan hanyoyi guda uku da ake bi wajen tallata haja a kafafen sada zumunta.

Su ne:

- A. Sitatus (Status)
- B. Zauruka (Groups/Pages)
- C. Rabawa (Sharing)

Jagorar *Delu Concept Services* ta jaddada cewa:

Harkar internet tana taka muhimmiyar rawa wajen tafiyar da cinikayya ta kasuwanci, kuma mafi akasarin masu sayen kayanmu daga internet ne. Wani lokacin duk da mutane sun san muna yin aikin koyaushe, sai ka ga ba a saye kayan da wuri ba. Amma muna dorawa a internet sai ka ga nan take an saye kayan da munka yi. A.D. Aliyu (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 9 ga watan Satumba, 2024)

A tattaunawar da aka yi da Khadijah Muhammad (Khady Turban and More),¹⁴⁷ ta bayyana cewa: “Lallai intanet shi ne ginshikin kasuwanci a yanzu. Ta hanyar intanet ne kayan da kake sayarwa za su je wurin da kai kanka ba ka taba tsammanin za su je ba.” K. Muhammad (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 12 ga watan Satumba, 2024).

A. Sitatus (Status)

A kafafen sada zumunta, sitatus shi ne wani ɗan tsokaci ko hoto ko gajeren bidiyo da ake ɗorawa, wanda yake ɗaukar waɗansu awanni kafin ya share kansa daga akawun ɗin wanda ya ɗora shi (daidai da tsarin kafar), wanda kuma duk masu bibiyar akawun ɗin wanda ya ɗora shi za su gan shi, sai ko idan an saita wani tsari na musamman da yake hana su gani, wanda ya danganta da yadda kafar take. Da wuya a yau mutum ya duba dukkannin sitatus ɗin WhatsApp ko Facebook ɗinsa ba tare da ya ci karo da tallace-tallacen hajoji daga Hausawa ba. Hausawa masu son wani kaya da aka tallata, suna da damar yi wa mai tallen magana a keɓance domin yin ciniki.

B. Zauruka (Groups/Pages)

Kafafen sada zumunta irin su WhatsApp da Facebook suna ba da damar buɗe zauruka. Zaure wani tsari ne inda ake samun masu akawun daban-daban sun taru wuri ɗaya ta yadda za su iya karanta sakonnin juna a lokaci ɗaya yayin da aka turo sakonnin ta cikin zauren. Wannan ya samar da wata hanyar kasuwanci a tsakanin Hausawa. Yawaitar ire-iren waɗannan zaurukan suna ƙara nuni da yadda Hausawa suke rungumar kasuwancin duniyar intanet. A duba misali a hoton da yake ƙasa:

¹⁴⁷ Tana sayar da sutura da kayan kwalliya.

Hoto Na 4.10: Misalin Zauren Kasuwanci a Kafar WhatsApp

Madogara: Zauren Kasuwancin *GIADE Trends Collections* a Kafar WhatsApp

Yayin da aka nazarci hoto na 4.10 da yake sama, za a lura da cewa yana da mambobi da suka kai ɗari shida da ashirin da takwas (628). Duk wata haja da aka turo ta cikin zauren, ɗaukacin mambobin za su gani. Masu so suna iya tuntuɓar waɗanda suka turo a keɓance domin kulla ciniki.

C. Rabawa (Sharing)

Sau da dama masu kasuwanci sukan tura sakonnin tallace-tallace ga abokansu a kafafen sada zumunta. Daga nan kuma sai su nemi abokan nasu su ma su tura wa abokansu. A haka tallar wata haja za ta yaɗu zuwa akawun ɗin mutane masu yawa. A irin wannan talla, yawanci akan sanya bayanan tuntuɓar mai sayar da kayan (misali lambar waya ko adireshi). Wannan ma wata hanya ce ta tallata haja a kafafen sada zumunta.

4.1.3 Dillanci (Affiliate Marketing)

Dillanci yana ɗaya daga cikin dadadɗun hanyoyin kasuwancin Hausawa. A Kamusun Hausa Na Jami'ar Bayero, an kawo ma'anar *dillanci* a matsayin "sana'ar da dillali ke yi." *Dillali* kuwa, an bayyana ma'anarsa a matsayin "mutumin da ke karɓar kayan mutane don ya sayar a ba shi la'ada" (Sa'id et al., 2006 sh. 103).

M. S. Muhammad (2020 sh. 237) kuwa ya kawo ma'anar *dillanci* da cewar: "Wata sana'a ce da maza da mata ke yi a tsakaninsu, ana kiran mai wannan sana'a da Dillali in namiji ne, Dillaliya in mace ce, akan yi dillanci a gida ko kasuwa." Za a iya lura da cewa, ma'anar tasa ba ta kauce wa wadda Sa'id et al (2006) suka bayar ba.

A takaice ke nan, dillanci sana'a ce da ta shafi karɓar kaya da dillali ko dillaliya suke yi daga hannun mai shi ko masu shi bisa yarjejeniyar ta musamman, tare da sayar da wannan kaya da karɓar ladan aikinsu da ake kira *la'ada*. A bisa haka, dillalai suna iya kasuwancinsu ko da ba su da jari. Nasarar kasuwancinsu ta dogara ne a kan iya ciniki da hulɗa da jama'a da kuma sanin jama'a ɗin.

Dillancin da ake gudanarwa a kan intanet yana kama da wanda ake gudanarwa a duniyar zahiri. Duk su biyun sun shafi yadda dillali yake koƙarin sayar da kayan da ya karɓi dillanci domin mai kaya ya biya shi la'ada. Akwai fitattun hanyoyin dillanci guda uku (3) a duniyar intanet. Sun kasance kamar haka:

1. Buɗe reshen kasuwanci
2. Dora likau da samfuran hajoji a kan kafar intanet ɗin dillali
3. Yada likau da samfuran hajoji a kafafen sada zumunta

4.1.3.1 Buƙe Reshen Kasuwanci

Akwai manyan kamfanoni da suke ba da damar a buƙe reshen kasuwanci a kansu. Hausawa suna iya amfani da wannan damar. Daya daga cikin manyan kasuwannin hadahadar kuɗin intanet ta duniya, Paxful, yana da wannan tsarin. Kai tsaye ya kira tsarin da suna “dillanci.”¹⁴⁸ Shi kuwa wanda yake dillancin, an ba shi suna “dillali.” Wani abin burgewa shi ne yadda aka fassara kafar Paxful zuwa harshen Hausa. Hakan yana kara nuni da yadda Hausawa suke rungumar hanyoyin neman kuɗi a kan intanet.

Hoto Na 4.11: Tsarin Dillanci a Kan Kamar Paxful

Madogara: An ɗauko daga <https://paxful.com/ha/buy-bitcoin-kiosk>.

A hoto na 4.11 da yake sama, an ga yadda Paxful suke bayar da damar a buƙe abin da ta kira “shago” a kan kafarta. Wato zai zama tamkar wani faramin shago da mai shi

¹⁴⁸ An fassara wannan kafa sukutum zuwa harshen Hausa tun a shekarar 2021-2022. Yayin da aka duba fassarar da aka yi wa shirinsu na “affiliate marketing” za a tarar an kira shi da “dillanci.”

zai rika samun kayayyakin daga ainihin uwar shagon, wato Paxful. A takaice ke nan, zai yi dillanci daga asalin babban kanti Paxful.¹⁴⁹

Yayin da dillali ya buɗe reshen kasuwanci a kan wata babbar kafa, to duk kuɗaɗen cinikin da ya yi za su tafi asusun ainihin masu kafar ne. Shi kuma za a ba shi la'ada daga ciki. Ya yi daidai da yadda a duniyar zahiri mutane suke buɗe karamin shago sannan su dogara da masu manyan shaguna. A irin wannan yanayi, mai karamin shagon yakan ɗauko kaya daga babban shago ba tare da yana da kuɗin biya ba. Bayan ya sayar, zai mayar da uwar kuɗi da riba ga mai babban shagon, yayin da shi kuma zai cire ribar da ya ɗora a sama.

4.1.3.2 Dora Likau Da Samfuran Hajoji a Kan Kafar Intanet Din Dillali

Wani salon dillanci a duniyar intanet wanda Hausawa suke cin gajiyarsa shi ne yada likau da samfuran hajoji a kan kafafen intanet. A wannan nau'in dillanci, dillali yakan kasance yana da kafar intanet tasa ta kansa. A kan wannan kafar ne zai ɗora likau ɗin wata haja. Masu ziyartar kafar tasa suna iya latsa likau ɗin domin ya kai su wurin da za su sayi kayan. A duba misali cikin hoto na 4.12 da yake kasa:

Hoto Na 4.12: Likau Lullube Cikin Hoto Domin Dillanci

Madogara: An ɗauko daga kafar Amsoshi (www.amsoshi.com).

¹⁴⁹ Fassara illahirin shafin zuwa Hausa na kara nuni da yadda Hausawa suke cikin wannan harkar dillanci a kan kafar.

Akwai tsarin da ake yi wanda zai ba su damar kammala sayayyar dƙungurungum dinta a kan kafar intanet dƙin dillalin. Akwai kuma tsarin da likau dƙin kai tsaye zai mayar da su kan ainihin kafar intanet dƙin mai kayan ne. Ko ma yaya abin ya kasance, na'urorin za su kundace rahoton cinikin da aka yi sakamakon biyowa ta likau dƙin. Yayin da aka kammala sayayyan wani kaya, to dillali zai samu kasonsa na riba, wato la'ada.

4.1.3.3 Yada Likau Da Samfuran Hajoji a Kafafen Sada Zumunta

Hausawa wafanda ba su da kafafen intanet ma suna da damar shiga a dama da su a harkar dillancin duniyar intanet. Za su iya hakan ne ta hanyar yada likau dƙin a akawun-akawun dƙinsu na kafafen sada zumunta. Wanda zai yi irin wannan dillanci, da farko zai buƙe asusu da kamfanin da zai yi wa dillancin. Daga nan za a ba shi likau wanda ya kebanta gare shi. Wannan likau dƙin ne zai rika yadawa a kafafen sada zumunta.

Yayin da aka bi likau dƙin dillali aka sayi wani kaya ko aka yi rajista, to za a kebe masa la'adarsa. A irin wannan nau'in dillanci, dillali yana iya buƙatar 'yan uwa da abokansa su taya shi yada likau dƙin. Ma'ana dai, bai zama dole ya kasance a kan akawun dƙinsa na sada zumunta ba, zai iya kasancewa a kan na kowa. Abu mai muhimmanci kawai shi ne ya kasance likau dƙin nasa ne wanda aka ba shi bayan ya buƙe asusu da kamfanin masu kaya.

Hausawa da yawa sun samu kudafe daga dillancin da suka fito daga kamfanonin:

- a. Chipper Cash
- b. Kuda
- c. Manhajar Abeg

d. PalmPay, da makamantansu¹⁵⁰

4.1.4 Hadahadar Kudin Intanet

Kudin intanet (crypto currency) wani nau'in kudi ne da ya samu a zamanance, wanda ba a ganin sa a duniyar zahiri sai dai a cikin intanet.¹⁵¹ Kudaden intanet nau'o'i na kudin bafini wadanda hadahadarsu take wanzuwa a duniyar intanet. Buhari (2024 SL. 8) ya bayyana shi a matsayin "kudi da ake amfani da su a cikin kwamfuta wanda za a iya saye da saidawa da su a cikin hanya mai sauki." Wani muhimmin abu game da su shi ne, ana iya sayen kudin intanet ta amfani da kudin zahiri. Ana kuma iya sayen su ta amfani da wani nau'in kudin intanet na daban.

Tun a shekarar 2022, kididigar Triple-A (2022 SL. 5) ta nuna cewa kashi goma da digo talatin da huɗu (10.34%) na 'yan Nijeriya sun mallaki kudin intanet. Binciken Statista (2024) ya nuna cewa, ya zuwa shekarar 2025, kimanin 'yan Nijeriya milayan biyu da dubu dari takwas da sittin (miliyan 25.86) ne za su kasance cikin hadahadar kudaden intanet (SL. 9).

Kudin intanet na farko shi ne Bitcoin¹⁵² wanda aka samar tun a shekarar 2008 (Reiff, 2024 SL. 32) sannan aka fara amfani da shi a shekarar 2009 (Batey, 2024 SL. 9).¹⁵³ Ya zuwa yau akwai nau'o'in kudaden intanet daban-daban wadanda a kullum suke kara

¹⁵⁰ A. Sani (Kebantacciyar Tattaunawa, Maris 6, 2023).

¹⁵¹ Duk da haka, akan samu yunkuri da shawarwarin a samar da wadansu daga cikinsu a duniyar zahiri. Idan aka yi haka, lallai sunansu da manufofinsu za su iya sauyawa.

¹⁵² Binciken Reiff (2024) ya nuna cewa, kafin Bitcoin an yi yunfurin samar da wadansu nau'o'in kudin intanet wadanda ba su yi dogon zango ba. Sun hada da eCash (wanda David Chaum ya tsara a cikin shekarar 1983), E-Gold (wanda Dr. Douglas Jackson da Barry Downey suka samar a shekarar 1996), Bit Gold (wanda Nick Szabo ya samar), B-Money (wanda wani da ya sakaya sunansa da Wei Dai ya samar a shekarar 1998), da kuma Hashcash (wanda aka samar a shekarun 1990 zuwa 1999).

¹⁵³ Wanda ya samar da Bitcoin ya bayyana sunansa a matsayin Satoshi Nakamoto. Sai dai har yanzu ba a san mai wannan sunan ba. Ba a ma san mutum guda ne ko kungiya ce ba. Domin samun farin bayani, a duba Batey (2024).

yawa saboda sababbi da ake samarwa. Pi yana ɗaya daga cikin waɗanda suka fi ƙaurin suna tsakanin Hausawa, inda har aka samu waƙoƙi¹⁵⁴ da maganganun malamai da masana daban-daban game da shi. Bayan haka, akwai bidiyoyi masu tarin yawa dangane da *'Yan Pi Netwok*.

Hadahadar kasuwar intanet ba ta rago ba ce. Sana'a ce ta jajirtacce wanda ya san darajar lokaci kuma yake amfani da shi. Sana'a ce ta mutanen da suke shirye su sadaukar da lokacinsu wurin bincike da karance-karance, tare da bin diddigin sababbin sauye-sauyen zamani a-kai-a-kai.

An samu Hausawa da dama da suke bayani game da lamuran da suka shafi kasuwancin kuɗin intanet. Yawanci sukan yi ne a tashoshin kan intanet masu zaman kansu. Wasu kuwa sukan buɗe makarantu na musamman a inda ake koyar da hadahadar kuɗafen intanet. Makarantun sukan kasance ko dai a duniyar zahiri ko a kan intanet, ko kuma duka biyu.

Sunusi Danjuma Ali tasha yake da ita a kan YouTube mai suna *SunusiCryptoTV*. Ya zuwa 10 ga watan Octobar shekarar 2024, kimanin mutane dubu ashirin da huɗu da ɗari ɗaya (24,100) ne suke bibiyar wannan tashar tasa. A duba hoton da yake kasa:

¹⁵⁴ <https://www.amsoshi.com/2021/12/yan-pi-network.html>

Hoto Na 4.13: Tashar Koyar Da Hadahadar Kuɗin Intanet a Kan YouTube

Madogara: <https://www.youtube.com/@SunusiCryptoTV/videos>

Karin misalai na Hausawa da suke koyarwa ko gabatar da laccoci na musamman game da kuɗin intanet sun haɗa da:

- a. Abdul Kabo¹⁵⁵
- b. Aminu Sirajo¹⁵⁶
- c. Injiniya Mujahid Muhammad Manga¹⁵⁷
- d. Umar Isma'il Muhammad¹⁵⁸
- e. Yusufuddee. A. Yusuf¹⁵⁹

Makarantun Hausawa na koyar da hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet waɗanda suke azuzuwa a duniyar zahiri sun haɗa da:

¹⁵⁵ Yana koyar da abubuwa daban-daban da suka shafi kasuwancin duniyar intanet. Sunan Tasharsa a YouTube *Abdulkabo Tech* (https://www.youtube.com/@Abdulkabo_tech).

¹⁵⁶ Sunan Tasharsa a YouTube *Aminu Tech* (<https://www.youtube.com/@aminutech>).

¹⁵⁷ Ya shahara wurin gabatar da laccoci a shafinsa da yake kan kafar TikTok. An fi sanin sa da suna Abumaher.

¹⁵⁸ Shi ne yake da tashar *Umar Top TV* YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/@umartoptv>).

¹⁵⁹ Shi ne yake da tashar *YDEEN* a YouTube (https://www.youtube.com/@iam_ydeen/videos).

- a. Arewa Trading Academy¹⁶⁰
- b. HydarFX Academy Kano¹⁶¹
- c. SMT Academy Kaduna¹⁶²

Hoto Na 4.14: Wasu Dalibai a Ajin Koyon Hadahadar Kuɗin Intanet a Makarantar *Arewa Trading Academy*

Madogara: https://www.tiktok.com/@yahaya_crypto

4.1.4.1 Kasuwannin Hadahadar Kuɗin Intanet

Kamar yadda ake da kasuwannin hadahadar nau’o’in kayayyaki daban-daban a duniyar zahiri, haka abin yake a duniyar intanet. A intanet, akwai manyan kasuwannin hadahadar kuɗin intanet. Kasuwannin suna da tsarinsu da ka’idojinsu. Sukan kasance cikin na’urori a tsarin kafafen intanet da manhajoji.

Yawanci akan gina su a tsarin da ake kira “mutum zuwa mutu” (Peer-to-peer (P2P)).

Wannan tsari ne da yake ba wa masu kasuwanci damar gudanar da cinikayya kai

¹⁶⁰ Za a iya duba su a https://www.tiktok.com/@yahaya_crypto.

¹⁶¹ Za a iya duba su a <https://www.tiktok.com/@hydarfx>.

¹⁶² Kafar intanet dɪnsu ita ce: <https://smtacademy.org/index.html>.

tsaye a tsakaninsu. Bugu da kari, ana killacewa da adana kudafe da kadarorin ‘yan kasuwa tare da ba su cikakken tsaro ta hanyar amfani da fasahar da ake kira *bulokcen* (blockchain).

Fasahar Bulokcen tana taka rawa sosai a fannin gudanar da harkallolin kuɗi cikin tsaro tare da adana tarihinsu. Tsari ne wanda ya kauce wa takunkumin bi ta hannun wasu (misali bankuna) wanda yake gudana cikin sigar keke-da-keke tsakanin ‘yan kasuwa da kwastomomi. Ya kuma kasance kashin bayan hadahadar kuɗaɗen intenet, waɗanda su ma alkibla ce da kasuwancin duniya ta dosa a yau.¹⁶³

Fitattun kasuwannin hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet sun haɗa da:

- a. Binance – (<https://www.binance.com/>)
- b. Crypto – (<https://crypto.com/>)
- c. Gate – (<https://www.gate.io/>)
- d. KUCOIN – (<https://www.kucoin.com/>)
- e. OKX – (<https://www.okx.com/>)
- f. Paxful – (<https://www.paxful.com/>)

4.1.4.2 Nau’o’in Hadahadar Kuɗin Intanet

Akwai manyan nau’o’in hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet guda biyu waɗanda Hausawa sukan shiga. Su ne (a) masu uwar kuɗi da (b) marasa uwar kuɗi. An samar da waɗannan rabe-rabe ta la’akari da amfani ko rashin amfani da uwar kuɗi a cikin kasuwancin. A takaice ke nan, akwai waɗanda suke bukatar uwar kuɗi kafin gudanar

¹⁶³ Domin samun cikakkun bayanai game da bulokcen (blockchain), ana iya duba Xu et al. (2019).

da su. Akwai kuma wafanda ba sa bukata. A kasa an kawo bayanai game da wafannan nau’o’in hadahadar kudafen intanet.

4.1.4.2.1 Masu Uwar Kudfi

Wannan nau’i ne na hadahadar kudin intanet wanda yake bukatar uwar kudfi kafin gudanarwa. Yana matuƙar bukatar kwarewa da nakaltar yanayin kasuwa. Yana iya zuwa da babbar hasara yayin da aka yi sake ko aka saba ka’idojin hadahadar. Wani abu kuma shi ne, dole ne mai gudanar da irin wannan nau’in hadahadar kudin intanet ya kasance yana bibiyar sauye-sauyen da suke faruwa a kasuwanni. Dole ne kuma ya rika sabunta iliminsa game da sababbin ka’idoji da matakan hadahadar, wanda hakan yakan kasance kalubale ga Hausawa masu yawa.¹⁶⁴

Shi ma wannan nau’in hadahadar kudafen intanet ya rabu zuwa gida biyu kamar haka:

(a) Kasuwanci (Trading) (Proof of Work (PoW))

(b) Kulle Kudfi (Farming/Yield Farming/Liquidity Farming/staking (proof of stake PoS))

4.1.4.2.1.1 Kasuwanci (Trading)

An tattauna ma’anar *kasuwanci* a babi na biyu. Ta la’akari da bayananku Tanko (2000 sh. 35) da Gummi (2014 sh. 77) da Abdullahi (2021 sh. 2), ana iya cewa *kasuwancin kudin intanet* fasaha ne na saye da sayarwa ko musanyen kudafen intanet domin samun riba, ta hanyar bin mataƙai da dabarun da suka hada da gano wurin sayen

¹⁶⁴ M.M. Manga (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 18 ga watan Satumba 2024)

kaya cikin sauƙin farashi da amfani da dabaru da ilimin sanin kasuwa da lokacin da sayar da hajar zai fi kawo riba.

Kasuwancin kuɗaɗen intanet ya shafi saye da sayar da kuɗaɗen tamkar dai yadda Hausawa da sauran al’ummomi suke gudanar da kasuwancin canjin kuɗaɗen ƙasashe a duniyar zahiri. Wani abin burgewa shi ne, ya zuwa yanzu, kuɗaɗen intanet an yi su ne kawai domin su kasance a duniyar intanet. Ba a kallon su ko a taɓa su. Haka kuma, kasuwannin da ake kasuwancinsu duk a kafafen intanet suke. Babu buƙatar a je kasuwa a duniyar zahiri domin gudanar da kasuwancin.

A irin wannan kasuwancin ne za a samu Bahaushe ya je kasuwar da ba a kallon ta a zahiri (kasuwar kan intanet), ya yi ciniki tare da mutumin da bai san shi ba, kuma bai san a inda yake ba a duniya, sannan ya sayi abin da ba zai taɓa kallon sa a duniyar zahiri ba ballantana ya taɓa shi (kuɗi ko kadarar intanet).

4.1.4.2.1.1.1 Ire-Iren Kasuwancin Kuɗin Intanet

Kasuwancin kuɗin intanet bai kasance cikin salo ku siga ɗaya ba. Yana da bambance-bambance masu yawa. Waɗansu daga cikin bambance-bambancen sun samu ne sakamakon nau’in jarin da ‘yan kasuwan suke amfani da su. Wasu kuwa sun samu ne sakamakon bambanci tsakanin kasuwannin. Haka kuma, akan samu bambanci ta fuskar dabarar gudanar da kasuwancin, kamar abin da ya shafi lokacin sayen kaya da lokacin sayarwa.

Ana iya raba kasuwancin kuɗin intanet waɗanda Hausawa sukan shiga zuwa manyan rukunoni guda huɗu kamar haka:

- a. Kasuwancin kuɗi-hannu
- b. Bashi mai ‘yanci
- c. Bashi mai takunkumi
- d. Dauwamammiyar kadarar intanet

Kowanne daga cikin waɗannan yana da tsarinsa da ka’idojin gudanar da shi. Haka kuma, Bahaushe dɓankasuwa yana iya gudanar da nau’o’in kasuwanci sama da ɗaya. Hasali ma, a rana ɗaya mutum yana iya ziyartar kasuwannin hadahadar kuɗin intanet daban-daban domin gudanar da kasuwanci.

A kasa an kawo bayanan waɗannan nau’o’in kasuwancin kuɗin intanet.

4.1.4.2.1.1.1 Kasuwancin Kuɗi-Hanu (Spot Trading)

Kamar yadda sunan ya nuna, wannan nau’in kasuwancin kuɗin intanet ne wanda da yake buƙatar jari a hannu yayin gudanarwa. Yana da tsari irin wanda Hausawa suke yi wa kirari da: “Hannun kuturu da makaho.” Zubinsa yana da matuƙar kama da na saye da sayar da hajoji a duniyar zahiri.

Wani ƙarin abin sha’awa dangane da kasuwancin kuɗin intanet na kuɗi-hannu shi ne, mai sayarwa yana da damarmakin saita akawun ɗinsa ta yadda akawun ɗin zai gudanar da abubuwa da dama ko da mai shi ba ya kan intanet a wannan lokaci.

Misalan abubuwan da zai iya saitawa sun haɗa da:

- 1. Saita Farashin Saye:** Dankasuwa yana iya sanya kuɗi a lalitar akawun ɗinsa sannan ya saita akawun ɗin da cewa, da zarar nau’in kuɗin intanet kaza (misali Bitcoin) ya sauƙo zuwa farashi kaza (misali naira miliyan ashirin da tara), to ya

saya masa. Yayin da aka yi wannan saitin, da zarar farashin Bitcoin ya sauko zuwa wannan farashi, to kwamfuta za ta saya wa dankasuwan adadin Bitcoin da ya saita.

- 2. Saita Farashin Sayarwa:** Dankasuwa yana iya saita cewa, da zarar farashin kuɗin abu kaza (misali Tether) ya kai kaza (misali miliyan uku) to kwamfuta ta sayar masa kai tsaye. Ko da ba ya kan intanet a wannan lokaci, kwamfuta za ta sayar idan aka cimma wannan farashi.

Bambancin wannan nau'in kasuwancin kuɗin intanet da sauran shi ne, kuɗin da dankasuwa yake da shi, shi ne kaɗai adadin kadarar intanet da zai iya saya. A bangare ɗaya kuwa, iya kaɗarar intanet da yake da ita, ita kaɗai zai iya sayarwa.

Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, kasuwannin hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet akan samar musu tsaro mai aminci domin bayar da kariya ga 'yankasuwa. Duk Bahaushen da aka damfara ko aka yi wa sata, to haƙiƙa ya yi sakaci ne, ko kuma ya shiga harkar ba tare da wadataccen ilimi ba. A kasa an kawo misalan matakan da za a iya cin karo da su yayin gudanar da wata harkallar kasuwancin kuɗin intanet a kasuwar duniyar baɗini:

1. Mai sayar da kuɗin intanet zai baje hajarsa tare da zayyana farashin hajar. A bangare ɗaya kuwa, zai zayyana nau'o'in hanyoyin da za a iya biyansa.¹⁶⁵
2. Mai sayen kuɗin intanet zai duba farashin da ya gamsu da shi, sannan ya tura bukatar kulla harkallar kasuwanci.

¹⁶⁵ Wannan ya shafi bankuna ko waɗansu hanyoyin biyan kuɗi na kan intanet da za su bayar da dama ga mai sayen kaya ya tura kuɗi zuwa ga mai sayarwa.

3. Da zarar ya tura adadin kaya da yake so, sannan su biyun suka nuna cewa ciniki ya fada, to na'urar kasuwar za ta kulle adadin hajar da ake bukata daga akawun din mai hajar tun kafin a tura masa kudin kayan.¹⁶⁶
4. Mai sayen kaya zai tura kudi tare da shaidar biya cikin hanyoyi da matakan da suka kebanta ga kasuwar. Daga nan zai danna alamar cewa ya biya kudin kaya a jikin harkallar da suka kulla.
5. Mai sayar da kaya zai duba ya tabbatar da kudi sun cika, sannan ya danna alamar bayar da tabbacin cewa lallai an biya shi.
6. Masu kasuwar za su tura kaya (wanda suka riga suka kulle kamar yadda aka zayyana a sama a lamba ta 3) zuwa ga akawun din wanda ya saya bayan sun cire kudin aikinsu (wanda yake daidai da kudin kasuwa a duniyar zahiri).

Idan wata jayayya ta shigo dangane da wannan harkallar kasuwanci, to jami'in kasuwar zai buɗe tattaunawa ta musamman. Zauren zai haɗa jami'in da kuma masu takaddamar, a inda kowa zai gabatar da hujjojinsa. Aikata rashin gaskiya a kasuwannin hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet yana kai ga an kulle akawun din mutum (mai aikata rashin gaskiyar). Hakan zai iya janyo masa babbar hasara. Wannan ma kalubale ne ga Hausawa kasancewar cikin harshen Ingilishi ake gudanarwa.

4.1.4.2.1.1.2 Kasuwancin Bashi Mai 'Yanci (Margin Trading)

Wannan ɗaya ne daga nau'o'in kasuwancin kuɗin intanet da Hausawa sukan shiga wanda yake bukatar uwar kuɗi. Bugu da ƙari, ɗan kasuwa yana da damar samun bashin kuɗi domin gudanar da kasuwanci. Wannan nau'in bashi ya kasance mai 'yanci

¹⁶⁶ Hikimar yin hakan ita ce, babu yadda za a yi mai sayar da kaya ya damfari mai saye. Misali, idan ba a kulle hajar ba, mai sayar da kaya yana iya tunanin ƙin tura kayan bayan an tura masa kuɗi.

ne saboda wanda ya karɓe shi yana da ‘yancin gudanar da kasuwancin da ya ga dama, kuma a lokacin da ya ga dama.

Kasuwa ce take ba da wannan bashi. Kowace kasuwar hadahadar kuɗin intanet tana da tsarinta da ka’idojinta na bayar da irin wannan bashin.¹⁶⁷ Wata muhimmiyar ka’ida ita ce, dole ne ya kasance dankasuwa yana da wafansu kuɗaɗe a cikin lalitar akawun ɗinsa kafin a ba shi bashi. Bayan wannan, akan yi la’akari da tarihin yanayin hulɗar kasuwancin dankasuwa wajen ba shi bashi. A kasuwar Binance, dankasuwa yana iya samun aron kuɗin da ya kai kaso ɗari da ashirin da biyar (125%) na uwar kuɗin da yake da shi.

Da farko dankasuwa zai sanya kuɗaɗensa a matsayin kafin alkalami (security deposit). Daga nan za a ara masa kuɗin da zai iya kasuwanci da shi a cikin kasuwar. Wannan zai ba shi damar samun riba mai kauri. Misali, wanda ya shiga da naira dubu ɗari (N100,000) kaɗai, idan ya ci ribar 10%, to ribar za ta kasance dubu goma (N10,000) kawai. Idan kuwa ya shiga da dubu ɗari biyu da ashirin da biyar (N225,000)¹⁶⁸ ne, to ribar 10% ɗinsa za ta kasance dubu ashirin da biyu da ɗari biyar (N22,500).

Dankasuwan da ya karɓi wannan nau’in bashin kuɗi yana da damar gudanar da kasuwanci iri biyu. Sun kasance kamar haka:

A. Saya (Long Position (Buying)): Yayin da mutum ya sayi kadarar intanet da kuɗin da aka ba shi rance, sai darajar kaya ya tashi, to zai sayar ya samu riba.

¹⁶⁷ Wannan yana ɗaya daga cikin kalubalen hadahadar kadarorin intanet. Dole ne dankasuwa ya riƙa karantawa da bibiyar sauye-sauyen da ake samu a tsakanin kasuwanni. Ba zai iya dogaro da bayanan wata kasuwa domin ya gudanar da kasuwanci a wata kasuwar ta daban ba.

¹⁶⁸ Bayan an ba shi bashin kaso ɗari da ashirin da biyar (125%) na uwar kuɗinsa

Dankasuwa yana iya karɓar bashi a daidai lokacin da alkaluma suka nuna cewa kayan da zai saya ya gama araha, sannan zai fara tashi ba da jimawa ba.¹⁶⁹

B. Sayarwa (Short Position (Selling)): Ana irin wannan tsarin ne yayin da ake tunanin farashi zai yi kasa. Yayin da aka ba wa dankasuwa kuɗin intanet (misali Dogs biyu (2)), to zai sayar. Da zarar farashi ya yi kasa (kamar yadda ya yi hasashe), hakan na nufin zai iya sayen kuɗin intanet ɗin da suka fi adadin waɗanda aka ba shi bashi. Da zarar ya saye su, zai mayar da waɗanda ya karɓi bashi, shi kuma ya riƙe sauran.¹⁷⁰

Babban kalubalen wannan wannan nau'in kasuwanci shi ne, da zarar hasara ta samu wanda ya karɓi bashi yadda har ta kai abin da aka yi hasarar ya kai adadin kafin alkalamin da ya sanya, to kai tsaye na'urar masu kasuwar za ta sayar da wannan kadara ta mayar da kuɗinta. Shi kuwa zai tashi *ba shi da tsuntsu ba shi da tarko*. Misali a nan shi ne, idan ɗan kasuwa ya sanya kafin alkalami na naira ɗari (₦100), sai aka ba shi kashi ɗari da ashirin da biyar (125%), to zai shiga kasuwa da naira ɗari biyu da ashirin da biyar ke nan (₦225). Idan har farashin abin da ya saya ya faɗi da darajar da ta kai ta naira ɗari (₦100), to hakan yana nufin kafin alkalamin da ya sanya ya tafi, saura bashin da aka ba shi kawai. A daidai wannan lokaci, na'ura za ta sayar da kayan nan take. Kuɗin da za a sayar ke nan zai kama naira ɗari da ashirin da biyar (₦125),

¹⁶⁹ Tashin kayayyaki a kasuwannin kuɗin intanet shi ake kira da *Korijar Kasuwa* (Green Market). Yayin da farashin kayayyaki suka yi kasa kuwa, shi ake kira *Jar Kasuwa* (Red Market).

¹⁷⁰ Sake sayen kaya da dankasuwa yake yi bayan ya sayar, shi ake kira *buy back* a Ingilishi (wato dai *sake saye*).

wanda shi ne daidai kudin da aka ba shi bashi. Don haka masu kasuwa za su dauki abinsu. Shi kuma ya tashi a tutar babu ke nan.

Daukar bashi da yawa yana tafe da riba da kuma haɗari. Idan aka samu riba, to za a sha romo. Yayin da faɗuwa ta auku kuwa, tana iya kai ga lakume kafin alkalami da mutum ya sanya. Ya kasance tamkar nau'oin kasuwancin da Hausawa suke yi wa lakabi da "gwari."

4.1.4.2.1.1.1.3 Kasuwancin Bashi Mai Takunkumi (Futures Trading)

Wannan ma nau'oin kasuwanci ne da ya funshi karɓar bashi. Yana matuƙar kama da wanda aka tattauna a sama a farkashin 4.1.4.2.1.1.1.2, wato *Bashi Mai 'Yanci*. Babban bambancinsu shi ne, ɗankasuwar da ya karɓi nau'oin wancan bashin yana da damar gudanar da kasuwanci a duk lokacin da ya so. Shi kuwa wannan nau'oin bashi, akwai fa'idar lokacin da za a iya gudanar da kasuwancin.

Bashi Mai Takunkumi nau'oin bashi ne da ake karɓa domin a aiwatar da wani takamaiman kasuwanci a wani takamaimai lokaci. Dankasuwa zai yi hasashe ne bisa ilimin sauyin farashin kasuwa. Idan sayen kaya zai yi ya ajiye domin sayarwa a nan gaba, zai saita wani lokaci a wata rana da yake hasashen zuwa lokacin farashin zai yi daraja sosai. Da zarar lokacin ya yi, na'ura za ta sayar da kayan ko da ɗankasuwan ba ya kan intanet. Idan sayan kaya zai yi kuwa, yana iya saita lokacin da yake hasashen farashi zai sauka sosai. Da zarar lokaci ya yi, to na'ura za ta saya masa. Daga nan sai batun sayarwa a lokacin da farashi ya sake tashi.¹⁷¹

¹⁷¹ Domin karin bayani, ana iya duba Bajpai (2024).

Wannan ma babban kalubale ne ga Hausawa. Za a iya lura da cewa, akwai kasada sosai a cikin wannan nau'in bashi. Waɗanda za su iya cin gajiarsa kawai su ne waɗanda suka naƙalci alkaluman da suke haifar da hawa da sauƙar farashin kayayyaki a kasuwannin duniyar kuɗin intanet.

4.1.4.2.1.1.1.4 Kasuwancin Dauwamammiyar Kadarar Intanet (NFT Trading)

NFT¹⁷² nau'in kadarar kan intanet ce da ta bambanta da sauran kadarorin ko kuɗaɗen kan intanet. Tsarinta daban ne kasancewar kowace guda tana cin gashin kanta ne. Ba a iya sauya ta da wani nau'in kuɗin intanet ko kadarar intanet. Wani abu kuma da NFT shi ne, kowanne nau'in kadara guda ɗaya ake samu. Ba kamar sauran nau'o'in kadarorin intanet ba ne da ake iya samun nau'i ɗaya cikin adadi mai yawa. Misali, binciken Lee (2024) ya tabbatar da cewa, an tanadi kimanin *Pi* da suka kai biliyan ɗari (biliyan 100).

Dauwamammiyar Kadarar Intanet tana zuwa cikin sigogin da suka haɗa da:

- a. Zane
- b. Tsofaffin kayayyaki
- c. Gidajen duniyar intanet
- d. Kayayykin cikin wasannin kan intanet
- e. Abubuwan duniyar zahiri da duniyar intanet

Ana amfani da kuɗin intanet wajen saye da sayar da su. Hausawa ba su cika gudanar da wannan nau'in kasuwanci ba. Bugu da ƙari, ya fara zama tsohon yayi kasancewar

¹⁷² NFT yana nufin *Non-Fungible Token*, wato kadarorin da ba za a iya maimaita su ko maye gurbinsu ba.

hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet ta fara boye shi. Duk da haka, dama ce ga Hausawa wacce za su iya shiga a dama da su.¹⁷³ Ya sayar da shi a cikin watan Maris na shekarar 2021.¹⁷⁴

Hoto Na 4.15: Dauwamammiyar Kadarar Intanet

Madogara: Conti & John (2023)

Za a iya lura da cewa, hoto na 4.15 da aka kawo a sama, zane ne kawai na wani abu da yake kama da biri. Wani abin burgewa da mamaki shi ne yadda kadarorin NFT suke da tsada. Akwai wanda ya sayar da hoton kakansa a kan kuɗin intanet da darajarsa ta kai miliyan ɗaya da dubu ɗari biyar a kuɗin Nijeriya (₦1,500,000).¹⁷⁵ Jack Dorsey wanda ya kasance shugaban kamfanin Twitter (Twitter, Inc) daga shekara ta 2015 zuwa 2021, ya sayar da rubutunsa na farko a kan kafar Twitter a matsayin Dauwamammiyar Kadarar Intanet. Ya sayar a kan farashin dalar Amurka miliyan biyu da dubu ɗari tara (\$2,900,000).¹⁷⁶

¹⁷³ Domin samun karin bayani, ana iya duba Cuban (2024) da Sharma (2024).

¹⁷⁴ Domin samun cikakken bayani, ana iya duba Locke (2021).

¹⁷⁵ An samu wannan bayani daga F. M. Bande, (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 10 ga watan Maris 2024). An tantance shi ta hanyar kallon makamantan labaran a kan intanet.

¹⁷⁶ A kuɗin Nijeriya a watan Oktobar shekarar 2024 (lokacin da dala ɗaya ta kai naira dubu ɗaya da ɗari bakwai), wannan adadin kuɗi a cikin naira zai kama biliyan huɗu da miliyan ɗari tara da da talatin (₦4,930,000,000).

Hoto Na 4.16: Dauwamammiyar Kadarar Intanet Daga Rubutun Jack Dorsey a Kan Kafar Twitter

Madogara: Locke (2021)

4.1.4.2.1.1.2 Dabarun Kasuwanci

Kamar dai kasuwancin duniyar zahiri, akwai bukatar Hausawa su nakalci dabarun kasuwanci yayin fara gudanar da hadahadar kuɗaɗen duniyar intanet. Hasali ma, ana bukatar bincike da karance-karance dangane da hadahadar kuɗaɗen duniyar intanet sama da yadda ake bukata a kasuwannin duniyar zahiri. Hakan ya zama wajibi kasancewar yadda a kullum ake samun sauye-sauyen ka'idojin gudanar da kasuwancin kuɗaɗen intanet.

Yawancin Hausawa waɗanda suke kukan tafka hasara sun shiga ne ba tare da wani ilimi ba, wato abin da Hausawa sukan ce “kama ra’aitan nasa.” Wannan yana nuna cewa, yana da matuƙar fa’ida Bahaushe ya nazarci ciki da wajen hulɗar, ba wai ya faɗa mata ido rufe ba. A koyaushe masu hadahadar kuɗin intanet sukan amsa tambayoyi makamantan waɗannan kafin su faɗa kasuwanci:

- a. Shin wane nau’in kaya zan saya?
- b. Shin yanzu ne ya dace in sayi kaya la’akari da alkaluman kasuwa?

- c. Shin yanzu ne ya dace in sayar da kaya la'akari da alkaluman kasuwa?
- d. Shin wane nau'in kasuwanci ya kamata in yi?
- e. Shin a wace kasuwa ya kamata in yi hulɗar kasuwancin?
- f. Shin wane farashi zan saka ko a kan wane farashi zan nemi kaya?
- g. Shin ta wace hanyar biyan kuɗi za a biya ni, ko kuma ta wace hanyar biyan kuɗi zan biya?

Akwai wasu muhimman dabarun hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet. Su ne kamar haka:

1. Kasuwancin Fakafaka (Scalping)

Wannan dabarar kasuwancin kuɗin intanet ce a inda ɗan kasuwa yake sayen kaya sannan ya sayar cikin kankanin lokaci. Nau'in kasuwanci ne da Hausawa suke yi wa kirari da "sha yanzu, magani yanzu." Mai gudanar da wannan nau'in kasuwanci yana bin karamar riba tare da guje wa yin hasara. Kwatakwata wannan nau'in kasuwancin ba ya haura mintuna kafin a kammala shi. Ma'ana dai, ana farawa ne sannan a kammala shi cikin mintuna kalilan.¹⁷⁷

2. Kasuwancin Rana (Day Trading)

Kamar yadda sunan ya nuna, dabarar kasuwancin kuɗin intanet ce da ake farawa sannan a kammala cikin rana ɗaya. Dankasuwa yana iya sayen kaya da safe, sannan ya yi ta bibiyar tashin farashi. Zuwa dare (ko kafin nan) zai iya sayarwa musamman saboda tsoron kada kasuwa ta juye cikin dare ya samu hasara alhali ba ya kusa (yana bacci). Yawanci ana farawa da kammala wannan nau'in kasuwanci cikin mintuna zuwa awowi kaɗan.

¹⁷⁷ An kawo cikakken bayanin wannan dabarar kasuwanci a kasuwar *FXOpen*. A duba *FXOpen* (2024).

3. Kasuwancin Bin Hawa Da Saukar Farashi (Swing Trading)

Wannan dabarar kasuwanci ce da ake amfani da kididdigar sauka da tashin farashi a kasuwanni daga kwamfuta. Akan gano lokacin da ya fi dacewa a shiga kasuwa ko a fita ta la'akari da alkaluman giraf daga kwamfutur da take karantar motsin hawa da saukan farashin kayayyaki. Yawanci akan dauki 'yan kwanaki kafin a kammala wannan nau'in kasuwanci (daga lokacin da aka sayi kaya zuwa lokacin da za a sayar).

Hoto Na 4.17: Giraf Din Hawa Da Saukar Farashi a Kasuwannin Kudaden Intanet

Madogara: Mitchell (2024)

A hoto na 4.17 da yake sama, za a iya lura da alamar hawa da saukar farashi. Wannan shi ne yake nuna *Koriyar Kasuwa* da kuma *Jar Kasuwa* (kamar yadda aka bayyana a karkashin 4.1.4.2.1.1.1.2). Fahimtar yadda ake amfani da alamomi da alkaluman yana bukatar ilimi na musamman.

4. Kasuwancin Doguwar Ajiya (Position Trading)

Wannan dabara ce ta kasuwancin kuɗin intanet inda ɗankasuwa yake ajiye kadarar da ya saya na wani lokaci mai tsawo (misali watanni ko shekaru) kafin sayarwa. Lamarin yana kama da yadda Hausawa sukan sayi wata kadara su ajiye ta na tsawon lokaci a duniyar zahiri.

5. Kasuwancin Bin Kasuwanni (Arbitrage Trading)

Wannan nau'i ne na dabarar kasuwancin kuɗin intanet wadda ta shafi sayen kadara a wata kasuwa tare da sayar da ita a wata kasuwa ta daban domin samun riba. Lamarin yana kama da yadda Hausawa sukan yi fatauci ko gudanar da kasuwancin bin kasuwanni a duniyar zahiri. Mai gudanar da wannan nau'in kasuwanci zai yi la'akari da bambancin farashin da yake tsakanin kasuwanni. Daga nan sai ya sayi kadara a kasuwar da take da sauƙin farashi sannan ya yi saurin kai ta kasuwar da take da tsada domin sayar da ita. Masu kasuwancin kuɗi a hannu (spot trading) sun fi amfani da wannan dabarar kasuwanci.

4.1.4.2.1.2 Noman Kuɗi (Farming)¹⁷⁸

Ana yi wa wannan nau'in hadahadar kuɗin intanet taken "Shaidar Bayar Da Gudummawa" wato "*Proof of Stake (PoS)*" a Ingilishi. Kalmar '*farming*' tana da fassarar '*noma*' a harshen Hausa. Abin da yake faruwa a irin wannan hadahadar kuɗin intanet makamancin wanda yake faruwa ne a harkar noma a duniyar zahiri. Masu noman kuɗi a kan intanet sukan kulle waɗansu kuɗaɗe na tsawon wani lokaci tare da

¹⁷⁸ Bayan *Farming*, wannan nau'in kasuwanci yana da sunaye da suka haɗa da "Yield Farming" da "Liquidity Farming" da "Staking."

hasashen cewa zuwa lokacin za su samu riba a kan kudafen da suka kulle. Abin ya yi kama da yadda Hausawa suke shuka amfanin gona kafan sannan su girbi amfani mai yawa. A. Sani (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 7 ga watan Nuwamba 2024) ya bayar da misalan noman kuɗi aka dama da Hausawa kamar haka:

- a. Cetus (<https://www.cetus.zone>)
- b. OKX Yield Aggregator (<https://www.okx.com>)
- c. PancakeSwap (<https://pancakeswap.finance>)
- d. Raydium (<https://raydium.io>)
- e. SUN.io (<https://sun.io>)
- f. Uniswap (<https://uniswap.org>)

4.1.4.2.2 Marar Uwar Kuɗi

Bayan nau'o'in kasuwancin kudafen intanet da suke buƙatar uwar kuɗi (wadanda aka tattauna a farkashin 4.1.4.1.1 a sama), akwai kuma wadanda ba sa buƙatar uwar kuɗi. A maimakon haka, jarin da Bahaushe dan kasuwa yake buƙata kawai shi ne wanda zai sayi kayan aiki. Kayan aikin kuwa sun haɗa da na'ura kamar waya ko kwamfuta da kuma datar burawuzin. Bayan haka akwai samar da tushen caji, kamar biyan kuɗin wutar lantarki ko na man janareta, da makamantansu.

Wannan ma fanni ne wanda ba a bar Hausawa a baya ba game da shi. Nau'o'in hadahadar kuɗin intanet da suke farkashin wannan rukuni su ne:

1. Hako (Mining)
2. Ruwan Kuɗi (Air Drop)

4.1.4.2.2.1 Hako (Mining, Proof-of-Work (PoW))

A bagiren hadahadar kudafen duniyar intanet, hako yana nufin wata tsararriyar hanya da ake bi ta amfani da na'urori da sabis din intanet da manhajoji na musamman domin tara wani nau'in kuɗi ko kadarar duniyar intanet. A Ingilishi ana kiran sa da suna '*minning*'. Wannan kalmar tana dɗaukar ma'anar hako ma'adanai daga kasa kamar zinariya da azurfa a duniyar zahiri kamar yadda Hausawa suka sani. A haɗikanin gaskiya abin da yake faruwa a haƙon kuɗi da kadararin duniyar intanet ana iya kwatanta shi da haƙon ma'adanan duniyar zahiri. Wani abu da yake kara jaddada hakan shi ne yadda Hausawa suke kiran jagaba a dukkannin nau'o'in kudafen duniyar intanet da suna '*Sisin Gwal*', wato '*Bitcoin*.'

Danmusa Gombe ya yi waka sukutum mai taken *Sisin Gwal*, inda a ciki yake cewa:

Sisin gwal tsada,
Mai wayo ka saye,

(Musa Muhammad Danmusa: Sisin Gwal)

Hausawa sun yi haƙon kudafen intanet masu yawa. M.M. Manga (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 7 ga watan Nuwamba 2024) ya bayyana waɗansu daga cikin kuɗaɗe ko kadararin intanet da ake haƙowa kamar haka:

- a. Bitcoin (BTC) (<https://bitcoin.org>)
- b. Ethereum Classic (ETC) (<https://ethereumclassic.org>)
- c. Monero (XMR) (<https://www.getmonero.org>)
- d. Litecoin (LTC) (<https://litecoin.org>)
- e. Ravencoin (RVN) (<https://ravencoin.org>)

- f. Zcash (ZEC) (<https://z.cash>)

4.1.4.2.2 Ruwan Kudɓi (Air Drop)

Wannan hanya ce ta mallakar kudɓi ko kadarar intanet ba tare da bukatar sanya uwar kudɓi/jari ba, sannan ba tare da an yi haƙo ba. A maimakon haka, za a samu kyautar kuɗaɗen ne tamkar ruwa daga sama. Wannan ya yi kama da yadda abin yake a Ingilishi inda aka kira shi da sunan *'Air Drop'*, wanda zai iya ɗaukar ma'anar jefo abubuwa daga sama.

Yawanci ya fi faruwa ga sababbin kuɗaɗen intanet. Suna iya bayar da kyautar waɗansu sulalla haka kawai. Suna kuma iya bayarwa bayan mutum ya tura musu bukatar samun kyautar. Ana kuma iya fitar da tsarin waɗansu ayyuka waɗanda idan mutum ya yi su, to za a ba shi kyautar kuɗin intanet. Ayyukan suna iya kasancewa tura sakonni a kafafen sada zumunta ko buɗe waɗansu likau, da dai makamantansu.

M.M. Manga (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 7 ga watan Nuwamba 2024) da A. Sani (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 7 ga watan Nuwamba 2024) sun tabbatar da cewa Hausawa masu yawa sun amfana da irin wannan tsarin. Misalan kuɗaɗen intanet da aka yi ruwansu sun haɗa da:

- a. Ambient (TBA) (<https://ambient.finance>)
- b. zkSync (ZKS) (<https://zksync.io>)
- c. Renzo (REZ) (<https://renzoprotocol.com>)
- d. Marginfi (MRGN) (<https://marginfi.com>)
- e. LayerZero (TBA) (<https://layerzero.network>)
- f. Wormhole (Wormhole Token) (<https://wormhole.com>)

4.1.5 Talla (Advertisement)

Kalmar *talla* ba sabuwa ba ce ga Hausawa. An Sa'id et al. (2006 sh. 423), an yi bayanin kalmar *talla* a matsayin: "(tàllà, sn., mc., jam., tàllàce-tàllàce) (i) yawo da kaya don sayarwa. (ii) rubuta bayanin wani abu a jaridu, ko makala takardu a bango ko jikin wani abu, don neman mai saye."

A wannan bagiren, *talla* tana nufin tallata haja ko ra'ayi ko akidar wani ko waƙansu domin samun kuƙfi. Kusan wannan nau'in talla ba a samun sa a duniyar zahiri – duk da akan samu makamantansa da ake gudanarwa a gidajen talabijin da na rediyo da kuma cikin finafinai. A yau Hausawa da dama sun yi nisa a wannan harkar kasuwanci. Ana gudanar da tallar kan intanet ta fuskoki daban-daban da suka haɗa da:

- i. Talla a kan kafafen intanet (websites & blogs)
- ii. Talla a shafuka da zaurukan kafafen sada zumunta
- iii. Talla ta hanyar raba likau

A. Talla a Kan Kafafen Intanet (Websites & Blogs)

Wanda yake da kafar intanet da ta gawurta, yana da damar ɗora tallace-tallace a kai. Tallar tana iya kasancewa ta fuskoki guda biyu, ko dai AdSense¹⁷⁹ ko kuma keɓantattun tallace-tallace.¹⁸⁰ A kasa an kawo misalin yadda aka ɗora talla a kafar Isyaku (www.isyaku.com).

¹⁷⁹ Wannan nau'in talla ne inda ake rajista da kamfanin Google. Kamfanin na Google ne zai rika karɓar tallace-tallace sannan ya rika ɗora waƙanda suka dace a kafar wanda ya yi rajistar (ta la'akari da nau'o'in mutanen da suke ziyartar kafar tasa).

¹⁸⁰ Wannan nau'in tallace-tallace ne da ake karɓa daga ɗaiɗaikun mutane ko kamfanoni ko ƙungiyoyi. Kai tsaye akan yi ciniki da yarjejeniyar yadda tallar za ta kasance (kamar abin da ya shafi farashi, da shafukan da za a ɗora su da tsawon lokacin da za su ɗauka kafin a sauke su).

Hoto Na 4.18: Talla a kafar intanet

Madogara: An dawko daga <https://www.isyaku.com/search/label/FADAKARWA>

A hoto na 4.18 da yake sama, za a ga yadda aka dora talla a kafar Isyaku. Mamallakin wannan kafa Bahaushe ne d’an jahar Kebbi, mai suna Isyaku Garba.

B. Talla a Shafuka Da Zaurukan Kafafen Sada Zumunta

Wadanda suke da zauruka da shafuka a kafafen intanet na da damar dora tallace-tallace idan sun cika ka’idojin da ake bukata. Ka’idojin sun danganta da kafar da kuma mutum ko mutane ko kamfanonin da za su ba da tallar. Bugu da fari, ka’idojin suna sauyawa lokaci zuwa lokaci.

Hausawa da dama suna samun kudɓi a YouTube da Facebook da Instagram da TikTok a dalilin irin wannan nau’in tallar. Mawakan Hausa na zamani da ‘yan barkwanci Hausawa masu yawa suna cin gajiyar wannan damar. Tuni masu tsara finafinan Hausa ma suka rungumi wannan nau’in kasuwanci inda suke sakin finafinansu a kan YouTube tare da dora tallace-tallace domin samun kudɓin shiga. Fitattun finafinan Hausa masu dogon zango da ake nunawa a kan YouTube sun haɗa da:

- a. Amayar TikTok

- b. Asin Da Asin
- c. Garwashi
- d. Izzar So
- e. Kalma Daya
- f. Kwalla
- g. Labarina
- h. Sarka
- i. Zagon Kasa
- j. Zallar Mata

Sauran 'yan finafinan Hausa da mawaƙa da 'yan barkwanci masu yawa suna da tashoshi a kafar YouTube. Wasu kuwa sun fi bayar da karfi a kan TikTok. Sukan dora tallace-tallace a wadannan kafafen. Misalansu sun hada da:

- a. Abubakar Sadauki (Aibs_Fulani)¹⁸¹
- b. Ali Muhammad Idris (Madagwal)¹⁸²
- c. Bello Galadanchi (Danbello)¹⁸³
- d. Mu'azu Muhammad (Bushkiddo)¹⁸⁴
- e. Nazifi Abdulsalam Yusuf (Nazifi Asnanic)¹⁸⁵

C. Talla Ta Hanyar Raba Likau

Wannan nau'in kasuwancin kan intanet ya shafi tura sakonnin talla na wani kamfani a kafafen sada zumunta ta sigar likau.¹⁸⁶ Mai wannan kasuwancin yana daukar likau da

¹⁸¹ A duba https://www.youtube.com/@abis_fulani.

¹⁸² A duba <https://www.youtube.com/@AliArtwork1>.

¹⁸³ A duba <https://www.youtube.com/@bellogaladanchi>.

¹⁸⁴ A duba <https://www.youtube.com/@Bushkiddo>.

¹⁸⁵ A duba <https://www.youtube.com/@nazifiasnanic>.

¹⁸⁶ A wadansu lokuta yakan kasance bidiyo ko hoto ko rubutu.

za a rika ba shi a kowace rana (ko wani lokacin da aka kayyade) sannan ya raba a kafafen sada zumunta irin su Facebook, TikTok, WhatsApp, da sauransu.

Hausawa da dama sun samu riba mai yawa daga wannan kasuwanci. Duk da haka wannan nau'in kasuwanci tamkar caca yake. Dalili kuwa shi ne, sau da dama ire-iren waƙannan nau'o'in kasuwanci suna yin batar dabo na farat ɗaya. A haka ake rufewa da kuɗaɗen waɗanda suka yi aiki ba a biya su ba, da kuma kuɗaɗen waɗanda suka sanya hannayen jari.¹⁸⁷ Daga cikin ire-iren waɗanda aka ci kasuwarsu kuma suka watse akwai:

- a. Uwork
- b. Insme
- c. MyBonus

4.1.6 Koyarwa a Kan Intanet (Online Tutoring)

Ci gaban zamani ya samar da hanyoyi daban-daban da ake iya bi domin koyo da koyarwa ba tare da an shiga aji a zahiri ba. Waɗannan hanyoyi sun haɗa da manhajoji da kafafen intanet. Samuwar cutar Korona a watan Disamba na shekarar 2019 da kuma yaɗuwarta a shekarar 2020 zuwa 2021 sun sanya manyan makarantu masu yawa a duniya sun koma tsarin koyarwa ta kan intanet yayin da ɗalibai da malamai suke kulle a gidajensu.

A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, ana ci gaba da samun ƙaruwar makarantun kan intanet. Ko a nan gida Nijeriya, makarantar kan intanet ta gwamnatin tarayya ba boyayyiya ba ce.

¹⁸⁷ An samu waɗannan bayanai daga tattaunawa da aka yi da Hausawa da suka ci irin wannan kasuwa a baya. A. Sani (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 11 ga watan Maris, 2023) ya yi cikakken bayanin yadda haɗƙallolin suke gudana.

Budaddiyar Jami'ar Najeriya wato *National Open University (NOUN)* tana da kwasakwasai masu tarin yawa, ciki har da Hausa.

Akwai manyan hanyoyi uku (3) da ake iya cin gajiyar koyarwa a duniyar intanet.

Hanyoyin su ne:

- i. Zamowa malami ko ma'aikaci na dindidin ko na wucin gadi a wata makarantar duniyar intanet
- ii. Zamowa malami mai cin gashin kansa wanda yake koyarwa a duniyar intanet
- iii. Aikin dindindin ko na wucin gadi a matsayin kwararre a wata makarantar duniyar intanet

4.1.6.1 Malamin Makarantar Kan Intanet (Online Tutor)

Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, makaranta a kan intanet ba ta takaita ga jami'o'i da sauran makarantun gwamnati ba kawai. Sun hada har da makarantu masu zaman kansu manya da kanana. Bugu da kari, sukan kasance cikin nau'o'i da sigogi daban-daban. Sun shafi na koyar da ilimin fannonin karatun boko da na addini, har zuwa kan koyar da sauran ilimummuka na rayuwar yau da kullum kamar kwamfuta ko kasuwanci ko girke-girke da dai sauransu. Wannan ma fage ne wanda tuni aka fara samun Hausawa a cikinsa.

Kowace makaranta tana da tsarinta daidai da muradunta. Ana iya nazartar makarantun kan intanet ta fuskoki guda biyu kamar haka:

- a. Makarantu
- b. Kafafen koyi-da-kanka

A – Makarantu

Akwai makarantun kan intanet masu tarin yawa a fadɓin duniya. Wadansu kuwa, suna da tsarin koyarwa ne iri biyu. Wato suna da tsarin koyarwa na kan intanet, da kuma na shiga aji a duniyar zahiri. Iri-iren wadannan makarantu sun samar da tsarin shiga aji iri biyu, ɗaya na duniyar zahiri, ɗayan kuwa na duniyar baɗini. Mutum yana iya tura buƙatar neman aiki zuwa ga ire-iren wadannan makarantu. Wani abin burgewa shi ne, Hausawa a wannan fage suna iya aiki da sama da makaranta ɗaya. Akan samu damar hakan ne kasancewar malami zai rika koyarwa ne daga gida, ba tare da buƙatar bata lokaci zuwa makaranta ba. Bugu da ƙari, ba sai makarantun da suke koyar da Hausa ba ne kaɗai Hausawa za su iya neman aiki. Hausawa suna iya tura buƙatar neman aikin koyar da duk wani kwas da suka ƙware a kowace makarantar kan intanet. Yana iya kasancewa kwas ɗin harshe ko lissafi ko wani kwas da ya shafi kimiyya da fasaha.

Misalan makarantun kan intanet waɗanda Hausawa (tamkar sauran ma'aikatan wuraren) za su iya neman aikin koyarwa a cikinsu sun haɗa da:

- a. Cambly (<https://cambly.com>)
- b. iTalki (<https://italki.com>)
- c. Lingoda (<https://lingoda.com>)
- d. National Open University (NOUN) – Nijeriya (<https://nou.edu.ng>)
- e. Outschoo (<https://outschoo.com>)
- f. Preply (<https://preply.com>)
- g. Verbling (<https://verbling.com>)

h. VIPKid (<https://vipkid.com>)

Ko bayan wadannan kafafen, Hausawa suna iya bincika jami'o'in duniya daban-daban wafanda suke da tsarin karantantarwa a kan intanet. Ana iya tura neman gurbin koyarwa a makarantun.

A - Kafafen Koyi-Da-Kanka

A intanet akwai kafafe masu yawa da suke matsayin makarantu. Malamai daban-daban sukan rubuta darussa su dora a kai. Masu son koyon darussan sukan biya kudi kafin su bude a kan na'urorinsu. Yayin da suka karance su, akwai jarabawa da aka riga aka tsara game da kowane darasi. Daliban za su rubuta jarrabawar. Idan sun ci, akwai takardar shaida wato satifiket da na'ura za ta tura musu. Misalan wadannan kafafe sun hada da:

Jadawali Na 14: Kafafen Koyi-Da-Kanka

	Kafafen Koyi-Da-Kanka	Likau
1.	Flowdiary	https://flowdiary.com.ng ¹⁸⁸
2.	Kajabi	https://kajabi.com
3.	LearnWorlds	https://learnworlds.com
4.	Podia	https://podia.com
5.	Skillshare	https://skillshare.com
6.	Teachable	https://teachable.com
7.	Thinkific	https://thinkific.com
8.	Udemy	https://udemy.com

Madogara: Bincikowa ta injunan nema

¹⁸⁸ Wannan makarantar a cikin harshen Hausa take.

Tsarin waƙannan kafafen ya bambanta. Akwai waƙanda malamai suke rubuta kwasakwasai sannan su sayar wa masu kafafen. Akwai kuma waƙanda ake hulɗa ta haɗin guiwa tsakanin malamai da masu kafafen. A kafafen da ake haɗin guiwa, duk wani kwas ɗin da aka samu kuɗi daga gare shi, to za a raba ribar tsakanin malamin da ya yi rubutun da kuma masu kafar. Za a yi rabon bisa tsarin kaso (%) da aka kulla yarjejeniya a kansa tun farko. Wannan dama ce ga Hausawa domin samun kuɗi tare da koyar da darussa da suka shafi adabi da al'ada da harshen Hausa.

4.1.6.2 Malamin Kan Intanet Mai Cin Gashin Kansa (Online Tutor/Freelance Tutor)

Kamar yadda aka bayyana a farkashin 4.1.6.1 da yake sama, makarantun kan intanet ba su takaita ga na gwamnati ba kawai. Sun haɗa har da masu zaman kansu, manya da kanana. A yau Hausawa masu yawa suna cin gajiyar wannan damar da zamani ya kawo. Wasu daga cikin fitattu da ake yawan jin ɗuriyarsu a duniyar intanet sun haɗa da:

- a. Manhajojin koyi-da-kanka
- b. Koyar da girke-girke
- c. Koyar da hada-hadar kuɗaɗen intanet
- d. Koyar da sauran nau'o'in ilimummuka

A - Manhajojin Koyi-Da-Kanka

Akwai manhajoji da ake samarwa na koyar da abubuwa daban-daban. A cikinsu akwai waƙanda suka shafi koyar da harshe. Manhajojin sukan ɗauki tsarin kwasakwasai na kyauta da waƙanda sai an biya kuɗi sannan a nazarce su. Misalansu sun haɗa da:

Sunan Manhaja

Tambari

Koyi Turanci

Learn Hausa Language

Learn Hausa with Audio

Mu Koyi Turanci

Madogara: Rumbun Manhajoji Na Google (Google PlayStore)

Ko bayan wannan, akwai Hausawar da suka ci gajiyar karatun Hausa ta hanyar haɗa manhajojin littattafai ko waƙoƙin Hausa ko waɗansu abubuwa da suka shafi ilimi. Yawanci sukan samu kuɗi daga gare su ta hanyar ɗora tallace-tallace. Misalan waɗannan manhajoji suna da yawa. Daga ciki akwai:

Sunan Manhaja

Magana Jari Ce Littafi Na Uku

Tambari

All Hausa Novels

Hausa Novel Lite: Book Media

Ruwan Bagaja MP3 Audio

Magana Jari Ce 1 2 3 by Abdulkarim Nasir

Madogara: Rumbun Manhajoji Na Google (Google PlayStore)

B - Koyar Da Girke-Girke

Wannan wani sabon fage ne da ya samu bunkasa musamman bayan shigowar manhajar TikTok a watan Satumba na shekarar 2016.¹⁸⁹ Fitattun waƙanda suka iya abinci a cikin Hausawa ‘yammata da matan aure da dama sun buƙe shafuka a TikTok. A cikin shafukan suna gabatar da laccoci inda suke koyar da girke-girke daban-daban. Wani ƙarin abin burgewa shi ne yadda suke yin darussan cikin bidiyo da sautin magana tare da kayatar da su ta hanyar sanya maganganun barkwanci.¹⁹⁰

Daga cikin waƙanda suke koyar da abinci a intanet cikin harshen Hausa akwai waƙanda suka yi matuƙar fice. Shahara da sanuwarsu har ta kai ga ana amfani da waƙansu kalamansu a matsayin sara. Misalan sara da aka samu sun haɗa da:

- a. **Ministan Sharholiya:** Take ne wanda Maryam Adam Hamza (Maryama’s Kitchen) mai koyar da girke-girke a kan TikTok take yi wa kanta.
- b. **Ina za ki? Dawo ki ga abin da na kawo mana!:** Kirari ne wanda Hafsat Fulany (Fulany’s Kitchen) take buƙe bidiyoyinta na TikTok da su.
- c. **Ku dai kun san wanda ya iya ya huta:** Kirari ne wanda Maryam Adam Hamza (Maryama’s Kitchen) take yi wa kanta a cikin bidiyoyinta da suke kan kafar TikTok.

Lokaci zuwa lokaci gwanayen girki sukan buƙe azuzuwan koyar da waƙansu nau’o’in abinci na musamman. Misali a lokacin da azumin watan Ramalana ya gabato, akan

¹⁸⁹ Domin samun ƙarin bayani game da samuwar TikTok, ana iya duba Tidy & Galer (2020).

¹⁹⁰ Daga cikin masu koyar da abinci da harshen Hausa a TikTok, akwai waƙanda asalinsu ba Hausawa ba ne. Duk da haka, sun taso da harshen Hausa sannan a cikin Hausawa. Ba su da wani harshe in ba Hausa ba. Waƙansu kuwa da suka iya harsuna biyu, sun ajiye nasu harshen sun rungumi Hausa a sakamakon yawan al’ummar Hausawa da suke kan TikTok.

samu yawaitar azuzuwan koyar da abinci. Za su sanya farashin yin rajista sannan su ayyana ranaku da manhaja da kuma tsarin koyar da abincin. Yawanci akan yi shi a kare ne a kan intanet. Sukan ɗan turo hotonu da gajerun bidiyoyin ɗanɗani-haukace a shafukansu domin zaburar da waɗanda ba su yi rajista ba su samu su yi.

A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, akwai waɗanda suke koyar da girke-girke a duniyar zahiri. Duk da haka, sukan tura sanarwar neman ɗalibai ne ta intanet. Bugu da ƙari, akan yi tururuwa zuwa azuzuwansu ne sakamkon ficensu a intanet (saboda bidiyoyi da hotunan abincinsu da suka karafɛ intanet).

A kasa an kawo misalan waɗansu Hausawa da suke cin gajiyar koyar da abinci a zamanance:

Jadawali Na 15: Wasu Masu Koyar Da Girke-Girke Da Taimakon Intanet

Suna	Inkiyar Kasuwanci	Gari	Nau'o'in Azuzuwa
A'isha Sulaiman	Yummy Bites	Abuja	Intanet da Zahiri
Aisha Delu Aliyu	Delu Concept Services	Sakkwato	Zahiri (tallatawa a intanet)
A'ishatu Muhammad Bazango	Amsoshi Kitchen	Zamfara	Intanet da Zahiri
Fatima Abdulkadir	Faty AK's Cakes & More	Katsina	Intanet da Zahiri
Fatima Hassan Hamma	Zara's Food & More	Bauchi	Intanet da Zahiri
Hafsat Fulany	Fulany's Kitchen	Kano	Intanet da Zahiri
Hajara Adamu Yusuf	Hajjo's Kitchen	Bauchi	Intanet da Zahiri
Khadija Abbas Sani	Khabs Kitchen	Kano	Intanet da Zahiri
Maryam Adam Hamza	Maryama's Kitchen	Damaturu	Intanet da Zahiri

Madogara: Tattaunawa da bibiyar bayanai a kafafen intanet

Wannan binciken ya fahimci cewa, tabbas Hausawan da suka zamanantar da sana'arsu ta abinci ta hanyar shiga intanet sukan samu riba sosai ta bangaren koyarwa. A kasa an kawo kiyasin kudaden da masu koyar da abinci suke karɓa daga kowace daliba.

Jadawali Na 16: Kiyasin Kudaden Da Ake Biya Yayin Shiga Ajin Koyar Da Abinci

Nau'in Dalibta	Azuzuwan Kan Intanet	Azuzuran Duniyar Zahiri
Aji mai dalibai da yawa (20 zuwa sama)	N5,000 – N25,000	N5,000 – 50,000
Aji mai dalibai kadan (kasa da 20)	N5,000 – 50,000	N5,000 – 50,000
Ajin daidai mutane (1-5)	N20,000 – 100,000	N20,000 – 200,000
Ajin manyan mutane na musamman	(Ba a samu misali ba)	N50,00 – 500,000 (wani lokaci har da farin kyaututtuka na alkairi)

Madogara: Tattaunawa da masu koyar da abinci a zamanance da bibiyar tallace-tallacensu a kan intanet¹⁹¹

C - Koyar Da Hadahadar Kudade Da Kadarorin Intanet

A yau akwai Hausawa da dama da suka dukufa wajen koyar da hadahadar kudade da kadarorin kan intanet. Bayan ita sana'ar kudaden intanet din kanta, wannan koyarwa da suke yi hanya ce ta samun kuɗi a gare su. Bugu da kari, koyarwar tana kara nuni da yadda Hausawa suke sake rungumar wannan ci gaban zamani.

¹⁹¹ An haɗa waɗannan alkaluma daga bayanan da suka fito daga Aisha Delu Aliyu (Delu Concept Services) da Fatima Abdulkadir (Faty AK's Cakes & More) da Khadija Abbas Sani (Khabs Kitchen).

A bangare ɗaya kuwa, ko bayan kufade da masu koyarwar suke samu, suna kuma samun waɗanda za su tura wa likau ko lambobin “gayyata” (referral) zuwa ga sababbin kufaden intanet ko waɗansu manhajoji. Gayyata wani tsari ne da yake ba wa masu akawun a wata manhaja ko kafa damar tura gayyata ga wasu mutane na daban. Yayin da suka yi amfani da likau ko lambar gayyatar da aka tura musu domin buɗe akawun, to wanda ya tura musun zai samu wani kamasho. Misali, idan haƙo (mining) suka yi, zai samu wani lada daga abin da suka tara. Idan kuma ruwan kuɗi aka yi musu, to shi ma zai samu kaɗan.¹⁹²

D - Koyar Da Harshe

Masana da manazarta harshen Hausa suna da damar koyar da harshe a duniyar intanet domin a biya su. Mutum yana iya buɗe akawun a ɗaya daga cikin kafonin tallata basira. Masu son a koyar da su wani abu game da harshen, za su tuntube shi yayin da suka ci karo da akawun ɗinsa a kan intanet. Baya ga haka, akan tuntubi kamfanonin fassara lokaci zuwa lokaci domin su nemo waɗanda za su iya koyar da wani harshe. Kamfanonin fassarar kuwa za su tuntubi ma’aikatansu domin samun waɗanda za su iya aikin.

Kafafen da za a iya rajista da su a matsayin malami mai koyarwa a kan intanet sun haɗa da:

- a. Freelancer – (<https://www.freelancer.com>)
- b. Guru – (<https://www.guru.com>)

¹⁹² A farkashin 4.1.4 an kawo misalan waɗannan. A ciki har da makarantun koyar da hadahadar kufaden intanet da suka haɗa da *Arewa Trading Academy* da *HydarFX Academy Kano* da *SMT Academy Kaduna*.

- c. LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com>)
- d. PeoplePerHour – (<https://www.peopleperhour.com>)
- e. TaskRabbit – (<https://www.taskrabbit.com>)

4.1.6.3 Aikin Kwangila a Matsayin Masani

Bayan nau’o’in koyarwa da aka ambata a sama, malamai masana suna da damar yin aikin kwangila a ire-iren waƙannan makarantun kan intanet. Lokaci zuwa lokaci makarantun sukan nemi malamai domin su rubuta musu wani kwas ko su yi musu gyare-gyare tare da sabunta kwasa-kwasai yayin da saka samu sababbin sauye-sauye a wannan fannin ilimi. Bayan haka, ana iya neman masanan domin duba dalibai a matakin digiri na biyu ko na uku. Misalan kwasakwasan Hausa da masana daban-daban suka rubuta wa Budadɗiyar Jami’ar Najeriya wato *National Open University (NOUN)* sun haɗa da:

Jadawali Na 17: Misalin Aikin Kwangilar Rubuta Kwasa-Kwasan Hausa

	Kwas	Masanin Da Ya Rubuta
1.	HAU 102: Gabatar Da Tarihin Hausawa (Introduction to the History of the People)	Dr. Aliyu Isa Sulaiman (KASU)
2.	HAU 117: Introduction to Hausa Cultural Studies	Dr. Ibrahim Abdullahi Sarkin Sudan (UDUS)
3.	HAU 210: Morphology of Hausa	Dr. Isah Abdullahi Muhammad (UDUS)
4.	HAU 211: Varieties of Prose in Hausa	Prof. Ibrahim Malumfashi (KASU)
5.	HAU 212: Syntax of Hausa I	Prof. Hafizu Miko Yakasai (BUK)

6.	HAU 214: Hausa Trades and Crafts	Dr. Abdullahi Sarkin Gulbi (UDUS)
7.	HAU 301: Phonology of Hausa II	Dr. Adamu Abdulsalam (FU Kashere)

Madogara: Kafar Intanet Ta NOUN (<https://nou.edu.ng>)¹⁹³

4.2 Hausawa Da Tanadi a Duniyar Intanet

An kawo bayani dangane da tanadin Hausawa a babi na biyu. Yayin da ake ci gaba da samun sauye-sauyen zamani, dabarun tanadin Hausawa sun ci gaba da sake samun canji da bunkasa. Tun kafin shigowar intanet aka ji wani sauyin zamani game da yadda Hausawa suke ajiyar kuɗi a Bakin Gambu. Yana cewa:

Don in nic ce randa,
Wani randa ta ruwa za shi ce min.
To, randa ma'ajin kudɗi ta dauriiii,
Sanda ba ajiya banki akai ba.
(Muhammad Gambo Fagada: Waƙar Kashe Mace)

Za a iya fahimtar cewa, a duniyar Hausawan zamanin wannan waƙar, tuni aka fara ajiyar kuɗi a bankuna. Hakan ya sa har tarihin al'adar ajiye kuɗi a cikin randa ya fara karanci a tsakanin al'umma. Wasu ba su san da cewa randa tana amfani wajen adana kuɗi ba. A maimakon haka, amfanin randa da suka sani kawai shi ne ajiye ruwa.

Samuwar intanet kuwa ya zo da sababbin hanyoyin tanadi. Fitattu daga cikin hanyoyin tanadin da Hausawa za su iya cin gajiyarsu sun haɗa da:

- a. Tsarin adana kuɗi a bankuna
- b. Kudɗin intanet/kadarar intanet
- c. Kudaden kasashen waje

¹⁹³ An ɗauko bayanar a cikin watan Oktoba, shekarar 2024.

4.2.1 Tsarin Adana Kudɓi a Bankuna

Ajiye kuɓi a banki a yau ya zama gama-gari. Ya kasance tamkar ajiye kuɓi a aljihu sakamakon yadda ake da hanyoyin taransifa cikin sauƙi.¹⁹⁴ Mai kuɓin yana iya amfani da su a duk lokacin da ya ga dama (sai dai idan akwai wata matsala ta musamman kamar rashin sabis ɗin intanet). A bisa wannan dalilin, a yanzu ba za a ɗauki ajiye kuɓi a banki cikin tsarin gama-gari a matsayin hanyar tanadi a tsakanin Hausawa ba.

Duk da bayanin da ya gabata a sama, akwai tsare-tsare na musamman a bankuna da suke ba wa mutum damar adana kuɓi a matsayin tanadi na dogon lokaci ko gajere. Kowane banki yana da irin nasa tsarin. Wannan bincike ya ci karo da Hausawa masu yawa da suke amfani da ire-iren waɗannan tsare-tsare. Waɗansu Hausawan sukan yi amfani da hanyoyi sama da ɗaya. Misalansu sun haɗa da:

A - Asusun Hajji (Hajji Savings)

Wannan wani tsarin asusu ne wanda ake yi a karkashin Hukumar Aikin Hajji Ta Kasa (National Hajj Commission of Nigeria (NAHCON)) da and Hukumomin Kula Da Jin Daɗi Da Walwalar Alhazai Na Jahohi (States Pilgrims Welfare Boards (SPWB)) tare da haɗin guiwar Bankin Jaiz (Jaiz Bank Plc.) (Jaiz Bank, 2024). Wannan nau'in asusu yana ba da damar tara kuɓi a hankali domin tanadin zuwa aikin Hajji.

Abubuwa biyu suna daga cikin dalilan da suka sa ya kasance mai nagarta. Na farko ya kasance wanda ya saka kuɓi a irin wannan nau'in asusu, to ba zai iya cirewa ba. Hakan zai ba shi kwarin guiwar dogewa domin ya ci gaba da tara kuɓin har su kai na

¹⁹⁴ Hanyoyi uku da aka fi amfani da su a yau na taransifa a tsakanin Hausawa su ne (i) amfani da manhaja, (ii) amfani da lamba (USSD), da kuma (iii) amfani da katin ATM domin wanda za a tura wa ya cire ta na'urar POS.

zuwa aikin Hajji.¹⁹⁵ Abu na biyu kuwa shi ne, za a rika yin kasuwanci da kudafen da mutum ya saka sannan a sanya masa wani kaso na ribar a kan kudafensa (NAHCON, 2021). Wannan dama ce ga Hausawa ta yin asusu domin tafiya Hajji, musamman yanzu da kudin kujerar Hajji ta yi tsada.

B – Asusun Yara

A dokar Nijeriya, sai yaro ya kai shekara goma sha takwas (18) kafin ya iya buɗe akawun a banki. Duk da haka, bankuna da dama sun fitar da tsarin yi wa yara asusu. Wannan cigaban zamani ne kan yadda ‘ya’yan Hausawa suke adana ‘yan kudafensu a asusun laka ko makamancin hakan. Ana yin wannan asusu ne bisa dalilai masu yawa da suka shafi tanadi na musamman a yaran. Yana iya kasancewa tanadin kudin tura su karatu ko buɗe musu kasuwanci ko gina musu gida ko sayen abin hawa ko yi musu aure, da makamantansu.

Yawanci bankuna sukan saka fa’idojin da dole a cike su kafin cire kudi a ire-iren wadannan akawun ɗin. Dole ne ya kasance za a cire kudin ne kawai domin biyan buƙatun yaran da aka buɗe akawun ɗin dominsu. Ko ba komai fa’idojin sukan rage yiwuwar cire kudi don biyan kananan buƙatun yau da kullum.

Bankunan Nijeriya masu yawa suna da wannan tsari. Hausawa suna iya buɗe wa ‘ya’yansu irin wannan asusu na zamani (na kan intanet). Daga cikin bankunan Nijeriya da suke da wannan tsari akwai:

¹⁹⁵ Duk da haka, ana iya fita gaba ɗaya daga cikin tsarin. Akwai fa’idojin da za a cike kafin fita.

Jadawali Na 18: Asusun Yara a Wasu Bankunan Nijeriya

	Sunan Banki	Sunan Asusu
1.	Access Bank	Early Savers Account ¹⁹⁶
2.	Ecobank Nigeria	MyFirst Account ¹⁹⁷
3.	First Bank	KidsFirst ¹⁹⁸
4.	Guaranty Trust Bank	Smart Kids Save (SKS) ¹⁹⁹
5.	Sterling Bank	I Can Save (Minor) ²⁰⁰
6.	United Bank For Africa	UBA Kiddies Account ²⁰¹
7.	Zenith Bank	Zenith Children's Account (ZECA) ²⁰²

Madogara: Fabmumng (2020), Dapo-Thomas (2024), Naira Compare (2024)

C – A Ci Daya a Adana Daya (Save as You Spend)

Kamar yadda aka bayyana a farkashin 4.2.1. a sama, ajiya a banki yau tamkar ajiye kuɗi a aljihu ne. Mai su yana iya yin taransifa a kowane lokaci. Domin samun damar adana kuɗi, bankuna sun fito da wani tsari mai suna *Save as You Spend*. Wannan tsari ne wanda yake ba wa kwastomomi damar adana kuɗaɗe. Hausawa suna da damar amfani da wannan tsari domin adana kuɗaɗensu a kan intanet.

Yanda tsarin yake aiki shi ne, mutum zai saita wani kaso (1%) da yake so a adana masa a duk lokacin da ya kashe kuɗi. A bisa misali, idan albashinsa naira dubu dari ne (100,000), yana iya saita cewa a rika ɗaukar kashi goma (10%) na duk kuɗaɗen da ya

¹⁹⁶ A duba <https://www.accessbankplc.com/personal/kids-teens/early-savers-account>.

¹⁹⁷ A duba <https://www.ecobank.com/ng/personal-banking/everyday-banking/savings-accounts/my-first>.

¹⁹⁸ A duba <https://www.firstbanknigeria.com/personal/accounts/savings/kidsfirst/>.

¹⁹⁹ A duba <https://www.gtbank.com/personal-banking/accounts/savings-investment-accounts/smart-kids-save-sks>.

²⁰⁰ A duba <https://sterling.ng/personal/i-can-save/>.

²⁰¹ A duba <https://www.ubagroup.com/nigeria/personal-banking/accounts/savings-accounts/kids-savings-account/>.

²⁰² A duba <https://www.zenithbank.com/zeca/>.

kashe. Duk taransifa ɗin da ya yi, za a cire adadin da ya kai kashi goma (10%) na abin da ya tura a adana masa a asusunsa na *A Ci Daya a Adana Daya*. Wannan yana nuna cewa, a lokacin da zai kashe kimanin dubu casa'in (90,000), zai zama an adana masa kimanin dubu goma (10,000).

Wannan hanya ce ta yin tanadi a zamanance domin amfani da kuɗaɗen da mutum ya tara a wani lokaci na daban. A kasa an kawo misalan wasu bankunan Nijeriya da suke da wannan tsarin, waɗanda kuma Hausawa suna iya amfani da su:

Jadawali Na 19: Tsarin A Ci Daya a Adana Daya a Wasu Bankunan Nijeriya

	Sunan Banki	Sunan Asusu
1.	Ecobank	Ecobank Save As You Spend ²⁰³
2.	Gruanty Trust Bank	Spend 2 Save ²⁰⁴
3.	Kuda	Spend + Save ²⁰⁵
4.	PalmPay	Spend & Save ²⁰⁶

Madogara: Akintaro (2023), Kafafen Intanet Na Bankuna

4.2.2 Kudɓin Intanet/Kadarar Intanet

Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, kuɗaɗe da kadararin intanet suna tafiya ne a tare. Bugu da kari, ana ba su suna ne a muhallin da suka kasance. Ma'ana dai, nau'in kuɗi a wani muhalli yana iya kasancewa kadara a wani muhallin na daban. A lokacin da aka haƙi

²⁰³ Kwastoma yana iya saita adana kashi ɗaya zuwa goma (1-10%) na dukkannin taransifa da zai yi. A duba <https://www.ecobank.com/group/news-and-media/news?news=20190814060018881|DXRCZJY99>.

²⁰⁴ Kwastoma yana iya saita adana kashi ɗaya zuwa biyar (1-5%) na dukkannin taransifa da zai yi. A duba <https://www.gtbank.com/personal-banking/services/e-banking/spend-2-save>.

²⁰⁵ Kuda ɗaya ne daga cikin bankunan kan intanet da suke tashe a Nijeriya. A duba <https://kuda.com/en-ng/save/>.

²⁰⁶ PalmPay ɗaya ne daga cikin bankunan kan intanet da suke tashe sosai a Nijeriya. Suna bayar da damar saita adana kashi ɗaya zuwa ɗari (1-100%) na dukkannin kuɗaɗen da mutum yake kashewa a kan manhajarsu.

wani nau'in kadara aka adana, to abin da aka adanan yana mazaunin kadara ne. Idan kuwa aka shiga kasuwa da shi domin saye da sayarwa, to 'yankasuwa suna kiran sa da suna kuɗin intanet.²⁰⁷

Duk da haka, akwai abubuwan da kai tsaye kadarori ne a kan intanet, duk kuwa da cewa ana sayar da su domin a sayi kuɗaɗen intanet ko kuma kuɗaɗen duniyar zahiri. Waɗannan sun fi shafar *dauwammun kadarorin intanet* waɗanda aka tattauna a farkashin 4.1.4.2.1.1.1.4 da yake sama.

Hausawa sukan tanadi kuɗaɗe ko kadarorin intanet su ajiye su na tsawon lokaci. Yayin da lokacin ya yi, za a sayar da su domin biyan bukata. An fi yin hakan musamman lokacin da ake son guje wa yawan faɗuwar darajar kuɗaɗen duniyar zahiri. Wasu daga cikin kadarorin intanet da ake adanawa sun haɗa da:

- a. Binance Coin (BNB)
- b. Bitcoin (BTC)
- c. Dauwammun Kadarorin Intanet (NFT)
- d. Ethereum (ETH)
- e. Tether (USDT)
- f. USD Coin (USDC)²⁰⁸

4.2.3 Kuɗaɗen Kasashen Waje

A farkashin 4.2.2 da yake sama, an nuna cewa a yau akan adana kuɗaɗe da kadarorin duniyar intanet a matsayin tanadi. A duniyar zahiri ma akan adana wasu nau'o'in

²⁰⁷ Wannan abin haka yake har a harshen Ingilishi inda ake da *cryptocurrency* da kuma *digital asset*, wato dai 'kuɗin intanet' da kuma 'kadarar intanet.' Hausawa da dama sun Hausantar da kalmar "crypto" zuwa "kirifto."

²⁰⁸ A duba Saifedean (2018) da Gonçalves et al., (2023).

kudafe musamman dalar Amurka. Daga cikin masu irin wannan asusu har da Hausawa. Akan yi hakan ne musamman da yake a tarihi, har kullum darajar dala karuwa take yi a kan naira. Haka wannan al'amari yake a duniyar intanet.

Ana iya buɗe akawun sannan a adana dala a ciki zuwa wani lokacin da ake buƙata. Wasu kuma sukan sayi dalar sannan su adana ta a wani wurin da ba za ta lalace ba. A shekarar 2016 zuwa 2018, jaridu a Nijeriya sun kawo labaran yadda wasu 'yan Nijeriya suka ajiye daloli har a cikin sokawe (soakaway).²⁰⁹ Masu shirin zuwa aikin Hajji ma suna iya adana kuɗafensu cikin dala. Hakan yana taimakawa wajen kauce wa yin hasara yayin da darajar naira ta faɗi. M.A. Ibrahim (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 13 ga watan Yuni 2024).²¹⁰

4.3 Nadewa

Samuwar intanet ya zo da sauye-sauye da ci gaba masu tarin yawa a fannin sana'o'i da kasuwanci. Hausawa suna da damarmaki sosai da za su iya cin gajiyarsu a waɗannan fannoni. Akwai hanyoyin samun kuɗi waɗanda kai tsaye sun dace ne su kasance gurabu na Hausawa. A cikin misalansu akwai ayyukan da suka shafi al'adu da kimiyyar harshe. A rashin uwa akan yi uwar ɗaki, a inda wasu daban waɗanda ba Hausawa ba suke maye waɗannan gurabu. Hakan kuwa babbar illa ce ga harshen da al'adun Hausa. A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, rashi ne ga su Hausawa. Dangane da sauran nau'o'in damarmakin da ake da su a kan intanet ma (waɗanda suka kasance na gama gari a tsakanin alu'ummomi daban-daban), an ga yadda wasu Hausawa suke shiga

²⁰⁹ A duba Nathan (2016) da Ozogwu (2016).

²¹⁰ Ma'aikaci ne a kamfani mai zaman kansa da yake aikin jagorancin sama wa mahajjanta bisa da jigilar su zuwa Hajji.

domin a dama da su. Ko wafanda da aka bar Hausawa a baya game da su, ana kyautata fatan ayyukan bincike irin wannan su haska hanya ga Hausawa domin su shiga a ci kasuwar da su.

BABI NA BIYAR

NAKALTAR SANA'O'I DA KASUWANJI A DUNIYAR INTANET

5.0 Shimfida

A babi na huɗu an tattauna hanyoyi daban-daban na sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet waɗanda Hausawa suke iya amfana da su. Daga cikinsu akwai waɗanda suka kasance gama-gari tsakanin mutanen duniya (ayyukan da suka shafi kimiyya da fasaha da koyar da darussa da sauransu). Waɗansu daga cikinsu kuwa, ana sa ran su kasance keɓantattu ga Hausawa. Babban misali a nan shi ne, duk aikin da ya shafi harshe ko al'ada, kai tsaye an fi son ɗan gado ya aiwatar da shi ba ɗan haye ba. Ma'ana a nan ita ce, an fi son wanda Hausa take matsayin harshen uwa a gare shi ya aiwatar da ire-iren ayyukan. Akan yi hakan ne don gudun abin da Bunza (2017) ya kira "Grammatical Rift" (p. 5) da "Cultural Lacuna" (p. 11) wato "Giɓin Nahawu" da "Giɓin Al'ada." Bayan haka, abubuwan da ake buƙata suna iya bambanta bisa bambance-bambancen da suke tsakanin nau'o'in sana'o'i da kasuwancin ko muhallan gudanar da su. Wannan ɓangare na aikin ya mayar da hankali ne a kan muhimman abubuwan da mai fokarin shiga harkar sana'o'i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet ya kamata ya sani. Sun haɗa da matakan nakaltar harkokin da kuma kalubale da illolin da suke cikinsu.

5.1 Matakan Sana'o'i Da Kasuwanci a Duniyar Intanet

Harkokin sana'o'i da kasuwanci na duniyar intanet suna buƙatar karatun ta-nitsu kafin fara gudanar da su. Faɗa musu ba tare da cikakken ilimi ba yawanci yakan kai ga hasara ko shan wahala. Yayi daidai da abin da Bahaushe yake cewa: "Iya ruwa fiɗ da kai."

Da dama daga cikin hanyoyin bida a duniyar intanet sun shafi hulfa da mutanen da ba Hausawa ba. Suna da al'adu da salailan mu'amalar zamantakewa wadanda ba dole ne su zamo iri daya da na Hausawa ba. Haka kuma, dokoki da ka'idojin nau'o'in hulfodi da ake gudanarwa suna da matuƙar tsauri da buƙatar a bi su sau-da-kafa. Muhimman abubuwan da mai ƙoƙarin shiga wannan layin ya kamata ya fahimta sun hada da:

- a. Kwarewa a fannin da aka dauka
- b. Sanuwa a duniyar intanet (online visibility)
- c. Samun sabis din intanet mai karfi da rashin yankewa
- d. Girmama lokaci
- e. Gaskiya da rikon amana
- f. Nakaltar harshe ko harsuna
- g. Koyon dabarun kirƙira da saurin yanke hukunci
- h. Tanadar na'urori masu sauri da inganci
- i. Wuri mai sirri da rashin hayaniya
- j. Nakaltar injunan fassara
- k. Ilimin kare kai daga damfara

5.1.1 Kwarewa a Fannin Da Aka Dauka

Aiki a kan intanet yana buƙatar matuƙar kwarewa irin wadda Hausawa suke yi wa kirari da "hannu ya iya jiki ya saba." A mafi yawan lokuta, ba a faye damuwa da satifiket ko matakin karatu ba. Babban abin da ake mayar da hankali a kansa shi ne 'kwarewa.' An fi damuwa da abin da mutum ya aiwatar a baya da kuma abin da zai iya aiwatarwa a yanzu. Dangane da wannan, wadanda suka fi samun aiki a kan intanet su

ne waƙanda suke da kyakkyawan tarihin ayyuka a baya. Hakan yana nuni da cewa sun ƙware a fannin da suke.

Makamancin wannan ne yake faruwa a fannin abin da ya shafi hulɗayyar kasuwanci a kan intanet. Hausawa da sauran mutane waƙanda suka gudanar da hulɗoɗin kasuwanci masu yawa ba tare da matsala ba, yawanci kafar intanet ko manhajar takan ba su tambari ko baji (badge) na musamman. Wannan tambari ko baji zai yi nuni ga matsayinsu a cikin kasuwar. Bugu da ƙari, zai yi manyan ayyuka guda biyu:

1. **Samun Kulawa Ta Musamman:** Waƙanda suke da babban matsayi a ire-iren waƙannan kafafe da kasuwannin kan intanet, jami'an da suke kula da kasuwannin za su riƙa ba su kulawa ta musamman. A duk lokacin da suka tuntuɓi *sashen taimako*, to za a saurare su cikin gaggawa.²¹¹
2. **Samun Abokan Hulɗa Masu Yawa:** Duk wanda yake kasuwancin kan intanet da zuciya ɗaya, to burinsa shi ne haɗuwa da 'yan kasuwa masu nagarta da sauƙin kai. Wanda yake da tambarin nagarta a akawun ɗinsa, lallai 'yan kasuwa masu yawa za su riƙa ribibin ganin sun yi hulɗar kasuwanci da shi.

5.1.2 Sanuwa a Duniyar Intanet (Online Visibility)

Harkallolin kan intanet sun dace da kirarin nan na Hausawa “a san mutum a san cinikinsa/sana'arsa.” Wani babban abu mai muhimmanci ga Bahaushe wanda yake neman ayyuka a kan intanet shi ne sanuwarsa a kan intanet ɗin. Dole ne ya sanu ta

²¹¹ Babban misali a nan shi ne baji na musamman wanda ake bayarwa a kan manhajar PalmPay, wato *Premium*. Baji ne wanda ake ba wa waƙanda suka cika wasu ƙa'idoji. Ka'idojin sun shafi gudanar da a kalla taransifa talatin (30) a wata da ajiye a kalla dubu goma (₦10,000) a cikin asusun, da dai sauransu. A duba Chidi (2024) ko manhajar PalmPay. Jami'an PalmPay suna bayar da kulawa ta musamman ga masu wannan matsayi.

yadda da zarar an tura neman ma'aikata a kan intanet da suke gudanar da irin aikin da yake yi, to zai fito cikin sakamakon da injin nema zai bayar. Misali, idan ana neman masu aikin fassara ne daga Hausa zuwa Ingilishi, to sanuwa a duniyar intanet ne zai ba wa ma'aikaci a wannan fannin damar bayyana har a tuntuƙe shi.²¹²

Dangane da wannan, dole ne Hausawa masu fokarin shiga harkar fassara a kan intanet su yi rajista da kamfanonin fassara daban-daban.²¹³ Bugu da ƙari, dole ne su buƙe akawun a kafafen baje hajar basira. Ire-iren kafofin da Hausawa ma'aikata masu zaman kansu a kan intanet suke yin rajista domin baje kolin fasaharsu sun haɗa da:

- a. Behance (www.behance.net)
- b. Dribbble (www.dribbble.com)
- c. Fiverr (www.fiverr.com)
- d. Freelancer (www.freelancer.com)
- e. Gengo (www.gengo.com)
- f. Guru (www.guru.com)
- g. LinkedIn (www.linkedin.com)
- h. PeoplePerHour (www.peopleperhour.com)
- i. ProZ (www.proz.com)
- j. Smartcat (www.smartcat.com)
- k. Toptal (www.toptal.com)
- l. TranslatorsCafe (www.translatorscafe.com)
- m. Upwork (www.upwork.com)²¹⁴

²¹² Rashin sanuwa a duniyar intanet ne ya sa Hausawa da suka ƙware a fassara da sauran ayyuka ba sa samun aiki. A maimakon haka, sai ake ba waɗanda ba ƙwararru ba sakamakon sun kasance sanannu ne a intanet.

²¹³ An kawo misalan kamfanonin fassara goma sha uku (13) waɗanda suke da sashen Hausa a ƙarƙashin 4.1.1.1 a babi na huɗu.

²¹⁴ Domin ƙarin bayani, ana iya duba Rai et al. (2019) da Duggan et al. (2020).

Ko bayan yin rajista da ire-iren waƙannan kafafe, dole ne Hausawa masu aiki a kan intanet su riƙa sabunta bayanansu lokaci zuwa lokaci.

5.1.3 Samun Sabis Din Intanet Mai Karfi Da Rashin Yankewa

Dukkannin hanyoyin sana'o'i da kasuwancin kan intanet suna da alaƙa da 'sabis din intanet.' Kamfanonin ayyuka a kan intanet masu yawa sukan tambayi yanayin karfin sabis din intanet na ma'aikaci kafin su ba shi aiki. Akwai kafafen da ake iya auna karfin intanet. Yayin da aka auna, za a dauki rahoton sannan a tura shi ga kamfanin da suka bukata. Misalan kafafen auna karfin intanet sun haɗa da:

- a. AT&T Internet Speed Test (www.att.com/support/speedtest)
- b. Fast.com (www.fast.com)
- c. Google Fiber Speed Test (<http://speed.googlefiber.net/>)
- d. Meteor by OpenSignal (<https://www.opensignal.com/apps>)
- e. Spectrum Speed Test (www.spectrum.com/internet/speed-test)
- f. Speedtest by Ookla (www.speedtest.net)
- g. Xfinity Speed Test (<https://speedtest.xfinity.com/>)

Yana da kyau Hausawa masu shirin shiga fagen su san da wannan ilimi. Yayin da suke auna karfin sabis din da suke amfani da, hakan zai taimaka musu wajen neman mafita idan akwai bukatar hakan.

5.1.4 Girmama Lokaci

Dole ne Hausawa da suke son yin fice a wannan fannin su naƙalci girmama lokaci. Girmama lokaci a nan yana nufin cika duk waɗansu alƙawura da mutum ya dauka dangane da lokaci. Alƙawarin yana iya kasancewa a rubuce ko kuma na fatar baki.

Mafi yawan ayyukan kan intanet suna tafiya ne da lokaci. Saba lokaci a wurin ma'aikacin kan intanet babban nakasu ne a gare shi.

Akwai kafafen intanet na ayyuka da suke da tsarin da yake nuna adadin lokacin da ma'aikaci ya taba sabawa. Daga cikinsu har da kafafen da Hausawa suke aiki a kai. A duk lokacin da dankwadon ya saba alkawarin lokaci, to za a tara mintuna ko awannin da ya kara a saman alkawarin, a dora su a kan akawun dinsa. Misali, idan an yi alkawri da shi zai tura wani sako ko ya kammala wani aiki karfe goma (10:00) na safe, sai kuma bai tura ba har sai karfe goma da minti biyar (10:05), to za a sanya mintuna biyar (5) din a kan furofayil dinsa. Idan a gaba ya sake saba mintuna bakwai (7), to za a kara su a kan mintuna biyar (5) din (sun zama goma sha biyu ke nan (2)). Ga misali a kasa:

Hoto Na 5.1: Misalin Mintunan Saba Alkawarin Lokaci a Kafar BLEND

Madogara: Akawun Din BLEND Mai Lamba

A hoto na 5.1 da aka kawo a sama, za a lura da cewa mai akawun din bai taɓa saba alkawarin lokaci ba ko da na minti ɗaya ne. Bugu da ƙari, ya kammala ayyuka ɗari da tamanin da takwas (188) waɗanda suka kai adadin kalmomi dubu ɗari da casa'in da ɗari biyu da sittin da bakwai (190,267). Hakan zai ba wa akawun ɗinsa daraja sama da na wasu da ba su da tarihin waɗannan nasarori a kan kafar.

5.1.5 Tsara Lokaci

Tsara lokaci wani mataki ne na tabbatar da girmama lokaci. Duk da haka, yana iya cin gashin kansa. Kai tsaye ya shafi daidaita lokaci domin amsa sakonnin kwastomomi daga ɓangarorin duniya daban-daban. Yana da muhimmanci a tuna cewa, garuruwa kamar su *Auckland* na ƙasar *New Zealand* suna da ƙarin awanni goma sha biyu zuwa goma sha uku (12-13) daga Nijeriya. Garuruwa irin su *Honolulu* da *Hawaii* na Amurka kuwa, suna bayan Nijeriya da awanni goma zuwa goma sha ɗaya (10-11).²¹⁵ Hausawa mazauna Nijeriya dole ne su yi la'akari da wannan domin tsara lokutansu.

Ya zama dole ga ma'aikata masu zaman kansu a kan intanet su yi la'akari da kwastomominsu, da wuraren da suka fito. Wannan ne zai ba su damar daidaita lokacinsu ta yadda za su iya bayar da amsar sakonnin da aka turo daga ƙasashe daban-daban ba tare da bata lokaci ba. Yana da kyau Hausawa su riƙe cewa, bayar da amsar sakonni cikin lokaci abu ne mai matuƙar muhimmanci a harkar ayyukan kan intanet.

Akwai kamfanonin da suke tura sanarwar aiki ga ma'aikata masu zaman kansu mabambanta a lokaci ɗaya. Waɗanda suke iya ba da amsa da wuri, da su ne za a

²¹⁵ Akan samu bambancin awa ɗaya ne kasancewar a yankunan can ana samun sauyin lokaci wanda yake bayar da tazara (ƙaruwa ko raguwar) ta awa guda.

tattauna har a samu wanda zai dauki aikin a cikinsu. A wasu lokutan kuwa, na'ura ce za ta tura aiki ga dan ma'aikaci (system assignment). Da zarar ba ya kusa, za ta soke aikin sannan ta tura wa wani na daban.

5.1.6 Gaskiya Da Rifon Amana

Kafin mutum ya shahara a wani fannin aiki ko kasuwancin kan intanet, dole ne ya kasance mai gaskiya da rifon amana. A duniyar zahiri ana da barayi da 'yan zamba da sauran miyagun mutane. Haka abin yake a duniyar intanet inda ake da 'yan damfara iri-iri. Wannan ya sa kafafen intanet da dama (musamman waƙanda suka shafi kasuwanci ko hulƙoƙin kuƙi) suke da tsauraran matakan tsaro. Aikata rashin gaskiya ko cin amana laifi ne da zai sa a rufe akawun ɗin mutum nan take. Ko da ma dai, waƙannan miyagun ɗabi'u ne a al'adar Hausawa. Kamar yadda Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma kuwa ya zayyana, ɗabi'un al'umma suna tasiri a kan mu'amalolin kasuwancinsu da sauran hulƙoƙinsu har a kan intanet.

A ɓangaren ayyukan da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe, kafafe da dama sukan jero sunayen waƙanda suka aikata rashin gaskiya. Kafafe irin su *Translation Directory* (<https://www.translationdirectory.com/>) suna da abin da suke kira *Black List*. Ya kasance tamkar *Bakin Littafi* a kan intanet inda suke sanya jerin waƙanda aka kama ko ake tuhuma da rashin gaskiya a fannonin ayyukan da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe. Hakan zai sa kamfanoni da ɗaiɗaikun ma'aikata su guji mu'amala da su. Yana da kyau Hausawan da suke shirin shiga fannin su san da wannan sannan su yi bakin kofarinsu wajen riko da gaskiya da amana.

5.1.7 Nakaltar Harshe Ko Harsuna

A farkashin 'A' a kasan 5.1 an bayyana cewa, ma'aikaci mai zaman kansa a kan intanet dole ne ya kware a fannin da ya dauka. Nakaltar harshe wani abu ne da ya shafi kwarewa, amma mai cin gashin kansa. Ga Hausawa waƙanda suke ayyukan da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe, nakaltar harshe wajibi ne a gare su, "farilla tusar mai bacci."

Dangane da sauran fannonin ayyukan kan intanet kuwa, nakaltar harshe yana taimakawa wajen tattaunawa da kwastomomi. Iya tsara zance da bayar da amsa yadda ya kamata abu ne mai muhimmanci a wannan fannin. Ya haɗa da zaɓen kalmomin da suka dace dangane da fannin da ake magana a kai.

Haka kuma, yayin da aka samu bambancin ra'ayi tsakanin ma'aikaci da mai duba ingancin aiki, nakaltar harshe yana taka rawa wajen fito da gaskiya game da jayayyar da ake yi (rebuttal). Hausawa sun yi gaskiya da suka ce "dokin mai baki ya fi gudu." Sau da dama waƙanda suka ba da aiki (clients) sukan yaudaru da zaƙin baki da sanin kalmomin fannu da wani ma'aikaci ya yi, musamman idan abokin jayayyarsa bai nakalci harshe ba. M.A. Umar (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 23 ga watan Octoba, 2023).

5.1.8 Koyon Dabarun Kirƙira Da Saurin Yanke Hukunci

Ilimi da basira baiwa ce da Allah yake ba wa ɗan'adam. Duk da haka, ɗan'adam yakan koyi dabarun da za su bunkasa masa kaifin basira da iya warware abubuwan da suka shiga duhu (Khilchenko & Perevoznikova, 2019 sh. 174). Duniyar intanet da na'urori fage ne mai matuƙar faɗi. Duk yadda mutum ya kware, akwai ranakun da zai ci karo da matsalolin da bai taɓa ganin su ko jin labarinsu ba. A irin wannan lokaci, dole ne ya

yi amfani da hikimomi domin gano bakin zaren. Wannan ya haɗa da bincike cikin kwarewa a kan intanet game da matsalar ko makamanciyarta.

Yawan korafi dangane da matsalolin da suka shafi intanet ko na'urori (da makamantansu) abu ne da yake janyo faɗuwar darajar ma'aikaci. Hakan ne ya sa daga cikin abubuwan da ake yawan bincikawa yayin ɗaukar ma'aikaci a kan intanet akwai (i) yadda yake tunkarar matsaloli, da kuma (ii) yadda ya iya aiki a cikin yanayin takura ko ujila. Yana da kyau Hausawan da suke aiki a wannan fannin su nakalci mata kai da dabarun yanke hukunci cikin hikima da hanzari.

5.1.9 Tanadar Na'urori Masu Sauri Da Inganci

Na'urori masu sauri da inganci sun kasance kashin gadon bayan ayyukan kan intanet. Jarin farko da Bahaushe ma'aikaci zai samu shi ne na'ura mai inganci da biyan bukata. Inganci ya haɗa da sauri da karfin sabis ɗin intanet da kuma rashin ɗaukar zafi.

Dole ne Hausawa su nakalci ɗabi'ar karbar sauyi. Sauye-sauye a wannan bagiren sun haɗa da koyon aiki da sababbin na'urori da manhajoji. Bincike daban-daban sun nuna yadda na'urori masu kyau da sabis ɗin intanet mai karfi suke taimakawa ga ayyukan kan intanet. Daga cikinsu akwai Cobo-Rendon & Maldonado-Trapp (2021) da Limniou (2021) da Hartley et al. (2023).

Ko ma wane irin nau'in harƙallar kasuwanci mutum yake yi a kan intanet, za a tarar yana buɗe kafafen intanet mabambanta a lokaci ɗaya a kan burawuzarsa. A wasu lokutan ma, yakan zama dole a yi amfani da burawuzozi daban-daban a lokaci ɗaya. Bugu da ƙari, ana iya buɗe manhajoji masu yawa a lokaci ɗaya. Duk waɗannan suna buƙatar na'ura mai inganci wadda ba za ta riƙa bayar da matsala ko tsaiko ba.

5.1.10 Wuri Mai Sirri Da Rashin Hayaniya

Wani abu da ya kamata Hausawa su riƙe shi ne, mafi yawan kamfanonin fassara sukan tura takardar yarjejeniyar riƙe sirri. Ana kiran ta da suna NDA (Non-Disclosure Agreement). Takardar yarjejeniya ce wadda a cikinta ma'aikacin kan intanet zai yi alkawarin riƙe sirrin duk waɗansu takardu ko bidiyoyi ko odiyo da aka turo masa a lokacin aiki. Zai kuma saka hannu kan amincewa da hukunce-hukuncen da doka ta tanadar idan ya saba wannan alkawari.²¹⁶

A bisa haka, dole ne Hausawa masu aikin zaman kansu su nakalci riƙe sirri tare da tanadar keɓantaccen wuri sirratacce domin gudanar da ayyukansu. Bugu da ƙari, yawancin ayyukan kan intanet suna buƙatar nitsuwa. Surutu yana iya haifar da kurakurai a ayyukan da ake gudanarwa sakamakon ɗauke hankalin ma'aikacin.

5.1.11 Nakaltar Injunan Fassara

Nakaltar injunan fassara kai tsaye ya shafi ayyuka ne waɗanda suke da alaƙa da ayyukan fannin kimiyyar harshe. Kafin bunkasar na'urori da intanet, Hausawa da sauran al'ummomi suna gudanar da fassara ne kawai ta hanyar rubutu. A yanzu an samu cigaban zamani sosai wanda ya haɗa da amfani da injunan fassara.

Injunan fassara (waɗanda ake kira *translation tools* a Ingilishi) fasahohin zamani ne da suka kasance cikin fasaloli daban-daban waɗanda suke taimaka wa ayyukan da

²¹⁶ Kamfanin *Translit Pro* sun bayyana cewa "The purpose of an NDA is to set out who and how a party can access and use the information in question, and to establish penalties for disclosing confidential information by accident or on purpose" (O'Farrell & Leschen, 2023 SL. 6). Ma'anar a nan ita ce, amfanin NDA shi ne samar da ƙa'idoji game da waɗanda za su iya samun bayanai da kuma ta yadda za su same su har ma da yadda za su yi amfani da su. Ya kuma shafi samar da hukuncin da zai faɗa kan waɗanda suka fitar da waɗannan bayanan sirri bisa kuskure ko ganganci.

suka shafi kimiyyar harshe.²¹⁷ Misalan injunan fassara da ake gudanar da ayyukan Hausa a kansu sun haɗa da:

1. SDL Trados Studio - Wanda kamfanin SDL suka samar (yanzu ɓangare ne na RWS Group)
2. MemoQ - Wanda kamfanin *MemoQ Translation Technologies* suka samar
3. Wordfast - Wanda kamfanin *Wordfast LLC* suka samar
4. Across Language Server - Wanda kamfanin *Across Systems GmbH* suka samar
5. Déjà Vu - Wanda kamfanin *ATRIL Solutions* suka samar
6. XTM Cloud - Wanda kamfanin *XTM International* suka samar
7. Memsourc (an sauya masa suna zuwa *Phrase*) - Wanda kamfanin *Memsourc* suka samar
8. Smartcat - Wanda kamfanin *Smartcat* suka samar
9. MateCat - Wanda kamfanin *MateCat* suka samar
10. OmegaT - Wanda kamfanin *OmegaT Project* suka samar
11. CafeTran Espresso - Wanda kamfanin *CafeTran* suka samar
12. Transifex - Wanda kamfanin *Transifex* suka samar
13. Crowdin - Wanda kamfanin *Crowdin LLC* suka samar

Nakaltar injunan fassara dole ne ga Hausawa masu son shiga a dama da su a wannan fannin. Rashin iya aiki da su naƙasu ne wanda yake haifar da rasa aiki daga kamfanoni.

²¹⁷ Domin ƙarin bayani game da injunan fassara da amfaninsu, ana iya duba O'Brien et al. (2013) da Almanna & Gu (2020).

5.1.12 Ilimin Kare Kai Daga Damfara

Akwai kalmomi guda biyu a Hausa da ake rubuta su cikin abajadin “damfara.” Sa’id et al. (2006 sh. 93) sun yi kokarin fayyace su kamar haka: (1) damfara (damfàraa, i,e,o,u, fi.) (i) jibga, ko dankara, ko maka kaya ko wani abu, d-d danna ko daddala. (ii) harhada kaya wuri guda. (2) damfara (dàmfaràa, sn., mc.) (i) yaudara ko zamba da ake yi wa wani mutum da yake zaton zai sami wata karuwa (ii) wala-wala. A wannan bincike, ana magana ne game da kalma ta biyu, wato wadda take daukar ma’anar yaudara ko zamba.

Daga cikin ayyukan masana da manazarta da suka tattauna batun damfara akwai Bunza (1994 sh. 2) da Maiyama (2008 sh. 27) waɗanda suka yi tarayya a kan wasu muhimman kalmomi a matsayin tubalan gina ma’anar damfara (karya da kwaɗayi da wayo da cuta ko zalunci). A taikaice ana iya cewa, damfara hanya ce ta amfani da dabarun yaudara don kwaɗaitar da wani samun wani abin alfanu dangin kuɗi ko wani abu mai daraja domin karɓar wani abu daga gare shi na dindindin.

Duk da ana damfara a duniyar zahiri, a yanzu ta fi yawa a duniyar intanet. Ayyukan Cross & Layt (2021) da Shang et al. (2023) sun kawo wasu nau’o’in damfara da ake yi a kan intanet tare da tattauna munin lamarin. A kullum waɗanda adireshin imel ðinsu ya yaɗu a kan intanet sukan samu saƙonnin imel na damfara masu tarin yawa.²¹⁸ Ta lambobin waya ma ‘yan damfara suna yawan kokarin gwada sa’arsu a kan mutane.

²¹⁸ Daɗinta ma shi ne, kamfanonin da ake buɗe akawun ðin imel da su, suna da tsarin da yake tura saƙonnin imel masu alamar damfara zuwa *sashen tarkace* “spam folder.”

Dole ne Hausawa masu ayyuka a kan intanet su nakalci hanyoyi da dabarun da ake bi domin kare kai daga 'yan damfaran kan intanet. Wasu daga cikinsu su ne:

- a. Ilimin iya tantance kafafen intanet na kasuwancin hakika da waƙanda aka kirƙira domin damfara²¹⁹
- b. Ilimin tantance likau ɗin da suke da tsaro da aminci da kuma waƙanda suke da rauni da alamun tambaya
- c. Ilimin matakan binciko bayanan duk wanda ya turo saƙo
- d. Ilimin tantance bayanan hakika da na 'yan damfara
- e. Nisantar zalama da saurin yanke hukunci game da al'amuran da suke da alamun rashin gaskiya a tattare da su

5.2 Tagomashin Sana'o'i Da Kasuwancin Duniyar Intanet

Samuwar hanyoyin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a kan intanet ya zo da alfanu mai yawa ga Hausawa da harshen Hausan kansa. Ya kawo cigaba ta fuskoki daban-daban da suka shafi bunkasar tattalin arzikin Hausawa da kuma saukaka musu hanyoyin samun kuɗi da dogaro da kai. A bangare ɗaya kuwa, ya taimaka wajen yayata harshe da al'adu da adabin Hausawa. A ƙasa an kawo wasu daga cikin tagomashin sana'o'i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet.

5.2.1 Bunkasar Tattalin Arzikin Hausawa

Samuwar ayyukan yi wani muhimmin mataki ne na bunkasa tattalin arzikin al'umma. Abin ya fi armashi musamman idan aka ce aiki ne wanda ya shafi samun kuɗi daga ayyukan da ake gudanarwa, sabanin sayar da abubuwa. Ma'ana dai, idan aiki al'umma

²¹⁹ Abubuwan da ake lura da su sun haɗa da daɗewar kafar intanet da tsarinta da sauransu.

suke gudanarwa ake biyan su, hakan ya fi riba sama da a ce wasu abubuwa suke sayarwa. Hakan yana faruwa ne kasancewar mai sayar da wani abu dole ne ya kashe kudafe kafin samar da shi.²²⁰

Nau'o'in ayyukan kan intanet da dama ba su buƙatar sayar da wani abin da ya shafi albarkatun kasa. A maimakon haka, ana iya cewa basira da fwarewa da kuma lokaci ake sayarwa. Wannan yana iya kasancewa dalilin da ya sa mafi yawan ayyukan kan intanet suke da tsarin biya na awa-awa. Misalan hanyoyin samun kuɗi a kan intanet waɗanda Hausawa suke cin gajiyarsu sun haɗa da ayyukan da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe²²¹ da ayyukan da suka shafi intanet da na'urori da waɗanda suka shafi baje koli/haja, da sauransu.

Duk kafafen sada zumunta da aka duba a yau za a tarar da akawun-akawun na Hausawa. Haka kuma, za a tarar da tallace-tallace da suke ɗorawa a kansu. Yayin da aka duba wata fitacciyar kalmar Hausa (misali wadda ta shafi wani abin amfani na yau da kullum ko wani al'amari mai jan hankali) a kan *YouTube* ko *TikTok*, jerin sakamakon da yake bayyana yana da tsawo sosai.

5.2.2 Yada Al'adu Da Harshe Da Adabin Hausawa

Ayyukan kan intanet daban-daban sun taimaka wajen yaɗuwar al'adu da harshe da adabin Hausa a kan intanet. Kafafen intanet irin su *Amsoshi* da *Bakandamiya* da

²²⁰ Misali manomi sai ya kashe kuɗi da lokaci wurin noma. Haka abin yake ga masu sauran sana'o'in da suka shafi samar da wasu abubuwa.

²²¹ A kan *Translation Directory* kaɗai, akwai Hausawa sama da ɗari biyar (500) da suka yi rajista a matsayin ma'aikata masu cin gashin kansu a kan intanet. Ana iya duba https://www.translationdirectory.com/translators/find_translators.php.

Makarantar Hausa da *WikiHausa* suna dauke da bayanai masu yawa gama da al'adun Hausawa.

A ɓangaren harshe kuwa, ko bayan rubuce-rubuce game da fannonin nahawun Hausa, a yau an samu kamusoshin Hausa a kan intanet. Kamusu matattara ce ta kalmomi da ma'anoninsu. Yana da matuƙar amfani ga bunƙasar harshe. Tuni Hausa ta yi wa sauran harsuna sa'o'inta zarra a wannan ɓangare. A rumbun manhajojin wayoyi na *PlayStore*, akwai manhajojin kamusoshin Hausa masu yawa. Suna kasancewa cikin tsari na musamman, daga cikinsu akwai:

- a. Kamusun kalmomin Hausa da bayanan Ingilishi
- b. Kamusun kalmomin Hausa da bayanan Hausa
- c. Kamusun kalmomin Hausa zuwa kalmomin Ingilishi
- d. Kamusun kalmomin Ingilishi zuwa kalmomin Hausa

Daga cikinsu akwai waɗanda ba a iya amfani da su sai da data. Hakan yana nufin ko da an sauke su a kan waya ko kwamfuta, to dole sai an kunna data kafin a iya amfani da su. Wasu daga cikinsu kuwa, da zarar an sauke su a kan kwamfuta ko waya, to ana iya amfani da su ko da babu data. Kaso na uku su ne waɗanda ba a sauke su a kan kwamfuta ko waya. A maimakon haka, ana yin amfani da data ne kawai a duba su a kan intanet. An kawo misali a kasa cikin hoto:

Hoto Na 5.2: Kamusun Hausa Na Kan Intanet

Madogara: Shafin Farko Na *Hausa Dictionary*:

http://hausadictionary.com/Main_Page

A hoto na 5.2 da yake sama, za a ga kamusu ne na Hausa wanda ake amfani da shi a kan intanet. Kamar yadda ake gani a cikin hoton, an ba da damar bincika kalma kai tsaye a gurbin da aka rubuta "Bincika <> Search." Da zarar mutum ya rubuta kalma a wannan wuri, to kamusun zai gabato da bayananta nan take. Bayan haka, an yi wani tsari na abajada. Yayin da mai nema ya latsa daya daga cikin abajadan, kamusun zai gabato masa da dukkanin kalmomi da suka fara da wannan harafi. A shekarar 2024 ma *WikiHausa* sun kafa harsashen samar da kamusun kan intanet. A duba hoto na 5.3 da yake kasa.

Hoto Na 5.3: Yunkurin WikiHausa Domin Samar Da Kamusu

Madogara: Kafar WhatsApp Din WikiHausa

5.2.3 Hutun Jiki

Wadansu daga cikin nau'o'in kasuwanci suna da saufin gudanarwa. Misali, kasuwancin sayar da data da katin waya da na wutar lantarki da talabijin duk saita su kawai ake yi a bar su a kan intanet. Dan kasuwa ba ya bukatar wata wahalar ciniki ko miƙa kaya. A maimakon haka, kwastomomi su ne za su biya kuɗi kawai su dauki kaya. Hausawa masu irin wannan kasuwanci, suna kwance sai dai su ji shigar kuɗi a akawun dɪnsu.²²² Ga misali daga wani shagon sayar da data na kan intanet na Hausawa:

Hoto Na 5.4 Shagon Kan Intanet Na AMLAS Data

Madogara: <https://app.amlasdata.com.ng>

A hoto na 5.4 da yake sama, za a iya ganin cewa wannan shagon an saita shi domin kwastomomi su sayi abubuwa da kansu. Duk abin da suka sayar, za su biya kuɗin ta kan intanet ba tare da bukatar yin magana da mai shago ba. Hakan ya nuna yadda Hausawa masu ire-iren wadannan kasuwancin kan intanet suke samun hutun jiki.

²²² Duk da haka akwai abubuwan da ake bukatar daga gare shi kamar fara kuɗi a lalitoci da duba daidaiton lamura da kuma sauraren koken kwastomomi.

5.2.4 Karancin Jin Rauni Sakamakon Aiki

Akan samu raunuka daban-daban a wuraren ayyuka a duniyar zahiri. Raunukan sukan samu a sakamakon hadurra na tuntube ko fadɗowar kayan aiki ko gobara ko fashewar abubuwa, da dai sauransu. Ayyukan da Hausawa suke yi a duniyar zahiri masu hadurra sun haɗa da kafintanci da walda da gini da tonon rijiya da sauransu. Ana kuma iya samun haɗari a hanyar zuwa wurin aiki. Duk waɗannan sun danganta da yanayin aikin da ma'aikaci yake gudanarwa da kuma wurin aikin.²²³

Hausawa masu ayyuka a kan intanet suna da karancin fargabar aukuwar ire-iren waɗannan hadurra. Dalili kuwa shi ne, aikinsu ba ya bukatar tafiye-tafiye (misali zuwa wurin aiki da dawowa a kullum). Idan a cikin gidansu suke gudanar da ayyukan, hakan yana nufin suna iya kasancewa a wuri ɗaya. Gidansu kuwa wuri ne wanda suka saba da shi.²²⁴

5.2.5 Cikakken 'Yanci Da Walwala

Hausawan da suke gudanar da kasuwanci ko ayyuka a kan intanet suna da cikakken 'yanci da walwala. Idan aka ɗauki ayyukan kan intanet a matsayin misalai, hakan a bayyana yake karara. Hausawa masu aiki a kan intanet sukan karɓi ayyuka ne a lokacin da suka ga dama kawai. Bugu da kari, sukan zaɓi ayyukan da suka ga dama sannan su yi watsi da waɗanda ba su kwanta musu a rai ba.²²⁵ A duk lokacin da wani

²²³ Nordin (2014) ya tattauna wasu daga cikin haɗurran da suke aukuwa a dalilin zuwa aiki.

²²⁴ Duk da haka akan iya samun rauni lokaci zuwa lokaci musamman idan ba a bi ka'idojin aiki ba. Misali, ana iya samun ciwon baya ko ciwon wuya sakamakon daɗewa ana zaune ko zama yadda bai kamata ba, da dai sauransu.

²²⁵ Yawanci ma'aikata masu cin gashin kansu sukan fi karɓar aiki idan lokacin kammala shi (deadline) bai yi musu dadai ba, ko saboda farashin bai gamshe su ba, da dai makamantan hakan.

kamfani zai turo aiki ta kan intanet, to dole sai ya bincika idan ma'aikaci yana da lokaci sannan yana da sha'awar karɓar aikin.²²⁶ A duba misali a kasa:

Hoto Na 5.5: Misalin tambayar ma'aikaci idan yana da damar karɓar aikin Hausa (availability check)

Madogara: Sakon imel daga kamfanin fassara na GoTransparent

A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, Hausawa masu ayyuka a kan intanet sun kauce wa takunkumin zuwa wurin aiki kullum. Sabanin ma'aikatan duniyar zahiri da suke buƙatar tafiya wurin aiki, ma'aikata masu zaman kansu a kan intanet suna iya zama a gidajensu domin gudanar da ayyukansu. Wani ƙarin 'yanci shi ne, mutum ɗaya yana da damar yin ayyuka a kamfanoni ko ɗaiɗaikun mutane daban-daban. Abin ya yi daidai da maganar Hausawa ta "in laila ta ƙiya a koma basha" ko kuma "gida biyu maganin gobara."

Su ma nau'o'in kasuwancin da ake saita su domin su gudanar da kansu a kan intanet (automation), suna bayar da damar samun 'yanci da walwala ga Hausawa 'yan kasuwa. Wannan ƙarin tagomashi ne a kan hutun jiki (kamar yadda aka tattauna a

²²⁶ Wannan shi ake kira *availability check* a harshen Ingilishi.

karkashin 5.2.3 a sama). Babban misali a nan shi ne, wanda yake da shagon sayar da katin waya da data a duniyar zahiri, to lallai dole ya rufe shagonsa ko kuma ya nemi yaron shago idan yana son tafiya wani wuri. Bahausye wanda yake da shagon kan intanet da yake sarrafa kansa kuwa, zai je wurin da ya ga dama a lokacin da ya ga dama ba tare da hadahadar kasuwancin shagonsa ya fuskanci wani kalubale ba.

5.2.6 Jari

Yayin da wani Bahaushe zai fara gudanar da wata sana'a ko kasuwanci a duniyar zahiri, to yana bukatar jari. Jarin da zai nema ya danganci nau'in sana'a ko kasuwancin da zai gudanar. Idan shago zai buɗe, to yana bukatar sayen fili da kuɗin gini, ko kuma karɓar haya. Haka kuma, akwai kashe kuɗin gyaran shago da biyan kuɗin wuta da na haraji. Makamancin haka ne yake faruwa ga masu sana'o'i kamar kafintan kasa (kafintan mata) da mai shagon kwamfuta ko kafe (cafe) da makamantansu.

Wani muhimmin abin burgewa tattare da hanyoyin samun kuɗi a duniyar intanet shi ne yadda ba su bukatar wani jari mai yawa. Jarin da ake bukata bai taka kara ya karya ba, duk da ya danganta da nau'in kasuwanci ko sana'ar da aka saka a gaba. Ana iya ɗaukar mai koyarwa a kan intanet a matsayin misali. Abin da yake bukata kawai shi ne na'ura da sabis ɗin intanet da kuma wutar lantarki. Hakan ya sha bamban da yadda abin yake a duniyar zahiri a inda aƙalla sai an tanadi aji ko azuzuwa.²²⁷

²²⁷ Domin samun karin bayani game da 'bukatar karamin jari' a matsayin tagomashin bidar kuɗi a duniyar intanet, ana iya duba Al-Jarf (2020) da Ren & Raghupathi (2023).

5.2.7 Rage Cunkoson Ababan Hawa Da Rage Cutar Da Muhalli

Wani alfanun da yake tattare da sana'o'i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet shi ne rage cunkoson ababan hawa a kan tituna. Hakan yana faruwa ne sakamakon ire-iren ayyukan nan ba su bukatar tafiya ofishi na musamman a wata ma'aikata ko kuma wurin aiki na musamman. Rage cunkoson ababan hawa kuwa, yana taimakawa wajen rage cutar da muhalli.

Binciken Güven (2024) ya tabbatar da cewa, ayyukan ma'aikata masu zaman kansu a kan intanet da kuma ayyuka daga gida ta kan intanet²²⁸ suna matukar taimakawa wajen rage cunkoson ababan hawa. Suna kuma taimakawa wurin takaita wasu illolin da ayyukan 'yan'adam suke yi wa muhalli. Hasan & Habib (2023) suna ganin, riƙo da dabarun gudanar da ayyuka ta kan intanet za su iya taimakawa har a bangaren rage barnata filaye. Hakan zai faru ne yayin da aka takaita amfani da filaye wurin gina ofisoshin ma'aikatu. A maimakon hakan, ma'aikata za su kasance suna gudanar da ayyuka daga gidajensu.

Ababen hawa da ake amfani da su, suna fitar da sinadarin kabon dai'ozayid (carbon dioxide (CO₂)). Wannan sinadari kuwa yana matukar illata muhalli, musamman abin da ake kira Ozon Leya (Ozone Layer).²²⁹ A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, cunkoson da ya yi yawa yana iya yin mummunan tasiri a kwakwalwar mutum. Hakan ya shafi saka masa damuwa da kagara (psychological stress). Wata mummunan illar da cunkoson ababen hawa yaka haifarwa ita ce yiwuwar karuwar saurin fushi da faɗa a tsakanin mutanen da abin ya shafa.

²²⁸ *Work From Home* (WFH)

²²⁹ Don karin bayani ana iya duba East et al. (2024).

A takaice ke nan, rage cunkoson ababan hawa a kan tituna zai taimaka wa muhalli. Wannan kuwa alfanu ne ga al'ummomin duniya baki ɗaya, ciki har da Hausawa. Bugu da ƙari, zai taimaka wa mutane ta fuskokin da suka shafi lafiyar jiki da na ƙwaƙwalwa da kuma kyautata zamantakewa.

5.3 Kalubalen Sana'o'i Da Kasuwancin Hausawa a Duniyar Intanet

Kalubalen sana'o'i da kasuwanci a nan yana nufin wasu al'amura ko yanaye-yanaye waɗanda suke haifar da naƙasu ko koma-baya dangane da harkokin sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet. A matakin duniya, akwai nau'o'in ƙalubale daban-daban da suke kawo tasgaro ga harkokin biɗa a duniyar intanet. Duk da haka, za a mayar da hankali kan waɗanda suka shafi Hausawa kawai. A kasa an kawo wasu ƙalubalen da suke yi wa Hausawa tarnaki a ƙoƙarinsu na rungumar hanyoyin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.

5.3.1 Matsalar Wutar Lantarki

Dukkannin nau'o'in ayyukan kan intanet da na'urori ake gudanar da su. Amfani da na'urori kuwa abu ne da yake buƙatar wutar lantarki. Wannan ya kasance wani babban kalubale ga ma'aikata masu zaman kansu a kan intanet da suke wuraren da ba su da dauwamammiyar wutar lantarki. Matsalar wutar lantarki ba baƙon al'amari ba ne a Nijeriya (ƙasar da take da yawan Hausawa sama da ko'ina a duniya). Ko bayan matsalar yawan ɗauke wuta, akan samu lalacewar wuta a matakin ƙasa baki ɗaya (national grid collapse). Ademola (2024) ya kawo rahoton cewa, a shekarar 2024 kaɗai, wutar ƙasar ta lalace har sau goma a tsakanin watan Janairu zuwa Nuwamba.

A jahohin arewacin Nijeriya kamar su Bauchi da Kano da Katsina da Sakkwato da Zamfara, Hausawa masu ayyuka a kan intanet da dama suna aiki ne cikin matuƙar takura. Hakan yana kawo musu naƙasu game da ayyukansu. Kammala aiki cikin lokaci yakan kasance kalubale babba. Sau da dama a bisa tilas sukan je gidajen sayar da mai ko kafe (cafe) domin samun caji kawai.²³⁰

5.3.2 Matsalar Sabis Din Intanet

Kamar yadda sunan ya nuna farara, a kan intanet ake gudanar da *ma'aikata masu zaman kansu a kan intnet*. Ko ma wane nau'in aikin kan intanet mutum yake gudanarwa, akwai gaƙar da dole sai ya buƙaci sabis. Za ta iya yiwuwa domin yaɗawa da tallata hajarsa, ko domin karɓar aiki ko gudanar da aikin ko kuma tura shi yayin da aka kammala.

Hausawa da suke gudanar da ayyuka a kan intanet musamman mazauna Nijeriya suna fuskantar wannan kalubale. Akan samu lokutan da ayyuka suke wuce su ko su kasa tura aiki cikin lokaci, da dai sauran matsaloli makamantan waɗannan. Idan aka ɗauki ayyukan fassara a matsayin misali, sau da dama akan gudanar da su ne a kan injunan fassara (kamar yadda aka tattauna a farkashin 5.1.11 a sama). Yayin da babu sabis ɗin intanet mai karfi, kai tsaye ba za a iya gudanar da ire-iren ayyukan ba.

5.3.3 Rashin Koyar Da Zamanantattun Darussa

A manyan da kananan makarantu a Nijeriya, an fi mayar da hankali kan ra'o'i da tsurar karatu a maimakon aiwatar da ilimi a aikace. Bugu da fari, sau da dama akan

²³⁰ A.M. Umar (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 18 ga watan Agusta 2023) da M.S. Wali (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 18 ga watan Agusta 2023) da J. Abdullahi (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 21 ga watan Nuwamba 2024).

koyar da abubuwa ne wadanda an riga da an wuce su a duniyar kimiyya da fasaha. Idan aka dauki fannin fassara a matsayin misali, har yau an fi mayar da hankali wajen koyar da ra'o'inta kawai. Wannan ya shafi ma'anar fassara da ire-irenta da barun gudanar da ita a gargajiyanca. Duk da bayanan za su iya kasance masu muhimmanci, ba su da wani tasiri mai yawa a duniyar fassarar yau.

A bangaren intanet da na'urori ma akan ci karo da irin wannan kalubale. Intanet wani al'amari ne mai sarfakiya tare da cakwakiya. Yana bukatar ilimi na musamman. Yana tafiya da harsuna na daban. Yayin gudanar da al'amuran intanet, akwai bukatar samun ilimin wadannan yaruka ko harsunan intanet.²³¹

Rashin samun ilimin wadannan harsunan intanet koma baya ne ga gudanar da harkokin kafafen intanet. Sun kasance tamkar tubalan ginin kafafen. Idan babu su, kafafen intanet ba za su iya wanzuwa ba kamar yadda ake kallon su. Akwai dalilai da suke sa Hausawa kasa a guiwa a wannan bangare na koyon harsunan intanet. Sun haɗa da:

- i. Babu wadatattun masu ilimin da za su koyar da harsunan intanet da kwamfuta.
- ii. Babu wadatattun santoci da makarantun koyar da harsunan intanet da kwamfuta.
- iii. Yawancin Hausawa ba su da ra'ayi a wannan bangaren ilimi.

²³¹ An kawo wasu daga cikinsu a babi na huɗu, a karkashin 4.1.1.2.1. Sun haɗa da CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) da HTML (Hypertext Markup Language) da PHP (Personal Home Page Tools) da sauransu.

- iv. Koyon harsunan kwamfuta da intanet yana bukatar biyan kuɗin horaswa. Yawancin waɗanda suke da ra'ayin koyon ba su da damar biyan kuɗin horaswar da ake bukata.

A ɓangare guda kuwa, harkar gudanar da kafafen intanet abu ne mai bukatar lokaci. Da farko akwai bukatar lokacin koyon harsunan kamar yadda aka ambata a sama. Samun wannan lokaci ba karamin kalubale ne ba. Da a ce akwai tallafi ga masu wannan hobbasawar, da haƙiƙa gudanar da kafafen zai zo da sauki. Dalili shi ne, tallafin zai ishe su biyan bukatur rayuwar yau da kullum. Haka na nufin kenan za su dukufa ka'in da na'in wajen aiki ba kama hannun yaro, tun da ba su tunanin rashin ruwan ciki wanda da shi ne ake jan na rijiya.

A shekarar 2022, Hukumar Kula Da Jami'o'i Ta Kasa (National Universities Commission (NUC)) ta yi wani hobbasa na sanya tsarin koyar da zamanantattun darussa a jami'o'i. Hakan zai kara samar da hanyoyin dogaro da kai ga waɗanda suka kammala karatun jami'a, sabanin yanzu da aka fi mayar da hankali kan ayyukan gwamnati kawai.²³² Kamar yadda NUC (2022 sh. 1) ta nuna, an saka kwasakwasai masu alaƙa da intanet da kwamfuta domin ɗalibai su sami ilimin zamani. Hakan ne zai ba su damar iya yin gwagwarmaya a duniyar yau.

²³² A wannan yunkuri, NUC ta samar da abin da ta kira 'Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS) for Nigerian Universities'.

5.3.4 Talauci

Talaucin²³³ da ake fama da shi a yankunan kasar Hausa wani kalubale ne ga ma'aikata a kan intanet. Da dama daga cikin hanyoyin samun kuɗi a kan intanet sun dogara ne ga al'ummar da ake gudanar da aiki dominta ko kuma ake yi mata talla. Ana iya tabbatar da hakan yayin da aka yi la'akari da cewa:

- a. Wanda ya buɗe kafar intanet ta Hausa sannan ya sanya masa tsarin yin rajista, lallai ba zai samu kwastomomi.
- b. Wanda ya buɗe kafar intanet ta Hausa sannan ya dogara a kan tallace-tallace domin samun kuɗin shiga, lallai ba zai samu wata riba ba. Hakan yana faruwa ne kasancewar kasar Hausa ba ta ɗaya daga cikin wuraren da ɗora tallace-tallace yake kawo kuɗi. Wannan ma yana da alaƙa kai tsaye da talaucin yankin da kuma rashin bunkasarsa a fannin sayayyan kayayyaki a kan intanet.
- c. Wanda ya kware a wani fannin aiki na kan intanet da ya shafi intanet da na'urori, yawanci sai dai ya rika neman ayyuka daga kasashen ketare. Hakan yana faruwa ne kasancewar a yankunan kasar Hausa babu cigaban yawaitar buƙatun ire-iren ayyukan (kamar bayar da tsaro a kafar intanet da makamantansu).

Wadannan matsaloli da sauran makamantansu sun kasance kalubalen da suke da alaƙa da tattalin arzikin Hausawa. Ko a duniyar zahiri, mutuwar al'adar sayen littattafai ba ta takaita ba ga rashin son karatu ba kawai. Tana da alaƙa da matsalolin

²³³ Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, talauci a nan yana nufin karancin kuɗaɗen da suke hannun al'umma waɗanda ba za su ishe su ba wajen biyan buƙatunsu na yau da kullum har su samu ragowar da za su kashe a kan abubuwan nishaɗi. Bai shafi arzikin albarkatun kasa ko wani nau'in arziki da zai iya kasancewa mai yawa a kasar Hausa ba.

kudi da suke damun dalibai da manazarta. Haka abin yake a duniyar intanet. Mafi yawan Hausawa ba su iya saya ko zama silar samun kudi ga ma'aikata a kan intanet.²³⁴

5.4.5 Rashin Karbar Sauyi

Dan'adam yana da dabi'ar kin karbar sauye-sauye a rayuwa. Wannan ne ma ya sa ake da ra'o'in "*resistance to change*" da "*cultural lag*" (kin karbar sauyi da like wa al'ada).²³⁵ Wadannan ra'o'i suna nuna cewa, dan'adam yana jin shakku da waswasi game da duk wani sauyi da aka gabato masa da shi a rayuwa. Zuciyarsa za ta raya masa cewa, tsohuwar hanyar da yake bi ita ce daidai. Zai kuma ji cewa, sabuwar hanyar tana iya kasancewa cike da kalubale da wahalhalu, sannan ba za ta bulle ba.

Mutum yana karbar sauyi a rayuwa yayin da ya yi amfani da abin da ake kira "*overcoming resistance to change*" (yakar dabi'ar kin karbar sauyi). Sau da dama yayin da mutum ya karfi sabon al'amari, zai yi mamakin kasancewar har ya fi tafarkin da yake bi a baya sauki da aminci. Bayan haka, zai yi mamakin yadda sannu a hankali zai saba da sabon sauyin da ya runguma. Sau da dama sauyi yakan zo wa mutum cikin sauki, ba kamar yadda a da yake tunanin ba zai iya sabo da shi ba.²³⁶ Masu kofarin samar da kafafen intanet na Hausa da sauran Hausawa masu aiki a kan intanet suna

²³⁴ A bangare daya, akwai tasirin karancin ilimin sayayya da gudanar da sauran lamura a kan intanet. Duk da haka, "samu ya fi iyawa." Masu wadata ba sa rasa hanyoyin da za su bi domin sayan abin da suke muradi a kan intanet.

²³⁵ Domin samun karin bayani ana iya duba Zhu & Zhu (2022) da Rizescu (2024).

²³⁶ Har ya zuwa shekarar 2024, akwai mutanen da suke amfani da samfurin *Microsoft Office 2007*. Sun fi karbar sababbi da aka samar wadanda an bunfasa su sama da na 2007. Wasu da suka karfi sauyin, sun nuna farin ciki da gamsuwa. Kamar haka abin yake a sauran bangarorin rayuwa. Wannan ne ya sa Bahaushe yake cewa: "Sai an gwada akan san na kwarai."

fuskantar wannan kalubale mai alaka da kin karbar sauyi a tsakanin Hausawa.

Binciken ya gano cewa:

- i. Ba su samun goyon bayan da ya kamata yayin da suka tinkari cibiyoyi ko sashe-sashen nazarin Hausa.²³⁷
- ii. Ba su samun goyon bayan da ya kamata yayin da suka tuntubi masana harshen Hausa.²³⁸
- iii. Ba a samun goyon baya daga daliban Hausa kamar yadda ya kamata.²³⁹

Cikin sauki, abin da ya kamata shi ne a bi maganar Bahaushe inda yake cewa: “Zamani riga.” Ya jaddada wannan batu a wurin da ya ce: “Zamani abokin tafiya.” Ta hanyar karbar sauyi ne kawai za a iya amfana da damarmakin da zamani ya zo da su.

5.4.6 Dokokin Gwamnati

“Dokoki” sun kasance ginshiki na farko a cikin muhimman ginshikai uku (3) na Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma. Wannan ginshiki ya nuna cewa, kwarin guiwa ko koma bayan haka game da kasuwanci yakan dogara ga dokokin da gwamnatoci da hukumomi suka gindaya dangane da kasuwancin. A hakikanin gaskiya, sau da dama

²³⁷ A kasashen da suka ci gaba, kusan abu ne da ya zama tilas kowane sashe a jami'a ya kasance yana da kafar intanet (za a iya tabbatar da hakan yayin da aka bincika duniyar intanet). Dangane da sashe-sashen nazarin Hausa, ba haka abin yake ba. Har ya zuwa 2020, wannan bincike bai ci karo da ko da sashen koyar da Hausa a Nijeriya ko Nijar guda daya da yake da kafar intanet tasa ta kansa ba! Wai “wata miyar sai a maƙwabta!” Duk da haka, a yanzu akwai sashe-sashen da suka zabura inda suka fara buɗe kafafen intanet na laburaren sashe ko domin mujallar sashe. Misalansu sun haɗa da www.tasambo.com da www.delac-elibrary.digital (mallakin Sashen Nazarin Harsuna da Al'adu, FUGUS) da www.dundaye.com (mallakin Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, UDUS) da www.yumsuk-hausa.digital (mallakin Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, YUMSUK).

²³⁸ An yi hira da Bunza, (2019) bayan ya dawo daga taron kara wa juna sani na kasa da kasa wanda aka gudanar a Folan. Ya bayyana cewa mallakar kafar intanet dole ne ga malami a kasashen da suka ci gaba. Wannan abu ba haka yake ba a kasar Hausa. Dangane da abin da wannan bincike ya gano, masana Hausa da suka mallaki kafafen intanet ba su da yawa.

²³⁹ Daliban Hausa sun fi kwarewa a kafafen sada zumunta kamar su Fesbuk da Was'af. Sukan bata lokaci matuƙa a ire-iren waɗannan shafuka. Da a ce za su mayar da hankali wajen bibiyar shafukan intanet na Hausa, to “da ba kwaɗo ba inji gaya.”

gwamnatoƙin ƙasashe sukan yi takun saka da mutanen da suka kawo wani sabon sauyin rayuwa. An samu irin wannan har a manyan ƙasashe irin Amurka a lokacin da aka fara yunkurin farko na kirkiro da kuɗin intanet. Ko a shekarar 2023, BBC sun kawo rahoton yadda Amurka take yaƙar harkar hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet. Rahoton Sherman (2023 SL. 4-11) ya kawo yadda gwamnatin Amurka take ƙoƙarin dakile ayyukan wasu kamfanonin hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet.

Makamancin wannan yana faruwa a Nijeriya. Hasali ma, abin da yake faruwa a Nijeriya ya fi muni. Gwamnati tana fakewa da cewa hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet shi ne ummul haɓa'isin faɗuwar darajar naira. Bugu da ƙari, takan ce ta hanyar kuɗaɗen intanet ne ake biyan masu ayyukan ta'addanci a Nijeriya. A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, Hausawa 'yan Nijeriya da suke wannan hulɗar kasuwanci sun tafi kan cewa zunzurutun rashin amana da rashin adalci ne suke saka gwamnati fito da waɗannan takunkumai.²⁴⁰

Gwamnatin Nijeriya ta saka takunkumai game da nau'o'in kasuwanci daban-daban na duniyar intanet. Abin ya faro tun daga kan takaita adadin kuɗin da za a iya turawa ƙasashen waje zuwa dala hamsin (\$50) kacal a wata. Sannu a hankali ma ya kasance ba za a iya tura ko sisi ba. Hakan ya yi mummunan tasiri ga Hausawan da suke ƙananan kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.

A lokacin da Hausawa da sauran 'yan Nijeriya suka rungumi kasuwancin kuɗaɗen intanet ka'in da na'in, sai kuma ga sababbin takunkumai da gwamnati ta gindaya. Sun shafi hana saye da sayar da kuɗaɗen intanet kwatakwa! An rufe asusun bankunan

²⁴⁰ An samu waɗannan bayanai ta hanyar shiga a dama da mai bincike (Participant Observation (PO)).

Hausawa masu yawa a dalilin wannan. Ta kai ga duk wanda ya tura kuɗi tare da bayani (transaction statement) wanda yake da alaƙa da kasuwancin kuɗin intanet (ko kuma shi aka turo masa kuɗin), to nan take za a kulle akawun ɗinsa na bankin.

Abin ya wuce nan inda har aka samu jami'an gwamnati²⁴¹ suna buɗe akawun a kasuwannin hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet. Za su shiga a matsayin 'yan basaja, tamkar dai 'yan kasuwa na haƙiƙa. Da zarar wani ɗan Nijeriya ya tura musu kuɗi da nufin kasuwanci, nan take za su kulle akawun ɗinsa na banki.²⁴² Jaridar *The African Report* (Rahoton Afirka) sun kawo bayanin yadda gwamnatin Nijeriya har ta kai ga kama jami'an kasuwar hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet mafi girma a duniya, wato Binance. Hakan ya sake jefa Hausawa da sauran 'yan Nijeriya da suke hadahadar kasuwanci a wannan kasuwa cikin babban kalubale (Asu, 2024).

5.4.7 Harshen Kasuwanci

Harshen da ya fi karɓuwa a duniya game da hadahadar kasuwancin duniyar intanet shi ne Ingilishi. Mafi yawan manyan kasuwannin duniyar intanet cikin harshen Ingilishi suke hulɗa. Da dama daga cikin waɗanda suke cikin wasu harsuna na daban sukan fassara kafofinsu zuwa Ingilishi. A kasa an kawo misalin manyan kamfanonin duniya da suke da alaƙa da sana'o'i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet. Za a iya lura da cewa, dukanninsu suna cikin harshen Ingilishi ne (ko da kuwa akan samu fassararsu cikin wasu harsunan).

²⁴¹ Masu kasuwancin kan intanet sukan ce ma'aikata ne daga Babban Bankin Nijeriya (Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)).

²⁴² Domin karin bayani game da takunkuman da gwamnatin Nijeriya ta sha gindayawa game da hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet da sauran nau'o'in kasuwancin kan intante, ana iya duba Asu (2024) da Obiezu (2024) da Okamgba (2024) da Onukwue (2024) da Uba (2024).

Jadawali Na 20: Manyan Kafafen Intanet Masu Alaka Da Sana'o'i da Kasuwanci a Intanet

Sunan Kafa	Kamfani	Babban Shafin Intanet	Babban Ofishi
1	Kasuwannin Kan Intanet		
Amazon	Amazon.com, Inc.	www.amazon.com	Seattle, Amurka
eBay	eBay Inc.	www.ebay.com	San Jose, Amurka
Alibaba	Alibaba Group Holding Limited	www.alibaba.com	Hangzhou, China
2	Kasuwannin Hadahadar Kufaden Intanet		
Binance	Binance Holdings Ltd.	www.binance.com	George Town, Cayman Islands
Coinbase	Coinbase Global, Inc.	www.coinbase.com	San Francisco, Amurka
Kraken	Payward, Inc.	www.kraken.com	San Francisco, Amurka
3	Kafafen Sada Zumunta		
Facebook	Meta Platforms, Inc.	www.facebook.com	Menlo Park, Amurka
YouTube	YouTube, LLC	www.youtube.com	San Bruno, Amurka
TikTok	ByteDance Ltd.	www.tiktok.com	Los Angeles, Amurka/Beijing, China
4	Manhajoji		
Apple	Apple Inc.	www.apple.com	Cupertino, Amurka
Microsoft	Microsoft Corporation	www.microsoft.com	Redmond, Amurka
Google	Alphabet Inc.	www.google.com	Mountain View, Amurka
5	Kufaden Intanet		
Bitcoin	Bitcoin	www.bitcoin.org	Ba shi da wuri takamaimai
Ethereum	Ethereum Foundation	www.ethereum.org	Ba shi da wuri takamaimai (yana

Sunan Kafa	Kamfani	Babban Shafin Intanet	Babban Ofishi
			ƙarƙashin jagorancin Ethereum Foundation in Zug, Switzerland)
Tether	Tether Operations Limited	www.tether.to	Road Town, Tortola, British Virgin Islands

Madogara: An tantance waƙannan bayanai daga kafafen intanet na kamfanonin

Wannan kalubale ne ga Hausawa, musamman waƙanda ba su nakalci harshen Ingilishi ba. Dalili kuwa shi ne, karanta bayanai musamman dokoki da ƙa'idojin harkalla a kan ire-iren waƙannan kasuwanni yakan zama abu mai wahala. Haka kuma, sashen taimako (help center) da na sasantaƙawa sukan kasance cikin Ingilishi ne. A takaice, harshen kasuwanci babban tarnaki ne ga Hausawa masu biƙa ko tanadi a duniyar intanet.

5.4.8 Samuwar Sauƙaƙan Na'urantattun Hanyoyin Gudanar Da Ayyuka

A baya-bayan nan ana ci gaba da samun sababbin hanyoyin zamani na gudanar da ayyukan da suka shafi kwamfuta da na'urori. Idan aka ƙauki ayyukan da suka shafi gyara hotuna da bidiyoyi da zane-zane a matsayin misali, za a tarar wannan kasuwa tana samun sauye-sauye. A yau akwai kafafen intanet da manhajoji da dama da suke aiwatar da waƙannan ayyuka cikin sauƙi. Ma'ana dai, an tsara su ta yadda duk mai so zai iya yi wa kansa ire-iren waƙannan ayyukan ba tare da ya biya kuƙi ga wani ma'aikaci don ya yi masa ba. A kasa an kawo misalansu:

- a. Adobe Express - (<https://www.adobe.com/express>)
- b. Canva - (<https://www.canva.com>)
- c. Clipchamp - (<https://www.clipchamp.com>)

- d. Fotor - (<https://www.fotor.com>)
- e. InShot - (<https://inshot.com>)
- f. iPiccy - (<https://ipiccy.com>)
- g. Kapwing - (<https://www.kapwing.com>)
- h. Photopea - (<https://www.photopea.com>)
- i. Pixlr - (<https://pixlr.com>)
- j. VEED.io - (<https://www.veed.io>)

Samuwar ire-iren wadannan kafafen intanet da manhajoji kalubale ne ga Hausawa da sauran al'ummomi masu irin wannan sana'ar kasancewar a har kullum suna kara rasa kwastomomi.

A ɓangaren ayyukan da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe ma akan samu kalubale makamantan wannan. Samuwar injunan fassara yana barazanar maye gurbin ma'aikatan fasasra masu yawa a duniya. Yanzu da ake ci gaba da samun ingancin injunan fassarar harshen Hausa, hakan yana zama kalubale ga Hausawa masu ayyukan fassara a kan intanet. Samuwar kirƙirariyar basira kuwa, barazana ce ga ayyukan da suka shafi kirƙirar rubutu.

5.4 Illolin Sana'o'i Da Kasuwanci a Duniyar Intanet

Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, 'illoli' a nan suna da bambanci da 'kalubalen' da aka tattauna a farkashin 4.3 da yake sama. Idan aka ce 'illolin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet,' to ana nufin matsalolin da harkoki da hulɗoɗi da sauran lamuran da suka shafi neman kuɗi da tanadi a duniyar intanet suke haifarwa. Ma'ana ke nan, wannan ɓangare na bincike zai mayar da hankali wajen tattauna ire-iren matsalolin

da suke aukuwa a sakamakon lamuran da suka shafi sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet, musamman masu alaƙa da Hausawa.

5.4.1 Illata Muhalli

Daga cikin harkoki da hadahadar kasuwancin intanet akwai waƙanda suke cutar da muhalli. Misali, haƙon kuɗaɗen intanet irin su Bitcoin yana illata muhalli matuƙa. Rahoton Osborne (2022) ya nuna cewa, illar da haƙon Bitcoin yake yi wa muhalli tana iya kai wanda man fetur yake yi ta fuskar fitar da sinadarin kabon. Hakan yana faruwa ne sakamakon cewa haƙon Bitcoin yana buƙatar manyan na'urori masu matuƙar jan wutar lantarki. Kiyasin wutar da ake ja a sakamakon haƙon Bitcoin a duniya, ya kai wutar da ake sha a illahirin wasu kananan ƙasashe. Bugu da ƙari, injuna da kwamfutocin da ake amfani da su suna fitar da tiririn sinadarai masu illata muhalli. Ayyukan da suka kawo bayanai game da illolin haƙon Bitcoin sun haɗa da na Truby (2018) da Gellersdörfer et al. (2020) da Cambridge Centre for Alternative Finance (2025) da Digiconomist (2025).

A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, ayyukan kan intanet a ƙasashe irin Nijeriya suna buƙatar hanyoyin samun wutar lantarki bayan na gama-gari da ake da shi. Wannan ya biyo bayan kalubalen wutar lantarki da ake fama da shi kamar yadda aka tattauna a ƙarƙashin 5.3.1 a sama. Sau da dama akan yi amfani da janareta domin samun wuta. Shi ma yana fitar da sinarin cabon wanda yake matuƙar illata muhalli.

5.4.2 Cutar Da Lafiya

Ba a ci karo da wani bincike da ya tabbatar da cewa yawan kallon sikirin yana haifar da dauwamammen ciwon ido ba. Duk da haka, masanan ido irin su Dakta Colman

Kraff sun tabbatar da cewa zai iya haifar da matsalolin da suka hada da kallo dishi-dishi da ciwon kai har ma da ciwon wuya idan abin ya yi tsanani.²⁴³ Hakan yakan faru ne musamman idan aka dade ana kallon sikirin. A bisa wannan, yana da kyau Hausawan da abin ya shafa su nakalci matakan kare lafiyar idanunsu.

A bangare daya kuwa, na'urori dangin waya da kwamfuta sukan fitar da wani nau'in tiriri (wanda ido ba ya gani) da ake kira radiyeshin. Binciken Abiola (2021) ya tabbatar da cewa radiyeshin da yake fita daga jikin kwamfuta yana haifar da illoli da dama, ciki har da hana haihuwa ga maza. Wannan yakan faru yayin da ake dora kwamfuta a kan cinya idan za a yi aiki, da makamantansu. A wannan gabar ma, yana da kyau Hausawa masu ta'ammuli da na'urori su bi matakan kare lafiyarsu.

Bayan wadannan, ana iya samun matsalar da ta shafi kwakwalwa sakamakon hadahadar kasuwancin kan intanet. Akwai hanyoyin neman kuɗi a kan intanet wadanda suke da matuƙar haɗari da dɒukar kasada. Sun haɗa da nau'o'in kasuwancin kuɗin intanet da na dauwamammun kadarorin kan intanet. Ana iya samun mummunan hasara ta farat ɗaya. Ko bayan haka, a kullum 'yan kasuwa suna cikin zulumin yadda abubuwa za su kaya.²⁴⁴ Haɗuwar ire-iren waɗannan damuwowi da zulumi suna iya jefa mutum cikin ciwon tunani ko su jawo masa bugun zuciya na farat ɗaya.²⁴⁵

²⁴³ Domin karin bayani, a duba Kraff (2021).

²⁴⁴ Wannan ya danganta daga mutum zuwa mutum. A bisa tsarin halittar ɗan'adam, wasu sun fi wasu jure wa damuwa da zulumi.

²⁴⁵ Domin karin bayani, a duba Sergeenkov (2024).

5.4.3 Fuskantar Damfara

Ma'aikata masu zaman kansu a kan intanet ba su samun shahara har sai an san su sosai a kan intanet (strong online presence). Wannan mataki ya haɗa har da yada bayanan tuntuba a kan kafaɗe daban-daban. Yaɗuwar bayanan tuntubar mutum kuwa a har kullum suna kara buɗe kofofi ga 'yan damfaran kan intanet. Suna amfani da su domin yunkurin damfarar masu su ta hanyoyi daban-daban.

Hausawa waɗanda bayanansu suke kan intanet suna cikin kalubalen fuskantar damfara. 'Yan damfara a kan intanet sun kasance nau'i-nau'i. Akwai waɗanda za su yi koƙarin damfarar mutum domin samun kuɗi ko wani abin duniya daga gare shi. Akwai kuma 'yan damfarar da za su ba wa mutum aiki alhali ba za su biya shi ba. Ga misali a kasa:

Hoto Na 5.6: Misalin Gargadi Game Da Kamfanonin Fassara Na 'Yan Damfara

SCAM ALERT: SHARE THIS MESSAGE WIDELY

VerbalTrans Technology appears to be operating as a **SCAM company** targeting linguists for unpaid labor. Owners: Soumya Ranjan Pattanaik, Bhakta Ranjan Mishra, and Smrutiranjana Pradhan.

Numerous linguists report that VerbalTrans owes them significant amounts for completed translation projects but has refused to make the agreed-upon payments. Furthermore, the company has become unresponsive, failing to answer emails and calls from freelancers seeking updates on their overdue invoices. VerbalTrans has repeatedly claimed that they have not received certain invoices and that they require additional time to process others. However, these explanations seem to be tactics to delay or avoid payment, as they contradict their own service agreement and established payment terms.

Madogara: Kamfanin fassara na ByLanguages (www.bylanguages.com) ya aiko wannan saƙo ranar 08/11/2024

Kamar yadda aka gani a hoto na 5.6 da yake sama, ire-iren waɗannan 'yan damfara sukan buɗe kafar intanet mai kayatarwa. Wanda ya duba zai yi zaton kamfanin

fassara ne na hakika. Yayin da aka yi musu aiki, daga nan za a daina jin duriyarsu. Irin wannan nau'in damfara da sauran makamantansu illoli ne da suka shafi ayyukan kan intanet.'

Wani nau'in kasuwancin damfara da ake yi a kan intanet shi ne na yada likau din da kamfani zai bayar ko gudanar da wani aiki na musamman (task) a kan intanet. Wasu daga cikin kamfanonin sukan bukaci a sanya hannun jari ko a yi rajista kafin fara kasuwancin. Yawancin wadanda suka shiga da farko-farko, sukan samu riba. Hakan zai sa su yi ta tallata abin ga abokansu musamman da yake ana ba da goro na musamman a duk wanda ya kawo wani sabon kwastoma (referral). A haka daga karshe ake rufewa da kudaden wadanda suka yi aiki ba a biya su ba, da kuma kudaden wadanda suka sanya hannayen jari.²⁴⁶ Hausawa masu yawa sun fada tarkon ire-iren wadannan kasuwancin damfara. Daga cikin wadanda aka yi a baya, kuma suka gudu da kudaden Hausawa akwai:

- d. Catly
- e. Dubai Gold Souk
- f. Insme
- g. MyBonus
- h. Uwork

Wadansu kuwa sukan fito ne da sigar kudin intanet (kirifto). Daga karshe sai su bukaci a saka kudi na kasuwancin a kan bulokcen (gas fee). Yayin da aka saka, sai

²⁴⁶ An samu wadannan bayanai daga tattaunawa da aka yi da Hausawa da suka ci wannan kasuwa. A. Sani (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 11 ga watan Maris, 2023) ya yi cikakken bayanin yadda harƙallolin suke gudana.

kuma su yi batar dabo, ko kuma su fito da wani farashin da ko kudafen da mutane suka saka ba za su iya fanshewa ba. A wannan bangaren ma an rufe da kudafen Hausawa. Daga cikin waƙanda Hausawa suka faɗa tarkonsu akwai:

- a. Aqua Protocol²⁴⁷
- b. Cold Wallet
- c. Rocket Rabbit
- d. Xblast

Ya zuwa watan Nuwamban shekarar 2024, akwai kasuwancin kan intanet guda biyu da Hausa da dama suke gudanarwa waƙanda suke da tsarin damfara. Lokaci ne zai nuna gaskiyarsu ko koma bayan hakan. Su ne:

- a. 52u
- b. Anchor

A - 52u

An fara gudanar da shi a shekarar 2024. Kafar intanet da suke amfani da ita ta kasance www.52u.today. Bugu da kari, suna iƙirarin cewa cibiyar kasuwancin tana Malesiya.²⁴⁸ A bayaninsu, manufarsu ita ce yaƙi da talauci da kuma bunkasa dogaro da kai.

52u yana da tsarin yin rajista. Matakan rajistarsa guda uku. Yayin da mutum ya yi rajista, sannan ya biya kuɗi, to 52u za su ba shi aron jari wanda za su saka masa a

²⁴⁷ Farko ya fito ne da suna “Gleam.” Daga baya ne suka mayar da sunansa “Aqua Protocol.”

²⁴⁸ Suna da ofishi a Constitution Road, 2nd Floor, KC Holding Building, Opposite Shema Filling Station, Kaduna.

akawun dinsa domin gudanar da kasuwanci da shi. Yawan kuɗin da za su saka masa, ya danganta da matakin rajista da ya yi. Matakan rajistan su ne:

- a. Basic – dalar Amurka ashirin (\$20)
- b. Silver – dalar Amurka hamsin (\$50)
- c. Gold – dalar Amurka dari biyu da hamsin (\$250)

Duk wanda ya ya yi rajistar matakin *Basic*, to za su ba shi dalar amurka dari uku da saban'in da biyar (\$375). Wannan bashi zai tsaya a akawun dinsa ne, ba zai iya fita ba. 52u ne za su yi amfani da kuɗin domin yi masa kasuwanci da su. Kasuwancin an gina shi ne a kan na'urantaccen tsari (automatic). A bisa haka, mutum ba ya buƙatar yin komai. Kasuwancin da kansa zai gudanar da kansa.

A kowane wata mutum zai samu ribar da ta kai kimanin dalar Amurka sittin da bakwai (\$67). Da zarar ya fara samun wannan ribar, za a riƙa cire kuɗin da aka ba shi ba shi (wato \$375) har zuwa lokacin da zai biya bashin duka. Idan ya kammala biyan bashi, to nan ne kuma zai fara cire ribar domin cin gajiya. Mafi karancin abin da za a iya cirewa shi ne dalar Amurka hamsin (\$50).

Shi ma yana da tsarin gayyata. Duk wanda ya gayyato wani, to zai samu kamasho.

B - Anchor

An fara gudanar da wannan kasuwanci a shekarar 2024. Kafar intaent da suke amfani da ita ta kasance <https://anchorit.live>. Harƙallar *Anchor* ta haɗa abubuwa daban-daban. Da farko dai suna da tsarin rajista mai azuzuwa biyu. Wani abu kuma shi ne, duk rajistar da mutum ya yi, akwai wata garabasa da za a ba shi. S. Muhammad

(kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 24 ga watan Nuwamba 2024) ya bayyana yadda tsarin yake kamar haka:

Tsari	Kudin Rajista	Garabasa
Silver	₦6,000	₦6,200
Pro	₦8,500	₦7,500

Wani abin lura shi ne, mutum ba zai iya cire garabasar da za a ba shi ba. A maimakon haka, za a ajiye su ne a cikin akawun dinsa, har sai sun taru. Za su taru ne ta hanyar sauran jinga da zai rika gudanarwa a kan akawun din. Wanda yake *Silver* sai kudinsa sun kai naira dubu talatin da takwas (₦38,000) kafin ya iya fitarwa. Wanda yake *Pro* kuwa, sai sun kai dubu arba'in da takwas (₦48,000).

Jingar da ake gabatarwa suna da yawa. Sukan kasance cikin tsarin wasannin kan intanet (online games) da kuma kallon bidiyoyi da kuma tsarawa da dora bidiyoyin tallata harkallar Anchor a kan intanet. Bayan haka, akwai nau'o'in jingar da danna kansu kawai ake buƙatar yi. Wanda yake *Silver* dole ne ya hau ya danna da kansa. Wanda yake *Pro* kuma, kwamfuta za ta rika danna masa. Sauran bangarorin da ake samun kuɗi daga gare su sun haɗa da barin kuɗi masu yawa a akawun ba tare da an cire ba, da shiga gasa da sauransu.

Bayan waɗannan, akwai tsarin gayyata. Idan mai *Silver* ya yi gayyata, za a ba shi naira dubu biyar da ɗari biyu (₦5,200). Idan *Pro* ne kuma, za a ba shi naira dubu bakwai da ɗari biyu (₦7,200). Garabasar gayyata ana cire su ne a ranakun Litinin da Alhamis

daga karfe tara zuwa goma sha daya na safe (9:00am – 11:00am). Mafi karancin kudin da mutum zai iya cirewa shi ne dubu goma (₦10,000).

C - Tsokaci

Yana da kyau a lura da cewa, *52u* da *Anchor* suna da zubi da tsari ne irin na kasuwancin kan intanet na damfara da suka gudu da kuɗaɗen Hausawa a baya (Misali, Dubai Gold Souk da Insme). Za a iya lura da cewa, duk nau’o’in kasuwancin kan intanet na damfara suna kofarin yin amfani da “yarda” wajen yaudarar mutane. Tsarin gayyata shi ne baban makamamin gina yarda da suka yi amfani da shi.

An lura da cewa, kafafen intanet dīnsu ba sa ɗauke da bayanan da ya kamata kasuwancin gaskiya ya ɗauka. Kafar *52u* (<https://www.52u.today>) kallonta kaɗai zai saka shakku a zuciyar wanda ya san kasuwannin duniyar intanet. Kafar ba ta tsaru ba, ta yadda har hoton shafin farko (homepage background image) ya boye kunshiyar kafar (menu bar).

Hoto Na 5.7: Hoton shafin farko na kafar *52u* ya boye kunshiya (menu)

Madogara: Kafar *52u* (<https://www.52u.today>)

Wani abin da ya kamata Hausawa su yi la'akari da shi, shi ne, duka kafafen biyu ba su da bayanan tuntuba. ko Anchor (<https://anchorit.live>) da ya kawo shafin, lambobin WhatsApp kawai aka sanya guda biyu. Babu adireshin da za a same su, sannan babu imel din kamfani. A duba hoton da yake kasa:

Hoto Na 5.8: Shafin tuntuba na kafar Anchor

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Madogara: An dauko kai tsaye daga shafin tuntuba na Anchor

(<https://anchorit.live/post/contact-us>) (Ranar 2 ga watan Janairu, 2025)

Duka kasuwancin biyu an tsara su bisa wani salon da dorewarsu zai yi wahala. Dalili kuwa shi ne, suna da riba mai yawa wadda ba za a iya gamsasshen bayanin tushensu da dorewarsu ba.

5.4.4 Karya Da Farfaganda Da Batanci

Duk wanda ya dogara da tallace-tallace a kafafen intanet wajen samun kuɗi, to fafutukarsa za ta karkata kan bin matakan kara samun kuɗin shiga. Waɗanda suka dogara a kan tallace-tallacen sun fi mayar da hankali a kan abubuwa guda biyu. Na farko shi ne mabiya (misali *followers* a TikTok ko *subscribers* a YouTube, da makamantansu). Na biyu kuwa shi ne yin tsokaci da jinjina ga abubuwan da mai akawun yake dorawa (*comment and like* waɗanda suke haɗuwa su bayar da abin da ake kira *engagement*).

A kokarin neman mabiya, masu kafa da dama sukan dora bidiyoyi na labaran karya ko farfaganda ko kuma batanci. Ko bayan yin batanci a tsakanin taurarin finafinan Hausa da mawaƙa da ‘yan siyasa, abin ya haɗa har da malaman addini. A taƙaice, akwai *‘yan soshiyal midiya* da suka shahara wajen amfani da miyagun halaye da dabi’u domin samun karin mabiya. Misalan munanan dabi’un sun haɗa da:

- a. Batanci
- b. Cin dunduniya
- c. Gulma
- d. Kazafi
- e. Tsegumi

Dangane da ire-iren waɗannan ne Dan’ido Katsina ya yi tsokaci da cewa:

9. Ga ‘yan siyasa ita midiya ku duba,
Nan ne wurin jawo tsokana da zamba,
Nan ne wurin ce ma gwaninka bai iya ba,
Nan ne wurin nuna abin da bai yi kyau ba,
Nan ne wurin haddasa gardama da gaba,
Dandali ne ake ba na fa’ida ba.
10. Batu na alkairi ba a son azawa,
Batu na sharri shi ne abin gwadawa,
‘Yan mintuka ka gani ya yi zagayawa,
Duk duniya kowa za ya yo ganowa,
Sirrin waninka a nan ka yi bayyanawa,
Babu da-na-sani tun da bai gama ba.

(Dan’iro Katsina: Waƙar Soshiyal Midiya Dandalin Matasa)

A nan Dan’iro Katsina ya nuna yadda kafafen sada zumunta suka zama wurin yada farfaganda da sharri da gulma da batanci. Sau da dama ana yin hakan ne domin samun mabiya a zauruka da shafukan sada zumunta.

5.4.5 Gurbata Kyawawan Al'adu

Daga cikin hanyoyin samun kuɗi da ake da su a kan intanet akwai waɗanda suka shafi ɗora bidiyoyi da sautuka da rubuce-rubuce. Idan aka ɗauki bidiyoyi a matsayin misali, suna iya kasancewa wakoki ko barkwanci ko koyar da wani nau'in al'ada (misali abinci) da makamantansu. Akan samu gurbatar al'adun Hausawa yayin da Hausawa suka yi riƙo da baƙin al'adu a kafafen intanet ko kuma suka gina ƙunshiyar shafukansu a kan munanan al'adu (misali batsa ko batanci da makamantansu). An kawo hakan a waƙar *Soshiyal Midiya* inda ake cewa:

3. A yadƙa alkairi kar a yadƙa zamba,
A nan ake mai da kaɗan ta zamma babba,
A nan ake haddasa ƙi a rai da gaba,
A nan ake tarbiyyar da ban faɗi ba,
A nan ake wargaza tarbiyyar su baba,
Duk a nan midiya in ba kus sani ba.

5. Waɗansu ko lamarin ba ni son tunawa,
Irin abin da idanu suke ganewa,
Waɗansu hoto na tsiraici za su sawa,
A midiya nan ne dandalin gwadawa,
Kowa irin mai halinsa zai kulawa,
Wa ya ce watta rana ba sa haɗe ba?

(Dan'iro Katsina: Waƙar Soshiyal Midiya Dandalin Matasa)

Dokokin addini da al'adun Hausawa sukan yi musu iyakoki a hulɗoɗinsu na kan intanet, kamar yadda ginshikan Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma suka zayyana. Duk da haka, Hausawa sukan ɗauki al'adun wasu al'ummu musamman Turawa da Indiyawa da Larabawa. Mafiya yawan waɗannan al'adu sun ci karo da na Hausawa. Gurbatatun al'adu da ake ɗauka a intanet sun fi shafar halayya da tufafi. Tasirin intanet a kan al'adun Hausawa ya ja hankalin manazarta da marubuta da dama. Daga cikin ciken rubuce-rubucen da suka fito da bayanai game da wannan batu akwai

Magaji (2018) da Almajir (2009) da Shehu & Aliyu (2019) da Shehu & Rambo (2019) da Sani (2022).

Dora ire-iren waɗannan munanan al'adu yana da illa ga Hausa da Hausawa ta fuskoki guda biyu. Da farko yana janyo tabarbarewar tarbiyya a tsakanin al'ummar Hausawa. A yau mata Hausawa masu yawa sun bi sahan dora bidiyoyi a TikTok da sauran kafafe ɗauke da maguzantattun kunshiya. Illa ta biyu kuwa ita ce mummunan wakilcin al'adun Hausawa a idon duniya. Abubuwan da suka bayyana a ire-iren bidiyoyin ga al'ummar duniya, su za su rike a matsayin al'adun Hausawa na hakika.

A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, ayyukan kan intanet irin su fassara da gyaran rubutu sun ba da dama ga waɗanda ba Hausawa ba su wakilci Hausawa. Mutane masu yawa sun yi rajista a matsayin masu fassarar Hausa a kafafen baje kolin fasaha irin su *Proz* da *Translation Directory*. Sau da dama akan ci karo da ayyukan fassara da aka gudanar waɗanda kai tsaye za a fahimci cewa ba Hausawa na hakika ba ne suka yi su. Hakan yakan kai ga samar da gurɓatattun bayanai game da harshe da al'ada da adabin Hausa.

5.5 Matakan Magance Matsalolin Sana'o'i da Kasuwancin Hausawa a Duniyar

Intanet

Kalubale da illolin sana'o'i da kasuwanci na Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba su samu gatan masana da manazarta Hausa ba. Har ya zuwa yau (2024), babu wadatattun binciken ilimi da aka gudanar game da su. Wannan bincike ya fahimce cewa, lallai kalubale da illolin sun kasance *kurar gardi*. Magance su ko shawo kansu ya fi karfin aikin mutum ɗaya. Akwai rawa da ɓangarorin al'umma ya kamata su taka tun daga

kan daidaiƙun mutane da kungiyoyi, har zuwa makarantu da kuma gwamnati kanta. A kasa an tattauna wasu matakan da za su iya taimakawa wajen magance kalubale da illolin da suka dabaibaiye da harkokin sana'o'i da kasuwanci na Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

5.5.1 Gurbin Daidaiƙun Mutane

Hausawa suna da rawar da za su iya takawa a matakin daidaiƙun mutane domin kauce wa wasu daga cikin illoli da kalubalen da suke tattare da sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Daga ciki akwai waƙanda tuni sun kasance jiki. Sun haɗa da matsalar wutar lantarki wadda ake bin yanyoyi irin su neman sola domin cajin kwamfuta da sauran na'urori, ko kuma fawa bank domin cajin waya. Wata hanya kuma ita ce kulla alaƙa da kafe (cafe) mafi kusa.

Matsalar sabis ma abu ne da daidaiƙun mutane ba su da wani babban yunkuri da za su iya yi game da shi. Duk da haka, dabarun rage matsalar sun haɗa da tanadin layukan waya daga kamfanoni sama da ɗaya, misali *Airtel* da *MTN* da *Etisalat* da *Glo*. Gida biyu maganin gobara, yayin da laila ta kiya sai a koma basha.

Bangarorin da fokarin daidaiƙun mutane zai iya samar musu da sauyi sun haɗa da:

A – Koyon Zamanantattun Darrusa

A yau lamarin koyo da koyarwa ya kasance al'amari mai sauƙi. Dangane da al'amura da dama, mutum ba ya buƙatar shiga aji domin a koyar da shi. Tuni kafafen intanet da manhajoji da dama suka kasance makarantu waƙanda a koyausha Hausawa za su iya ziyarta domin kwankwafan ilimi. Hasali ma, da dama daga cikin abubuwan da mutum

zai koya dangane da intanet da na'ura, bincike da kuma yau da gobe ne za su koya masa, ba wani malami a aji ba.

"Idan za a sha giya a sha ta dubu!" Duk wanda ya sa sana'o'i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet a gaba, yana da matuƙar muhimmanci ya yi yunkuri a karan kansa wajen samun cikakken ilimi dangane da harƙallar da yake yi. Hausawa za su iya samun cikakkun bayanan da suke nema ta hanyar:

- i. Bibiyar tashoshi da shafukan da ake koyar da nau'in abin da yake son kwarewa a kai (YouTube da TikTok da Facebook da sauransu)
- ii. Yin rajista da makarantu masu zaman kansu da suke koyar da nau'in ilimin da yake son koya
- iii. Bincike a kafafen intanet da suke dora ire-iren bayanan
- iv. Tattaunawa da ingantattun sakago na kirƙirariyar basira (AI bots)

B – Kiyaye Lafiyar Jiki Da Ta Muhalli

Ya zama dole Hausawa su kiyaye lafiyar jikinsu da ta muhallinsu domin dorewar rayuwa mai inganci. Hakan zai faru ne ta hanyar kauce wa duk wasu abubuwan da sukan iya illata lafiya. Sun hada da:

- i. A guje wa dora kwamfuta a kan cinya yayin da ake aiki da ita, ko wasu na'urorin da suke fitar da tiririn radiyeshin.
- ii. A yi kofarin kauce wa ci-da-zuci da hana rai hutu da zummar kammala aiki. Hakan zai taimaka wajen kauce wa kamuwa da ciwon kai na wucin gadi ko matsananciyar gajiya mai illata jiki.

- iii. Kauce wa harkalloli masu zubi irin na caca wadanda za su kai ga cutuwar kwakwalwa.
- iv. Amfani da dabarar nan ta 20-20-20 domin kauce wa ciwon ido na wucin gadi ko kallo bishi-bishi.²⁴⁹

Wadansu karin hobbasawa da daidaiƙun mutane za su iya yi su ne:

C - Dole ne Hausawa masu harkalla a kan intanet su nakalci matakan kare kai daga damfara kamar yadda aka tattauna a karkashin 5.1.12 a sama.

D - Dole ne Hausawa su yi kokarin sabawa da karɓar sauyi cikin hikima da kwarewa. Daga nan kuma sai su bi hanyoyi da matakan da za su iya sauyawa ko jan hankalin kwastomominsu domin cigabansu da na kasuwancinsu ko harkallolinsu.

E - Yayin da mutum ya kware sosai a fannin da ya ɗauka, zai iya neman tallafi ko haɗin guiwa daga kamfanoni da cibiyoyi daga wurare daban-daban.

F - Kasancewar Ingilishi shi ne babban harshen kasuwanci a duniyar yau, yana da kyau Hausawa masu sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet su nakalci harshen. Akalla ya kasance sun samu ilimin da zai ba su damar fahimtar dokoki da ka'idoji da kuma bayanan kasuwanci da harkalloli da ake rubutawa cikin harshen Ingilishi.

G - Yana da kyau Hausawa su nemi kwarewa a fannin da za a daɗe kafin tasirin zamani ya kashe masa kasuwa. Wadannan su ne ire-iren harkallolin da a nan

²⁴⁹ Wannan hanya ce da masana kiwon lafiya suka samar domin kare ido yayin da ake aikin da ya shafi kallon sikirin. Yadda ake yi shi ne, a duk bayan mintuna ashirin (20) da aka yi ana kallon sikirin, to a kalli wani abu da yake da tazarar kafa ashirin (20) daga wurin da ake. Za a kalle shi ne na kimanin tsawon sakanni ashirin (20). Wannan yana taimakawa wajen wartsakewar ido da hana shi tara gajiya. A duba Marcin (2017).

kusa na'urori da kirkirarrun basira ba za su iya maye gurbin mutanen da suke da kwarewa a fannonin ba.

H – Yana da kyau Hausawa su nuna kishin bunƙasa al'ummarsu da kyawawan al'adunsu. Waƙanda harƙallolinsu suka shafi dora kunshiya a kan intanet (online contents) suna da rawar da za su iya takawa ta hanyar kara bayyana wa duniya haƙiƙanin al'adu da harshe da adabin Hausawa.

5.5.2 Gurbin Iyaye

Iyaye a kasar Hausawa suna da rawar da za su taka a fokarin hada karfi da karfe domin Hausa da Hausawa su hau tudun-na-tsira dangane da gwagwarmayar sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Wannan ya shafi iyayen da 'ya'yansu suke kan turbar sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet, har ma da waƙanda ba su ba. Iyaye za su iya taka rawa ta fuskoki kamar haka:

A – Tarbiyya

Tarbiyya aba ce mai muhimmanci a al'adar Hausawa da addininsu. Takan gyara tsarin rayuwar mutum domin ya zama mai nitsuwa da sanin ya-kamata. Iyaye suna iya mayar da hankali wajen hana 'ya'yansu hulɗa da intanet da na'urori ta fuskokin da hulɗar za ta iya gurbata musu tarbiyya. Bayan jan hankali da addu'a ga yaran nasu, suna iya sanya ido sannan su rika bibiyar yanaye-yanayen hulɗar 'ya'yansu da intanet da na'urori.

Yin irin wannan huɓɓasa zai taimaka wajen fokarin kare tarbiyyar yaran nasu. A bangare ɗaya kuwa, zai kasance ne suna fokarin dakatar da waƙanda suka riga suka

rungumi gurbata tarbiyya a matsayin hanyar tara mabiya a kafon intanet. Dalili kuwa shi ne, raguwar masu bibiyar ire-iren shafukan, shi ne zai rage kimar shafukan tare da kassara manufinsu.

B - Tallafi Da Karfafa Guiwa

Yara suna bukatar tallafi da karfafa guwa daga iyayensu, musamman a kan al'amuran da suka shafi gobensu. Rawar da za su iya takawa a nan ta hada da karfafa wa yaran guiwa da kalamam baki da kuma tallafa musu da kudaden da suke bukata domin fara gudanar da nau'in kasuwancin da suke da kudirin gudanarwa. Yana da kyau iyaye Hausawa su san da wannan, sannan su yi bakin kokarinsu don ganin ba a bar 'ya'yan Hausawa a baya ba.

C - Fadakarwa

Hausawa suna cewa: "Abin da babba ya hango, yaro ko ya hau Dala ba zai iya hangowa ba." Sau da dama yara sukan rungumi wani al'amari da tunanin cewa hanya ce mai bullewa. Wasu sukan yi hakan ba da wani ilimi ba, sai kawai don sun ga wasu sun samu nasara a sanadiyyar nau'in kasuwancin. Sun manta da cewa *idan wani ya yi rawa ya samu kudi, wani in ya yi duka yake sha*. Yayin da tafiya ta yi tafiya, a nan ne take bayyana musu cewa kallon kitse suke yi wa rogo.

Tun farko iyaye suna iya bibiyar muradun 'ya'yansu tare da daidaita musu tunaninsu da fadakar da su yayin da suka yi wani ragon tunani. Haka kuma, suna iya fadakar da su game da taka-tsantsan da duniya da kauce wa tarkon 'yan damfara da kuma riko da gaskiya da amana.

5.5.3 Gurbin Kungiyoyi

Kungiyoyin da suke da alaƙa da harshen Hausa suna da rawar da za su iya takawa domin bunƙasawa da inganta harkokin sana'o'i da kasuwancinsu a duniyar intanet. Yana da kyau dukkannin kungiyoyin Hausa su yi la'akari da *zamananci* da *shirin game duniya* a cikin manufofinsu. Bugu da ƙari, ya kamata su gudanar da kungiyoyin ta la'akari da zamani da ƙoƙarin kawo nau'o'in cigaba da za su taimaki 'yan kungiyar da al'ummar da kuma harshen kansa. Ya kamata ƙoƙarinsu ya mayar da hankali kan cikakken amfani da lokaci domin yin nasara dangane da muradu na gajere da dogon zango.

Kai tsaye suna iya taka rawa ta ɓangarorin da suka haɗa da:

- i. Dangane da matsalar wutar lantarki, suna iya magana da murya ɗaya zuwa ga hukumomi da gwamnatoci domin ingantawa. Haka kuma, suna iya ƙoƙarin samar da wata mafita ta wucin gadi kamar sola a ofishi ko janareta.
 - ii. Kungiya tana iya tara kuɗi ko neman tallafi domin samar wa mambobinta sabis mai ƙarfi. Babban misali a nan shi ne, kungiya tana iya yin rajista domin samun sabis ɗin intanet mai ƙarfi kamar na *Starlink*.²⁵⁰
 - iii. Kungiya tana iya yin tsari mai kyau domin koyar da zamanantattun darussa ga 'ya'yanta, har ma da wasu daga cikin al'umma na kusa da na nesa. Za ta iya yin hakan ta hanyar haɗa kai da masana daga cikinta ko gayyato wasu daga waje.
- Bugu da ƙari, za su iya taimakon yara da matasa 'yan makaranta ta hanyar kai

²⁵⁰ *Starlink* sabis ne na intanet wanda yake tashe yau a duniya. Mallakin kamfanin SpaceX (Space Exploration Technologies Corp.) ne wanda yake karkashin jagorancin Elon Musk. Ya zuwa shekarar 2024, SpaceX sun tura satilayit sama da dubu huɗu (4,000) zuwa sararin samaniya. Suna kuma ƙoƙarin tura ƙarin wasu domin inganta ƙarfin sabis ɗin intanet da suke samarwa a faɗin duniya. Domin ƙarin bayani ana iya duba *eoPortal* (2024) da *Starlink* (2024).

musu ziyarar wayar da kai da shirya musu azuzuwa na musamman a lokacin hutu.

- iv. Kungiyoyi daban-daban suna iya haɗa kai wajen tura kokensu ga gwamnati dangane da wasu takunkumai da suka fahimci ba za su haifar da ɗa mai ido ba.
- v. Kungiyoyi suna iya faɗakar da mambobinsu da kuma al'umma dangane da abubuwa da dama masu alaƙa da sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Daga cikinsu akwai matakan kare muhalli da lafiyar jiki da na kauce wa faɗawa homar 'yan damfara. Za su iya yin hakan ta hanyar tarurruka da rubuce-rubuce a kafafen sada zumunta da kafafen intanet da kuma shirye-shirye a kafafen watsa labarai.
- vi. Bunkasa al'ada da adabi da harshen Hausa yana daga cikin manufofin kusan dukkannin kungiyoyin Hausa. Yana da kyau a yau su bi zamanantattun hanyoyi domin gudanar da wannan aikin. Sun haɗa da buɗe kafafen intanet domin samar da kyakkyawa kuma tsaftatatten wakilci ga Hausa da Hausawa. Wani abu kuma shi ne kara huɓɓasa wajen faɗakar da yara da matasa domin rungumar sana'o'i da rage zaman banza. Raguwar zaman banza zai taimaka wajen rage ayyukan assha da suke da alaƙa da duniyar intanet.

5.5.4 Gurbin Makarantu Da Cibiyoyin Bincike

Sashe-sashen nazarin Hausa a jami'o'i da manyan makarantu da kuma cibiyoyin bincike su ne suke kan gaba ta fuskar faɗa-a-ji game da abubuwan da suka shafi nazarin Hausa. Suna iya taka rawa a dukkannin bangarorin da aka lissafa a farkashin 4.5.3 da yake sama. Ko bayan waɗancan, suna da muhimman bangarori da za su iya bayar da gudummawa. Sun haɗa da:

A – Samar Da Babbar Kungiya

Har ya zuwa yau, duk wani yunkuri na samar da babbar kungiya ko wata cibiya da ta hada dukkannin sashe-sashe da cibiyoyin nazarin Hausa yana tattare da kalubale. A shekarar 2024 an sabunta wannan yunkuri a lokacin wani taron kara wa juna sani na kasa da kasa da aka gudanar a Jami'ar Ahmadu Bello da take Zariya. An yi kokarin zaɓen sababbin shuwagabanni da za su jagoranci Kungiyar Hausa.²⁵¹ A duba hoto da yake kasa:

Hoto Na 5.9: Sababbin shuwagabannin Kungiyar Hausa da aka zaɓa ranar 30/10/2024

- unanimously nominates and approves an interim committee for the resuscitation of the professional association- **HAUSA STUDIES** as follows:
 - 1) Prof. Hafizu Miko Yakasai, Bayero University, Kano Chairman
 - 2) Prof. Salisu Garba Kargi, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria;
 - 3) Prof. Aliyah Adamu, Sokoto State University, Sokoto;
 - 4) Dr. Hauwa Muhammad Bugaje, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria;
 - 5) Dr. Hassan Usman Gadaka, Umar Sulaiman College of Education, Gashua;
 - 6) Dr. Aliyu Isa Sulaiman, Kaduna State University, Kaduna;
 - 7) Dr. Auwal Abdullahi Salisu, Kano State Secondary Education Board, Kano;
 - 8) Dr. Mustafa Wali Sambo, AlQalam University, Katsina; and
 - 9) Dr. Muhammad Sulaiman Abdullahi, Bayero University, Kano;

Dr Shuaibu Hassan,
Head of Department

Prof. Salisu Garba,
LOC, Chairman

Mal. Abubakar Sarki Muhammad
Secretary, Communique Committee

Madogara: Takardar rahoton taron Kasa Da Kasa Na Kara Wa Juna Sani Game Da Harsunan Afirka, wanda aka gudanar ranar 29 – 30 ga watan Oktoba ta shekarar 2024 a Jami'ar Ahmadu Bello, Zariya²⁵²

²⁵¹ M.S. Wali (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 24 ga watan Disamba 2024)

²⁵² A duba Department of African Languages and Cultures, Ahmadu Bello University (2024)

Akwai bukatar karfafa wannan yunkuri domin kafa fungiyar da za ta zama uwa ga dukkannin masana da manazarta Hausa. Karfin fada-a-jin da za ta samu zai taimaka ta fuskoki da dama da suka hada da:

- i. Za ta iya magana a gwamnati dangane da wasu hukunce-hukunce ko ka'idojin da suke da illa ga Hausa da Hausawa.²⁵³ Bugu da kari, suna iya tura bukatur samun damarmakin da za su iya bunkasa Hausa, musamman ta fannonin da suka shafi sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.
- ii. Za ta samar da hanya mafi sauƙi na yanke hukunci dangane da wasu abubuwan da suke da ruƙani ko janyo sabani a nazarin Hausawa. Sun hada da fassarar kalmomin fannu da abin da ya shafi hanyoyin gudanar da bincike da ka'idojin rubutu da sauransu. Ta haka ne kuma za a samu hanya mafi sauƙi na yanke hukunci game da matakan da za su taimaka wajen inganta lamuran da suka shafi sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

B – Zamanantar Da Harkokin Koyo Da Koyarwa

Ko da ma dai, sabon tsarin koyarwar da aka kawo na *Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS)* ya mayar da hankali sosai a kan zamanantar da harkokin koyo da koyarwa.²⁵⁴ Akwai bukatar sashe-sashen nazarin Hausa da kuma cibiyoyin bincike su yi amfani da wannan dama domin sanya zamanantattun kwasakwasai waƙanda za su taimaki dalibai a gwagwarmayar sana'o'i da kasuwanci na duniyar intanet. Wani abin da zai kara taimakawa shi ne rage ba da karfi a kan

²⁵³ Misalansu sun hada da mayar da darasin Hausa na zaƙi a makarantun sakandare. Wani misalin shi ne tilasta wa masu son karantar Hausa a jami'o'i zana Adabin Ingilishi (English Literature) a jarabawar JAMB (Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board).

²⁵⁴ A duba NUC (2022).

haddace batutuwa. A maimakon haka, a himmatu kan gina tunanin dalibai da koya musu dabarun amfani da fikira da basira wajen fara ayyukan dogaro da kai.²⁵⁵

5.5.5 Gurbin Gwamnati

Gwamnati ita ce uwa uba a duk wani cigaba ko sauyi da za a iya samu. Ita take fitar da dokoki tare da zartar da su dangane da fannonin rayuwa daban-daban, ciki kuwa har da lamuran da suka shafi ilimi. Kyawawa kuma tsararrun dokoki suna da matuƙar muhimmanci, wanda ko a Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma sun kasance ginshiki na farko. Da goyon gwamnati ne kawai za a iya samun sauyi mai amfani da zai kai ga bunkasar hanyoyin dogaro da kai na zamani. Gwamnati tana da muhimman rawa da za ta iya takawa da suka haɗa da:

- i. Gwamnati za ta iya mayar da hankali kan inganta wutar lantarki tare da fito da tsare-tsare da za su ba wa kananan sana'o'i damar samun intanet mai inganci. Wannan zai taimaka musamman a masu harkokin da suka shafi sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Haka kuma, za ta iya kara mayar da hankali a kan tallafa wa masu kananan sana'o'i da suke da alaƙa da sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.
- ii. Gwamnati za ta iya ci gaba da haɗa kai da manazarta da makarantu domin kara zamanantar da kwasa-kwasai. Hakan zai tabbatar da ana yaye dalibai masu wayewar kai game da hanyoyin dogaro da kai a zamanance. Haka kuma, tana iya fitar da shirye-shirye a gidajen rediyo da kafafen talabajinin da

²⁵⁵ Kasashen da suka ci gaba sun fi mayar da hankali a kan bunkasa basirar kirƙira sama da haddace batutuwa da bayanai. Hasali ma, akwai masana da suke kalubalantar tsarin jarabawa a makarantu. Suna da fahimtar cewa, jarabawa ba ta kara komai face taƙaita tunanin dalibai zuwa ga ƙoƙarin cin jarabawa a maimakon fahimtar kwas da amfani da hikimomin da suke cikinsa domin inganta rayuwa. Domin ƙarin bayani, ana iya duba Pantami (2022) da Stellar (2022).

tarurrukan kara wa juna sani masu manufar cusa wa mutane dabi'ar son karbar sauyi. A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, wannan yunkuri zai iya ɗaukar manufar faɗakarwa da koyar da hanyoyi da matakan kauce wa matsalolin da suke tattare da biɗa a duniyar intanet. Matsalolin sun haɗa da waɗanda suke illata lafiya da muhalli da fuskantar damfara da kuma abubuwan da suka shafi gurɓacewar al'adun ɗa'a da mutunci.

- iii. Wani babban gudummawa da gwamnati za ta iya bayarwa shi ne tabbatar da janye duk waɗansu takunkumai marasa kwaɗkwaran tushe waɗanda suke dakusar da harkokin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.

5.6 Naɗewa

Duk da ɗimbin alfanun da suke tattare da harkokin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet, lallai suna dabaibaye da wasu illoli da kalubale waɗanda suka keɓanta ga Hausawa da waɗanda suke gama-gari. Illolin kuwa sukan shafi lafiyar jiki da kwaɗwalwa da muhalli, har ma da zamantakewa. Waɗannan matsaloli ba za a iya shawo kansu ba har sai an samu sa hannun ɓangarorin al'umma daban-daban. Sun haɗa da ɗaiɗaikun mutane da iyaye da ƙungiyoyin ɗalibai da manazarta Hausa da kuma makarantu da cibiyoyin bincike, har ma da gwamnati kanta. Gyaruwar lamura a wannan fannin abu ne da zai yi matuƙar taimakawa. Ko bayan kare kyawawan al'adu, za a samu ayyukan yi da raguwar zaman banza. Hakan kuwa zai samar da bunƙasar tattalin arziki da raguwar ƙanana da manyan laifuka da kuma cigaban ƙasa baki ɗaya.

BABI NA SHIDA

KAMMALAWA

6.1 Takaitawa

Intanet ya samu ne a shekarar 1983. Samuwar kafafen intanet ya zo da wani juyin-juya-hali a kusan dukkanin al'amuran duniya, ciki har da Hausawa. Tuni duniya ta karkata a kan amfani da intanet domin gudanar da al'amuran yau da kullum. Daga ciki kuwa har da abubuwan da suka shafi:

- a. Addini
- b. Ilimi
- c. Kiwon lafiya
- d. Shugabanci
- e. Siyasa
- f. Tattalin arziki

Tafiya ta yi tafiya inda duniyar intanet ta kasance wata duniya ta daban da take buƙatar wakilcin Hausa da Hausawa. Harkokin tattalin arziki masu yawa da suka shafi sana'o'i da kasuwanci sun koma kan intanet. Abin har ya kai ga an samu kasuwanni daban-daban a kan intanet waƙanda Hausawa suka fara shiga ana damawa da su. A cikinsu ana hadahadar saye da sayarwa tamkar yadda ake yi a duniyar zahiri. Wannan kuwa ya shafi har da hadahadar kuɗaɗen intanet.

A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, an samu sauye-sauye ta fuskar ayyuka a duniya. Shigowar intanet ya buɗe ƙofar gudanar da ayyuka masu yawa a kan intanet. Nau'o'in ayyukan da ake gudanarwa a duniyar intanet waƙanda suka shafi Hausawa sun haɗa da:

- a. Baje haja/koli

- b. Bincike
- c. Dillanci
- d. Gyaran hotuna da na'urori
- e. Hadahdar kufade da kadarorin intanet
- f. Intanet da na'urori
- g. Kimiyyar harshe
- h. Tallace-tallace

Duk waɗannan sun samar da wani sabon babi tare da kafa ayar tambaya game da alkiblar kasuwanci a duniya. Dole ne Hausawa su yi la'akari da alkiblar kasuwancin duniya domin su ma su taka kyakkyawar rawan kidan zamani. Wani abin da ya kamata a mayar da hankali kansa kuma shi ne, da dama daga cikin ayyukan kan intanet ɗin suna da alaƙa da al'ada. Misali ayyukan da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe kamar fassara da fassaran kan sikirin, duk suna da alaƙa ta kai tsaye da al'ada. Haka abin yake dangane da tsarawa da gyaran bidiyoyi da hotuna, ko kuma ɗora ƙunshiya (content) a kan kafafen intanet a matsayin hanyar neman kuɗi. A taƙaice ke nan, al'amari ne wanda yake buƙatar Hausawa su shiga ciki a dama da su domin bayar da kyakkyawan wakilci ga al'adu da harshe da adabinsu.

Waɗannan dalilai da sauran makamantansu su suka haifar da kafa harsashen binciken. An gina shi bisa manufar nazartar damarmakin da Hausawa suke da shi waɗanda suka shafi neman kuɗi a duniyar intanet tare da nazartar ƙalubale da matsalolin da suke tattare da su don a samu hanyoyin mancewa. Cimma wannan manufa zai haska damarmaki da buɗe wa Hausawa hanyoyin shiga a dama da su a

harkokin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Hakan kuwa zai rage rashin aikin yi tare da inganta tattalin arziki. Bugu da ƙari, zai taimaka wajen kare kyawawan al'adun Hausawa.

An dade ana bincike dangane da sana'o'i da kasuwanci a fannoni daban-daban a duniya. An gudanar da bincike masu yawa a farfajiyar nazarin Hausa (kamar na Aliyu, 2018 da Asiru, 2009 da CMG Hausa, 2022 da Muryar Hausa²⁴ Online Media, 2020 da Musa & Yusuf, 2019 da Nasir, 2021 da Rimmer et al., 1985 da Saleeman & Adamu, 2022 da Sallau, 2000 da Sani et al., 2023 da sauransu). A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, an gudanar da bincike da dama dangane da duniyar intanet a cikin harsuna daban-daban. A shekarun baya-bayan nan, ana samun ƙaruwan rubuce-rubucen ilimi dangane da lamuran da suka shafi duniyar intanet (kamar na Abubakar, 2007 da Almajir, 2008 da Ashiru, 2012 da BBC Hausa, 2010 da CMG Hausa, 2022 da Gana, 2020 da Makuwana, 2011 da Mukoshy, 2016 da Sani, 2022 da Sani et al., 2023 da sauransu). Wani abin lura shi ne, duk da rubuce-rubucen da aka yi dangane da kasuwanci da sana'i da sauran hanyoyin sana'o'i da kasuwanci, ba a samu cikakken binciken ilimi dangane da damarmakin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet waɗanda Hausawa suke da su ba. Ko binciken Jibril (2023), ya takaita ne kawai a kan hanyoyin mata 'yan kasuwa musamman a Kano suke bi domin tallata hajarsu a kan WhatsApp da Instagram. Wannan bincike ya yi bakin ƙoƙari wajen cike giɓin ta hanyar kawo muhimman bayanai da suka shafi:

- a. sana'o'i da kasuwancin da Hausawa suke gudanarwa a duniyar intanet da

- b. damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su na wasu nau'oin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a kan intanet da
- c. kalubale da illolin da suke dabaibaye harkokin, da kuma
- d. hanyoyin da matakan magance kalubale da illolin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.

An dora aikin a kan Ra'in Tsarin Zamantakewar Al'umma (Institutional Theory). Ra'in ya tallafi aikin wajen nazartar yadda dokokin gwamnati da kuma al'adu da ra'ayoyin Hausawa suke tasiri a kan sana'o'insu da kasuwancinsu na kan intanet. Haka kuma, dokokin gwamnati da tanade-tanaden al'adu suna tasiri kan damarmakin sana'o'in da Hausawa suke da su na kasuwanci a kan intanet. Duk kasuwar da ba ta dace da tanade-tanaden al'ada da addinin Hausawa ba, takan kasance abar tsangwama a cikin al'umma.

Duk da an takaita farfajiyar binciken zuwa sana'o'i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet, bagiren ya kasance mai faɗi. Hakan ya sa an yi amfani da dabarun gudanar da bincike daban-daban domin cin nasarar tattara bayanai da kwankwance su domin samar da ingantaccen sakamako. An gina binciken a kan tsarin Nazarin Al'adu a Duniyar Intanet (Digital Ethnography). Dabarun tattara bayani da aka yi amfani da su, su ne 'halarta da sa ido' (participant observation) wanda ta haka ne aka samu bayanai tare da fahimtar al'adu da yanaye-yanayen wasu lamura da suka shafi sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Sauran hanyoyin sun hada da hira da wasu mutane na musamman da kuma karance-karance.

Ta bin wadannan hanyoyin tattara bayanai tare da taimakon ra'o'in da aka dora aikin a kai, binciken ya yi nasarar:

- a. Bayani dangane da sana'o'i da kasuwanci a bagiren tattalin arziki, a duniyar zahiri da duniyar intanet
- b. Bitar ayyukan da aka gudanar wafanda suke da alaka da sana'o'i da kasuwanci ko Hausa da Hausawa a duniyar intanet
- c. Kawo jerin nau'o'in ayyuka da sauran harkokin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet wafanda Hausawa za su iya cin gajiyarsu
- d. Kawo bayanai game da abubuwan da ake bukata domin samun nasara a fannin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet
- e. Tattauna kalubale da illolin da suke dabaibaiye da harkokin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet, musamman wafanda suka shafi Hausawa da kasar Hausa
- f. Gabatar da rawar da bangarorin al'umma daban-daban (daidaike mutane da iyaye da kungiyoyi da makarantu da cibiyoyin bincike da gwamnati) za su iya takawa domin shawo kan kalubale da illolin da suka shafi sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet

6.2 Sakamakon Bincike

Bayan tattara bayanai masu alaka da binciken tare da kwankwance su, binciken ya gano abubuwan da kai tsaye suka bayar da damar cimma maƙasudansa. Muhimman abubuwan da binciken ya gano su ne:

Tambayar Bincike ta 1: Waɗanne nau’o’in sana’o’i da kasuwancin kan intanet ne Hausawa suka runguma a yau?

Tuni Hausawa suka fara yin nisa a fannin sana’o’i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Suna gudanar da nau’o’in kasuwanci da kwadago da tanadin kuɗi da kadarorin intanet daban-daban a mata kai daban-daban. Akwai Hausawa masu yawa da suka yi rajista a matsayin ma’aikata a kan intanet. Sukan samu ayyuka a fannonin da suka kware kamar fassara ko gyaran rubutu ko gina kafafen intanet da sauransu. Haka kuma Hausawa masu yawa sun rungumi harkar kuɗin intanet a yau. Abin ya kai ga har kafafe irin su Paxful sun fassara dukkannin muhimman sakonninsu zuwa Hausa domin kara ba wa Hausawa damar kasuwanci ba tare da tasgaro ba. Wani fannin da Hausawa suka fara yin nisa a kai shi ne buɗe kafafen intanet da tashoshi da zauruka a shafukan sada zumunta. Hakan yana ba su damar ɗora tallace-tallace domin samun kuɗaden shiga.

Tambayar Bincike ta 2: Waɗanne abubuwa ake buƙata domin cin gajiyyar damarmakin sana’o’i da kasuwanci da ake da su a duniyar intanet?

Akwai abubuwa masu yawa da Hausawa suke buƙata domin cin gajiyyar damarmakin da ake da su na sana’o’i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Abubuwan da ake buƙata suna iya mambanta kasancewar sun danganta da nau’o’in harkallolin da aka saka a gaba. Gama-gari daga cikinsu su ne na’ura mai inganci da intanet mai sauri da wutar lantarki da kwarewa a fannin da aka ɗauka da sanuwa a kafafen intanet. Wasu ƙarin abubuwan da ake buƙata su ne naƙaltar harshen kasuwanci da kwarewa a kan na’urorin da suka shafi aikin da mutum yake gudanarwa (misali, injunan fassara ga mai aikin fassara a kan intanet). Haɗa waɗannan abubuwa da amfani da su yadda ya

kamata zai ba wa mutum damar karɓar ayyuka a kan intanet domin samun kuɗaɗen halal masu kauri ba tare da baƙar wahala ba.

Tambayar Bincike ta 3: Waɗanne kalubale ne suka dabaibaye lamarin sana’o’i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet?

Binciken ya gano cewa, duk da tarin alfanu da sauƙi da kuma cigaba da harkokin sana’o’i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet suke tattare da su, suna dabaibaye da wasu kalubale da kuma illoli. Kalubalen sun shafi abubuwan da suke kawo tasgaro ga harkar sana’o’i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet. Daga cikin waɗanda suka shafi Hausawa akwai matsalar wutar lantarki da ta sabis ɗin intanet da na harshen intanet da harshen kasuwancin kan intanet da makamantansu. A ɓangare ɗaya kuwa, illolin da suke tattare da sana’o’i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet sun shafi matsalolin da harkokin suke haifarwa. Misalansu sun haɗa da illata lafiya da muhalli da gurbata al’adu. Sanin ire-iren kalubale da matsalolin nan da suke tattare da harkokin sana’o’i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet zai taimaka wa masu son fara harkokin, “sanin ruwa, fid da kai.”

Tambayar Bincike ta 4: Waɗanne mataƙai ne za a iya bi domin shawo kan kalubalen da suka dabaibaye sana’o’i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet?

Daga ƙarshe, binciken ya zaƙulo wasu hanyoyin da Hausawa za su iya bi domin shawo kan kalubale da illolin da suke tattare da harkokin sana’o’i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. An fahimci cewa, rukunonin al’umma daban-daban suna da rawar da za su iya takawa game da hakan. Yayin da ɗaɗaɗaƙun mutane da iyaye za su iya taka rawa a matakinsu, ƙungiyoyin Hausawa za su iya taimakon mambobinsu har ma da wasu daban daga cikin al’umma. Makarantu da hukumomi kuwa za su iya taka rawa ta fuskoki da dama da suka haɗa har da faɗakar da al’umma da koyar da zamanantattun

darussa da jan hankalin gwamnati da sauransu. Gwamnati kuwa tana da gifi mai muhimmanci da za ta iya cikewa ta hanyar bayar da tallafi ta fuskoki daban-daban da inganta harkokin da kuma tabbatar da sanya dokoki da tsare-tsare waƙanda za su saukafa harkokin sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.

6.3 Shawarwari

A karkashin 6.2 da yake sama, an kawo sakamakon wannan bincike waƙanda kai tsaye suka shafi makasudan binciken guda huɗu (4). A wannan bangaren kuma (6.3) za a mayar da hankali ne a kan bayar da wasu shawarwari da binciken ya tanada bayan zurfafa nazari.

Tambayar Bincike ta 1: Waƙanne nau'o'in sana'o'i da kasuwancin kan intanet ne Hausawa suka runguma a yau?

A babi na huɗu (4), karkashin (4.1 zuwa 4.2.2), an kawo jerin damarmakin da Hausawa suke da su na cin gajiyar sana'o'i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Yana da kyau Hausawa su yi amfani da waƙannan kyawawan damarmaki. Shiga a dama da su a wannan bagire zai ba su damar samun ayyukan yi da bunkasa tattalin arzikinsu tare da samar da kyakkyawan wakilci a duniyar intanet. Wakilcin da za su samar a duniyar intanet kuwa zai taimaka wajen kare al'adunsu har ma da harshe da adabinsu. A bangare ɗaya kuwa, zai taimaka wajen kara buɗe kofofin damarmaki Hausawa. Hakan zai faru ne yayin da duniya ta sake lura da mamayar Hausa da tilascin damawa da Hausawa domin yawansu da tasirinsu a duniyar intanet.

Tambayar Bincike ta 2: Waɗanne abubuwa ake bukata domin cin gajiyyar damarmakin sana’o’i da kasuwanci da ake da su a duniyar intanet?

A babi na biyar (5), karkashin (5.1.1 zuwa 5.1.11), an kawo wasu jerin abubuwan da Hausawa suke bukata domin cin gajiyyar damarmakin sana’o’i da kasuwanci a duniyar intanet. Yana da kyau Hausawa su hobbasa domin amfani da wannan dama. Za su iya yin hakan ta hanyar neman ilimin da kwarewar da ake bukata (misali, koyon nau’in aikin kan intanet da sanin na’urori da fahimtar harshen kasuwanci). Haka kuma, ya kamata su jajirce kan riƙo da gaskiya da amana da mutunta lokaci yayin hulɗar kasuwancin. Bugu da ƙari, yana da kyau su jajirce wajen gina kansu a duniyar intanet (online presence).

Tambayar Bincike ta 3: Waɗanne ƙalubale ne suka dabaibaye lamarin sana’o’i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet?

Yana da kyau Hausawa su naƙalci ƙalubale da illolin da suke tattare da harkokin sana’o’i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet kafin su yanke hukuncin farawa. Hakan ne kaɗai zai tsiratar da su daga faɗawa cikin matsalolin. Dole ne mai ƙoƙarin fara harkar ya cire kasala sannan ya nazarci matakan gudanarwa da dokoki da ƙa’idoji da kuma matakan kare kai daga damfara. Haka kuma, yana da muhimmanci ya sami ilimin matakan kiyaye lafiyarsa da na muhallinsa domin samun amincin rayuwa.

Tambayar Bincike ta 4: Waɗanne mataakai ne za a iya bi domin shawo kan ƙalubalen da suka dabaibaye sana’o’i da kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet?

Domin samun cigaban zamani mai dorewa, lallai akwai bukatar haɗa ƙarfe da ƙarfe tsakanin rukunonin al’umma. Akwai bukatar kowa ya taka rawar da ta kamace shi domin samar da cigaban da ake muradi. Ko da daidaiƙun mutane sun yi bakin

kofarinsu, ba za a iya samun nasarorin da suka kamata ba face sai da sa hannun sauran rukunonin al'umma. A bisa haka:

- a. Yana da kyau a sami haɗin kai tsakanin gwamnati da makarantu da hukumomin bincike da kuma ƙungiyoyi domin magance matsaloli da kalubalen da suka shafi sana'o'i da kasuwancin duniyar intanet.
- b. Yana da kyau Hausawa a kowane mataki su tuna cewa, su ne kaɗai za su iya tashi su kare al'adunsu da harshensu da adabinsu. A bisa haka, ya kyautu a sami haɗin kai tsakanin sashe-sashen nazarin Hausa da cibiyoyin bincike da kuma ɗaɗaɗaikun mutane domin yin aiki tukuru a wannan fannin cigaban zamani.
- c. Yana da kyau a tuna cewa, cigaba da sauye-sauyen zamani ba za su jira kowane mutum ko wani harshe ba. Ya rage ga Hausawa su shiga sahan *gudun ya da kanin wani* da ake yi, ko kuma su yi sakaci duniya ta yi gaba ta bar su a baya. Akwai bukatar Hausawa su zabura da wuri domin 'da zafi-zafi ake dukan ƙarfe.' Ko da Hausa ta taka rawar gani a duniyar zahiri, a yanzu zamani ya zo inda gasa ta koma duniyar intanet. Shi kuwa zamni "riga ce."

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KAFAFEN DA AKA ZIYARTA

Yayin gudanar da wannan bincike, an ziyarci kafafen intanet daban-daban domin tattara bayanai. Kafafen intanet da aka ziyarta waɗanda aka ambata a cikin aikin a matsayin misalai su ne:

1. 52u - <https://www.52u.today>
2. A.Y.M. Shafa Holdings Limited - <https://aymshafaholdings.com/>
3. Access Bank - <https://www.accessbankplc.com>
4. Adobe Express - <https://www.adobe.com/express>
5. Adobe Photoshop - <https://www.adobe.com/products/photoshop.html>
6. Adobe Premiere Pro - <https://www.adobe.com/products/premiere.html>
7. Adobe Stock - <https://stock.adobe.com>
8. Affinity Photo - <https://affinity.serif.com/photo/>
9. AfterAcademy - <https://afteracademy.com/blog/What-are-the-different-types-of-network>
10. Alamy - <https://www.alamy.com>
11. Alibaba - <https://www.alibaba.com>
12. Amazon - <https://www.amazon.com>
13. Ambient (TBA) - <https://ambient.finance>
14. AMLAS Data - <https://app.amlasdata.com.ng>
15. Amsoshi - <https://www.amsoshi.com/>
16. Anchor - <https://anchorit.live>
17. Andovar - <https://www.andovar.com/>
18. AOL Search - <https://search.aol.com>
19. Ask.com - <https://www.ask.com>
20. AT&T Internet Speed Test - www.att.com/support/speedtest
21. Atlas.ti - <https://atlasti.com>
22. Baidu - <https://www.baidu.com>
23. Bakandamiya - <https://bakandamiya.com/>
24. Bayan-Tech - <https://bayan-tech.com/>

25. Belden - <https://www.belden.com/blogs/network-types>
26. Binance - <https://www.binance.com/>
27. Bing - <https://www.bing.com>
28. Bing Translator - <https://www.bing.com/translator>
29. Bitcoin (BTC) - <https://bitcoin.org>
30. Cal Interpreting & Translations (CIT) - <https://calinterpreting.com/>
31. Cambly - <https://cambly.com>
32. Canva - <https://www.canva.com>
33. CapCut - <https://www.capcut.com/>
34. Cetus - <https://www.cetus.zone>
35. Clipchamp - <https://www.clipchamp.com>
36. Crowdin - <https://crowdin.com/>
37. Crypto - <https://crypto.com/>
38. Dangote Sugar - <https://dangote.com/our-business/sugar-refining/>
39. Datamundi - <https://www.datamundi.be/cms/>
40. db Group - <http://www.dbgroupintl.com/>
41. Dreamstime - <https://www.dreamstime.com>
42. DuckDuckGo - <https://duckduckgo.com>
43. EA Language Solutions - <http://www.ealanguagesolutions.com/>
44. Ecobank - <https://www.ecobank.com>
45. Encyclopedia Britannica - <https://www.britannica.com/>
46. Ethereum Classic (ETC) - <https://ethereumclassic.org>
47. Etsy - <https://www.etsy.com>
48. Facebook - <https://www.facebook.com>
49. Fast.com - <www.fast.com>
50. Filmora - <https://filmora.wondershare.com/>
51. Final Cut Pro - <https://www.apple.com/final-cut-pro>
52. First Bank Nigeria - <https://www.firstbanknigeria.com>
53. Fiverr - <https://www.fiverr.com>
54. Flowdiary - <https://flowdiary.com.ng>
55. Foap - <https://www.foap.com>

56. Fotor - <https://www.fotor.com>
57. Freelancer - <https://www.freelancer.com>
58. Gate - <https://www.gate.io/>
59. Getty Images - <https://www.gettyimages.com>
60. GIMP (GNU Image Manipulation Program) - <https://www.gimp.org/>
61. Google - <https://www.google.com>
62. Google Fiber Speed Test - <http://speed.googlefiber.net/>
63. Google Forms - <https://forms.google.com>
64. Google Translate - <https://translate.google.com>
65. GTBank - <https://www.gtbank.com>
66. Guru - <https://www.guru.com>
67. Hausa Dictionary - http://hausadictionary.com/Main_Page
68. Hausa Wikipedia - https://ha.wikipedia.org/wiki/Babban_shafi
69. Hikaya Bakandamiya - <https://hikaya.bakandamiya.com/>
70. IM Translator - <https://imtranslator.net/>
71. iMovie - <https://www.apple.com/imovie/>
72. info.cern.ch - <http://info.cern.ch>
73. InShot - <https://inshot.com>
74. Instagram - <https://www.instagram.com>
75. iPiccy - <https://ipiccy.com>
76. iTalki - <https://italki.com>
77. Javatpoint - <https://www.javatpoint.com/types-of-computer-network>
78. Jiji - <https://jiji.ng>
79. Jumia - <https://www.jumia.com>
80. Kajabi - <https://kajabi.com>
81. Kapwing - <https://www.kapwing.com>
82. KineMaster - <https://www.kinemaster.com/>
83. KUCOIN - <https://www.kucoin.com/>
84. Kuda - <https://kuda.com>
85. Lanfrica (HausaMT) - <https://lanfrica.com>
86. LayerZero (TBA) - <https://layerzero.network>

87. LearnWorlds - <https://learnworlds.com>
88. Lightworks - <https://lwks.com/>
89. Lingoda - <https://lingoda.com>
90. LinkedIn - <https://www.linkedin.com>
91. Litecoin (LTC) - <https://litecoin.org>
92. Maguzawa - <http://maguzawa.dyndns.ws/>
93. Makarantar Hausa - <https://www.makarantarhaus.com/>
94. Marginfi (MRGN) - <https://marginfi.com>
95. Mars Translation - <https://www.marstranslation.com>
96. Masakhane (NLP Project) - <https://www.masakhane.io>
97. memoQ - <https://www.memoq.com/>
98. Meteor by OpenSignal - <https://www.opensignal.com/apps>
99. Misau Model Academy - <https://misaumodel.com.ng>
100. Monero (XMR) - <https://www.getmonero.org>
101. MyMemory Translation - <https://mymemory.translated.net>
102. National Open University (NOUN) – Nijeriya - <https://nou.edu.ng>
103. Nile Bridge - <http://nilebridge.com/docs/index.php>
104. NVivo - <https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo>
105. OKX - <https://www.okx.com/>
106. OKX Yield Aggregator - <https://www.okx.com>
107. One Hour Translation - www.onehourtranslation.com
108. Outschool - <https://outschool.com>
109. Packy Caruso – Language & Communication Services - <https://packycaruso.weebly.com/>
110. PancakeSwap - <https://pancakeswap.finance>
111. Paxful - <https://www.paxful.com>
112. PeoplePerHour - <https://www.peopleperhour.com>
113. Photopea - <https://www.photopea.com>
114. PhotoScape X - <http://x.photoscape.org/>
115. Phrase - <https://phrase.com/>
116. Pixlr - <https://pixlr.com>

117. Podia - <https://podia.com>
118. Preply - <https://preply.com>
119. R - <https://www.r-project.org>
120. Rano Rice Mill - <https://aarano.org.ng/>
121. Ravencoin (RVN) - <https://ravencoin.org>
122. Raydium - <https://raydium.io>
123. Renzo (REZ) - <https://renzoprotocol.com>
124. Router-Switch - <https://www.router-switch.com/>
125. Sawa Tech - <https://sawa-tech.com/>
126. Shotcut - <https://shotcut.org/>
127. Shutterstock - <https://www.shutterstock.com>
128. Skillshare - <https://skillshare.com>
129. SMT Academy - <https://smtacademy.org/index.html>
130. SmugMug - <https://www.smugmug.com>
131. Snapseed - <https://snapseed.online/>
132. Spectrum Speed Test - www.spectrum.com/internet/speed-test
133. Speedtest by Ookla - www.speedtest.net
134. SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) - <https://www.ibm.com/spss>
135. Stars 21 - <https://www.stars21.com/>
136. Stata - <https://www.stata.com>
137. Sterling Bank - <https://sterling.ng>
138. SUN.io - <https://sun.io>
139. SurveyMonkey - <https://www.surveymonkey.com>
140. TaskRabbit - <https://www.taskrabbit.com>
141. Teachable - <https://teachable.com>
142. Thinkific - <https://thinkific.com>
143. TikTok - <https://www.tiktok.com/@hydarfx>
144. TMS - <http://gt.gotransparent.com/>
145. Translated - <https://www.translated.net>
146. Translation 2 - <https://translation2.paralink.com>
147. UBA - <https://www.ubagroup.com>

148. Udemy - <https://udemy.com>
149. Uniswap - <https://uniswap.org>
150. Upwork - <https://www.upwork.com>
151. VEED.io - <https://www.veed.io>
152. Verbling - <https://verbling.com>
153. VIPKid - <https://vipkid.com>
154. VSCO - <https://vSCO.co/>
155. WikiHausa - <https://wikihaus.com.ng>
156. Wirestock - <https://www.wirestock.io>
157. Wordfast - <https://www.wordfast.net/>
158. Wormhole (Wormhole Token) - <https://wormhole.com>
159. Xfinity Speed Test - <https://speedtest.xfinity.com/>
160. Yahoo - <https://www.yahoo.com>
161. Yandex - <https://www.yandex.com>
162. YouTube - <https://www.youtube.com>
163. Zcash (ZEC) - <https://z.cash>
164. Zenfolio - <https://www.zenfolio.com>
165. Zenith Bank - <https://www.zenithbank.com>
166. zkSync (ZKS) - <https://zksync.io>

RATAYE

Wannan ɓangare na rataye yana ɗauke da hotuna da wasu bayanai da suke da alaƙa da aikin. An raba shi zuwa rukuni-rukuni domin sauƙin dubawa. Rukunonin da suke karkashinsa su ne:

- a. Rataye Na 1: Kafafen Intanet Na Hausa
- b. Rataye Na 2: Kafafen Intanet da Aka Nazarta na Kamfanonin da Suke Sana'o'i a Kan Intanet
- c. Rataye Na 3: Zauruka Da Shafukan Kafafen Sada Zumunta Da Aka Bibiya Domin 'Halarta Da Sa Ido' (Participant Observation)
- d. Rataye Na 4: Wafanda Aka Yi Hira Da Su
- e. Rataye Na 5: Allon Tallace-Tallacen Wasu Hausawa a Kan Intanet

Rataye Na 1: Kafafen Intanet Na Hausa

A kullum ana kara samun sababbin kafafen intanet na Hausa. Wannan yana nuni ga cigaba da Hausa take samu a duniyar intanet. A kasa an kawo jerin kafafen intenet na Hausa da binciken ya ziyarta.

1. Abincin Hausawa - <https://abinci.com/>
2. Al'ummar Hausa - <https://www.alummarhaus.com.ng/>
3. Amsoshi - <https://www.amsoshi.com/>
4. Arewa Fresh - <https://www.arewafresh.com.ng/>
5. Arewa Nishadi - <https://www.arewanishadi.com/>
6. Arewa Swag - <https://www.arewaswag.com.ng/>
7. Arewa24 News - <https://www.arewa24news.com/>
8. Arewarmu - <https://www.arewarmu.com.ng/>

9. Azare Online - <http://azareonline.com/>
10. Baban Sadik - <https://www.babansadik.com/>
11. Bakandamiya - <https://www.bakandamiya.com/>
12. Batsa Post - <https://www.batsapost.com/>
13. Dala FM - <https://dalafmkano.com/>
14. Dandali - <http://www.dandali.com/>
15. Duniyarso - <http://duniyarso.blogspot.com/>
16. Freedom Radio Kano - <https://freedomradionig.com/>
17. Gidan Karatu - <https://www.gidankaratu.com>
18. Gidan Novels - <https://gidannovels.guidetricks.com/>
19. Gidan Rediyon Amurka - <https://www.voahausa.com/>
20. Gidan Rediyon Bejin - <http://hausa.cri.cn/>
21. Gidan Rediyon Faransa - <http://ha.rfi.fr/>
22. Gobir Mob - <https://gobirmob.com/ha/>
23. Gumel - <http://www.gumel.com/>
24. Haiman - <http://www.haiman.com.ng/>
25. Hausa Dictionary - <http://hausadictionary.com/>
26. Hausa Gett - <https://www.hausagett.com.ng/>
27. Hausa Loaded - <https://www.hausaloaded.com/>
28. Hausa Ng - <http://www.hausang.com/>
29. Hausa Online - <https://hausasonline.wordpress.com/>
30. Hausa Top - <http://www.hausatop.com/>
31. Hausa Trust - <https://www.hausatrust.com/>
32. Hausa Weddings - <https://hausaweddings.com/>
33. Hausawa Site - <https://www.hausawasite.com.ng/>
34. Hutu Dole - <https://hutudole.com/>
35. Isyaku - <https://www.isyaku.com/>
36. Jakadan Fasaha - <https://www.jakadanfasaha.com/>
37. Jaridar Aminiya - <https://aminiya.dailytrust.com.ng/>
38. Jaridar Hausa - <https://jaridarhaus.com/>
39. Jaridar Leadership Hausa - <https://hausaleadership.ng/>

40. Kalubale - <https://qalubale.news.blog/>
41. Kano Online - <http://kanoonline.com/>
42. Katsina Post Hausa - <http://katsinaposthaus.com/>
43. Madubiya - <https://www.madubiya.com/>
44. Makarantar Hausa - <https://makarantarhaus.com/>
45. Managarciya - <https://managarciya.com/>
46. Muryar 'Yanci - <https://www.muryaryanci.com/>
47. Muryar Hausa 24 - <https://www.muryarhaus24.com.ng/>
48. Rumbun Ilimi - <https://www.rumbunilimi.com.ng/>
49. SM Gusau - <https://www.smgusau.com.ng/>
50. Teach Yourself Hausa - <http://www.teachyourselfhaus.com/>
51. Tsangayar Adabi - <http://tsangayaradabi.blogspot.com/>
52. WikiHausa - <https://www.wikihaus.com.ng/>
53. Zahra Muhammad Mahmud - <http://zahramuhammadmahmud.blogspot.com/>

Rataye Na 2: Kafafen Intanet Da Aka Nazarta Na Kamfanonin Da Suke Sana'o'i a Kan Intanet

	Kamfani	Kafar Intanet
Kasuwancin Kan Intanet Sayar da Kayayyaki		
1.	Amazon	www.amazon.com
2.	eBay	www.ebay.com
3.	Jumia	www.jumia.com
4.	Alibaba	www.alibaba.com
5.	Etsy	www.etsy.com
6.	Walmart	www.walmart.com
7.	ASOS	www.asos.com
8.	Shein	www.shein.com
9.	Gymshark	www.gymshark.com
10.	Konga	www.konga.com
Kafafen Intanet da Suka Shafi Gudanar da Ayyuka		
11.	Fiverr	www.fiverr.com
12.	Upwork	www.upwork.com
13.	Toptal	www.toptal.com
14.	TaskRabbit	www.taskrabbit.com
15.	Freelancer	www.freelancer.com
16.	PeoplePerHour	www.peopleperhour.com
17.	99designs	www.99designs.com
18.	Guru	www.guru.com
19.	Thumbtack	www.thumbtack.com
20.	Clarity	www.clarity.fm

	Kamfani	Kafar Intanet
Kafafen da Suke Samun Kudi ta Hanyar Rajista da Mambobi Suke yi		
21.	Netflix	www.netflix.com
22.	Spotify	www.spotify.com
23.	Amazon Prime	www.amazon.com/prime
24.	Disney+	www.disneyplus.com
25.	Hulu	www.hulu.com
26.	Birchbox	www.birchbox.com
27.	Blue Apron	www.blueapron.com
28.	Adobe Creative Cloud	www.adobe.com/creativecloud
29.	LinkedIn Premium	www.linkedin.com/premium
30.	Patreon	www.patreon.com
Kafafen Intanet da Ake Samun Kudi ta Hanyar Dogaro da Abubuwan da Ake Dorawa a Kansu Content		
31.	YouTube	www.youtube.com
32.	Medium	www.medium.com
33.	BuzzFeed	www.buzzfeed.com
34.	Huffington Post	www.huffpost.com
35.	Mashable	www.mashable.com
36.	TechCrunch	www.techcrunch.com
37.	The Verge	www.theverge.com
38.	Vice	www.vice.com
39.	Linda Ikeji Blog	www.lindaikejisblog.com
40.	Business Insider	www.businessinsider.com
Kafafen Koyar da Karatu da Bayar da Horaswa		
41.	Coursera	www.coursera.org

	Kamfani	Kafar Intanet
42.	Udemy	www.udemy.com
43.	Khan Academy	www.khanacademy.org
44.	edX	www.edx.org
45.	Skillshare	www.skillshare.com
46.	LinkedIn Learning	www.linkedin.com/learning
47.	MasterClass	www.masterclass.com
48.	FutureLearn	www.futurelearn.com
49.	Duolingo	www.duolingo.com
50.	Alison	www.alison.com
Kafafen Sayar da Na'urantattun Kirkire-Kirkire Digital Products		
51.	Envato Market	www.envato.com
52.	Creative Market	www.creativemarket.com
53.	ThemeForest	www.themeforest.net
54.	Shutterstock	www.shutterstock.com
55.	Adobe Stock	www.stock.adobe.com
56.	Pond5	www.pond5.com
57.	Canva	www.canva.com
58.	Gumroad	www.gumroad.com
59.	Codecanyon	www.codecanyon.net
60.	iStock	www.istockphoto.com
Kafafen Hadahadar Kudfi da Saka Hannayen Jari		
61.	PayPal	www.paypal.com
62.	Robinhood	www.robinhood.com
63.	Coinbase	www.coinbase.com
64.	E*TRADE	www.etrade.com

	Kamfani	Kafar Intanet
65.	Charles Schwab	www.schwab.com
66.	Vanguard	www.vanguard.com
67.	Fidelity Investments	www.fidelity.com
68.	Binance	www.binance.com
69.	Wealthfront	www.wealthfront.com
70.	Betterment	www.betterment.com
Kafafen da Suka Shafi Kiwon Lafiya		
71.	WebMD	www.webmd.com
72.	Healthline	www.healthline.com
73.	MyFitnessPal	www.myfitnesspal.com
74.	Headspace	www.headspace.com
75.	Calm	www.calm.com
76.	Fitbit	www.fitbit.com
77.	Zocdoc	www.zocdoc.com
78.	Talkspace	www.talkspace.com
79.	BetterHelp	www.betterhelp.com
80.	Noom	www.noom.com
Kafafen da Suka Shafi Tafiye-Tafiye da Masaukai		
81.	Airbnb	www.airbnb.com
82.	Booking.com	www.booking.com
83.	Expedia	www.expedia.com
84.	TripAdvisor	www.tripadvisor.com
85.	Zillow	www.zillow.com
86.	PropertyPro Nigeria	www.propertypro.ng
87.	PrivateProperty Nigeria	www.privateproperty.com.ng

	Kamfani	Kafar Intanet
88.	Jumia Travel	www.travelstart.com.ng
89.	Tutu.ru	https://www.tutu.ru
90.	Hotels.ng	www.hotels.ng

Rataye Na 3: Zauruka Da Shafukan Kafafen Sada Zumunta Da Aka Bibiya Domin 'Halarta Da Sa Ido' (Participant Observation)

	Suna	Rukuni	Yawan Mabiya ²⁵⁶	Lifau
Zaurukan WhatsApp				
41.	Bakandamiya Reading Clum - BRC	Tattaunawa, ilimantarwa da tallata litattattafai	341	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
42.	BBC News Hausa	Yadfa labarai (Channel)	1,161,309	https://whatsapp.com/channel/0029VahbuTkEwEjqW42kXB2K
43.	GIADE Trends Collections	Tallan kayayyaki nau'ukan tufafi	457	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
44.	KASUWAR KALAMBAINA	Tallata haja	99	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
45.	Littattafan Hausa Zalla Daga marubuta daban daban	Tura rubuce-rubuce da odiyo da tallata littattafai	249	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
46.	MARUBUTA:	Tallata littattafan Adabin Kasuwar Kano	606	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
47.	Pi Updates	Kudin intanet	83	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
48.	RFI Hausa	Yadfa labarai (Channel)		https://whatsapp.com/channel/0029VafIzTDJkK7AzyjH5R20
49.	TAMBAYA DA AMSA	Tambayoyi da amsoshi game da mas'aloli da suka shafi Musulunci (Channel)	10,123	https://whatsapp.com/channel/0029VaA8YpB42DcZdoRuCj3G

²⁵⁶ Wannan ya takaita ne ya zuwa 6 ga watan Oktoba, shekarar 2025.

	Suna	Rukuni	Yawan Mabiya ²⁵⁶	Lifau
50.	WEB 3.0 MINING	Kudin intanet	164	Bai shafe shi ba (zaure ne ba channel ba)
Zauruka da Shafukan Facebook				
51.	Hadiza Aliyu	Dandalin hira da jaruman Kannywood	1,800,000 +	https://web.facebook.com/AdizatouGabon
52.	Arewa Radio 93.1	Gidan rediyo	1,100,000 +	https://web.facebook.com/arewaradio931
53.	Freedom Radio Nigeria	Gidan rediyo	1,900,000 +	https://web.facebook.com/FreedomRadioNigeria
54.	Maibiredi Tv	Gidan talabijin	494,000+	https://web.facebook.com/maibiredity
55.	Amsoshi 360	Labarai da barkwanci	19,100+	https://web.facebook.com/amsoshi360
56.	MATAN JOS AJIN FARKO KASUWANCI ZALLAH	Tallata haja	48,700+	https://web.facebook.com/groups/1473822286777322/
57.	Kasuwancin kayan hannu tare da dillanci	Kasuwanci da dillanci (musamman na kayan hannu)	286,500+	https://web.facebook.com/groups/860393198758763
58.	HADDIN MAGANIN MATA ZALLAH	Magunguna	75,600+	https://web.facebook.com/groups/3529442237382569/
59.	Crypto Hausa Nigeria - Africa	Hadahadar kudaden intanet	244,500+	https://web.facebook.com/groups/125428506013657
60.	KASUWAR GIDAJE DA FILAYE	Tallata haja	225,700+	https://web.facebook.com/groups/639950390394829
Tashoshin YouTube				

	Suna	Rukuni	Yawan Mabiya ²⁵⁶	Lifkau
61.	Abdulkabo Tech	Koyar da hanyoyin samun kuɗi a kan intanet	16,800+	https://www.youtube.com/@Abdulkabo_tech
62.	ABIS_FULANI	Labarai da barkwanci	100,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@abis_fulani
63.	Ali Artwork	Barkwanci	173,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@AliArtwork1
64.	Aminu Tech	Kimiyya da fasaha	36,400+	https://www.youtube.com/@aminutech
65.	Amsoshi TV	Karatun Hausa	7,100+	https://www.youtube.com/@AmsoshiTV
66.	Bushkiddo	Barkwanci	102,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@Bushkiddo
67.	Dan Bello	Ilimi, barkwanci, kasuwanci	91,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@bellogaladanchi
68.	Nazifi Asnanic	Waka	290,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@nazifiasnanic
69.	SCTv Africa	Hadahadar kuɗafen intanet	53,000+	https://www.youtube.com/@SctvAfrica
70.	Umar Top TV YouTube	Kimiyya da fasaha	3,840+	https://www.youtube.com/@umartoptv
Akawun-Akawun na TikTok				
71.	Ali Jita	Waka	1,500,000	https://www.tiktok.com/@realalijita
72.	Arewa multiclassic foods	Magungunan gargajiya da girke-girke	59,300+	https://www.tiktok.com/@arewa_multiclassic_food
73.	Dauda Kahutu Rarara	Waka	2,000,000 +	https://www.tiktok.com/@kahuturara

	Suna	Rukuni	Yawan Mabiya²⁵⁶	Lifau
74.	Fulanys_kitchen_kano	Girke-girke	491,100+	https://www.tiktok.com/@fulanys_kitchen_kano
75.	HydarFx	Hadahadar kudaden intanet	33,800+	https://www.tiktok.com/@hydarfx
76.	Kasuar Bello	Sayar da kayayyaki	170,600+	https://www.tiktok.com/@kasuarbello
77.	KING KABEER	Barkwanci	2,500,000 +	https://www.tiktok.com/@kingkabeer66
78.	Maibiredi Charity Foundation	Gidauniya	21,500+	https://www.tiktok.com/@maibiredicharityfoundati
79.	Maryaaamah	Girke-girke	984,100+	https://www.tiktok.com/@maryamaskitchen
80.	Yahaya_Crypto	Hadahadar kudaden intanet	81,800+	https://www.tiktok.com/@yahaya_crypto

Rataye Na 4: Wafanda Aka Yi Hira Da Su

	Suna	Matsayi	Yanki
Malamai (Masana Hausa)			
1.	Prof. Abdullahi Ibrahim Sarkin Sudan	Farfesa, masanin al'adun Hausawa	Sakkwato
2.	Prof. Umar Aliyu Bunza	Farfesa, masanin al'adun adabin Hausa	Kebbi
3.	Prof. Abdullahi Sarkin Gulbi	Farfesa, masanin al'adun Hausawa	Zamfara
4.	Prof. Abdullahi Isah Muhammad	Farfesa, masanin harshen Hausa	Sakkwato
5.	Dr. A.R. Bakura	Dakta, masanin adabin Hausa	Zamfara
6.	Dr. Jibril Yusuf	Dakta, masanin adabin Hausa	Kaduna
7.	Dr. Abdurrahman Ali	Dakta, masanin adabi	Katsina
8.	Dr. Abdulmalik Aminu	Dakta, masanin harshen Hausa	Zariya
9.	Dr. Muhammad Sulaiman Abdullahi	Dakta, masanin harshen Hausa	Kano
10.	Mal. Yusuf Gama	Malami a jami'a, masanin harshe	Jigawa
11.	Mal. Ibrahim Dalha	Malami a sakandare, mai bincike game da al'adun Hausawa	Jigawa
Masu Gudanar da Kafafen Intanet			
12.	Mr. Uwe Seibert	Mai gudanar da kafafen intanet na Hausa, mai kafafen Hausa Online da Karin Magana	Jamani
13.	Muhammad Muhammad	Masanin wayoyin salulula,	Bauchi

	Suna	Matsayi	Yanki
		mai kasuwancin waya	
14.	Mal. Lawan Dalha	Mai gudanar da kafar intanet ta Hausa, shi ne yake da kafar Bakandamiya	Nasarawa
15.	Bashir Ahmed	Mai gudanar da kafar intanet ta Hausa, shi ne yake da kafar Hutu Dole	Kaduna
16.	Abubakar Muhammad Tsangarwa	Mai gudanar da kafar intanet ta Hausa, shi ne yake da kafar Rumbun Ilimi	Jigawa
17.	Bello Muhammad	Mai gudanar da kafar intanet ta Hausa, shi ne yake da kafar Makarantar Hausa	Sakkwato
18.	Shehu Auwal	Mai gudanar da kafar intanet ta Hausa, shi ne mataimakin mai kafar Amsoshi	Kano
19.	Mohammed Atabo	Mai gudanar da kafar intanet ta Hausa, shi ne yake da kafar Gidan Karatu	Kebbi
Masu Kasuwancin Abinci Tare da Azuzuwan Koyar da Girke-Girke a Kan Intanet			
20.	Aisha Delu Aliyu	Tana nau'ukan abinci iri-iri tare da tallata sana'arta ta hanyar kafafen sada zumunta. Tana gudanar da azuzuwan koyar da abinci. Ita ce take da <i>Delu Concept Services</i> .	Sakkwato
21.	Fatima Abdulkadir	Tana kasuwancin abinci	Katsina

	Suna	Matsayi	Yanki
		tare da tallatawa a kan intanet. Tana kuma koyar da girke-girke. Ita ce take da <i>Faty AK's Cakes & More.</i>	
22.	Khadija Abbas Sani	Tana kasuwancin abinci tare da tallatawa a kan intanet. Tana kuma koyar da girke-girke. Ita ce take da <i>Khabs Kitchen.</i>	Kano
23.	Hajara Adamu Yusuf	Tana kasuwancin abinci tare da tallatawa a kan intanet. Tana kuma koyar da girke-girke. Ita ce take da <i>Hajjo's Kitchen.</i>	Bauchi
24.	A'ishatu Muhammad Bazango	Tana kasuwancin abinci tare da tallatawa a kan intanet. Tana kuma koyar da girke-girke. Ita ce take da <i>Amsoshi Kitchen.</i>	Zamfara
Masu Gusantar da Kasuwanci a Kan Intanet da Kasuwancin Kudɗen Intanet			
25.	Abdulrahman Muhammad Manga	Kwararre a fannin kasuwancin kudaden intanet	Bauchi
26.	Engr. M.M. Mujahid	Kwararre a fannin kasuwancin kudaden intanet	Bauchi
27.	Abdura'uf Sani	Yana kasuwanci a kan intanet, kuma yana kasuwancin kudaden intanet. Shi ne yake da <i>'Yar Masara Data.</i>	Bauchi
28.	Khalid Sani	Yana kasuwanci a kan intanet. Shi ne yake kula	Jigawa

	Suna	Matsayi	Yanki
		da <i>AMLAS Data</i> .	
29.	Muhammad Bello	Masanin intanet, mai gina kafafen intanet	Bauchi
30.	F. M. Bande	Kwararre a fannin kasuwancin kudaden intanet	Kebbi
31.	Mal. A.M. Umar	Kwararren mai fassara a kan intanet. Yana yi wa Facebook da Google da wasu manyan kamfanoni a duniya fassara.	Zamfara
32.	Dr. M.S. Wali	Kwararren mai fassara a kan intanet. Yana yi wa Google da wasu manyan kamfanoni a duniya fassara.	Sakkwato
33.	Jamilu Abdullahi	Kwararren mai bayar da tsaro a kan intanet (server security)	Bauchi
Sauran Mutane da Aka yi Hira da su			
34.	Malama Rukayya Muhammad	Mai adace (uwar adashe)	Zamfara
35.	Malam M. Hamma Kafinta	Dattijo mai sana'ar kafintanci	Bauchi
36.	Baba Ladi	Dattijuwa, gwada a jauran karago da kalwa	Bauchi
37.	Malama Zainab Sani	Mai sana'ar sayar da abinci	Bauchi
38.	Sa'idu Umar Yahaya	Masanin wayoyin salulula, mai kasuwancin waya	Kaduna

Rataye Na 5: Allon Tallace-Tallacen Wasu Hausawa a Kan Intanet

Aisha Delu Aliyu (Delu Concept Services)

1. SHINKAFA	N500
2. MAI	N300
3. MADARA	N100
4. MILO	N50
5. SUGAR	N50
6. TALIYA	N100
7. INDOMIE	N100
8. KWAI	N70
9. MAGGI	N100/50
10. ARISH	N100
11. MACARONI	N100
12. TABARMA	N70
13. ATAMPA	N50
14. LACE / SHADDA	N150
15. TIYARA	N50
16. TAKALMA/JIKKA	N70
17. COOLER	N150/100
18. BLANDER	N200/150

MUM SABIRA

Mai Adashe

ADDRESS: Mana Karama Area, Sokoto
GSM: 08133884070

KATIN ADASHE

Take: Ajiya Maganin Watarana

Suna: _____

Adireshi: _____

Rana: _____

Lamba Waya: _____

Sahannun Customer
Sahannun Manager

Sumayya Kabiru (Mum Sabira Collections)

CRYPTO SCHOOL

08063291678 - 08036087943

Admission Form

1. Student's Name _____
2. Class apply for _____
3. Address: _____
4. Phone Number _____
5. Medical condition _____
6. Name of the Guardian _____
7. Phone Number of Guardian _____
8. Address of the Guardian _____

CRYPTO SCHOOL OFFICIAL ONLY

1. Recommendation _____
2. Admission Number _____

Co-ordinator Sign

Date

RULES AND REGULATION FOR CRYPTO SCHOOL STUDENT

1. Respecting teachers and CRYPTO SCHOOL rules and regulation is mandatory
Girmama Malamai da dokokin kungiyar CRYPTO SCHOOL wajibi ne
2. Regularity and punctuality is mandatory
zuwa koda yaushe akan lokaci wajibi ne
3. Monthly fees and learning material are essential
Biyar kudin wata da sayen kayan karatu wajibi ne
4. Decent dress is unavoidable for both male and female
Saka kammallallar sutura wajibi ne ga dalibi ko daliba
5. Violating any of above rules can lead to punishment or ex-communicating student form
Taka daya daga cikin dokokin da aka oza kan janya hukunta dalibi ko korar dalibi gaba daya daga Makaranta.
6. Violating any of the above rules can lead to dismissal or any relevant disciplinary measure
Sabawa kowace Ka'ida ta makaranta yakan iya sa a kori dalibi ko yanke wani hukunci daya can-canta
7. Prompt payment of fees and purchase of material is mandatory
Biyar Kudin Makaranta akan tsari da kuma sayen kayan karatu ga kowane dalibi

STUDENT'S SIGNATURE

DATE

Crypto School (Makarantar Kudin Intanet)

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Kan Najeriya (Karo Na 64) 3:28
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Tushe: https://www.youtube.com/@iam_ydeen/videos

Yusufuddee. A. Yusuf yana da dandali a kafar YouTube wadda kimanin mutane dubu ashirin da dari bakwai (20,700) suke bibiya ya zuwa ranar 10 ga watan Octobar shekarar 2024. Yana koyar da harkokin da suka shafi fasahohin zamani musamman kwamfuta da kudin intanet.